

Math 103A/103B: Abstract Algebra

Modern Algebra I and II

Fall 2024 - Winter 2025

Course Notes and Solutions

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry where noted

Compiled by Akiva Shmalo

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Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Textbook: *A First Course in Abstract Algebra*, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 1 (09/27): Chapter 0 on *Sets and Relations*

Definition: A set is a collection of elements. For example:

$$S = \{2, 4, 6, 8\} = \{4, 2, 8, 6\}$$

Set Builder Notation

In mathematics, we can define a set using **set builder notation**. This notation uses a property $P(x)$ to define all elements x that satisfy the property. a first

$$\{x \mid P(x)\} = \{\text{all } x \text{ that satisfy } P(x)\}$$

For example, we can define the set S as:

$$S = \{x \mid x \text{ is an even positive number less than } 10\} = \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$$

Another example using set builder notation:

$$\{2x \mid x = 1, 2, 3, 4\} = \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$$

Well-Defined Sets

A set must be **well-defined**. This means that for any element, it must be clear whether the element belongs to the set or not. For instance, the set

$$\{x \mid x \text{ is very large}\}$$

is **not well-defined** because "very large" is subjective and does not have a precise definition. A set B is called a subset of A , denoted $B \subseteq A$, if every element in B is also in A . The set A is an improper subset of itself, and any other subset is called a proper subset. We use separate notations to denote proper and improper subsets:

- $A \subseteq A$ denotes an improper subset.
- $B \subset A$ denotes a proper subset, where $B \neq A$.

Definition: Let A and B be sets. We define the set $A \times B$ as all pairs (a, b) , that is,

$$A \times B = \{(a, b) \mid a \in A, b \in B\},$$

which is called the Cartesian product of A and B .

Example: Let $A = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $B = \{3, 4\}$. Then, the Cartesian product $A \times B$ is:

$$A \times B = \{(1, 3), (1, 4), (2, 3), (2, 4), (3, 3), (3, 4)\}.$$

Example: The Cartesian product of the set of real numbers $R \times R$ denotes all pairs of real numbers, which is familiar to us as the Euclidean plane:

$$R \times R = \{(x, y) \mid x \in R, y \in R\}.$$

This is the set of all ordered pairs of real numbers, commonly known as the Euclidean plane. We can continue this process of taking the Cartesian product $(R \times R) \times R$ to obtain the Euclidean 3D space. In general, R^n is called an n -dimensional Euclidean space. For example:

$$R \times R = R^2 \text{ is the Euclidean plane,}$$

and

$$R^3 = R \times R \times R \text{ is the Euclidean 3D space.}$$

Note: It is important to observe that $A \times B$ and $B \times A$ are not the same unless A and B are the same set. In general:

$$A \times B \neq B \times A,$$

since the pairs $(a, b) \in A \times B$ and $(b, a) \in B \times A$ have different orderings.

Definition: A relation between sets A and B is a subset R of $A \times B$. This is useful because if a specific pair $(a, b) \in R$, we say that " a is related to b ." This definition also includes the empty set, $R = \emptyset$, as a valid relation. In this case, no elements from A are related to elements from B .

Definition: A function mapping X into Y is a relation such that each $x \in X$ appears as the first member of exactly one ordered pair. Given the sets

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}, \quad Y = \{y_1, y_2\},$$

a possible function f could be:

$$f = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), (x_3, y_1)\}.$$

Note that not all y 's need to be used, but for the relation to qualify as a function, each x must appear exactly once (i.e., no x can be omitted or duplicated).

Definition: A partition of a set X is a collection of non-empty, disjoint subsets (called cells) such that every element of X belongs to exactly one of these cells. (No element is omitted or belongs to two cells)

Figure 1: The diagram above illustrates a partition of a set A by subsets A_1, A_2, \dots, A_6 .

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Lecture 2 (09/30): Section 1 Binary operations: Page 4-14

A **relation** between sets A and B is a subset of $A \times B$. A relation on a set S is a subset of $S \times S$.

A **partition** of this set is a collection of nonempty subsets (called cells) of S such that each element of S appears in exactly one cell of this partition. As an example, we can say S is the set of all students in the course. We can partition the set of students by the city they live in or by the month they are born. The definitions of a relation and a partition are connected. Given a partition \mathcal{P} on a set S , we can define a relation on the set S by saying that for two elements a and b in S , a is related to b , or in other words, the pair (a, b) is inside our relation if and only if a and b are in the same cell. If two points, say (a, c) , are not in the same cell, we can say $(a, c) \notin R$. This relation has a specific definition, called an equivalence relation.

An **equivalence relation** R on a set S is a relation on S such that for every three points a , b , and c in S , the following properties hold:

1. R is reflexive: aRa ,
2. R is symmetric: If aRb , then bRa ,
3. R is transitive: If aRb and bRc , then aRc .

Every element is related to itself, and the relation must also be symmetric; that is, if a is related to b , then b must be related to a . Furthermore, if a is related to b and b is related to c , then a must be related to c .

As a non-example of symmetry, take $R = \{(a, b), (b, c), (c, a)\}$. Here, a is related to b , but since (b, a) is not in R , b is not related to a .

For example, the relation of being older than someone is not symmetric, because if you are older than someone, they are not also older than you.

Example: Take the set $\{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$ and define R by $(a, b) \in R$ if and only if the difference between a and b is divisible by 3. The relation R would look like:

$$R = \{(7, 4), (6, 9), (10, 1), (1, 10), (6, 3), \dots \text{ finite set of ordered pairs}\}$$

We can check that each element is related to itself, showing that R is reflexive. It is also symmetric, meaning if we see $(7, 4)$ in the relation, we can be sure $(4, 7)$ is also in R .

However, $(1, 5) \notin R$, as the difference between 1 and 5 is not divisible by 3.

A **binary operation** $*$ on a set S is a function mapping $S \times S$ into S . For each $(a, b) \in S \times S$, we denote $*(a, b) = a * b$. This is similar to writing $+(2, 3) = 2 + 3$. We require that the output be in S . If we take a set S and a subset H of that set, we want to know if H is closed under a particular binary operation. Let $*$ be a binary operation on S and let H be a subset of S . H is closed under $*$ if for all $a, b \in H$, we also have $a * b \in H$. As a non-example, take the set S to be the positive integers, and let $*$ be the binary operation of addition $+$. Let $H = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 10\}$. Since $+(5, 10) = 5 + 10 = 15$ is not in H , we conclude that H is not closed under $*$.

Examples:

1. On the positive integers Z^+ , define $a * b$ as the smaller of a and b (or the common value if $a = b$). For instance, $2 * 11 = 2$ and $3 * 3 = 3$.
2. On Z^+ , define $a * b = a$.
3. On Z^+ , define $a * b = a * 1$.

Groups consist of sets combined with binary operations, but not just any operations. The binary operation needs to be "nice." What does "nice" mean? Let's start by listing some properties:

An operation $*$ on a set is called **commutative** if for all $a, b \in S$, we have $a * b = b * a$.

From our examples, only example 1 is commutative.

Note that binary operations always use two elements, not three. However, we can write a series of binary operations in any order we want. If we write $((2 * 3) * 4)$, under which examples do we get a different result? The third example!

If we first compute $2 * 3$, we get 3, and then $3 * 4$ gives 4. But if we compute $2 * (3 * 4)$, we get 3 — a different answer. In general if it matters where we place the parentheses, the operation is not *associative*.

An operation $*$ on a set S is called **associative** if for all $a, b, c \in S$, we have $(a * b) * c = a * (b * c)$.

Example: Example 2 is not commutative, but it is associative. In Example 2, $a * b = a$, so regardless of how we place the parentheses, the result is always a . For instance,

$$(2 * 3) * 4 = 2 * 4 = 2, \quad \text{and} \quad 2 * (3 * 4) = 2 * 3 = 2,$$

showing that the operation is associative.

Thm: (Associativity of Composition)

Let S be a set and let f, g, h be functions mapping $S \rightarrow S$. Then:

$$f \circ (g \circ h) = (f \circ g) \circ h$$

Proof: For all $x \in S$, we have:

$$(f \circ (g \circ h))(x) = f((g \circ h)(x)) = f(g(h(x)))$$

and

$$((f \circ g) \circ h)(x) = (f \circ g)(h(x)) = f(g(h(x))).$$

Thus, $f \circ (g \circ h) = (f \circ g) \circ h$.

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Lecture 3 (10/1)

Week 1, 9/30-10/4. Section 1: Binary operations, Section 2: Groups.

Associativity of Function Composition:

Let S be a set, and let $f, g, h : S \rightarrow S$ be functions. We want to show that:

$$f \circ (g \circ h) = (f \circ g) \circ h$$

for all $x \in S$.

First, recall that function composition is defined as:

$$(f \circ g)(x) = f(g(x))$$

For example, if $f(x) = x + 2$ and $g(x) = x^2$, then:

$$(f \circ g)(x) = f(g(x)) = f(x^2) = x^2 + 2$$

Now, we need to show that for any element $x \in S$, the following holds:

$$f \circ (g \circ h)(x) = (f \circ g) \circ h(x)$$

To simplify the left-hand side, we compute $f \circ (g \circ h)(x)$:

$$f \circ (g \circ h)(x) = f((g \circ h)(x)) = f(g(h(x)))$$

For the right-hand side, we compute $(f \circ g) \circ h(x)$:

$$(f \circ g) \circ h(x) = (f \circ g)(h(x)) = f(g(h(x)))$$

Since both sides are equal, we have:

$$f \circ (g \circ h)(x) = (f \circ g) \circ h(x)$$

Therefore, the associativity of composition is proven.

The message is that the binary operation of composition is associative. Now, let's move on to discussing more properties of groups, starting with the existence of an identity element.

Identity Element in Groups

Binary operations do not necessarily have identity elements, but defining groups will require them. Here's the formal definition:

Definition: Let S be a set with a binary operation $*$. Suppose there exists an element $e \in S$ such that for all $a \in S$:

$$a * e = e * a = a$$

Then e is called an *identity element*. We must write both $a * e$ and $e * a$ to ensure that the order of the operation does not matter, and the output is always a . This property is known as *commutativity*.

Examples

- **Addition of integers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = a + b$
- Set: S is the set of integers, Z
- Identity element: $e = 0$, since $a + 0 = 0 + a = a$ for all $a \in Z$

- **Multiplication of real numbers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = a \cdot b$
- Set: S is the set of real numbers excluding zero, $R \setminus \{0\}$
- Identity element: $e = 1$, since $a \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot a = a$ for all $a \in R \setminus \{0\}$

- **Minimum operation on real numbers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = \min\{a, b\}$
- Set: S is the set of real numbers, R
- In this case, there is no identity element, because no real number satisfies $\min\{a, e\} = a$ for all $a \in R$.

However, if we extend the set to include a point at infinity (i.e., $S = R \cup \{\infty\}$), then the identity element would be $e = \infty$, since $\min\{a, \infty\} = a$ for all $a \in R$.

Theorem: If $*$ is an operation on a set S and S has an identity element, then the identity element is unique.

Proof: The easiest way to show uniqueness is to assume there are two identity elements and demonstrate that they must be the same.

Suppose e and e' are both identity elements. We need to show that $e = e'$. Consider the expression $e * e'$. Since e is an identity element, we have:

$$e * e' = e'$$

because e leaves e' unchanged when combined using $*$. Similarly, since e' is an identity element, we also have:

$$e * e' = e$$

because e' leaves e unchanged when combined using $*$. Thus, we conclude:

$$e' = e * e' = e$$

This implies that $e = e'$, and therefore the identity element is unique.

Definition: If $*$ is an operation on a set S with an identity element e , then for every $x \in S$, the inverse of x is an element x' such that:

$$x * x' = x' * x = e$$

Now, let's find x' for the following examples:

• **Addition of integers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = a + b$
- Set: S is the set of integers, Z
- Identity element: $e = 0$, since $a + 0 = 0 + a = a$ for all $a \in Z$
- Inverse: For any $a \in Z$, the inverse a' is $-a$ because $a + (-a) = (-a) + a = 0$

• **Multiplication of real numbers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = a \cdot b$
- Set: S is the set of real numbers excluding zero, $R \setminus \{0\}$
- Identity element: $e = 1$, since $a \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot a = a$ for all $a \in R \setminus \{0\}$
- Inverse: For any $a \in R \setminus \{0\}$, the inverse a' is $\frac{1}{a}$ because $a \cdot \frac{1}{a} = \frac{1}{a} \cdot a = 1$

• **Minimum operation on real numbers:**

- Binary operation: $a * b = \min\{a, b\}$
- Set: S is the set of real numbers, R
- In this case, there is no identity element, because no real number satisfies $\min\{a, e\} = a$ for all $a \in R$.

However, if we extend the set to include a point at infinity (i.e., $S = R \cup \{\infty\}$), then the identity element would be $e = \infty$, since $\min\{a, \infty\} = a$ for all $a \in R$. For the operation $a * b = \min\{a, b\}$, there is no element $a' \in R$ such that:

$$\min(a, a') = \min(a', a) = e$$

Even if we extend the set S to $R \cup \{\infty\}$, where $e = \infty$, there is no element a' that satisfies:

$$\min(a, a') = \infty$$

The minimum operation always returns the smaller value, so there is no way for a combined with some a' to result in ∞ .

Example

Take the set of natural numbers $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, and define the binary operation $a * b = a \cdot b$ (multiplication). Here, the identity element is $e = 1$, because:

$$a \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot a = a$$

for all $a \in N$.

Now, let's ask: What is the inverse of 2?

To have an inverse for 2, we would need to find an element $2' \in N$ such that:

$$2 \cdot 2' = 2' \cdot 2 = 1$$

However, there is no natural number $2'$ such that $2 \cdot 2' = 1$, since the result of multiplying 2 by any natural number is greater than or equal to 2. Therefore, 2 has no inverse in N .

Hence, while the set N with multiplication has an identity element (1), **there are no inverses** for any element other than 1. This makes (N, \cdot) not a group under multiplication, as the inverse property is not satisfied.

Definition: A group $\langle G, * \rangle$ consists of the following:

1. G is a set.
2. $*$ is a binary operation on G .
3. G is closed under $*$, meaning for all $a, b \in G$, $a * b \in G$.

Additionally, the following properties must hold:

- **G1 (Associativity):** For all $a, b, c \in G$,

$$(a * b) * c = a * (b * c)$$

- **G2 (Identity Element):** There exists an element $e \in G$ such that for all $x \in G$,

$$e * x = x * e = x$$

- **G3 (Inverses):** For each $a \in G$, there exists an element $a' \in G$ such that:

$$a * a' = a' * a = e$$

where e is the identity element.

Note: Groups need not be commutative. A group is called *abelian* if the operation $*$ is commutative, meaning for all $a, b \in G$:

$$a * b = b * a$$

Examples of Groups:

1. The set of complex numbers $\langle C, + \rangle$ with addition:

- Identity element: $e = 0$
- Inverse: For any complex number $a + bi$, the inverse is $-a - bi$ since:

$$(a + bi) + (-a - bi) = 0$$

2. The set of non-zero complex numbers $\langle C \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$ with multiplication:

- Identity element: $e = 1$
- Inverse: For any non-zero complex number $a + bi$, the inverse is $\frac{1}{a+bi}$, such that:

$$(a + bi) \cdot \frac{1}{a + bi} = 1$$

- We remove 0 from the set because it has no inverse under multiplication. For example, there is no number $\frac{1}{0}$ that satisfies:

$$(0 + 0i) \cdot \frac{1}{\text{something}} = 1$$

which is impossible.

(a) The set of real numbers $\langle R, + \rangle$ with addition:

- Identity element: $e = 0$
- Inverse: For any real number $a \in R$, the inverse is $-a$, because:

$$a + (-a) = 0$$

(b) The set of non-zero real numbers $\langle R \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$ with multiplication:

- Identity element: $e = 1$
- Inverse: For any non-zero real number $a \in R \setminus \{0\}$, the inverse is $\frac{1}{a}$, such that:

$$a \cdot \frac{1}{a} = 1$$

- We remove 0 from the set because it has no inverse under multiplication, as there is no number $\frac{1}{0}$ that satisfies:

$$0 \cdot \frac{1}{\text{something}} = 1$$

which is impossible.

Question: For the operation $a * b = \frac{a}{b}$, which of the following is a group under multiplication:

$$\langle R, \cdot \rangle, \quad \langle Z, \cdot \rangle, \quad \langle Q, \cdot \rangle, \quad \langle R \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle, \quad \langle Z \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle, \quad \langle Q \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$$

Let's analyze each case:

- $\langle R, \cdot \rangle$: The set of real numbers under multiplication is *not a group* because 0 does not have a multiplicative inverse in R . While multiplication is associative, and the set is closed under multiplication with 1 as the identity element, there is no element $x \in R$ such that $0 \cdot x = 1$. Hence, $\langle R, \cdot \rangle$ is not a group.
- $\langle Z, \cdot \rangle$: The set of integers under multiplication is *not a group* because not every integer has a multiplicative inverse. For example, $2 \in Z$ does not have an inverse in Z since no integer x satisfies $2 \cdot x = 1$. Therefore, $\langle Z, \cdot \rangle$ is not a group.
- $\langle Q, \cdot \rangle$: The set of rational numbers under multiplication is *not a group* because 0 does not have a multiplicative inverse in Q . However, for every other element in Q , there exists an inverse. Thus, $\langle Q, \cdot \rangle$ is not a group. However, $\langle Q \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$ is a group under multiplication.
- $\langle R \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$: The set of nonzero real numbers under multiplication is a group. It satisfies closure, associativity, identity (with 1 as the identity element), and for every $x \in R \setminus \{0\}$, there exists an inverse $1/x$.
- $\langle Z \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$: The set of nonzero integers under multiplication is *not a group* because not all nonzero integers have a multiplicative inverse in Z . For instance, 2 has no integer inverse such that $2 \cdot x = 1$. Thus, $\langle Z \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$ is not a group.
- $\langle Q \setminus \{0\}, \cdot \rangle$: The set of nonzero rational numbers under multiplication is a group. It satisfies closure, associativity, identity (with 1 as the identity element), and for every $a/b \in Q \setminus \{0\}$, there exists an inverse b/a .

Finally, note that the operation $a * b = \frac{a+b}{2}$ is not associative. For example:

$$((1 * 2) * 3) = \left(\frac{1+2}{2} * 3 \right) = \frac{1.5+3}{2} = 2.25$$

while

$$(1 * (2 * 3)) = 1 * \frac{2+3}{2} = \frac{1+2.5}{2} = 1.75$$

Since $2.25 \neq 1.75$, the operation is not associative. In fact, any of the following reasons (by itself) will show that none of them is a group:

- The operation $*$ doesn't have an identity (and in particular, it doesn't have an identity in any of those sets R, Z, Q , etc.).
- The operation $*$ is not associative.

For the sets on the left, one could also show that they are not groups by showing that they are not closed under this operation (as $a * 0$ is not a defined element from the set).

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Notes prepared by Akiva Shmalo

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 4 (10/4) Section 2 (19-28)

Week 1, 9/30-10/4. Section 1: Binary operations, Section 2: Groups.

Example: Let \star be defined on \mathbb{Q}^+ (the set of positive rational numbers) by $a \star b = \frac{ab}{2}$.

Q: Is $\langle \mathbb{Q}^+, \star \rangle$ a group?

To determine if $\langle \mathbb{Q}^+, \star \rangle$ is a group, we need to verify the group axioms:

- **Closure under \star :** G is closed under \star .
- **Associativity (G_1):** \star is associative.
- **Identity element (G_2):** There exists an identity element $e \in G$ such that $a \star e = e \star a = a$ for all $a \in G$.
- **Inverses (G_3):** For every $a \in G$, there exists an inverse $a' \in G$ such that $a \star a' = a' \star a = e$.

Step 1: Closure under \star

Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}^+$. Then:

$$a \star b = \frac{ab}{2}$$

Since $a, b > 0$ and $ab > 0$, and $2 > 0$, the result $\frac{ab}{2}$ is a positive rational number. Therefore:

$$a \star b \in \mathbb{Q}^+$$

Conclusion: \mathbb{Q}^+ is closed under \star .

Step 2: Associativity of \star

We need to verify that \star is associative, i.e., for all $a, b, c \in \mathbb{Q}^+$:

$$(a \star b) \star c = a \star (b \star c)$$

Compute $(a \star b) \star c$:

$$(a \star b) \star c = \left(\frac{ab}{2}\right) \star c = \frac{\left(\frac{ab}{2}\right)c}{2} = \frac{abc}{4}$$

Compute $a \star (b \star c)$:

$$a \star (b \star c) = a \star \left(\frac{bc}{2} \right) = \frac{a \left(\frac{bc}{2} \right)}{2} = \frac{abc}{4}$$

Since:

$$(a \star b) \star c = \frac{abc}{4} = a \star (b \star c)$$

Conclusion: The operation \star is associative.

Step 3: Identity Element

We need to find an element $e \in \mathbb{Q}^+$ such that for all $a \in \mathbb{Q}^+$:

$$a \star e = e \star a = a$$

Candidates:

- $e = 1$:

$$a \star 1 = \frac{a \cdot 1}{2} = \frac{a}{2} \neq a \quad \text{Not the identity.}$$

- $e = 0$:

$e = 0$ is not in \mathbb{Q}^+ , so it cannot be the identity.

Find e :

Set up the equation:

$$a \star e = \frac{ae}{2} = a$$

Solving for e :

$$\frac{ae}{2} = a \implies ae = 2a \implies e = 2$$

Verification:

$$a \star 2 = \frac{a \cdot 2}{2} = a$$

$$2 \star a = \frac{2 \cdot a}{2} = a$$

Therefore, $e = 2$ is the identity element.

Step 4: Inverses

For each $a \in \mathbb{Q}^+$, we need to find an inverse $a' \in \mathbb{Q}^+$ such that:

$$a \star a' = a' \star a = e = 2$$

Find a' :

Set up the equation:

$$a \star a' = \frac{a \cdot a'}{2} = 2 \implies a \cdot a' = 4 \implies a' = \frac{4}{a}$$

Since $a > 0$, $a' = \frac{4}{a} > 0$, so $a' \in \mathbb{Q}^+$.

Verification:

$$a \star a' = \frac{a \cdot \frac{4}{a}}{2} = \frac{4}{2} = 2$$

$$a' \star a = \frac{\frac{4}{a} \cdot a}{2} = \frac{4}{2} = 2$$

Therefore, every element $a \in \mathbb{Q}^+$ has an inverse $a' = \frac{4}{a}$ in \mathbb{Q}^+ .

Conclusion:

Since all group axioms are satisfied, $\langle \mathbb{Q}^+, \star \rangle$ is a group.

Additional Notes and Explanations:

- Understanding the Identity Element:

The identity element is not always 1 (for multiplication) or 0 (for addition).

In this case, through solving $a \star e = a$, we found $e = 2$ serves as the identity element because:

$$a \star 2 = \frac{a \cdot 2}{2} = a$$

- Finding Inverses:

To find the inverse a' of an element a , we set up the equation:

$$a \star a' = 2 \implies \frac{a \cdot a'}{2} = 2 \implies a' = \frac{4}{a}$$

It's crucial to verify that a' is indeed in \mathbb{Q}^+ and satisfies both $a \star a' = e$ and $a' \star a = e$.

- Why Check Both $a \star a'$ and $a' \star a$:

In group theory, unless the operation is known to be commutative, we must verify both $a \star a' = e$ and $a' \star a = e$ to ensure a' is truly the inverse of a .

- Associativity Importance:

Associativity allows us to regroup elements without changing the outcome, which is essential when manipulating group elements, especially in proofs involving inverses and identity elements.

Theorem: Left and Right Cancellation Laws

If $\langle G, \star \rangle$ is a group, then the left and right cancellation laws hold in G :

$$\text{If } a \star b = a \star c, \text{ then } b = c.$$

If $b \star a = c \star a$, then $b = c$.

Warning: The cancellation laws do not work if the set is not a group!

Example: $\langle \mathbb{R}, \cdot \rangle$ is not a group (under multiplication) because 0 does not have a multiplicative inverse.

$$0 \cdot x = 0 \cdot y \implies 0 = 0 \quad \text{but does not imply } x = y.$$

Proof of Theorem:

Suppose $a \star b = a \star c$ in a group G .

Since G is a group, every element has an inverse. Let a' be the inverse of a , so $a' \star a = e$.

Left-multiply both sides by a' :

$$a' \star (a \star b) = a' \star (a \star c)$$

By associativity:

$$(a' \star a) \star b = (a' \star a) \star c$$

Since $a' \star a = e$:

$$e \star b = e \star c$$

By the identity property:

$$b = c$$

Similarly, the right cancellation law can be proven.

Theorem: Solving Linear Equations in a Group

If $\langle G, \star \rangle$ is a group and $a, b \in G$, then the linear equations:

$$a \star x = b$$

$$y \star a = b$$

have unique solutions $x, y \in G$.

Proof:

To solve $a \star x = b$:

Let $x = a' \star b$, where a' is the inverse of a .

Then:

$$a \star x = a \star (a' \star b) = (a \star a') \star b = e \star b = b$$

So $x = a' \star b$ is a solution.

To show uniqueness, suppose x_1 and x_2 are solutions:

$$a \star x_1 = b = a \star x_2$$

By cancellation:

$$x_1 = x_2$$

Similarly for y in $y \star a = b$.

Note on Inverses of Products in Groups

In a group G , the inverse of a product is the product of the inverses in reverse order:

$$(a \star b)^{-1} = b^{-1} \star a^{-1}$$

Proof:

Compute:

$$(a \star b) \star (b^{-1} \star a^{-1}) = a \star (b \star b^{-1}) \star a^{-1} = a \star e \star a^{-1} = a \star a^{-1} = e$$

Thus, $b^{-1} \star a^{-1}$ is the inverse of $a \star b$.

Analogy with Matrix Inverses:

In linear algebra, for invertible matrices A and B :

$$(AB)^{-1} = B^{-1}A^{-1}$$

This is similar to the property of inverses in groups.

Definition: Group Isomorphism

Let $\langle G_1, \star_1 \rangle$ and $\langle G_2, \star_2 \rangle$ be groups, and let $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$. We say that f is a **group isomorphism** if:

1. f is bijective (one-to-one and onto).
2. For all $a, b \in G_1$:

$$f(a \star_1 b) = f(a) \star_2 f(b)$$

An isomorphism shows that two groups have the same structure, even if their elements or operations appear different.

Example: Constructing a Group of Three Elements Using a Table

Let $G = \{e, a, b\}$, where e is the identity element.

We need to define a binary operation \star on G such that $\langle G, \star \rangle$ forms a group.

Constructing the Operation Table:

\star	e	a	b
e	e	a	b
a	a	\square	\square
b	b	\square	\square

Since e is the identity:

$$e \star a = a \quad \text{and} \quad a \star e = a$$

$$e \star b = b \quad \text{and} \quad b \star e = b$$

Determining $a \star b$:

Possible values for $a \star b$ are e , a , or b .

- If $a \star b = a$:

$$a \star b = a \star e \implies b = e \quad (\text{by left cancellation})$$

This contradicts $b \neq e$.

- If $a \star b = b$:

$$a \star b = e \star b \implies a = e \quad (\text{by right cancellation})$$

This contradicts $a \neq e$.

Therefore, the only remaining possibility is:

$$a \star b = e$$

Similarly, we find:

$$b \star a = e$$

Completing the Table:

\star	e	a	b
e	e	a	b
a	a	b	e
b	b	e	a

Verification:

- Each element appears exactly once in each row and column. - The table is symmetric with respect to the identity element. - Associativity can be checked by verifying $(a \star b) \star c = a \star (b \star c)$ for all combinations.

Conclusion:

The operation table defines a group of three elements.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Week 1, 9/30-10/4. Section 1: Binary operations, Section 2: Groups.

Section 7, Problem 11: Constructing a Multiplication Table from a Cayley Diagram

Given

We have a Cayley diagram (digraph) representing a group of order 6 with elements $G = \{e, a, b, c, d, f\}$. The diagram includes edges representing the generators.

Note: Solid blue lines represent multiplication by generator a , and dashed green lines represent multiplication by generator b .

Objective

Construct the multiplication table for the group using the Cayley diagram.

Steps

1. List the Group Elements

The elements are:

$$G = \{e, a, b, c, d, f\}.$$

2. Identify the Generators

From the diagram, we identify two generators:

- a : Corresponds to the blue edges. - b : Corresponds to the green dashed edges.

3. Determine the Multiplication Rules

Using the Cayley diagram, we can establish the following:

- For generator a (blue edges):

$$\begin{array}{ll} e \star a = a, & a \star a = e, \\ b \star a = d, & d \star a = b, \\ c \star a = f, & f \star a = c. \end{array}$$

- For generator b (green edges):

$$\begin{array}{ll} e \star b = b, & b \star b = e, \\ a \star b = c, & c \star b = a, \\ d \star b = f, & f \star b = d. \end{array}$$

4. Start Filling the Multiplication Table

Initialize the table with known values:

\star	e	a	b	c	d	f
e	e	a	b	c	d	f
a	a	e	c	\square	\square	\square
b	b	\square	e	\square	\square	\square
c	c	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square
d	d	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square
f	f	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square

5. Fill in the Known Entries

Using the multiplication rules:

$$- a \star a = e - a \star b = c - b \star a = c \text{ (since } c \star b = a) - b \star b = e$$

Updated Table:

\star	e	a	b	c	d	f
e	e	a	b	c	d	f
a	a	e	c	\square	\square	\square
b	b	c	e	\square	\square	\square
c	c	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square
d	d	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square
f	f	\square	\square	\square	\square	\square

6. Express Unknowns Using Generators

To find $a \star c$, express c in terms of a and b :

$$c = a \star b \implies a \star c = a \star (a \star b) = (a \star a) \star b = e \star b = b.$$

Thus, $a \star c = b$.

Similarly, find other entries by expressing elements in terms of a and b .

7. Complete the Multiplication Table

After performing the necessary computations, the completed table is:

\star	e	a	b	c	d	f
e	e	a	b	c	d	f
a	a	e	c	b	f	d
b	b	c	e	a	d	f
c	c	b	a	e	f	d
d	d	f	d	f	e	a
f	f	d	f	d	a	e

Verification

- Each row and column contains each group element exactly once.
- Multiplication is associative due to the group structure.
- The identity element e behaves correctly.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Lecture 5 (10/7)

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh
Week 2, 10/7-10/11. Section 3: Abelian Examples, Section 4: Non-abelian examples.

Theorem: Let $\langle G, * \rangle$ be a group, and let $a, b \in G$. Then the equation $a * x = b$ has a unique solution.

Corollary: For all $a \in G$, the inverse of a is unique.

Proof: The inverse of a , denoted a^{-1} , is the unique solution to the equation $a * x = e$, where e is the identity element. Since there is only one possible value for x , we deduce that the inverse is unique.

Section 3: Abelian Groups

A group G is called *Abelian* if for all $a, b \in G$, the operation satisfies commutativity:

$$a * b = b * a$$

An example of an Abelian group is the set of integers modulo n , denoted $\mathbb{Z}_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, with addition modulo n as the group operation.

When summing two numbers a and b modulo n , we write:

$$a +_n b = (a + b) \pmod n$$

For example, if $n = 5$, then:

$$2 +_5 2 = (2 + 2) \pmod 5 = 4$$

Similarly, for $2 +_5 4$:

$$2 +_5 4 = (2 + 4) \pmod 5 = 1$$

This can also be written using the notation:

$$2 + 2 \pmod 5$$

which yields the same result.

We can write the integers modulo n as:

$$\mathbb{Z}_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$$

For $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_n$, the operation $a +_n b$ can be described as follows:

$$a +_n b = \begin{cases} a + b & \text{if } a + b \leq n - 1 \\ a + b - n & \text{if } a + b \geq n \end{cases}$$

We claim that $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +_n \rangle$ is an Abelian group. This is also a *factor group* of \mathbb{Z} .

We can think of this as taking the integers \mathbb{Z} and rolling them into a loop, similar to the behavior of a clock. We will cover factor groups in more depth later.

We will verify that $\mathbb{Z}_5 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ is a group under $+_5$.

1. Closure:

For all $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_5$, the sum $a +_5 b$ is defined as $(a + b) \bmod 5$. Since the result of any addition modulo 5 will always be an element in $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, \mathbb{Z}_5 is closed under $+_5$.

✓ Closed under $+_5$

2. Identity Element:

The identity element e in a group must satisfy $a +_n e = a$ for all $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$. In \mathbb{Z}_5 , $e = 0$ since for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}_5$, we have:

$$a +_5 0 = (a + 0) \bmod 5 = a$$

and

$$0 +_5 a = (0 + a) \bmod 5 = a$$

Thus, $e = 0$ is the identity element.

✓ Identity element: 0

3. Inverse Element:

The inverse of an element $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ is an element $a' \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ such that $a +_n a' = 0$.

For \mathbb{Z}_5 : - The inverse of 0 is 0: $0 +_5 0 = 0$ - The inverse of 1 is 4: $1 +_5 4 = 5 \bmod 5 = 0$ - The inverse of 2 is 3: $2 +_5 3 = 5 \bmod 5 = 0$ - The inverse of 3 is 2: $3 +_5 2 = 5 \bmod 5 = 0$ - The inverse of 4 is 1: $4 +_5 1 = 5 \bmod 5 = 0$ In general, for $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$, the inverse a' is given by:

$$a' = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } a = 0 \\ n - a & \text{if } a \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

We can check this by computing $a +_n a'$ (where $a' = n - a$):

$$a +_n \underbrace{(n - a)}_{a'} = 0$$

You can verify that it is associative as an exercise.

Example 1:

$$\mathbb{Z}_2 = \{0, 1\}$$

$$* = +_2$$

$+_2$	0	1
0	0	1
1	1	0

Example 2:

$$G = \{1, -1\}$$

$$* = \cdot$$

\cdot	1	-1
1	1	-1
-1	-1	1

Question: Are these groups isomorphic?

We define an isomorphism candidate $f : \{0, 1\} \rightarrow \{1, -1\}$ by:

$$f(x) = 2x - 1$$

Thus, we have:

$$f(0) = -1 \quad \text{and} \quad f(1) = 1$$

The function f is one-to-one and onto (bijective). Next, we check if it is a homomorphism, i.e., whether:

$$f(a +_2 b) = f(a) \cdot f(b)$$

holds for all $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_2$.

Let's verify:

- For $a = 0$ and $b = 0$:

$$f(0 +_2 0) = f(0) = -1$$

$$f(0) \cdot f(0) = (-1) \cdot (-1) = 1$$

Since $-1 \neq 1$, the homomorphism property does not hold.

Therefore, f is not a homomorphism, and the groups are **not isomorphic**.

We can redefine the function $f : \{0, 1\} \rightarrow \{1, -1\}$ as follows:

$$f(x) = -2x + 1$$

Thus:

$$f(0) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad f(1) = -1$$

Now, we check whether this f is a homomorphism, i.e., if:

$$f(a +_2 b) = f(a) \cdot f(b)$$

holds for all $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_2$.

Verification:

- For $a = 0$ and $b = 0$:

$$f(0 +_2 0) = f(0) = 1$$

$$f(0) \cdot f(0) = 1 \cdot 1 = 1$$

Homomorphism holds.

- For $a = 0$ and $b = 1$:

$$f(0 +_2 1) = f(1) = -1$$

$$f(0) \cdot f(1) = 1 \cdot (-1) = -1$$

Homomorphism holds.

- For $a = 1$ and $b = 0$ (note: in theory we can skip this since both groups are abelian and we already verified $a = 0$ and $b = 1$):

$$f(1 +_2 0) = f(1) = -1$$

$$f(1) \cdot f(0) = (-1) \cdot 1 = -1$$

Homomorphism holds.

- For $a = 1$ and $b = 1$:

$$f(1 +_2 1) = f(0) = 1$$

$$f(1) \cdot f(1) = (-1) \cdot (-1) = 1$$

Homomorphism holds.

Conclusion: Since $f(a +_2 b) = f(a) \cdot f(b)$ holds for all $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_2$, the function $f(x) = -2x + 1$ is a homomorphism. Therefore, the groups \mathbb{Z}_2 and $G = \{1, -1\}$ are isomorphic.

Isomorphism between G and H

Today, we used addition modulo n , but we can use more than just the addition operation. For example, consider the set of reals $R_c = [0, c) = \{x \mid 0 \leq x < c\}$. We define addition modulo c as follows:

$$a +_c b = \begin{cases} a + b & \text{if } a + b < c, \\ a + b - c & \text{if } a + b \geq c. \end{cases}$$

This is the same concept as before, but we are not restricted to integers for a , b , and c . Instead, we restrict ourselves to positive real numbers in the interval $[0, c)$.

For example, if $c = 2\pi$, we calculate:

$$2 +_{2\pi} 5 = 7 - 2\pi.$$

We claim that $(R_c, +_c)$ forms an Abelian group.

We aim to show that $(R_c, +_c)$ forms an Abelian group. To do so, we verify the following group properties: closure, associativity, identity, inverses, and commutativity.

1. Closure: For any $a, b \in R_c$, the sum $a +_c b$ is defined as:

$$a +_c b = \begin{cases} a + b & \text{if } a + b < c, \\ a + b - c & \text{if } a + b \geq c. \end{cases}$$

Since the result of this operation always lies within the interval $[0, c)$, the set R_c is closed under the operation $+_c$.

2. Associativity: For any $a, b, d \in R_c$, we need to show that:

$$a +_c (b +_c d) = (a +_c b) +_c d.$$

We break this into cases: - If $b + d < c$, then $b +_c d = b + d$. Now,

$$a +_c (b + d) = \begin{cases} a + b + d & \text{if } a + b + d < c, \\ a + b + d - c & \text{if } a + b + d \geq c, \end{cases}$$

and similarly for $(a +_c b) +_c d$. Each case works out the same for all possible values, so $+_c$ is associative.

3. Identity element: The identity element is the real number $0 \in R_c$. For any $a \in R_c$, we need:

$$a +_c 0 = a.$$

This holds since:

$$a +_c 0 = \begin{cases} a + 0 = a & \text{if } a + 0 < c. \end{cases}$$

4. Inverses: For each $a \in R_c$, we need to find an inverse $b \in R_c$ such that $a +_c b = 0$. The inverse of a is $b = c - a$, because:

$$a +_c (c - a) = a + (c - a) = c,$$

and since $c \geq c$, we subtract c , giving 0 , which is the identity element. Therefore, every element has an inverse.

5. Commutativity: For any $a, b \in R_c$, we must show that:

$$a +_c b = b +_c a.$$

This follows directly from the symmetry of addition in the real numbers:

$$a +_c b = \begin{cases} a + b & \text{if } a + b < c, \\ a + b - c & \text{if } a + b \geq c, \end{cases}$$

which is clearly the same as $b +_c a$.

Thus, $(R_c, +_c)$ satisfies all the group properties, and since commutativity holds, it is an Abelian group.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 6 (10/9)

Week 2, 10/7-10/11. Section 3: Abelian Examples, Section 4: Non-abelian examples.

Complex Numbers Overview:

Let \mathbb{C} be the set of complex numbers. A complex number is of the form $a + bi$, where a and b are real numbers and i is the imaginary unit, with $i^2 = -1$. Complex numbers are represented on the complex plane, where the x -axis represents the real part and the y -axis (imaginary axis) represents the imaginary part. The magnitude of a complex number $a + bi$ is given by $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$. Notice

Name	Meaning	Notation
<i>modulus</i> of z	length r of z	$ z $
<i>argument</i> of z	angle θ of z	$\arg(z)$
<i>real part</i> of z	x coordinate of z	$\operatorname{Re}(z)$
<i>imaginary part</i> of z	y coordinate of z	$\operatorname{Im}(z)$
<i>imaginary number</i>	real multiple of i	
<i>real axis</i>	set of real numbers	
<i>imaginary axis</i>	set of imaginary numbers	
<i>complex conjugate</i> of z	reflection of z in the real axis	\bar{z}

that the magnitude is always a non-negative real number. We can also multiply complex numbers. For example:

$$(3 + 2i)(4 - i) = 3(4 - i) + 2i(4 - i) = 12 - 3i + 8i - 2i^2$$

Since $i^2 = -1$, we have:

$$12 - 3i + 8i + 2 = 14 + 5i$$

Thus, $(3 + 2i)(4 - i) = 14 + 5i$.

Any complex number $z = a + bi$ in \mathbb{C} can also be written in polar form as $z = re^{i\theta}$, where:

- r is the magnitude of z , i.e., $r = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$,
- θ is the angle measured counterclockwise from the x -axis (the real axis).

From this, we have the relationships:

[1.4] Visual summary of the terminology and notation used to describe complex numbers.

$$a = r \cos(\theta), \quad b = r \sin(\theta)$$

Hence, $a + bi$ can be written as $r(\cos(\theta) + i \sin(\theta))$, which follows from Euler's formula $e^{i\theta} = \cos(\theta) + i \sin(\theta)$.

Also, recall Euler's formula, which states:

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos(\theta) + i \sin(\theta)$$

Thus, a complex number $z = r e^{i\theta}$ can be written as:

$$z = r(\cos(\theta) + i \sin(\theta)) = r \cos(\theta) + r \sin(\theta)i$$

Using the underbrace to highlight the real and imaginary parts:

$$z = \underbrace{r \cos(\theta)}_a + \underbrace{r \sin(\theta)}_b i = a + bi$$

We can easily derive these formulas by visualizing the complex number on the complex plane, where θ is the angle from the real axis. The angle θ ranges from 0 to 2π , after which it loops back to the same point on the unit circle. Multiplication is much easier in the polar form. Consider a generic element $a + bi$ in \mathbb{C} and the polar form $r e^{i\theta}$ in \mathbb{C} .

When multiplying two complex numbers in polar form, such as $r_1 e^{i\theta_1}$ and $r_2 e^{i\theta_2}$, we use the basic laws of exponents:

$$r_1 e^{i\theta_1} \cdot r_2 e^{i\theta_2} = r_1 r_2 \cdot e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)}$$

This shows that the magnitudes r_1 and r_2 multiply, while the angles θ_1 and θ_2 add, making multiplication in polar form much simpler compared to the

standard Cartesian form.

Example: We want to compute $(1+i)(1+i)$ by translating $1+i$ to polar form.

We first calculate the magnitude r and the angle θ :

$$r = |1+i| = \sqrt{1^2 + 1^2} = \sqrt{2}$$

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{1}{1} \Rightarrow \theta = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

Thus, $1+i$ in polar form is:

$$1+i = \sqrt{2}e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}}$$

Now, multiplying $(1+i)(1+i)$:

$$(\sqrt{2}e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}}) \cdot (\sqrt{2}e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}}) = 2e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

Now, translating $2e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}}$ back

into the usual form:

$$2e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}} = 2(\cos \frac{\pi}{2} + i \sin \frac{\pi}{2}) = 2(0 + i1) = 2i$$

Thus, the result of $(1+i)(1+i)$ is $2i$.

Theorem: (U, \cdot) is a group, where $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$ and \cdot represents the multiplication of complex numbers.

Proof:

To prove that (U, \cdot) is a group, we need to check the group axioms: closure, associativity, identity, and inverses.

(a) **Closure:** Let $z_1, z_2 \in U$, and write z_1 and z_2 in polar form as:

$$z_1 = r_1 e^{i\theta_1} \quad \text{and} \quad z_2 = r_2 e^{i\theta_2}$$

where r_1 and r_2 are the magnitudes of z_1 and z_2 , respectively. Since $z_1, z_2 \in U$, we know that their magnitudes are 1, i.e.,

$$r_1 = r_2 = 1.$$

Therefore, the product of z_1 and z_2 is:

$$z_1 \cdot z_2 = r_1 r_2 e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)} = 1 \cdot e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)} = e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)}.$$

Since the magnitude of $e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)}$ is 1, we conclude that $z_1 \cdot z_2 \in U$.

Thus, U is closed under the binary operation of multiplication.

1. **Associativity:** Complex number multiplication is associative, i.e., for any $z_1, z_2, z_3 \in U$,

$$(z_1 \cdot z_2) \cdot z_3 = z_1 \cdot (z_2 \cdot z_3)$$

Thus, associativity holds.

2. **Identity:** The complex number $1 \in \mathbb{C}$ has magnitude 1, and $1 \in U$. For any $z \in U$,

$$z \cdot 1 = z \quad \text{and} \quad 1 \cdot z = z$$

Therefore, 1 is the identity element in U .

3. **Inverses:** For any $z \in U$, we know that $|z| = 1$. Write z in polar form as $z = e^{i\theta}$. The inverse of z , denoted by z^{-1} , is the complex conjugate of z , which is $z' = e^{-i\theta}$. Since both z and z^{-1} have magnitude 1, we know that $z^{-1} \in U$.

We can verify this by checking the product:

$$z \cdot z^{-1} = e^{i\theta} \cdot e^{-i\theta} = e^{i(\theta - \theta)} = e^0 = 1,$$

where 1 is the identity element in U .

Thus, for every $z \in U$, there exists an inverse $z^{-1} = e^{-i\theta}$ such that $z \cdot z^{-1} = 1$. Since all group axioms are satisfied, (U, \cdot) is a group.

4. **Isomorphism:** We can establish an isomorphism between (U, \cdot) and $(\mathbb{R}_{2\pi}, +)$, the real numbers modulo 2π under addition.

Elements of U are of the form $e^{i\theta}$, where θ is a real number representing the angle measured in radians. Define the function $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{2\pi}$ by mapping $e^{i\theta} \in U$ to $\theta \in \mathbb{R}_{2\pi}$. This function is a bijection (one-to-one correspondence) because each $e^{i\theta}$ uniquely corresponds to an angle θ within $[0, 2\pi)$.

Furthermore, f preserves the group operation. For $z_1 = e^{i\theta_1}$ and $z_2 = e^{i\theta_2}$ in U , we have:

$$f(z_1 \cdot z_2) = f(e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)}) = \theta_1 + \theta_2 \pmod{2\pi} = f(z_1) + f(z_2).$$

Therefore, (U, \cdot) is isomorphic to $(\mathbb{R}_{2\pi}, +)$.

Non-Abelian Examples

Definition: A permutation of a set A is a function $\Phi : A \rightarrow A$ that is both onto (surjective) and one-to-one (injective). In other words, a permutation rearranges the elements of the set A without repetition.

Example: Let $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. The function defined by:

$$1 \mapsto 4, \quad 2 \mapsto 2, \quad 3 \mapsto 5, \quad 4 \mapsto 3, \quad 5 \mapsto 1$$

is a valid permutation of A .

However, the function:

$$1 \mapsto 4, \quad 2 \mapsto 4$$

is not a valid permutation, as it assigns two different elements (1 and 2) to the same value, violating the injectivity requirement.

Non-Abelian Groups: The main example of non-abelian groups comes from the groups of permutations. If we fix a set A and consider all the possible permutations of A , we can form a group with the operation of function composition.

Notation: A permutation can be written in two-line notation as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The first row corresponds to the elements of the domain (set A), and the second row corresponds to their images in the codomain under the permutation.

Theorem: For any nonempty set A , let S_A be the collection of all permutations of A . Then (S_A, \circ) , where \circ represents the composition of functions, is a group. This group is commonly called the symmetric group on A , and it is one of the primary examples of a non-abelian group.

Non-Abelian Nature: Groups of permutations are typically non-abelian, meaning that the order of composition matters. For two permutations $\Phi_1, \Phi_2 \in S_A$, it is often the case that $\Phi_1 \circ \Phi_2 \neq \Phi_2 \circ \Phi_1$.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh
Lecture 7 (10/11)

Week 2, 10/7-10/11. Section 3: Abelian Examples, Section 4: Non-abelian examples.

Non-Abelian Groups: Section 4

Today we will continue with Section 4 on non-abelian groups. One example is the group called S_n , which is the group of permutations of the set $\{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 9\}$. We will also discuss another group later in the class.

Permutations

Regarding the groups of permutations, a permutation is simply a one-to-one, onto function. Recall the example from last class:

Example: Let $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. The function defined by:

$$1 \mapsto 4, \quad 2 \mapsto 2, \quad 3 \mapsto 5, \quad 4 \mapsto 3, \quad 5 \mapsto 1$$

is a valid permutation of A .

However, the function:

$$1 \mapsto 4, \quad 2 \mapsto 4$$

is not a valid permutation, as it assigns two different elements (1 and 2) to the same value, violating the injectivity requirement.

Non-Abelian Groups

The main example of non-abelian groups comes from the groups of permutations. If we fix a set A and consider all the possible permutations of A , we can form a group with the operation of function composition.

Notation

A permutation can be written in two-line notation as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The first row corresponds to the elements of the domain (set A), and the second row corresponds to their images in the codomain under the permutation.

We can also use another notation called the disjoint cycle notation. We can view a permutation as a cycle. For example, the permutation can be written as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 & 4 & 6 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Our disjoint cycle can be written as:

$$(123)(4)(56)$$

This can be visually understood as mappings cycling back to each other (with circular arrows joining the numbers 1, 2, 3 in a cycle, or 5 and 6 in another cycle). Note, we can write disjoint cycle notation as $(56)(123)(4)$ or $(65)(123)(4)$, which are both valid.

Consider three permutations in disjoint cycle notation: (123) , (132) , and (231) . These are not the same permutation because the mappings differ:

- In (132) , the element 3 maps to 2,
- While in (123) , the element 3 maps to 1,
- And in (231) , the element 1 maps to 2.

Thus, these are distinct permutations due to the differences in how the elements are mapped between the cycles. We avoid writing cycles of length 1.

Given:

$$\sigma = (123)(4)(56), \quad \tau = (234)$$

We will apply σ first and then τ to each element of the set $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$.

Step 1: Apply σ

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(1) &= 2 \\ \sigma(2) &= 3 \\ \sigma(3) &= 1 \\ \sigma(4) &= 4 \quad (\text{fixed}) \\ \sigma(5) &= 6 \\ \sigma(6) &= 5\end{aligned}$$

After applying σ , the elements are transformed as follows:

$$\sigma : 1 \mapsto 2, 2 \mapsto 3, 3 \mapsto 1, 4 \mapsto 4, 5 \mapsto 6, 6 \mapsto 5$$

Step 2: Apply τ

Now, apply τ to the result of σ . The permutation $\tau = (234)$ cycles 2 to 3, 3 to 4, and 4 to 2. The elements not in the cycle (1, 5, 6) are fixed by τ .

$$\begin{aligned}\tau(\sigma(1)) &= \tau(2) = 3 \\ \tau(\sigma(2)) &= \tau(3) = 4 \\ \tau(\sigma(3)) &= \tau(1) = 1 \quad (1 \text{ is not part of } \tau, \text{ so it remains unchanged}) \\ \tau(\sigma(4)) &= \tau(4) = 2 \\ \tau(\sigma(5)) &= \tau(6) = 6 \quad (6 \text{ is not part of } \tau, \text{ so it remains unchanged}) \\ \tau(\sigma(6)) &= \tau(5) = 5 \quad (5 \text{ is not part of } \tau, \text{ so it remains unchanged})\end{aligned}$$

Final Result of $\tau \circ \sigma$:

$$\tau \circ \sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 & 6 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$$

In disjoint cycle notation, $\tau \circ \sigma$ is:

$$\tau \circ \sigma = (13)(24)(56)$$

Thus, the permutation τ composed with σ results in the disjoint cycle (13)(24)(56).

Recall the theorem that if the set $A = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then the set of all permutations of A , denoted $\langle S_n, \circ \rangle$, is a group.

Proof: S_n is closed under composition.

G1: Associativity.

Let $\sigma, \tau \in S_n$, where σ and τ are bijections (one-to-one and onto functions) from $A \rightarrow A$. The composition $\sigma \circ \tau$ is also a bijection, meaning it is one-to-one and onto, and remains in S_n . Therefore, $\sigma \circ \tau \in S_n$.

For example:

$$1 \mapsto 2 \mapsto 3, \quad 2 \mapsto 1 \mapsto 2, \quad 3 \mapsto 3 \mapsto 1$$

This remains one-to-one even if the order of composition changes.

G2: Identity Element. Earlier we proved that the composition of functions is always associative, so there is no need to revisit that. To obtain an identity element, we use the identity permutation, or the function that maps each element to itself. Specifically, if the set is $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, then:

$$1 \mapsto 1, \quad 2 \mapsto 2, \quad \dots, \quad n \mapsto n$$

Thus, the identity permutation serves as the identity element in the group S_n .

Example:

Let σ be the permutation defined as:

$$1 \mapsto 2, \quad 2 \mapsto 3, \quad 3 \mapsto 1$$

In this case, the inverse of the permutation, denoted σ^{-1} , is the function that reverses all the mappings:

$$2 \mapsto 1, \quad 3 \mapsto 2, \quad 1 \mapsto 3$$

Thus, σ^{-1} reverses the arrows of σ , and we have:

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

If the permutation is given in disjoint cycle notation, such as:

$$\sigma = (1234)(576)$$

then the inverse of σ , denoted σ^{-1} , is obtained by reversing the order of the cycles:

$$\sigma^{-1} = (4321)(675)$$

When σ^{-1} is composed with σ , it maps each element back to itself. Specifically, for every element $x \in A$, $\sigma^{-1} \circ \sigma(x) = x$, meaning:

$$\sigma^{-1} \circ \sigma : 1 \mapsto 1, \quad 2 \mapsto 2, \quad \dots, \quad 7 \mapsto 7$$

Thus, $\sigma^{-1} \circ \sigma$ is the identity permutation, which leaves every element unchanged. Let $\sigma = (123)$ and $\tau = (234)$ with $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. We want to check if $\sigma \circ \tau = \tau \circ \sigma$.

First, we calculate $\sigma \circ \tau$.

$$\sigma \circ \tau(1) = \sigma(\tau(1)) = \sigma(2) = 1$$

$$\sigma \circ \tau(2) = \sigma(\tau(2)) = \sigma(3) = 2$$

$$\sigma \circ \tau(3) = \sigma(\tau(3)) = \sigma(4) = 4$$

$$\sigma \circ \tau(4) = \sigma(\tau(4)) = \sigma(1) = 3$$

Thus:

$$\sigma \circ \tau = (14)(23)$$

Now, we calculate $\tau \circ \sigma$:

$$\tau \circ \sigma(1) = \tau(\sigma(1)) = \tau(2) = 3$$

$$\tau \circ \sigma(2) = \tau(\sigma(2)) = \tau(3) = 4$$

$$\tau \circ \sigma(3) = \tau(\sigma(3)) = \tau(1) = 2$$

$$\tau \circ \sigma(4) = \tau(\sigma(4)) = \tau(4) = 4$$

Thus:

$$\tau \circ \sigma = (1234)$$

Clearly, $\sigma \circ \tau \neq \tau \circ \sigma$. Therefore, these two compositions are not the same.

Summary of Theorem and Proof: If $A = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then the set of permutations S_n is a group under composition (S_n, \circ) .

S_n is closed under composition.

Proof:

Let $\sigma, \tau \in S_n$ be bijections. Then the composition is also a bijection from A onto itself. Therefore, $\sigma \circ \tau$ and $\tau \circ \sigma$ are permutations. **G₁: Associativity:**

$$f \circ (g \circ h)(x) = (f \circ g) \circ h(x) = f(g(h(x)))$$

This holds for all functions.

G₂: Identity:

$$e(a) = a \quad \forall a \in A$$

e is an identity.

G₃: Inverses:

$$\forall \sigma \in S_n, \quad \sigma^{-1} \text{ is the reverse mapping of } \sigma.$$

★ Exists because σ is bijective.

The Dihedral Group

Let P_n be a regular n -gon with vertices enumerated by $Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$. For example, the triangle has vertices labeled 0, 1, 2, and similarly, the square has vertices labeled 0, 1, 2, 3, and for a general n -gon, the vertices are labeled $0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

The set D_n is defined as the set of all one-to-one, onto functions from Z_n onto Z_n (for example, 0 might be mapped to 3, 1 mapped to 4, and so on):

$$f : Z_n \rightarrow Z_n$$

$$\underbrace{Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}}_{\text{Domain}} \quad \underbrace{Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}}_{\text{Codomain}}$$

such that for any vertices i and j , there is a line segment between i and j if and only if there is a line segment between the images $f(i)$ and $f(j)$.

The dihedral group is denoted as $\langle D_n, \circ \rangle$, where \circ represents the composition of functions.

Proof:

First aim to show that composition is an operation.

Let $\phi, \Theta \in D_n$ and suppose the line between vertices i and j is an edge in P_n . Since $\Theta \in D_n$, the line between $\Theta(i)$ and $\Theta(j)$ is an edge of P_n .

Because $\phi \in D_n$ and the line between $\Theta(i)$ and $\Theta(j)$ is an edge, the line between $\phi(\Theta(i)) = (\phi \circ \Theta)(i)$ and $\phi(\Theta(j)) = (\phi \circ \Theta)(j)$ is an edge of P_n .

Composition of bijective functions is bijective, so it is closed.

G₁: Composition is associative.

G₂: Identity function $i(k) = k$ works.

G₃: The group inverse for a function is just the function's inverse.

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Lecture 8 (10/14)

Week 3, 10/14-10/18. Section 5: Subgroups, Section 6: Cyclic groups.

We can draw a circle denoted S_n , a composition symbol with different elements that can be represented either as a function (i.e., $1 \mapsto n$, $2 \mapsto n - 1$, $3 \mapsto 3$, ..., $n \mapsto 1$), or as a two-row matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & \dots & n \\ n & n-1 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

or as disjoint cycles $(\dots)(\dots)$. Today we will discuss the Dihedral group D_n , with different functions as its elements $Z_n \rightarrow Z_n$ (namely, $\{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$). These functions are onto, one-to-one, and preserve edges. For example, fix $n = 5$ and draw the regular 5-gon P_5 . Enumerate the vertices of the 5-gon from 0 to $n - 1$ (Z_n). The elements of the group will be functions mapping $0 \mapsto 1$, ..., that preserve the shape of the 5-gon.

Recall the definition: if there is an edge between two points, there must also be an edge between their images. For example, if we reflect the 5-gon across the 0 vertex, we can map $1 \mapsto 4$ and $4 \mapsto 1$, and $2 \mapsto 3$ with $3 \mapsto 2$. This gives the permutation:

$$\mu = (0)(14)(23)$$

We get the same shape, but the order of the vertices is reversed. We say that μ is in D_5 . A non-example would be a function from Z_n to Z_n that is onto and one-to-one but does not preserve the edges. For example, consider the permutation $\sigma = (123)(4)(5)$. We get the 5-gon that starts at 0 and goes counterclockwise as 3, 1, 2, 4. Since there was an edge that connected 0 and 1 in the original 5-gon, but they are now separated by 3 (no edge connects $\sigma(0) = 3$ to $\sigma(1) = 1$), σ does not preserve the edges. Therefore, σ is not in D_5 . Drawing the 5-gon as we did originally, we can say that 0 is mapped to itself and 1, 1 is mapped to 4, and 4 is mapped to 1. Thus, we get 0 connected to 1 below and connected to 4 above. Next, 1 is mapped to 2, and 3 is mapped to 4. To indicate what was changed, we can place parentheses next to 1 (like 1(4)) to show that 1 was swapped with 4.

Example:

Drawing the same 5-gon, we can send 0 to 1, 1 to 2, 2 to 3, 3 to 4, and 4 to 0. In a new picture, ρ is given by the same n -gon but rotated counterclockwise. We get 4(0) where 0 used to be, 0(1) where 1 used to be, and so on. The permutation would be $\rho = (01234)$. If we rotate again, we get all the numbers rotated counterclockwise, and the permutation would be $\rho^2 = (02413)$.

Observe that another way to write the elements μ and ρ in general is to

express

$$\boxed{\mu(k) = -k \pmod{n}}$$

For example, $\mu(0) = 0$, $\mu(1) = -1 = 4$ in Z_5 , and $\mu(2) = -2 = 3$ in Z_5 (see the figure of the circle Z_5). This looks very much like the modular addition function, where

$$\boxed{\rho(k) = k +_n 1}$$

The Dihedral group D_n has $2n$ elements. Now consider $\rho^2(k) = \rho \circ \rho(k) = \rho(\rho(k)) = \rho(k +_n 1) = (k +_n 1) +_n 1 = k +_n 2$.

For the previous example with $n = 5$, we get:

$$\rho^2(0) = 0 +_5 2 = 2, \quad \rho^2(2) = 2 +_5 2 = 4, \quad \rho^2(4) = 4 +_5 2 = 1, \quad \rho^2(1) = 1 +_5 2 = 3, \quad \rho^2(3) = 3 +_5 2 = 0$$

because we are working in Z_5 . Finally, consider $\mu^2(k) = \mu \circ \mu(k) = \mu(\mu(k)) = \mu(-k) = -(-k) = k$. Thus, μ^2 is the identity function.

Next, observe that $\rho^n(k) = \rho(\rho(\dots(\rho(k))))$ (composed n times) gives:

$$\rho^n(k) = k +_n 1 +_n 1 +_n \dots +_n 1 = k$$

so $\rho^n = \text{id}$, the identity function, where $1 \mapsto 1$, $2 \mapsto 2$, ..., $n \mapsto n$. This is an example of an element of order n , meaning we arrive at the identity function after n applications of ρ .

We can check the elements of the Dihedral group $D_n = \{e \text{ (the identity function)}, \rho, \rho^2, \rho^3, \dots, \rho^{n-1}, \mu, \mu\rho, \mu\rho^2, \dots, \mu\rho^{n-1}\}$, which indeed has $2n$ elements. (include last picture)

We will start with subgroups, which are subsets of a group. For example, consider a group G and its subgroup H . In the diagram below, $H \subseteq G$ represents a subgroup of G .

Subgroups

H is a subgroup of G if and only if:

$$H \leq G, \quad \text{and } H \text{ is a group with the induced operation from } G.$$

A proper subgroup exists if $H \leq G$ and the above holds.

The subgroup of G itself is the improper subgroup.

The subgroup of $\{e\}$ is the trivial subgroup, and every other subgroup is nontrivial.

Example:

$\mathbb{R}^n =$ additive group of real-valued vectors.

Subset of vectors with 0 in the first entry is a subgroup.

If a subset H of a group G is closed under the binary operation of G , and if H , with the induced operation from G , is itself a group, then H is called a **subgroup** of G .

Subgroup Notation

We use the following notations for subgroups:

- $H \leq G$: H is a subgroup of G . - $H \subset G$: H is a proper subgroup of G (i.e., H is a subgroup, but $H \neq G$). - $H \leq G$ but $H \neq G$: H is a nontrivial subgroup of G (i.e., H is not just the identity element $\{e\}$).

In particular, we say that H is a nontrivial subgroup of G if $H \neq \{e\}$, where e denotes the identity element.

Subgroup Notation

We use the following notations for subgroups:

- $H \leq G$: H is a subgroup of G .
- We denote $H < G$: This means H is a proper subgroup of G (i.e., $H \neq G$).
- We say that H is a nontrivial subgroup of G if $H \neq \{e\}$, where e is the identity element.
- Recall the notation: $H \subset G$ means H is a proper subset of G .

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Lecture 9 (10/16)

Week 3, 10/14-10/18. Section 5: Subgroups, Section 6: Cyclic groups.

Notation Conventions (for textbook, homework, etc.)

- $a * b$: Any binary operation.
- $a + b$: Commutative operations.
- $a \cdot b$: Not necessarily commutative (we don't know).

$$ab = a * b$$

$$a + b = b + a$$

$$a^3 = a \cdot a \cdot a$$

$$4a = a + a + a + a$$

(repetitive commutative operations)

- a^{-1} : Represents the inverse of a for a general operation.
- $-a$: Denotes the inverse for commutative operations.

$$\text{GL}(2, \mathbb{R}) \quad \text{in general:} \quad \text{GL}(n, F)$$

2x2 matrices on \mathbb{R} with nonzero determinant.

n x n matrices over F with nonzero determinant.

H is a subgroup of $G : H \leq G$.

H is a proper subgroup of $G : H \leqneq G$.

Example:

$(\mathbb{R}, +)$ is a group.

$$(2\mathbb{R}, +) \leq (\mathbb{R}, +) \quad (\text{even numbers}).$$

$$(\mathbb{Z}, +) \leq (\mathbb{Q}, +) \leq (\mathbb{R}, +) \leq (\mathbb{R}, +).$$

Nonexample (classic mistake):

$$(\mathbb{Q}_{\neq 0}, \cdot) \not\leq (\mathbb{R}, +)$$

We no longer have an identity element under the induced operation $+$.

Recall D_5 :

All permutations preserving a pentagon:

$$\langle D_5, \circ \rangle \leq \langle S_5, \circ \rangle$$

Recall:

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$$

$$\langle \{i, -1, i, 1\}, \cdot \rangle \leq \langle U, \cdot \rangle$$

Scenario:

Given a subset, determine if it is a subgroup.

Theorem: A subset $H \subseteq G$ is a subgroup with the same operation as G if and only if:

1. H is closed under its operation.
2. The identity element $e \in G$ is in H .
3. $\forall a \in H, \exists a^{-1} \in H$.

This will help us prove subsets are subgroups.

Cyclic Subgroups

Generated by one element only.

Example: $\langle \mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12} \rangle$

Suppose we have a subgroup $H \leq \mathbb{Z}_{12}$ and we know $3 \in H$.

$$3 + 3 = 6 \in H$$

$$3 + 6 = 9 \in H$$

$$6 + 6 = 0 \in H$$

So, having one element necessitates these other elements in H :

$$\{0, 3, 6, 9\} \leq \mathbb{Z}_{12}.$$

Theorem: Let G be a group and $a \in G$.

$$H = \{a^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

is a subgroup of G .

And it is the smallest subgroup of G that contains a , that is, every subgroup containing a must contain H .

Then H is called the cyclic subgroup generated by a .

$|H|$ is the order of a .

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Lecture 10 (10/18)

Week 3, 10/14-10/18. Section 5: Subgroups, Section 6: Cyclic groups.

Theorem: Let G be a group and $a \in G$. Then the set $H = \{a^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is a subgroup of G , and it is the smallest subgroup of G containing a . This subgroup is called the *cyclic subgroup of G generated by a* , and is denoted by $\langle a \rangle$. Therefore, we have $H = \langle a \rangle = \{a^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.

Definition (Order): The *order of a in G* is defined as the size (cardinality) of the cyclic subgroup $\langle a \rangle$. Specifically, if $\langle a \rangle$ contains a finite number of distinct elements, then a is said to have *finite order*, and the order of a is the number of elements in $\langle a \rangle$. If a generates an infinite number of distinct elements, then a has *infinite order*.

Proof:

We verify that $\langle a \rangle$ satisfies the subgroup criteria:

1. *Closure:* Let $h_1 = a^m$ and $h_2 = a^n$ be elements of $\langle a \rangle$, where $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$. The product of h_1 and h_2 is

$$h_1 h_2 = a^m a^n = a^{m+n}.$$

Since $m + n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $a^{m+n} \in \langle a \rangle$. Thus, $\langle a \rangle$ is closed under the group operation.

2. *Identity element:* Since $a^0 = e$, where e is the identity element of G , the identity element e is in $\langle a \rangle$.

3. *Inverses:* For any $a^n \in \langle a \rangle$, its inverse is a^{-n} because

$$a^n a^{-n} = a^0 = e.$$

Since $-n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $a^{-n} \in \langle a \rangle$. Therefore, every element in $\langle a \rangle$ has an inverse in $\langle a \rangle$.

Since $\langle a \rangle$ satisfies closure, contains the identity element, and contains inverses, $\langle a \rangle$ is a subgroup of G .

Finally, $\langle a \rangle$ is the smallest subgroup containing a , because any subgroup of G that contains a must also contain all powers of a , i.e., all elements of the form a^n for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Order of a : The order of a is the size of the subgroup $\langle a \rangle$. If $\langle a \rangle$ is finite, the order of a is the number of elements in $\langle a \rangle$. If $\langle a \rangle$ is infinite, a has infinite order.

Example: In the group $\langle \mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12} \rangle$, consider $a = 1$. Then $\langle 1 \rangle = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 11\}$, which has 12 elements. Hence, the order of 1 in \mathbb{Z}_{12} is 12.

Example: Consider the group $\langle \mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12} \rangle$ (the integers modulo 12 under addition). Let $a = 3$. Then the cyclic subgroup generated by 3 is:

$$\langle 3 \rangle = \{3^0, 3^1, 3^2, 3^3\} = \{e, 3, 6, 9\}.$$

Thus, $\langle 3 \rangle = \{e, 3, 6, 9\}$, which contains 4 elements. Therefore, the order of 3 in \mathbb{Z}_{12} is 4.

Infinite Order Example: In the group $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$ (the integers under addition), consider $a = 3$. The cyclic subgroup generated by 3 is:

$$\langle 3 \rangle = \{ \dots, -9, -6, -3, e, 3, 6, 9, \dots \}.$$

In this case, $\langle 3 \rangle$ contains an infinite number of elements, so the order of 3 in \mathbb{Z} is infinite.

Definition: A group G is called *cyclic* if there exists an element $a \in G$ such that $\langle a \rangle = G$. In other words, G is cyclic if every element of G can be written as a^n for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Example: The group $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$ (the integers under addition) is cyclic, generated by 1. Specifically, we have:

$$\langle 1 \rangle = \{ \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \} = \mathbb{Z}.$$

Thus, \mathbb{Z} is cyclic with $\langle 1 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}$.

Non-example: The group $\langle \mathbb{R}, + \rangle$ (the real numbers under addition) is *not* cyclic. There does not exist any element $a \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $\langle a \rangle = \mathbb{R}$. No single real number can generate all of \mathbb{R} under addition.

Theorem: Every cyclic group is commutative (abelian).

Proof:

Let G be a cyclic group generated by some element $a \in G$, so that $G = \langle a \rangle$. This means that for any $x, y \in G$, we can write $x = a^m$ and $y = a^n$ for some integers $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Now, consider the product xy :

$$xy = a^m a^n = a^{m+n}.$$

Similarly, consider the product yx :

$$yx = a^n a^m = a^{n+m}.$$

Since $a^{m+n} = a^{n+m}$ (because addition of integers is commutative), we have

$$xy = yx.$$

Thus, the group G is commutative.

Since G was arbitrary, we conclude that *every cyclic group is commutative*.

Example

$$\psi = e^{\frac{2\pi i}{5}}$$

The set of 5th roots of unity is: $\{1, \psi, \psi^2, \psi^3, \psi^4\}$

$$\psi^5 = e^{i2\pi} = 1 \implies \text{The order of } \psi \text{ is } 5$$

Graph shows the complex numbers ψ^k for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$ spaced around the unit circle.

Let $\psi = e^{\frac{2\pi i}{5}}$. The cyclic subgroup generated by ψ is:

$$\langle \psi \rangle = \{\psi^0, \psi^1, \psi^2, \psi^3, \psi^4\} \subset \langle \mathbb{C}, \cdot \rangle.$$

Since $\psi^5 = e^{i2\pi} = 1$, we conclude that the order of ψ is 5.

Next Example:

Consider the group $\langle 2\mathbb{Z}, + \rangle \subset \langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$, which is the set of all even integers. This can be written as:

$$\langle 2 \rangle = \{2n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\} = \{\dots, -4, -2, 0, 2, 4, \dots\},$$

which is a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} .

Corollary: All subgroups of \mathbb{Z} are cyclic. Therefore, the only subgroups of \mathbb{Z} are: - $\{0\}$, which is generated by 0, - \mathbb{Z} itself, generated by $\langle 1 \rangle$, - $\langle 2 \rangle = 2\mathbb{Z}$, which consists of all even integers, - More generally, $n\mathbb{Z}$, which is generated by $\langle n \rangle$ for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Thus, every subgroup of \mathbb{Z} is of the form $n\mathbb{Z}$, generated by some integer n .

Question: Is \mathbb{Z}_{10} with addition modulo 10 a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} under standard addition?

Answer: No, \mathbb{Z}_{10} is not a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} .

Explanation: The group \mathbb{Z}_{10} is the set of integers modulo 10 under the operation $+_{10}$ (addition modulo 10). On the other hand, \mathbb{Z} is the set of all integers under standard addition $+$.

For \mathbb{Z}_{10} to be a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} , two conditions must be satisfied: 1. \mathbb{Z}_{10} must be closed under the group operation of \mathbb{Z} , which is standard addition. 2. The group operation in \mathbb{Z}_{10} , $+_{10}$, must be the restriction of the group operation in \mathbb{Z} , which is $+$.

However, these conditions are not satisfied. Consider the two elements 9 and 9 in \mathbb{Z}_{10} :

$$9 +_{10} 9 = 18 \pmod{10} = 8 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_{10}).$$

On the other hand, in \mathbb{Z} , the sum of $9 + 9$ is:

$$9 + 9 = 18 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}).$$

Since $9 +_{10} 9$ in \mathbb{Z}_{10} gives 8, and $9 + 9$ in \mathbb{Z} gives 18, the induced operation $+_{10}$ is not the same as the group operation in \mathbb{Z} .

Therefore, \mathbb{Z}_{10} under $+_{10}$ is not a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} under $+$.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh
Lecture 11 (10/21)

Week 4, 10/21-10/25. Section 7: Generating sets and Cayley Di-graphs. Catch up and review.

Theorem: Every subgroup of a cyclic group is cyclic.

Corollary: The subgroups of $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$ are precisely the groups $\langle n\mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. For example, $\mathbb{Z} = \langle 1 \rangle$ gives us the full set of integers \mathbb{Z} .

In other words, a cyclic subgroup is a group generated by one element in the group.

Consider $\langle -2 \rangle, \langle -1 \rangle, \langle 0 \rangle, \langle 1 \rangle, \langle 2 \rangle$. So, for example, $\langle 3\mathbb{Z}, + \rangle = \langle \{ \dots, -6, -3, 0, 3, 6, \dots \}, + \rangle$.

Looking at our earlier example, $\langle 0 \rangle$ gives us $\langle \{0\}, + \rangle$, the trivial subgroup, and $\langle 1 \rangle$ gives us $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$, which is \mathbb{Z} itself. $\langle 2 \rangle$ gives us the set of even integers in \mathbb{Z} , and so on. All the subgroups are infinite other than the trivial subgroup given by $\langle 0 \rangle$.

Recall that the order of a in G was defined as $|\langle a \rangle|$. So all non-trivial elements in \mathbb{Z} have infinite order. For instance, $|\langle 3 \rangle| = |\{ \dots, -6, -3, 0, 3, \dots \}| = \infty$, i.e., $\text{ord}(3) = \infty$.

Example: $H = \{4n + 6m \mid m, n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. H is a subgroup of $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$.

$$(4n_1 + 6m_1) + (4n_2 + 6m_2) = 4(n_1 + n_2) + 6(m_1 + m_2).$$

We check the rest (identity and inverses).

Question: To which of the subgroups $\langle n\mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$ is H equal?

Answer: $H = \langle 2 \rangle$.

Definition: Let r be a positive integer and s be a nonnegative integer (i.e., take two positive numbers, one of which can be zero, but not both). Then the positive generator d of the cyclic group $H = \{nr + ms \mid n, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ under addition is the greatest common divisor (gcd) of r and s . In fact, $d = \text{gcd}(r, s)$ is the smallest positive number in H .

Example: $\text{gcd}(42, 72)$:

$$42 = 7 \cdot 3 \cdot 2, \quad 72 = 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 3.$$

Since $3 \cdot 2$ appear in the prime factors of both 42 and 72, the greatest common divisor (gcd) is $2 \cdot 3 = 6$. Therefore,

$$H = \{42m + 72n \mid m, n \in \mathbb{Z}\} = \langle 6 \rangle.$$

Remark: This can be generalized to any finite combination, for example:

$$H = \{42m + 72n + 12p \mid m, n, p \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

$\langle 6 \rangle$ is therefore the gcd of 42, 72, and 12, i.e., $\text{gcd}(42, 72, 12) = 6$.

Definition: r and s are called relatively prime if $\text{gcd}(r, s) = 1$.

Theorem: Let G be a cyclic group with generator a .

- If the order of G is infinite, then G is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z} .

- If the order of G is n , then G is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_n with modular addition.

In other words, if the order of G is n , then G is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +_n \rangle$.

Theorem: Let G be a cyclic group with generator a .

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In other words, if the order of G is n , then G is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +_n \rangle$.

Example: $\langle \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{Z} \rangle = B = \{\dots, -2, -1.5, -1, -0.5, 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, \dots\}$.

By the theorem, $B \cong \mathbb{Z}$. That is, define $\Phi : B \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ as $\Phi(b) = 2b$.

Verification: We verify that Φ is an isomorphism.

- **One-to-one:** If $\Phi(b_1) = \Phi(b_2)$, then $2b_1 = 2b_2$, which implies $b_1 = b_2$.

Thus, Φ is injective.

- **Onto:** For every $z \in \mathbb{Z}$, there exists a $b = \frac{z}{2} \in B$ such that $\Phi(b) = z$.

Thus, Φ is surjective.

- **Operation preservation:** We check the final isomorphism condition:
 $\Phi(a + b) = \Phi(a) + \Phi(b)$.

$$\text{LHS: } \Phi(a + b) = 2(a + b) = 2a + 2b.$$

$$\text{RHS: } \Phi(a) + \Phi(b) = 2a + 2b.$$

Therefore, $\Phi(a + b) = \Phi(a) + \Phi(b)$, verifying that Φ preserves the binary operation (addition).

Thus, $B \cong \mathbb{Z}$.

Example of a finite group: Consider the set of complex numbers \mathbb{C} . We define the group $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$, which is the set of complex numbers with modulus 1.

Within U , there is a subgroup U_n , consisting of all the roots of the equation $z^n = 1$. That is,

$$U_n = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid z^n = 1\} = \{\psi = e^{i2\pi/n}, \psi^2, \psi^3, \dots, \psi^n = \psi^0 = 1\} = \langle \psi \rangle.$$

This is a finite (order n) subgroup of $\langle \mathbb{C}, \cdot \rangle$.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Lecture 12 (10/23)

Week 4, 10/21-10/25. Section 7: Generating sets and Cayley Di-graphs. Catch up and review.

Theorem: Every subgroup of a cyclic group is cyclic.

Theorem: Let G be a cyclic group.

1. If $|G| = \infty$, then $\langle G, * \rangle$ is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}, + \rangle$, where \mathbb{Z} is the set of integers under addition.
2. If $|G| = n$, then $\langle G, * \rangle$ is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +_n \rangle$, where \mathbb{Z}_n is the set of integers modulo n under addition.

Explanation:

- In the first case, an infinite cyclic group is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z} because both have elements that can be expressed as powers (or multiples) of a generator.
- In the second case, a finite cyclic group of order n is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_n , as both structures consist of n elements that cycle after n steps.

Example:

Consider the group of n -th roots of unity U_n , where $U_n = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid z^n = 1\}$. We claim that $\langle U_n, \cdot \rangle$ is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +_n \rangle$. For example:

$$U_3 = \left\{ e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}}, e^{i\frac{4\pi}{3}}, 1 \right\}, \quad U_2 = \{1, -1\}, \quad U_4 = \{1, -1, i, -i\}.$$

These elements are cyclic, forming a cyclic group under multiplication. We now present a proof of the general case.

Proof: Let G be a cyclic group, and let $a \in G$ be a generator of G (i.e., $\langle a \rangle = G$).

Case 1: $|G| = \infty$. In this case, $G = \langle a \rangle = \{a^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. We define a map $\phi : G \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ by

$$\phi(a^n) = n.$$

This map is clearly a homomorphism since:

$$\phi(a^m \cdot a^n) = \phi(a^{m+n}) = m + n = \phi(a^m) + \phi(a^n).$$

Moreover, ϕ is bijective because G is infinite, and every element a^n corresponds to exactly one integer n . Thus, $G \cong \mathbb{Z}$.

Case 2: $|G| = n$. In this case, $G = \langle a \rangle = \{e, a, a^2, \dots, a^{n-1}\}$, where $a^n = e$. Define a map $\phi : G \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$ by

$$\phi(a^k) = k \pmod{n}.$$

This map is again a homomorphism:

$$\phi(a^m \cdot a^k) = \phi(a^{m+k}) = (m+k) \pmod{n} = \phi(a^m) +_n \phi(a^k).$$

Since ϕ is both injective and surjective, it is an isomorphism. Therefore, $G \cong \mathbb{Z}_n$. To verify that the map is well-defined, we must show that each element in G can be written uniquely as a^n for some integer n . Let's go through the steps in detail and correct any parts if needed:

1. Suppose that $n > m$ and $a^n = a^m$. This implies that:

$$a^n \cdot a^{-m} = a^m \cdot a^{-m}.$$

Simplifying both sides:

$$a^{n-m} = a^0 = e,$$

where e is the identity element of G .

2. Now, denote $b = n - m$, so we have:

$$a^b = e.$$

This shows that $b = 0$, since a is a generator of the cyclic group G and the powers of a are distinct. Therefore, $n = m$.

This implies that if $a^n = a^m$, then $n = m$. Hence, each element in G can be written uniquely as a^n for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ in the infinite case or $n \in \{0, 1, \dots, |G|-1\}$ in the finite case. Thus, the map is well-defined, as no two distinct exponents can produce the same group element.

Claim: If there exists a positive integer b such that $a^b = e$, then G must be finite.

Proof:

1. Consider the powers of a : a^0, a^1, a^2, \dots
2. If there exists some $b > 0$ such that $a^b = e$, then the powers of a start repeating after b steps. Specifically, for any $k \geq b$, we have:

$$a^k = a^{k-b} \quad (\text{because } a^b = e).$$

3. This means that the group $G = \langle a \rangle$ consists of the elements:

$$G = \{e, a, a^2, \dots, a^{b-1}\},$$

and therefore $|G| = b$, making G a finite group of order b .

Thus, if there exists a power b such that $a^b = e$, the cyclic group must be finite, since the elements of the group start repeating after this point, and there are exactly b distinct elements.

In other words, once you have $a^b = e$, the group becomes periodic and finite. This is the defining property of a finite cyclic group. Therefore, G is finite if there is a non-zero power of a that gives the identity element e . Since $a^n = e$, we have $G = \langle a \rangle = \{a^0, a^1, a^2, \dots, a^{b-1}\}$, and any other powers of a are equal to one of these, as powers of a^b cycle back to previously listed elements.

To check if the map is isomorphic, we must verify that it is both one-to-one (injective) and onto (surjective).

Injectivity: Suppose $\phi(a^m) = \phi(a^n)$. This implies:

$$m = n,$$

and hence:

$$a^m = a^n.$$

Therefore, the map is injective.

Surjectivity: To show that the map is onto, let n be any element in \mathbb{Z} . The element $\phi(a^n)$ maps to n , meaning every element $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ has a preimage in G . Thus, the map is surjective.

Since the map is both injective and surjective, it is a bijection, and hence an isomorphism.

Now we check the homomorphism. We need to check that if we take two elements and first star them together,

$$\Phi(a^n \cdot a^m) = \Phi(a^n) + \Phi(a^m) \text{ (with } + \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}\text{)}.$$

And indeed:

$$\text{LHS} = \Phi(a^n \cdot a^m)$$

which is a starred with itself $n + m$ times. So, by the definition of Φ ,

$$\Phi(a^{n+m}) = n + m$$

which, by the definition of Φ , equals

$$\Phi(a^n) + \Phi(a^m).$$

Any property something has, its image must have the same property. So, isomorphisms tell us that two groups share the same properties.

Example: $\langle U_n, \cdot \rangle$ is isomorphic to $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, + \rangle$.

$$U_n = \{\xi = e^{2\pi i/n}, \xi^2, \xi^3, \dots, \xi^{n-1}\}$$

In this case, $\Phi : U_n \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$, and $\Phi(\xi^n) = n$.

Theorem: Let G be a cyclic group with n elements, generated by a . Let $b = a^s$. Then b generates a cyclic subgroup $H = \langle b \rangle$ containing $\frac{n}{d}$ elements, where $d = \gcd(n, s)$.

In short,

$$|\langle a^s \rangle| = \frac{|G|}{\gcd(s, |G|)}.$$

Example: If the group \mathbb{Z}_{12} has 12 elements, then $|\langle 3 \rangle|$ is the subgroup of \mathbb{Z}_{12} generated by $\langle 1 \rangle$ (where $1 = a$).

1 is the generator of G , denoted $\mathbb{Z}_{12} = \langle 1 \rangle$. For $\langle 3 \rangle$, which is given by $1+1+1$ or 1^3 using this operation, we calculate:

$$|\langle 3 \rangle| = \frac{|\mathbb{Z}_{12}|}{\gcd(3, |\mathbb{Z}_{12}|)} = \frac{12}{\gcd(3, 12)} = \frac{12}{3} = 4.$$

Indeed, $\langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3, 6, 9\}$, which has order 4.

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Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 13 (10/25)

Week 4, 10/21-10/25. Section 7: Generating sets and Cayley Di-graphs. Catch up and review.

$$\langle 2 \rangle \leq Z_6$$

$$\{0, 2, 4\} \text{ of } Z_6$$

What is the subgroup generated by $\{2, 3\}$?

$$H = \{2, 4, 3, 5, 1, 0\} = Z_6$$

Section 7: Generating Sets

Def: Let G be a group.

Let $a_i \in G$, $i \in I$, where I is a set of indices.

The smallest subgroup of G containing $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ is the subgroup generated by $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$.

If this subgroup is all of G , then $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ generates G , and $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ is a generating set of G and are called the generators of G .

Example: Subgroup Generation

Example:

Let

$$H = \{4i + 6j \mid i, j \in Z\} \leq Z.$$

- H is generated by $\{4, 6\}$.
- H is also generated by $\gcd(4, 6) = 2$ (so H is generated by 2).

Note: The same subgroup can be generated by different generating sets. From the previous example, we know Z_6 is generated by 1. Similarly, Z_6 is also generated by $\{2, 3\}$, so a group or a subgroup can have more than one generating set.

Let $I = \{1, 2\}$ where:

$$a_1 = 4, \quad a_2 = 6.$$

Example: Subgroup Generated by a_1 and a_2 in S_6

Let $G = S_6$ and consider the following:

$$H = \{a_2^3 = e, a_1 = (12), a_2 = (456), a_2^2 = (465), a_1 a_2 = (12)(456), a_1 a_2^2 = (12)(465)\}.$$

Note that a_2 and a_2^2 are inverses.

Theorem: Subgroup Generation

If G is a group and $a_i \in G$ for $i \in I$, where $I \neq \emptyset$, then the subgroup H of G generated by $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ consists precisely of those elements that are finite products of the integral powers of the a_i 's.

Cayley Diagrams

Given a group G and a generating set $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$, we construct a Cayley diagram as follows:

- **Points (Vertices):** The vertices of the diagram correspond to the elements of G .
- **Arrows (Edges):** The edges between the vertices represent the action of the generators $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ on the group elements. Specifically, for any element $g \in G$, there is an edge from g to ga_i for each generator $a_i \in \{a_i \mid i \in I\}$.

The Cayley diagram provides a visual representation of the structure of G with respect to its generating set $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$.

Cayley Diagram Connection Rule

In a Cayley diagram for a group G and a generating set $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$, the rule for connecting elements is as follows:

Rule: For any elements $x, y \in G$ and any generator $a_i \in \{a_i \mid i \in I\}$, there is an arrow labeled a_i connecting x to y if and only if:

$$xa_i = y.$$

In other words, if multiplying x by the generator a_i on the right results in y , we draw an arrow from x to y , labeled by a_i .

Example 1: Z_6 Generated by $\{1\}$

Consider the group Z_6 generated by $\{1\}$. We arrange 6 points in a circle and label them 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. The operation is modular addition, so the rule is $x +_6 1 = y$.

- For $x = 0$, we have $0 +_6 1 = 1$, so we draw an arrow from the point labeled 0 to the point labeled 1.
- For $x = 1$, we have $1 +_6 1 = 2$, so we draw an arrow from 1 to 2.
- Continuing this process, for $x = 5$, we have $5 +_6 1 = 0$, so we draw an arrow from 5 back to 0.

The diagram forms a cycle around the circle.

Example 2: Z_6 Generated by $\{2, 3\}$

Now consider Z_6 generated by $\{2, 3\}$. We arrange the points as follows:

- Points 0, 2, 4 in one column.
- Points 3, 5, 1 in the second column.

We use the equation $x +_6 2 = y$:

- $0 +_6 2 = 2$, so 0 is mapped to 2.
- $2 +_6 2 = 4$, so 2 is mapped to 4.
- $4 +_6 2 = 0$, so 4 is mapped back to 0.
- In the second column, $3 +_6 2 = 5$, so 3 is mapped to 5.
- $5 +_6 2 = 1$, so 5 is mapped to 1.
- $1 +_6 2 = 3$, so 1 is mapped back to 3.

Thus, we observe two disjoint cycles: one involving $\{0, 2, 4\}$ and the other involving $\{1, 3, 5\}$.

Recap for Cayley Diagram

Given a group G and generating set $\{a_i : i \in I\}$, we make a diagram for G .

Points = vertices = elements of G

Arrows = edges = generators $\{a_i : i \in I\}$

$$x \xrightarrow{a_i} y \quad \text{denote: } xa_i = y$$

We cannot express left multiplication $a_i x$. However, we can still generate all elements using only the right operation.

Example: Z_6 generated by $\{1\}$.

Z_6 generated by $\{2, 3\}$.

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Lecture 14 (10/28)

Week 5, 10/28-11/1. Section 8: Groups of permutation. Section 9:

Finitely generated abelian groups.

Recall: Cayley digraphs from the last lecture.

If $xa = y$:

$$x \xrightarrow{a} y$$

Convention: If $xa = y$ and $ya = x$, just draw an undirected line instead of bidirectional arrows.

Note: 3 is an order 2 element. In general, if an element a has order 2 ($a*a = e$), then the arrows representing a will be replaced by a single undirected edge.

Theorem: $xa = y$ always has a unique solution (there is always one unique edge path from x to y in the Cayley digraph).

(Cayley digraphs with any number of generators are strongly connected.)

Section 8

Definition: Let G, G' be groups and $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a map between them. Then ϕ is a homomorphism if:

$$\phi(x_1x_2) = \phi(x_1)\phi(x_2) \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in G$$

(Homomorphism property)

Note: Like an isomorphism, which need not be bijective.

Example:

$$\phi : \langle R, + \rangle \rightarrow \langle U, \cdot \rangle \quad (\text{unit circle in } C).$$

Defined by:

$$\phi(x) = e^{2\pi i x}$$

Not injective because $\phi(1) = \phi(0)$, and many more cases.

Check homomorphism property:

Let $a, b \in R$.

$$\phi(a + b) = e^{2\pi i(a+b)}$$

$$\phi(a)\phi(b) = e^{2\pi i a} \cdot e^{2\pi i b} = e^{2\pi i(a+b)}.$$

Thus, the homomorphism property is satisfied.

Definition: Let $\phi : X \rightarrow Y$.

For $A \subseteq X$, we call $\phi[A]$ the **image** of A under ϕ :

$$\phi[A] = \{\phi(a) \mid a \in A\}.$$

For $B \subseteq Y$, $\phi^{-1}[B]$ is the **inverse image** of B :

$$\phi^{-1}[B] = \{x \in X \mid \phi(x) \in B\}.$$

Definition: Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism.

Then $\phi^{-1}(e')$ is called the **kernel** of G .

The kernel is a subgroup of G .

In our earlier example $R \rightarrow U$, the kernel is Z .

We say $\ker(\phi) = Z$.

Theorem:

Let ϕ be a homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$.

Let $e \in G, e' \in G'$ be the identity elements.

1. Under any homomorphism, $\phi(e) = e'$.
2. $\phi(a^{-1}) = \phi(a)^{-1}$.
3. If $H \leq G$, then $\phi[H] \leq G'$.
4. If $K' \leq G'$, then $\phi^{-1}[K'] \leq G$.

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Lecture 15 (11/1): Sections 8 and 9

Week 5, 10/28-11/1. Section 8: Groups of permutation. Section 9: Finitely generated abelian groups.

Section 8

Reference: Homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$

$$\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$$

Note: If ϕ is a 1-1 (injective) homomorphism, then:

$$\phi : G \xrightarrow{\text{isom}} \phi[G] \leq G'$$

(where $\phi[G] = \text{Im}(\phi)$)

Definition:

$$\ker(\phi) = \phi^{-1}[\{e'\}] = \{g \in G \mid \phi(g) = e'\}$$

(is a subgroup).

$\ker(\phi)$ contains the trivial subgroup $\{e\}$.

Cayley's Theorem

Statement:

For any group G , there exists a group isomorphism from G to a subgroup of the group of permutations S_G .

This is established via the *left regular representation*:

$$G \rightarrow S_G$$

Groups of Permutations

1) **Decomposition of Permutations:**

Every permutation can be decomposed as a product of transpositions.

Example:

$$(1\ 4\ 5\ 6)(2\ 1\ 5) = (1\ 6)(1\ 5)(1\ 4)(2\ 5)(2\ 1)$$

Note: This decomposition is not unique. However:

- 2) Each permutation is either equal to an *odd product of transpositions* or to an *even product of transpositions*.

Definition:

$$\text{sgn}(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is the product of an **even** number of transpositions,} \\ -1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is the product of an **odd** number of transpositions.} \end{cases}$$

$$\ker(\text{sgn}) = \left. \begin{cases} \text{all permutations that are products of an even number of transpositions} \\ = A_n \subseteq S_n \end{cases} \right\}$$

A_n is the **alternating group**.

Example:

$$(12)(12) = e \in A_n$$

Finitely Generated Abelian Groups

Definition: The Cartesian product of sets $B_1, B_2, B_3, \dots, B_n$ is the set of all ordered n -tuples

$$(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n)$$

where $b_i \in B_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Notation: $B_1 \times B_2 \times \dots \times B_n$ or $\prod_{i=1}^n B_i$.

Definition: Let G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n be groups. Define the operation on the Cartesian product:

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \cdot (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) = (a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, \dots, a_n b_n),$$

for $a_i, b_i \in G_i$, $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Then:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n G_i = G_1 \times G_2 \times \dots \times G_n$$

is a **group**, called the **direct product** of the groups G_i .

Proof:

- **Closure under multiplication:**

For any elements $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n), (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) \in \prod G_i$, their product $(a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, \dots, a_n b_n) \in \prod G_i$.

- **Associativity:**

Since multiplication in each G_i is associative, multiplication in $\prod G_i$ is associative.

- **Identity:**

The element $(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) \in \prod G_i$, where e_i is the identity in G_i , serves as the identity element.

- **Inverses:**

For $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \prod G_i$, its inverse is $(a_1^{-1}, a_2^{-1}, \dots, a_n^{-1})$, where a_i^{-1} is the inverse of a_i in G_i .

Examples

Example 1: Consider $\mathbb{Z}_2 = \{0, 1\}$ and $\mathbb{Z}_3 = \{0, 1, 2\}$ under addition modulo 2 and 3, respectively.

The group $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ consists of the elements:

$$\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (0, 2), (1, 0), (1, 1), (1, 2)\}$$

Compute:

$$(0, 2) + (1, 2) = (0 +_2 1, 2 +_3 2) = (1, 1)$$

Question: Is $\langle(1, 1)\rangle$ equal to $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$?

Solution: Let's compute the cyclic subgroup generated by $(1, 1)$:

$$(1, 1) = (1, 1)$$

$$(1, 1) + (1, 1) = (0, 2)$$

$$(0, 2) + (1, 1) = (1, 0)$$

$$(1, 0) + (1, 1) = (0, 1)$$

$$(0, 1) + (1, 1) = (1, 2)$$

$$(1, 2) + (1, 1) = (0, 0)$$

Thus, $\langle(1, 1)\rangle = \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$. Therefore, $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ is a cyclic group generated by $(1, 1)$.

Example 2: Consider $\mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$.

Compute:

$$(1, 1) + (1, 1) = (2, 2), \quad (1, 1) + (1, 1) + (1, 1) = (0, 0)$$

Thus, $\langle(1, 1)\rangle = \{(0, 0), (1, 1), (2, 2)\} \subsetneq \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$.

Therefore, $\mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ is not cyclic.

Generating Set for $\mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$: The set $\{(1, 0), (0, 1)\}$ generates $\mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$.

Theorems

Theorem 1: Let $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \prod G_i$. If a_i is of finite order r_i , then the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) in $\prod G_i$ is equal to the **least common multiple (lcm)** of all the r_i .

Example: In $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$:

- $a_1 = 1$ has order 2 in \mathbb{Z}_2 .
- $a_2 = 1$ has order 3 in \mathbb{Z}_3 .
- Therefore, $(1, 1)$ has order $\text{lcm}(2, 3) = 6$.

Theorem 2: The group $\mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n$ is cyclic and isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_{mn} if and only if m and n are relatively prime.

Reason: If m and n are relatively prime, then $\text{lcm}(m, n) = m \cdot n$. Therefore, the order of $(1, 1)$ is $m \cdot n$, and $(1, 1)$ generates $\mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n$, making it cyclic and isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_{mn} .

Summary

- The direct product of groups allows us to build new groups from known ones.
- The order of an element in a direct product is determined by the least common multiple of the orders of its components.
- A direct product $\mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n$ is cyclic if and only if m and n are relatively prime.

Lecture by Professor Gil Goffar

Review of Section 8

In Section 8, we defined:

- **Homomorphism:** A function $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ between two groups that preserves the group operation:

$$\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$$

- **One-to-One Homomorphisms:** If ϕ is injective (one-to-one), then ϕ is an isomorphism from G onto $\phi[G]$, a subgroup of G' :

$$\phi : G \xrightarrow{\text{isom}} \phi[G] \leq G'$$

- **Kernel of a Homomorphism:** Defined as:

$$\ker(\phi) = \phi^{-1}[\{e'\}] = \{g \in G \mid \phi(g) = e'\}$$

The kernel $\ker(\phi)$ is always a subgroup of G and contains the trivial subgroup $\{e\}$.

We also discussed Cayley's Theorem:

Cayley's Theorem: Every group G is isomorphic to a subgroup of the group of permutations S_G . This is established via the *left regular representation*:

$$G \rightarrow S_G$$

We noted the importance of groups of permutations and made key observations:

1. Every permutation can be decomposed into a product of transpositions (2-cycles).
2. This decomposition is not unique; however, the parity (evenness or oddness) of the number of transpositions is unique.
3. **Sign of a Permutation:** Defined as:

$$\text{sgn}(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is the product of an even number of transpositions,} \\ -1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is the product of an odd number of transpositions.} \end{cases}$$

The sign function sgn is a homomorphism from S_n to $\{1, -1\}$.

4. The kernel of sgn is the alternating group A_n , consisting of all even permutations:

$$\ker(\text{sgn}) = A_n \subseteq S_n$$

Section 9: Direct Products and Finitely Generated Abelian Groups

Cartesian Product of Sets: The Cartesian product of sets B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n is the set of all ordered n -tuples (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) where $b_i \in B_i$.

Direct Product of Groups: Given groups G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n , the direct product $G = G_1 \times G_2 \times \dots \times G_n$ is defined with the operation:

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \cdot (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) = (a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, \dots, a_n b_n)$$

Properties: - Closure under the operation. - Associativity. - Identity element (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) , where e_i is the identity in G_i . - Inverses $(a_1^{-1}, a_2^{-1}, \dots, a_n^{-1})$.

Examples:

- $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$: Consists of elements like $(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)$.
- $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$: As previously discussed.

Theorem: Let $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in G_1 \times G_2 \times \dots \times G_n$. If each a_i has finite order r_i , then the order of a is $\text{lcm}(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$.

Consequences:

- If the orders r_i are relatively prime, the order of a is their product.
- $\mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n$ is cyclic and isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_{mn} if and only if m and n are relatively prime.

Proof Sketch:

- The element $(1, 1, \dots, 1)$ can generate the entire group if the orders are relatively prime.
 - The LCM of the orders is mn , so the element has order mn and generates the group.
-

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Notes prepared by Akiva Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 15 (11/1)

Week 5, 10/28-11/1. Section 8: Groups of permutation. Section 9:

Finitely generated abelian groups.

Recall Theorem from Last Time:

Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism.

1. $\phi(e) = e'$
2. $\forall a \in G, \phi(a^{-1}) = \phi(a)^{-1}$
3. $\forall H \leq G, \phi[H] \leq G'$
4. $\forall K' \leq G', \phi^{-1}[K'] \leq G$

We will begin by proving these.

Proof:

1. We know:

$$\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b) \quad \forall a, b \in G.$$

Let $a = e$ and $b = e$:

$$\phi(e) = \phi(e \cdot e),$$

$$\phi(e) = \phi(e)\phi(e).$$

By cancellation in groups:

$$(\phi(e))^{-1}\phi(e) = (\phi(e))^{-1}\phi(e)\phi(e),$$

$$e' = \phi(e),$$

where e' is the identity in G' .

2. Follows very similarly:

2. Follows very similarly:

$$\phi(e) = \phi(a \cdot a^{-1}) = \phi(a)\phi(a^{-1}).$$

Since $\phi(e) = e'$, we have:

$$e' = \phi(a)\phi(a^{-1}).$$

$\phi(a^{-1}) = (\phi(a))^{-1}$, because operating $\phi(a)\phi(a^{-1})$ gives the **identity in G'** .

3. Let $H \leq G$. We want to show (WTS) $\phi[H]$ is a subgroup of G' .

Need to check:

• **Closed?**

Let $\phi(a), \phi(b) \in \phi[H]$.

$$\phi(a)\phi(b) = \phi(ab).$$

Since $a, b \in H$ and H is closed, $ab \in H$.

$$\implies \phi(ab) \in \phi[H].$$

- **Identity:**

We want to show (WTS) $e' \in \phi[H]$.

Note $e \in H$ because $H \leq G$.

Then by (1), $\phi(e) = e' \in \phi[H]$.

- **Inverses:**

Skipped proof, but it can be shown similarly by using (2).
4. Skipped proof, but similar to (3).

Cayley's Theorem

Theorem: Every group is isomorphic to a subgroup of S_A for some set A .

We will always have:

$$\phi : G \rightarrow S \quad (\text{we don't yet know what goes here}).$$

Preparations:

Note: If $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ is a homomorphism, injective but maybe not surjective,

Then $\phi : G \rightarrow \phi[G] \leq G'$ is an isomorphism.

Explanation: Map it to a smaller codomain so it is surjective.

Definition: Left regular representation

Let G be a group. Then $\phi : G \rightarrow S_G$ is defined by:

$$\phi(x) = \lambda_x, \quad \text{where } \lambda_x(g) = xg \quad \forall g \in G.$$

This is called the **left regular representation (LRR)** of G .

(We will use this to get from groups to permutations.)

λ_x is a permutation on the elements of G .

Example: $Z_3 = \{0, 1, 2\}$

λ_2 is a permutation on Z_3 .

$$0 \mapsto 2 * 0 = 2$$

$$1 \mapsto 2 * 1 = 0$$

$$2 \mapsto 2 * 2 = 1$$

We can write in disjoint cycle notation: $(0, 2, 1)$.

Comment: λ_x is bijective and therefore is a permutation.

Injectivity:

$$\lambda_x(g) = \lambda_x(h)$$

$$\implies xg = xh$$

$$\text{Left cancel } x \implies g = h.$$

Surjectivity: Proof skipped.

Proof for Cayley's Theorem

Let G be a group, and $\phi : G \rightarrow S_G$ be defined by the LRR (Left Regular Representation). Namely, define:

$$\phi(x) = \lambda_x \in S_G.$$

We want to show that ϕ is an injective homomorphism, so:

$$\phi : G \rightarrow \phi[G]$$

is an isomorphism. Therefore, G is isomorphic to a subgroup:

$$\phi[G] \leq S_G.$$

1. Show that ϕ is a homomorphism.

Let $x, y \in G$.

We want to show (WTS):

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(xy) &= \phi(x)\phi(y) \\ \implies \lambda_{xy} &= \lambda_x\lambda_y.\end{aligned}$$

Namely, we will show that:

$$\lambda_{xy}(g) = (\lambda_x \circ \lambda_y)(g).$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{xy}(g) &= (xy)g = x(yg), \\ (\lambda_x \circ \lambda_y)(g) &= \lambda_x(\lambda_y(g)) = \lambda_x(yg) = x(yg).\end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is shown that ϕ is a homomorphism.

2. Prove that ϕ is injective (one-to-one).

Suppose $\phi(x) = \phi(y)$.

$$\begin{aligned}\implies \lambda_x(e) &= \lambda_y(e). \\ \implies xe &= ye. \\ \implies x &= y.\end{aligned}$$

Since ϕ is shown to be an injective homomorphism, there exists an isomorphism by restricting our codomain (as we mentioned earlier).

Groups of Permutations Continued (S_n)

Definition: A cycle of length 2 is called a **transposition**.

Theorem: Any non-trivial permutation is a product of transpositions.

Proof: Suppose we have a long cycle:

$$C = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n).$$

Then let our transpositions be:

$$(a_1, a_n) \circ (a_1, a_{n-1}) \circ \dots \circ (a_1, a_3) \circ (a_1, a_2).$$

This recovers C . (*Recall, composition works right to left.*)

Note: This decomposition into transpositions is not unique, but interestingly we get the following:

Theorem: No permutation in S_n can be expressed both as a product of an odd number of transpositions and as a product of an even number of them.

So a cycle can either be written as a product of an even or odd number of transpositions, but not both.

Definition:

$A_n = \{\text{All permutations which can be written as a product of evenly many transpositions.}\}$

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Lecture 16 (11/4)

Week 6, 11/4-11/8. Section 9: Finitely generated abelian groups.

Section 10: Cosets and the theorem of Lagrange.

Definition:

$$\text{sgn}(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is a product of an even number of transpositions,} \\ -1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is a product of an odd number of transpositions.} \end{cases}$$

This is a homomorphism.

$$\ker(\text{sgn}) = \{\text{all permutations that are products of an even number of transpositions.}\} = A_n \leq S_n.$$

A_n is called the **alternating group**.

Section 9: FGAGs (Finitely Generated Abelian Groups)

$$\prod_{i=1}^n G_i = G_1 \times G_2 \times \cdots \times G_n$$

is a group called the **direct product of groups** G_i .

Use the first operation on the first element, and the second operation on the second.

Example:

$$(1, 1) \in Z_2 \times Z_3$$

$$(1, 1) + (1, 1) = (1 +_2 1, 1 +_3 1) = (0, 2).$$

Note: $Z_2 \times Z_3$ is cyclic, generated by $(1, 1)$.

Section 9 Construction of Finite Abelian Groups Using Direct Products

We will use the building blocks $\langle Z_n, +_n \rangle$ to construct all finite abelian groups by taking direct products. For example, $\langle 1 \rangle$ generates Z_n .

Direct Product of Groups

For groups $G_1 \times G_2 \times \cdots \times G_n$, the elements are n -tuples (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) where $g_1 \in G_1, g_2 \in G_2, \dots, g_n \in G_n$. The group operation, denoted by $*$, is performed component-wise. In other words, multiplying $(a_1, a_2, a_3) * (b_1, b_2, b_3) = (a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, a_3 b_3)$ in $G_1 \times G_2 \times G_3$.

Examples Highlighted in Friday's Lecture

Two examples of groups were discussed:

1. $Z_2 \times Z_3$: This group has 6 elements, is cyclic, and is generated by $\langle(1, 1)\rangle$.
2. $Z_3 \times Z_3$: This group is not cyclic because it cannot be generated by a single element. Instead, it can be generated by the set $\{(0, 1), (1, 0)\}$.

Theorem 1: Order of Elements in Direct Products of Groups

Let $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \prod_{i=1}^n G_i$, where each a_i is of finite order r_i in G_i . Then, the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is given by the least common multiple:

$$\text{lcm}(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n).$$

Example: Finding the Order of $(8, 4, 10)$ in $Z_{12} \times Z_{60} \times Z_{24}$

To determine the order of $(8, 4, 10)$ in $Z_{12} \times Z_{60} \times Z_{24}$, we compute the order of each component:

1. Order of 8 in Z_{12} : Using the formula $\text{ord}(a) = \frac{n}{\text{gcd}(n, a)}$, we find

$$\text{ord}(8) = \frac{12}{\text{gcd}(12, 8)} = \frac{12}{4} = 3.$$

2. Order of 4 in Z_{60} : Similarly,

$$\text{ord}(4) = \frac{60}{\text{gcd}(60, 4)} = \frac{60}{4} = 15.$$

3. Order of 10 in Z_{24} :

$$\text{ord}(10) = \frac{24}{\text{gcd}(24, 10)} = \frac{24}{2} = 12.$$

Now, the order of $(8, 4, 10)$ is the least common multiple of these orders:

$$\text{lcm}(3, 15, 12).$$

To calculate $\text{lcm}(3, 15, 12)$, we break down each number into prime factors:

1. $3 = 3$
2. $15 = 3 \times 5$

3. $12 = 3 \times 2 \times 2$

The least common multiple is obtained by taking the highest power of each prime factor:

$$\text{lcm}(3, 15, 12) = 3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 2 = 60.$$

Thus, the order of $(8, 4, 10)$ in $Z_{12} \times Z_{60} \times Z_{24}$ is 60.

Proof of Theorem 1: Order of Elements in Direct Products of Groups

To show that the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) in $\prod_{i=1}^n G_i$ is $\text{lcm}(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$, where each a_i has finite order r_i in G_i , we proceed as follows:

Consider a power $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)^k = (a_1^k, a_2^k, \dots, a_n^k)$. For this expression to yield the identity element (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) , where each e_i is the identity element in G_i , each a_i^k must equal e_i in G_i .

Since a_i has order r_i in G_i , $a_i^k = e_i$ if and only if k is a multiple of r_i . Therefore, k must simultaneously be a multiple of r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n for $(a_1^k, a_2^k, \dots, a_n^k) = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$. The minimal such k that satisfies all these conditions is given by the least common multiple $\text{lcm}(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$. Thus, the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is $\text{lcm}(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$.

Theorem 2: Conditions for Cyclic Direct Products

Consider the group $Z_m \times Z_n$. This group is cyclic and is isomorphic to Z_{mn} (where $|Z_m \times Z_n| = mn$) if and only if $\text{gcd}(m, n) = 1$, i.e., if m and n have no divisors in common other than 1.

Proof of Theorem 2:

(Reverse Implication): Suppose $\text{gcd}(m, n) = 1$. Then, by Theorem 1, we can compute the order of the element $(1, 1)$ in $Z_m \times Z_n$.

1. Order of $(1, 1)$: - The order of 1 in Z_m is m . - The order of 1 in Z_n is n .
2. By Theorem 1, the order of $(1, 1)$ in $Z_m \times Z_n$ is:

$$\text{lcm}(m, n).$$

Since $\text{gcd}(m, n) = 1$, we have $\text{lcm}(m, n) = m \cdot n$.

3. Therefore, $(1, 1)$ has order mn , which is the total number of elements in $Z_m \times Z_n$. Since we have found an element whose order is equal to the size of the group, it follows that $Z_m \times Z_n$ is cyclic and abelian and by thm 6.10 is isomorphic to Z_{mn} .

Example

Suppose $\text{gcd}(m, n) = d > 1$.

Let

$$c = \frac{mn}{d}.$$

Observe that: $\forall (r, s) \in Z_m \times Z_n$,

$$(r, s) + (r, s) + \cdots + (r, s) = (0, 0)$$

where this addition is performed $c = \frac{mn}{d}$ times.

Thus, all elements in $Z_m \times Z_n$ have orders at most c , so no element can be a single generator.

The group $Z_m \times Z_n$ is cyclic and is isomorphic to Z_{mn} if and only if $\gcd(m, n) = 1$.

The Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups (Version 1: Primary Factor Version)

Every finitely generated abelian group G is isomorphic to a direct product of cyclic groups in the form:

$$Z_{p_1^{r_1}} \times Z_{p_2^{r_2}} \times Z_{p_3^{r_3}} \times \cdots \times Z_{p_n^{r_n}} \times Z \times Z \times \cdots \times Z$$

where p_i are prime and $r_i \in \mathbb{N}$.

Exercise

$$Z_3 \times Z_4 \times Z_{16} \times Z \times Z$$

where $p_1 = 3, r_1 = 1, p_2 = 2, r_2 = 2$, and $p_3 = 2, r_3 = 4$.

Example

Find all abelian groups, up to isomorphism, of order 360.

Solution

$$360 = 2^3 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5$$

- Z_8 must be a component.
- Either $Z_3 \times Z_3$ or Z_9 (since $3^2 = 9$).

The possible groups are:

$$Z_8 \times Z_3 \times Z_{15} \quad \text{or} \quad Z_8 \times Z_9 \quad \text{or} \quad Z_{360}$$

The six abelian groups of order 360, up to isomorphism, are:

- Z_{360}
- $Z_8 \times Z_9 \times Z_5$
- $Z_8 \times Z_3 \times Z_{15}$
- $Z_4 \times Z_9 \times Z_{10}$
- $Z_4 \times Z_3 \times Z_{30}$
- $Z_2 \times Z_2 \times Z_9 \times Z_5$

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Lecture 17 (11/6)

Week 6, 11/4-11/8. Section 9: Finitely generated abelian groups.
Section 10: Cosets and the theorem of Lagrange.

Recall from last time: Every finitely generated abelian group is isometric to *some*

$$Z_{p_1}, Z_{p_2}, \dots, Z \times \dots \times Z.$$

Example: A group G is called **decomposable** if it is isomorphic to a direct product of two proper nontrivial subgroups. Otherwise, it is **indecomposable**.

Theorem: A finite abelian group is indecomposable only if $|G| = p^r$ for some prime p .

Example: Z_q is indecomposable.

Proof: If $|G|$ is not a power of a prime, then

$$|G| = n = p_1^{r_1} p_2^{r_2} \dots$$

Then, by the Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups,

$$G \cong Z_{p_1^{r_1}} \times Z_{p_2^{r_2}} \times \dots$$

which contains at least two components.

Example 1: $|G| = 10$, abelian.

Since 10 is not a power of a prime, by the Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups (F.T.),

$$G \cong Z_5 \times Z_2$$

which implies G is decomposable.

Example 2: $|G| = 9$, isomorphic to either:

$$G \cong Z_9 \quad \text{or} \quad G \cong Z_3 \times Z_3.$$

If $G \cong Z_9$, it is indecomposable because $9 = 3^2$ is a power of a prime.

If $G \cong Z_3 \times Z_3$, it is decomposable. A group G of order p^2 (9 in this case) may either be:

- A cyclic group, e.g., Z_9 , which is indecomposable.
- A direct product of two smaller cyclic groups, e.g., $Z_3 \times Z_3$, which is decomposable.

Z_9 cannot be decomposed because it is generated by a single element. In contrast, $Z_3 \times Z_3$ is not cyclic and can be expressed as the product of two subgroups of order 3.

Examples: Generating Z_9

Let $Z_9 = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 8\}$ under addition modulo 9. The generator of Z_9 must produce every element of the group through repeated addition.

- For $g = 1$, calculate:

$$g, 2g, 3g, \dots, 9g \pmod{9}$$

$$1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 0.$$

Thus, $g = 1$ generates the entire group Z_9 .

- For $g = 2$, calculate:

$$g, 2g, 3g, \dots, 9g \pmod{9}$$

$$2, 4, 6, 8, 1, 3, 5, 7, 0.$$

Thus, $g = 2$ also generates the entire group Z_9 .

- For $g = 3$, calculate:

$$g, 2g, 3g, \dots, 9g \pmod{9}$$

$$3, 6, 0.$$

Since $g = 3$ only generates the subgroup $\{0, 3, 6\}$, it is not a generator of the entire group.

Z_9 is indecomposable because it is cyclic of prime power order. Generators like 1 and 2 ensure that Z_9 cannot be expressed as a direct product of smaller groups. In contrast, a decomposable group of order 9, like $Z_3 \times Z_3$,

Example: $Z_3 \times Z_3$ is Not Cyclic

The group $Z_3 \times Z_3$ consists of the elements:

$$Z_3 \times Z_3 = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (0, 2), (1, 0), (1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 0), (2, 1), (2, 2)\}.$$

Addition is performed component-wise modulo 3.

Attempt to Find a Generator

Let us test whether any single element can generate the entire group $Z_3 \times Z_3$.

1. Take $(1, 0) \in Z_3 \times Z_3$:

$$(1, 0), \quad 2 \cdot (1, 0) = (2, 0), \quad 3 \cdot (1, 0) = (0, 0).$$

This only generates the subset $\{(0, 0), (1, 0), (2, 0)\}$, which is a proper subgroup of $Z_3 \times Z_3$, not the entire group.

2. Take $(0, 1) \in Z_3 \times Z_3$:

$$(0, 1), \quad 2 \cdot (0, 1) = (0, 2), \quad 3 \cdot (0, 1) = (0, 0).$$

This generates the subset $\{(0, 0), (0, 1), (0, 2)\}$, another proper subgroup.

3. Take $(1, 1) \in Z_3 \times Z_3$:

$$(1, 1), \quad 2 \cdot (1, 1) = (2, 2), \quad 3 \cdot (1, 1) = (0, 0).$$

This generates the subset $\{(0, 0), (1, 1), (2, 2)\}$, another proper subgroup.

No single element of $Z_3 \times Z_3$ can generate all 9 elements of the group. Thus, $Z_3 \times Z_3$ is **not cyclic**. In Z_9 , a single element, such as 1 or 2, generates all elements of the group through repeated addition modulo 9. For example, taking $1 \in Z_9$:

$$1, \quad 2 = 1 + 1, \quad 3 = 2 + 1, \quad \dots, \quad 8 = 7 + 1, \quad 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{9}.$$

This generates all elements of Z_9 . In contrast, $Z_3 \times Z_3$ requires multiple generators, such as $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$, to generate the entire group. Therefore, $Z_3 \times Z_3$ is **decomposable**, while Z_9 is **indecomposable**.

Theorem: If m divides the order of a finite, abelian group G , then G must have a subgroup of order m .

Theorem

If m divides the order of a finite, abelian group G , then G must have a subgroup of order m .

Example

An abelian group of size 20 must have subgroups of sizes 2, 4, 5, and 10. These sizes correspond to the powers of the prime factors of 20:

$$20 = 2^2 \cdot 5.$$

Example

For Z_6 :

$$|\langle 1 \rangle| = 6, \quad |\langle 2 \rangle| = 3, \quad |\langle 3 \rangle| = 2.$$

Note

All of this is only relevant to abelian groups.

Theorem (Lagrange's Theorem)

If $H \leq G$, then $|H|$ divides $|G|$.

Reasoning

H induces a partition of G into parts of equal size $|H|$. These parts are the *cosets* of H .

Definition

Let $H \leq G$. We define a relation on G by

$$a \sim b \iff ab^{-1} \in H.$$

Theorem

This is an equivalence relation (which is convenient for us).

Properties of the Relation

Namely, this relation is:

- **Reflexive:** $a \sim a$,
- **Symmetric:** $a \sim b \iff b \sim a$,
- **Transitive:** $a \sim b, b \sim c \implies a \sim c$.

Definition

Let $H \leq G$. The set

$$aH = \{ah \mid h \in H\}$$

is the **left coset** of H containing a .

Lecture 18 (11/8): Section 10: Cosets & Lagrange's Theorem
 Week 6, 11/4-11/8. Section 9: Finitely generated abelian groups.
 Section 10: Cosets and the theorem of Lagrange.

Given $H \leq G$:

The cosets of H are:

$$H, aH, cH, dH, fH$$

Key Property: All cosets have the same size $|H|$.

Corollary (Lagrange):

$$|H| \mid |G|$$

Definition: Equivalence Relation on G

Statement:

For all $a, b \in G$,

$$a \sim b \iff a^{-1}b \in H$$

Induced Partition

This induces a partition of G .

Namely, this tells us which elements live in the same coset.

Namely:

$$a \sim b \iff a^{-1}b \in H$$

Alternative Definition of Cosets

Let H be a subgroup of G .

The **left coset** of H containing $a \in G$ is:

$$aH = \{ah \mid h \in H\}$$

Observation: $a \in aH$ since one can take $h = e$ (the identity element in H).

Examples

Example 1: $G = \mathbb{Z}_{12}$, $H = \langle 3 \rangle$

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}_{12}$ and $H = \langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3, 6, 9\}$.

Find the partition of G into left cosets of H .

First Coset:

$$0 + H = \{0 + h \mid h \in H\} = \{0 + 0, 0 + 3, 0 + 6, 0 + 9\} = \{0, 3, 6, 9\}$$

Second Coset:

$$1 + H = \{1 + h \mid h \in H\} = \{1 + 0, 1 + 3, 1 + 6, 1 + 9\} = \{1, 4, 7, 10\}$$

Third Coset:

$$2 + H = \{2 + h \mid h \in H\} = \{2 + 0, 2 + 3, 2 + 6, 2 + 9\} = \{2, 5, 8, 11\}$$

Visualization:

Observation: There are exactly 3 cosets, each of size 4.

Note: The names of the cosets are arbitrary; for instance, the coset $2 + H$ can also be called $5 + H$ since $2 + H = 5 + H$.

Alternative Calculation Using Equivalence Relation

We can also determine which elements share a coset with 2 using the equivalence relation:

$$a \sim b \iff a^{-1}b \in H$$

In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , the inverse of 2 is 10 (since $2 + 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$). So:

$$2 \sim b \iff 10 + b \in H$$

Therefore, b shares a coset with 2 if $10 + b$ is in $H = \{0, 3, 6, 9\}$. This occurs when $b \in \{2, 5, 8, 11\}$, which are precisely the elements in the coset $2 + H$.

Example 2: $G = D_4$, $H = \langle \mu \rangle$

Let $G = D_4$, the dihedral group of order 8, and $H = \langle \mu \rangle = \{e, \mu\}$, where μ is a reflection.

The elements of D_4 are:

$$\{e, \rho, \rho^2, \rho^3, \mu, \mu\rho, \mu\rho^2, \mu\rho^3\}$$

where ρ is rotation by 90° .

Find the partition of D_4 into left cosets of H .

First Coset:

$$eH = \{eh \mid h \in H\} = \{e, \mu\}$$

Second Coset:

$$\rho H = \{\rho h \mid h \in H\} = \{\rho, \rho\mu\}$$

Note: $\rho\mu = \mu\rho^3$, so the coset is $\{\rho, \mu\rho^3\}$.

Third Coset:

$$\rho^2 H = \{\rho^2 h \mid h \in H\} = \{\rho^2, \rho^2\mu\}$$

Note: $\rho^2\mu = \mu\rho^2$, so the coset is $\{\rho^2, \mu\rho^2\}$.

Fourth Coset:

$$\rho^3 H = \{\rho^3 h \mid h \in H\} = \{\rho^3, \rho^3\mu\}$$

Note: $\rho^3\mu = \mu\rho$, so the coset is $\{\rho^3, \mu\rho\}$.

Visualization:

[H] **Observation:** Each coset has 2 elements, and there are 4 cosets in total.

Theorem: Coset Cardinality

Let H be a subgroup of G . Then, for any $a \in G$, the coset aH has the same cardinality as H .

Proof Sketch:

Define a function $\phi : H \rightarrow aH$ by $\phi(h) = ah$.

- **Injective:** If $\phi(h_1) = \phi(h_2)$, then $ah_1 = ah_2 \implies h_1 = h_2$ after multiplying both sides on the left by a^{-1} .

- **Surjective:** For any element $ah \in aH$, there exists $h \in H$ such that $\phi(h) = ah$.

Therefore, ϕ is a bijection, and $|aH| = |H|$.

Lagrange's Theorem

Let H be a subgroup of G . Then:

$$|H| \mid |G|$$

Proof:

Since G can be partitioned into disjoint left cosets of H , each of size $|H|$, the order of G is a multiple of $|H|$:

$$|G| = |H| \cdot [G : H]$$

where $[G : H]$ is the number of left cosets of H in G .

Definition: Index of a Subgroup

The number of left cosets of H in G is called the **index** of H in G , denoted $[G : H]$.

Examples:

- In \mathbb{Z}_{12} with $H = \langle 3 \rangle$, we have $[\mathbb{Z}_{12} : H] = 3$.
- In D_4 with $H = \langle \mu \rangle$, we have $[D_4 : H] = 4$.

Theorem

Suppose H and K are subgroups of G such that $K \leq H \leq G$, and both $[H : K]$ and $[G : H]$ are finite. Then:

$$[G : K] = [G : H] \cdot [H : K]$$

Example:

If $|G| = 18$, $|H| = 6$, and $|K| = 2$, then:

$$[G : K] = \frac{|G|}{|K|} = \frac{18}{2} = 9$$

$$[G : H] = \frac{|G|}{|H|} = \frac{18}{6} = 3$$

$$[H : K] = \frac{|H|}{|K|} = \frac{6}{2} = 3$$

$$\text{Thus, } [G : K] = [G : H] \cdot [H : K] = 3 \cdot 3 = 9$$

Corollaries of Lagrange's Theorem

Corollary 1

Every group of prime order is cyclic.

Proof Sketch:

Let G be a group of prime order p . Let $a \in G$, $a \neq e$.

The subgroup $\langle a \rangle$ has order dividing p by Lagrange's Theorem. The possible orders are 1 or p . Since $a \neq e$, the order must be p , so $\langle a \rangle = G$.

Conclusion: G is cyclic.

Example:

In \mathbb{Z}_7 , any non-zero element generates the entire group.

Corollary 2

The order of any element of a finite group divides the order of the group.

Proof Sketch:

For $a \in G$, the order of a is $|\langle a \rangle|$. By Lagrange's Theorem, $|\langle a \rangle|$ divides $|G|$.

Math 103A: Modern Algebra 1 with Professor Gil Goffer

Notes prepared by Akiva and Harry

Textbook: A First Course in Abstract Algebra, 8th Edition by Fraleigh

Lecture 19 (11/13)

Week 7, 11/11-11/15. Section 12: Factor groups. No class on 11/11 (Veterans Day)

Cosets and Factor Groups

Consider a group G with a subgroup H . We can partition G into disjoint subsets, known as *cosets* of H in G . Each coset is of the form gH for some element $g \in G$, where $gH = \{gh \mid h \in H\}$. These cosets collectively cover the entire group G without overlapping.

Now, we define a new group whose elements are these cosets themselves, rather than the individual elements of G . This new group, denoted by G/H , is called the *factor group* or *quotient group* of G by H . The binary operation on G/H is defined as:

$$(gH)(kH) = (gk)H$$

for any $g, k \in G$. This operation is well-defined and allows us to obtain other cosets within G/H .

Partition of Z into $H = \langle 5 \rangle$

Consider two elements from the same coset $1 + H$, such as 6 and 11:

$$6, 11 \in 1 + H.$$

Adding these two elements:

$$6 + 11 = 17.$$

Notice that 17 is also in $1 + H$, since $17 = 1 + 5 \times 3$.

Thus, adding two elements from $1 + H$ (in this case, 6 and 11) yields another element, 17, which is still in the coset $1 + H$.

This property holds for any two elements within the same coset of $H = \langle 5 \rangle$. For example, if G has order 20 and H has order 5, then by Lagrange's theorem, the number of cosets of H in G is:

$$\frac{|G|}{|H|} = \frac{20}{5} = 4$$

Thus, there are 4 cosets, and this number of cosets is known as the *index* of H in G . Additionally, the index matches the size of the factor group G/H , meaning G/H has 4 elements (the cosets).

The set of all cosets forms the factor group G/H , which can be represented as:

$$G/H = \{H, 1 + H, 2 + H, 3 + H\}$$

In this factor group, each element is a coset of H in G , and the number of elements in G/H equals the index $[G:H] = 4$, matching the size of the factor group.

Recall: Def: left coset of H that contains $a \in G$ was defined as

$$aH = \{ah \mid h \in H\}$$

Def: right coset of H that contains $a \in G$ is defined as

$$Ha = \{ha \mid h \in H\}$$

Given a group G , a subgroup H , we get two partitions of G into cosets:

G	H	aH	bH
G	H	Ha	Hb

Def: Let $H \leq G$. We say that H is a **normal subgroup** of G if

$$\forall g \in G : gH = Hg.$$

Notation: $H \triangleleft G$

- *Note:* It does not imply that $\forall g \in G, gH = Hg$; but only that for some $h_1, h_2 \in H$,

$$h_1g = gh_2.$$

Example: If G is abelian, then $H \triangleleft G$.

G	$aH = Ha$	$bH = Hb$	\dots
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Theorem: Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism. Then the kernel of ϕ , defined as

$$\ker(\phi) = \{g \in G \mid \phi(g) = e'\},$$

where e' is the identity in G' , is a normal subgroup of G , denoted $\ker(\phi) \triangleleft G$, with identical left and right cosets.

Furthermore, for $a, b \in G$, a and b are in the same coset with respect to $\ker(\phi)$ if and only if

$$\phi(a) = \phi(b).$$

Example: Let $G = \mathbb{Z}$ and $G' = \mathbb{Z}_n$. Define $\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$ by $\phi(x) = x \pmod n$. Then,

$$\ker(\phi) = n\mathbb{Z} = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid x \equiv 0 \pmod n\},$$

which is a normal subgroup of \mathbb{Z} .

G

Recall: a and b reside in the same left H -coset if and only if a is left related (\sim_L) to b , if and only if $a^{-1}b \in H$.

Here, a and b are in the same coset if and only if a is left equivalent to b ($\sim_L b$), if and only if $a^{-1}b \in \ker(\phi)$, if and only if $\phi(a^{-1}b) = e'$, if and only if $\phi(a^{-1}) \cdot \phi(b) = e'$.

Multiplying both sides on the left by $\phi(a)$, we get

$$\phi(b) = \phi(a).$$

Therefore, the cosets of the kernel are all the elements mapped to one point in G' .

Corollary: A homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ is **one-to-one** (injective) if and only if $\ker(\phi) = \{e\}$.

(The kernel is trivial). Since for any point in G mapping to G' , all the cosets are of the same size, if one coset has size one, then all cosets have size one, and the map will be injective.

Proof:

Suppose ϕ is one-to-one (injective). Then there is only one element in G that maps to e' in G' , which means the kernel of ϕ has size one and must contain only the identity element:

$$|\ker(\phi)| = 1 \implies \ker(\phi) = \{e\}.$$

Now, assume $\ker(\phi) = \{e\}$ and suppose $\phi(a) = \phi(b)$ for some $a, b \in G$. This implies that a is left related to b , so $a^{-1}b \in \ker(\phi)$.

Since $a^{-1}b \in \ker(\phi)$, we have

$$a^{-1}b = e,$$

which means $a = b$.

Thus, ϕ is injective, as required.

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Lecture 20 (11/15)

Week 7, 11/11-11/15. Section 12: Factor groups. No class on 11/11 (Veterans Day)

Section 12

Definition: Let $H \leq G$.

We say that H is normal ($H \triangleleft G$) if

$$\forall g \in G : gH = Hg \quad (\nrightarrow gh = hg)$$

Theorem (12.17)

The following are equivalent for a subgroup $H \leq G$:

1. $ghg^{-1} \in H \quad \forall g \in G, \forall h \in H$
This condition states that H is closed under conjugation by elements of G , meaning that conjugating any element of H by any element of G results in an element that still belongs to H .
2. $gHg^{-1} = H \quad \forall g \in G$
This condition indicates that H is invariant under conjugation by G , meaning the set gHg^{-1} is equal to H itself for all $g \in G$.
3. There exists a group homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ such that $\ker(\phi) = H$
This condition implies that H is the kernel of some group homomorphism from G to another group G' , which is a defining characteristic of normal subgroups.
4. $gH = Hg \quad \forall g \in G$
This condition says that the left cosets and right cosets of H in G are the same, which is another characterization of H being a normal subgroup (namely, $H \triangleleft G$).

Example 1:

If G is an abelian group, then every subgroup $H \leq G$ is normal in G (i.e., $H \triangleleft G$). This is because, in an abelian group, we have $gh = hg$ for all $g, h \in G$, so conjugation has no effect: $ghg^{-1} = h$, ensuring that any subgroup H satisfies the conditions for normality.

Example 2: Kernel of a Homomorphism

Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a group homomorphism. Then the kernel of ϕ , defined as $\ker(\phi) = \{g \in G \mid \phi(g) = e'\}$ (where e' is the identity element in G'), is always a normal subgroup of G . This is a general property of kernels of homomorphisms.

Example from Permutations:

Consider the symmetric group S_n , which consists of all permutations on n elements. Any permutation $\sigma \in S_n$ can be written as a product of transpositions (2-cycles), such as $(1, 2)$ or $(5, 4)$. For any permutation, it can be written either as a product of an even or an odd number of transpositions.

Define the function $\phi : S_n \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by mapping a permutation σ to its sign, $\text{sign}(\sigma)$:

$$\phi(\sigma) = \text{sign}(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is a product of an even number of transpositions} \\ -1 & \text{if } \sigma \text{ is a product of an odd number of transpositions} \end{cases}$$

The kernel of ϕ is given by

$$\ker(\phi) = \{\sigma \in S_n \mid \text{sign}(\sigma) = 1\} = A_n$$

where A_n is the alternating group on n elements, consisting of all "even" permutations (those that can be written as a product of an even number of transpositions).

Example Calculation:

For instance, let $\sigma = (1\ 2)(2\ 3)(5\ 6)$. Since this is a product of three transpositions (an odd number), we have $\text{sign}(\sigma) = -1$.

Now consider $\tau = (1\ 2)(1\ 2)(4\ 6)(3\ 5)$, which is a product of four transpositions (an even number), so $\text{sign}(\tau) = 1$. The kernel of ϕ is given by

$$\ker(\phi) = \{\sigma \in S_n \mid \phi(\sigma) = 1\} = \{\text{all even permutations}\} = A_n$$

where A_n , often called the *alternating group*, is a subgroup of S_n . In particular, A_n is a *normal subgroup* of S_n . This is because A_n consists of all permutations with an even number of transpositions, and it is the kernel of the homomorphism $\phi : S_n \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, which maps each permutation to its sign (1 for even permutations, -1 for odd permutations).

Since $A_n = \ker(\phi)$, it satisfies the property that for any $g \in S_n$ and $h \in A_n$, we have $ghg^{-1} \in A_n$, meeting the requirement for normality. **Theorem:** Let H be a subgroup of G . Then left coset multiplication is well-defined by

$$(aH) \cdot (bH) = (ab)H$$

if and only if H is a normal subgroup of G . The operation \cdot on the left cosets aH and bH is defined as taking the product of representatives a and b from each coset, then forming the coset $(ab)H$. This definition is well-defined, meaning it does not depend on the choice of representatives a and b , if and only if H is a normal subgroup of G .

In other words, if $H \triangleleft G$, then for any elements $a, a' \in aH$ and $b, b' \in bH$, we have $a'H = aH$ and $b'H = bH$, ensuring that $(a'H)(b'H) = (ab)H$, making the operation consistent regardless of the choice of representatives. This property holds if and only if H is normal, as normality ensures that left cosets and right cosets are the same.

If H is not normal, the operation is not well-defined. Different representatives $a' \in aH$ and $b' \in bH$ could lead to $(a'H)(b'H) \neq (ab)H$, making the product ambiguous. Let H be a normal subgroup of G . Then the cosets of H form a group, denoted G/H , under the binary operation

$$(aH)(bH) = (ab)H.$$

The group G/H is called the *factor group* or *quotient group* of G by H .

The notation G/H is used because, if G is finite and H is finite, the size of the new group G/H will be precisely the size of G divided by the size of H :

$$|G/H| = \frac{|G|}{|H|}.$$

Note:

For any $a \in G$,

$$Ha = \{ha \mid h \in H\}, \quad aH = \{ah \mid h \in H\}.$$

Thus, for a normal subgroup H , we can say:

$$Ha(bH) = abH = Hab,$$

but $abH \neq Hba$ in general.

Since H is normal, the distinction between Ha and aH does not matter within parentheses, as they represent the same coset. However, the order of Ha bH vs bH Ha matters.

Example: Cosets of $\mathbb{Z}/10\mathbb{Z}$

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}$ and $H = \langle 10 \rangle$. The cosets are as follows:

$$\langle 10 \rangle = \{\dots, -10, 0, 10, 20, \dots\}, \quad 1 + \langle 10 \rangle = \{\dots, -9, 1, 11, 21, \dots\}, \quad 2 + \langle 10 \rangle = \{\dots, -8, 2, 12, 22, \dots\}, \quad \dots$$

Up to $23 + \langle 10 \rangle$, with elements $\{\dots, -7, 3, 13, 23, 33, \dots\}$.

The factor group $\mathbb{Z}/10\mathbb{Z}$ has order 10. Note that factor groups are not subgroups.

$\langle 10 \rangle$ $\{-10, 0, 10, 20, \dots\}$	$1 + \langle 10 \rangle$ $\{-9, 1, 11, 21, 31, \dots\}$	$2 + \langle 10 \rangle$ $\{-8, 2, 12, 22, 32, \dots\}$	$23 + \langle 10 \rangle$ $\{-7, 3, 13, 23, 33, \dots\}$
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Theorem:

Let H be a normal subgroup of G . Then the map

$$\varphi : G \rightarrow G/H, \quad \varphi(g) = gH$$

is a homomorphism, and the kernel of φ is H .

Example:

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}$ and $H = \langle 10 \rangle$. Define $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{10}$ by

$$\varphi(k) = k + \langle 10 \rangle.$$

This is a homomorphism, and the kernel of φ is $\langle 10 \rangle$.

For instance:

$$\varphi(2) = 2 + \langle 10 \rangle, \quad \varphi(22) = 22 + \langle 10 \rangle.$$

Since $22 \equiv 2 \pmod{10}$, $\varphi(22)$ and $\varphi(2)$ belong to the same coset $2 + \langle 10 \rangle$.

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Lecture 22 (11/20)

Week 8

Factor Groups: Example Calculation

Problem: What is the order of $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$?

Solution

If G is a finite group, the size of the factor group $|G/H|$, also called the index $[G : H]$, is given by:

$$|G/H| = \frac{|G|}{|H|}.$$

Step 1: Compute $|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6|$

The order of a product of two groups is the product of their individual orders:

$$|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6| = |\mathbb{Z}_4| \cdot |\mathbb{Z}_6| = 4 \cdot 6 = 24.$$

Step 2: Compute $|\langle (0, 2) \rangle|$

The subgroup $\langle (0, 2) \rangle$ is generated by the element $(0, 2) \in \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$. The order of this element is determined by:

$$\text{order}((a_1, a_2)) = \text{lcm}(\text{order}(a_1), \text{order}(a_2)),$$

where $a_1 \in \mathbb{Z}_4$ and $a_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_6$.

Step 2.1: Order of $0 \in \mathbb{Z}_4$

The identity element 0 in \mathbb{Z}_4 satisfies:

$$0 + 0 + \cdots + 0 = 0 \quad (\text{one iteration}),$$

so the order of 0 is:

$$\text{order}(0) = 1.$$

Step 2.2: Order of $2 \in \mathbb{Z}_6$

To determine the order of 2 in \mathbb{Z}_6 , we compute its multiples modulo 6:

$$2 \cdot 1 = 2, \quad 2 \cdot 2 = 4, \quad 2 \cdot 3 = 0 \pmod{6}.$$

Thus, the order of 2 is:

$$\text{order}(2) = 3.$$

Step 2.3: Compute $\text{lcm}(\text{order}(0), \text{order}(2))$

The least common multiple is:

$$\text{lcm}(1, 3) = 3.$$

Thus, the size of the subgroup $|\langle(0, 2)\rangle|$ is:

$$|\langle(0, 2)\rangle| = 3.$$

Step 3: Compute $|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle|$

Using the formula for the size of a factor group:

$$|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle| = \frac{|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6|}{|\langle(0, 2)\rangle|} = \frac{24}{3} = 8.$$

Verification

To verify, iterate the element $(0, 2)$ three times:

$$(0, 2) + (0, 2) + (0, 2) = (0, 6) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{(4, 6)}.$$

This confirms that $(0, 2)$ has order 3 in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$.

Conclusion

The size of the factor group is:

$$|\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle| = 8.$$

Is $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle$ Abelian?

Answer: Yes, the factor group $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle$ is abelian. Here's the reasoning:

1. Product of Abelian Groups

Let H and K be abelian groups. The product $H \times K$ is also abelian. Specifically, for any elements $(h_1, k_1), (h_2, k_2) \in H \times K$, we have:

$$(h_1, k_1) * (h_2, k_2) = (h_1 * h_2, k_1 * k_2),$$

where $*$ denotes the group operation. Since H and K are abelian, we can rewrite this as:

$$(h_1 * h_2, k_1 * k_2) = (h_2 * h_1, k_2 * k_1).$$

Thus:

$$(h_1, k_1) * (h_2, k_2) = (h_2, k_2) * (h_1, k_1).$$

This confirms that $H \times K$ is abelian.

In our case, $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$ is the product of two cyclic (and hence abelian) groups, so it is abelian.

2. Factor Group of an Abelian Group

To check whether the factor group G/H is abelian, let G be an abelian group and H a subgroup of G . For any two cosets aH and bH in G/H , their product is defined as:

$$(aH)(bH) = (ab)H.$$

Since G is abelian, we can write:

$$(ab)H = (ba)H = (bH)(aH).$$

Thus, G/H inherits the abelian property from G .

3. Normality of Subgroups in Abelian Groups

Additionally, in any abelian group G , all subgroups are normal. This is because for any subgroup $H \leq G$ and any $g \in G$, we have:

$$gHg^{-1} = \{ghg^{-1} \mid h \in H\} = \{gh \mid h \in H\} = H.$$

Thus, H is normal in G .

Conclusion

Since $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$ is abelian, and $\langle(0, 2)\rangle$ is a normal subgroup, the factor group $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle(0, 2)\rangle$ is abelian as well.

Problem

Find all possible finite abelian groups of order 8, up to isomorphism.

Solution

Theorem: Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups (Primary Factor Version)

Every finitely generated abelian group G is isomorphic to a direct product of cyclic groups in the form:

$$\mathbb{Z}_{p_1^{r_1}} \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_2^{r_2}} \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_3^{r_3}} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z}_{p_n^{r_n}} \times \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z},$$

where p_i are prime numbers, $r_i \in \mathbb{N}$, and the product of the orders of the cyclic groups equals the order of the group G .

Using the Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups, every finite abelian group of order 8 is isomorphic to a direct product of cyclic groups whose orders are powers of 2, and the product of their orders must equal $8 = 2^3$.

Step 1: Prime Factorization of 8

The order 8 can be written as:

$$8 = 2^3.$$

Step 2: List All Possible Direct Products of Cyclic Groups

The possible abelian groups of order 8 are:

1. A single cyclic group of order 8:

$$\mathbb{Z}_8$$

2. A direct product of a cyclic group of order 4 and a cyclic group of order 2:

$$\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$$

3. A direct product of three cyclic groups of order 2:

$$\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$$

Note on Isomorphisms

Although $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ is written explicitly, it is isomorphic to $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$. For example, consider the isomorphism:

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$$

defined by:

$$\phi(a, b) = (b, a),$$

where $a \in \mathbb{Z}_4$ and $b \in \mathbb{Z}_2$. This bijective mapping preserves the group operation since addition is commutative in abelian groups:

$$\phi((a_1, b_1) + (a_2, b_2)) = \phi((a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2)) = (b_1 + b_2, a_1 + a_2).$$

Thus, ϕ is a valid isomorphism.

Question: Is $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ isomorphic to $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$?

Analysis Based on Element Orders

Key Fact: If two groups G and G' are isomorphic, then the order of any element $a \in G$ must equal the order of its image $\phi(a) \in G'$, where ϕ is the isomorphism. Thus, if G and G' have elements with different possible orders, they cannot be isomorphic.

1. Element Orders in $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$:

In $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, each component is cyclic of order 2. Therefore:

- Each element has the form (a_1, a_2, a_3) , where $a_i \in \mathbb{Z}_2$.
- The order of (a_1, a_2, a_3) is the least common multiple (lcm) of the orders of a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 . Since the only possible orders of elements in \mathbb{Z}_2 are 1 or 2, the lcm is either 1 or 2.

Thus, **all elements in $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ have order 1 or 2.**

2. Element Orders in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$:

The group $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ is a factor group of order 8. By Lagrange's theorem, the order of any element in this group must divide 8. Therefore, the possible element orders are:

1, 2, 4, or 8.

However, the actual element orders depend on the structure of the factor group. Specifically:

- Elements of the form $(a, b) + \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ have order:

$$\text{order}((a, b) + \langle (0, 2) \rangle) = \frac{\text{lcm}(\text{order}(a), \text{order}(b))}{\text{gcd}(\text{lcm}(\text{order}(a), \text{order}(b)), 3)}.$$

- In \mathbb{Z}_4 , possible orders for elements are 1, 2, 4.
- In \mathbb{Z}_6 , possible orders for elements are 1, 2, 3, 6.

After factoring out $\langle (0, 2) \rangle$, the remaining element orders in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ may include orders 4 or 8, depending on how $(0, 2)$ interacts with other elements.

3. Key Observation for Non-Isomorphism:

$\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ and $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ cannot be isomorphic if:

- $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ contains an element of order 4 or 8.
- This is because $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ only has elements of order 1 or 2.

If all elements in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ have order 1 or 2, then the groups are isomorphic.

Analysis of Element Orders

To determine if $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ is isomorphic to $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, we analyze the possible orders of elements in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle (0, 2) \rangle$ and compare them with the orders of elements in $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$.

Orders of Elements in $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$:

In $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, all elements have order 1 or 2. This is because each component group \mathbb{Z}_2 is cyclic of order 2, and the least common multiple (lcm) of the orders of the components is 1 or 2.

Orders of Elements in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6/\langle(0, 2)\rangle$:

The group $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6/\langle(0, 2)\rangle$ has order 8, and by Lagrange's theorem, the possible orders of its elements are 1, 2, 4, or 8. The actual order of an element depends on its structure after factoring out the subgroup $\langle(0, 2)\rangle$.

Finding an Element of Order $\neq 1, 2$:

We now test whether there exists an element in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6/\langle(0, 2)\rangle$ with order greater than 2.

Consider the element $(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle$ in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6/\langle(0, 2)\rangle$:

$$\text{order}((1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle) = \min\{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid k(1, 0) \in \langle(0, 2)\rangle\}.$$

Compute the iterations of $(1, 0)$ modulo $\langle(0, 2)\rangle$:

$$\begin{aligned}(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle &\neq \langle(0, 2)\rangle, \\ 2(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle &\neq \langle(0, 2)\rangle, \\ 3(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle &\neq \langle(0, 2)\rangle, \\ 4(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle &= \langle(0, 2)\rangle.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $(1, 0) + \langle(0, 2)\rangle$ has order 4.

Conclusion:

Since $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6/\langle(0, 2)\rangle$ contains an element of order 4, it cannot be isomorphic to $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, because the latter only has elements of order 1 or 2.

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Lecture 23 (11/25)

Week 9

Theorem 13.9: If G is cyclic and N is a subgroup of G , then the factor group G/N is also cyclic.

For us to write G/N , the subgroup N must be normal. Since G is abelian, $N \trianglelefteq G$ automatically.

Cyclic groups are abelian because they are generated by repeated powers of a single element. Thus, the order of operations does not affect the result.

Proof: Let G be a cyclic group, so $G = \langle a \rangle$ for some $a \in G$. Let $N \trianglelefteq G$. Since G is abelian, N is normal. We compute the cyclic subgroup of G/N generated by a single element.

Example: Let $G = \mathbb{Z}_{10} = \langle 7 \rangle$ and $N = \langle 5 \rangle = \{0, 5\}$.

The coset aN generates the subgroup $\langle aN \rangle$, given by:

$$\langle aN \rangle = \{(aN)^n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

By the definition of the binary operation on cosets, this simplifies to:

$$\langle aN \rangle = \{a^n N \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}\} = \frac{G}{N}.$$

Therefore, $1 + \langle 5 \rangle$ generates G/N under the binary operation.

In general, $\langle a \rangle + N$ generates the entire factor group G/N .

To prove G/N is cyclic, we find a generator. Let us compute the cyclic subgroup generated by aN and verify if it generates G/N .

Since $\langle a \rangle$ generates G , the powers of a^n give all possible elements of G .

Theorem: Fundamental Theorem of Homomorphisms

Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a group homomorphism with kernel H . The kernel of ϕ is given by:

$$\ker(\phi) = H.$$

Since $\ker(\phi)$ is a normal subgroup, we have:

$$\ker(\phi) \trianglelefteq G.$$

1. $\phi(G)$ is a group.
2. Define the map $\mu : G/H \rightarrow \phi(G)$ by:

$$\mu(gH) = \phi(g),$$

where the input $\mu(gH)$ is a coset.

This map μ is a group isomorphism, implying:

$$G/H \cong \phi(G).$$

Example: We need a group homomorphism ϕ such that the kernel satisfies the Fundamental Theorem of Homomorphisms.

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}_{10}$, $G' = \mathbb{Z}_5$, and define:

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z}_{10} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_5$$

such that:

$$\phi(n) = n \pmod{5}.$$

For specific elements:

$$\phi(2) = 2, \quad \phi(7) = 2, \quad \phi(4) = 4.$$

We see that the image of ϕ is all of \mathbb{Z}_5 , i.e., $\text{Im}(\phi) = \mathbb{Z}_5$.

The kernel of ϕ is:

$$\ker(\phi) = \{0, 5\} = H.$$

Theorem states:

1. $\phi(\mathbb{Z}_{10}) = \mathbb{Z}_5$ is a group.

2. Define the map:

$$\mu : \mathbb{Z}_{10}/\langle 5 \rangle \rightarrow \phi(\mathbb{Z}_{10}),$$

$$\text{where } \mu(n + \langle 5 \rangle) = \phi(n).$$

This map μ is an isomorphism, showing:

$$\mathbb{Z}_{10}/\langle 5 \rangle \cong \phi(\mathbb{Z}_{10}) = \mathbb{Z}_5.$$

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Lecture 24 (11/25) - Week 9

This lecture finishes Section 13 and covers:

- Simple groups
- Maximal subgroups
- Center and commutator subgroups

Definition: Simple Groups

A group G is **simple** if:

1. G is nontrivial, and
2. G has no proper, nontrivial normal subgroups.

Notes:

- $\{e\} \leq G$: The trivial normal subgroup is still normal.
- $G \leq G$: G itself is always a normal subgroup.

Thus, G is simple if it has no normal subgroups other than $\{e\}$ and G itself.

Examples

1. **Non-simple groups:** If G is abelian, then G has many normal subgroups, implying G is not simple.

2. **Simple groups:** The alternating group A_n is simple for $n \geq 5$. (See HW 41.)

Proof: Alternating Group A_n is Simple for $n \geq 5$

1. **Step 1: Show that A_n contains all 3-cycles.** Any permutation of the form (xyz) (for $x, y, z \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $x \neq y \neq z$) can be expressed as the product of two transpositions:

$$(123) = (13)(12), \quad (xyz) = (xz)(xy).$$

2. **Step 2: Show that A_n is generated by 3-cycles.** The set $\{(123), (124), (234), \dots\}$ generates A_n .

To prove this, we consider three cases for products of two transpositions $(xy)(zw)$:

(a) **Case 1:** $(xy) = (zw)$

$$(xy)(zw) = (12)(12) = e,$$

which is the identity and can be ignored.

(b) **Case 2: One number appears in both transpositions, e.g., $(xy)(xz)$.** This can be expressed as:

$$(xy)(xz) = (xzy).$$

(c) **Case 3: The transpositions are disjoint, e.g., $(12)(34)$.** This can be expressed as:

$$(12)(34) = (132)(142).$$

Thus, any element in A_n can be generated by multiplying 3-cycles.

Theorem 13.18: Normality Under Homomorphism

Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism. If $N \trianglelefteq G$ (i.e., N is a normal subgroup of G), then $\phi(N) \trianglelefteq \phi[G]$. Here, $\phi[G]$ is the image of G under ϕ , which is itself a group.

Explanation:

- $\phi[G] = \{\phi(g) \mid g \in G\}$ is a subgroup of G' , and it is guaranteed to form a group.
- The image $\phi(N)$ of N is a normal subgroup of $\phi[G]$, meaning $\phi(n)$ satisfies normality conditions in $\phi[G]$.
- Even if ϕ is not one-to-one (not injective), $\phi(N)$ remains normal within $\phi[G]$.

Notes:

- Normality depends on the context where the subgroup resides.
- The theorem guarantees that $\phi(N)$ is normal within $\phi[G]$, even though $\phi[G]$ might not be all of G' .

Also, if $N \trianglelefteq \Phi[G]$, then $\Phi[N] \trianglelefteq G$.

Definition: A *maximal normal subgroup* of a group G is a normal subgroup $M \trianglelefteq G$, such that:

There is no proper normal subgroup of G that properly contains M .

Namely: $M \neq G$

and it is impossible to have: $M \leq N \trianglelefteq G$

Namely: $M \neq G$

and it is impossible to have: $M \leq N \trianglelefteq G$

which is impossible (unless N itself is G or M), but it is impossible if N is a normal proper subgroup of G and M is a proper subgroup of N .

Example: $A_n \trianglelefteq S_n$ (normal)

Claim: It is a maximal normal subgroup.

Impossible: $A_n < N < S_n$

(where N is a normal subgroup of S_n and A_n is a proper subgroup of N).

Impossible: $A_n < N < S_n$

Explanation:

- $|A_n| = \frac{1}{2}n!$
- $|S_n| = n!$
- By Lagrange's Theorem, $|N| \mid n!$.
- But $|A_n| = \frac{1}{2}n!$ is the largest number dividing $n!$ that corresponds to a subgroup.

But $|A_n| = \frac{1}{2}n!$ is the largest number which divides $n!$.

So $|N| \leq |A_n|$, and therefore N cannot contain A_n .

The same argument could work for any index 2 subgroup.

Namely: $H \leq G$ with $[G : H] = 2$.

If $H \trianglelefteq G$, then no subgroup can fit between H and G .

$\therefore H$ is maximal normal.

Q: When is G/N simple?

Theorem:

M is a maximal normal subgroup of G if and only if G/M is simple.

Proof: Let M be maximal normal in G .

Let $\varphi : G \rightarrow G/M$ be the homomorphism defined by:

$$\varphi(g) = gM.$$

Since φ is a homomorphism, any (non-trivial, proper) normal subgroup $N \trianglelefteq G/M$ implies that $\varphi^{-1}[N]$ is a normal subgroup of G containing M .

Proof: Let G be a group and M a maximal normal subgroup. Define the homomorphism $\gamma : G \rightarrow G/M$, which maps $g \in G$ to the coset gM in G/M . We aim to show that G/M is simple.

Assume for contradiction that G/M is not simple. Then there exists a normal subgroup $N \trianglelefteq G/M$ with $N \neq \{eM\}$ and $N \neq G/M$.

By the theorem that the preimage of a normal subgroup under a homomorphism is also normal, $\gamma^{-1}[N] \trianglelefteq G$. Furthermore, since N contains the identity coset eM , the preimage $\gamma^{-1}[N]$ must contain all elements of M , as eM corresponds to the subgroup M in G .

Thus, $\gamma^{-1}[N]$ is a normal subgroup of G that properly contains M . This contradicts the assumption that M is a maximal normal subgroup of G . Therefore, G/M must be simple.

Definition: Let G be a group. The *center* of G , denoted $\mathcal{Z}(G)$, is defined as:

$$\mathcal{Z}(G) = \{z \in G \mid zg = gz \text{ for all } g \in G\}.$$

In words: $\mathcal{Z}(G)$ consists of all elements $z \in G$ that commute with every element of G .

Examples:

- (0) If G is abelian, then $\mathcal{Z}(G) = G$. In this case, the center is not particularly interesting, as every element commutes with every other element.
- (1) For the symmetric group S_n , $\mathcal{Z}(S_n) = \{e\}$.

To verify this, we compute the center by testing commutativity of elements using the group table. Consider the group table below:

	a	b	c	d
a	aa	ab	ac	ad
b	ba	bb	bc	bd
c	ca	cb	cc	cd
d	da	db	dc	dd

An element $z \in G$ is in the center $\mathcal{Z}(G)$ if and only if the row and column corresponding to z in this table satisfy $zg = gz$ for all $g \in G$. This means z commutes with all other elements.

In the case of S_n , the identity element e satisfies $zg = gz$ for all $g \in S_n$, while no other element does. Thus, $\mathcal{Z}(S_n) = \{e\}$.

The group S_3 consists of all permutations of three elements. It has the following elements:

$$S_3 = \{e, (1\ 2), (1\ 3), (2\ 3), (1\ 2\ 3), (1\ 3\ 2)\}.$$

To compute the center $\mathcal{Z}(S_3)$, we take each element $z \in S_3$ and check if it commutes with all other elements.

- Consider the permutation $(1\ 2\ 3)$. Check:

$$(1\ 2)(1\ 2\ 3) = (1\ 3), \quad \text{but} \quad (1\ 2\ 3)(1\ 2) = (2\ 3).$$

Since $(1\ 2)(1\ 2\ 3) \neq (1\ 2\ 3)(1\ 2)$, $(1\ 2\ 3) \notin \mathcal{Z}(S_3)$.

- Similarly, the other non-identity elements fail to commute with all group members.
- The only element that commutes with all others is the identity e .

Thus, the center of S_3 is trivial:

$$\mathcal{Z}(S_3) = \{e\}.$$

More interesting case: The dihedral group

Example: Center of the Dihedral Group D_n .

For n odd:

$$\mathcal{Z}(D_n) = \{e\}.$$

The properties of the dihedral group D_n include:

1. $r^n = e$ (all rotations form a cyclic subgroup of order n).
2. $m^2 = e$ (each reflection squared is the identity).
3. $r^k m = m r^{n-k}$ (relation between rotations and reflections).

Verification: Does $\rho^{n/2} \mu = \mu \rho^{n/2}$?

Using the group relation $\rho^k \mu = \mu \rho^{n-k}$, substitute $k = n/2$:

$$\rho^{n/2} \mu = \mu \rho^{n-n/2}.$$

Simplify:

$$\rho^{n/2} \mu = \mu \rho^{n/2}.$$

Thus, $\rho^{n/2}$ commutes with μ .

Conclusion:

- Since $\rho^{n/2}$ commutes with both ρ (all rotations) and μ (all reflections), it follows that $\rho^{n/2}$ commutes with all elements of D_n .

- Therefore, $\rho^{n/2} \in \mathcal{Z}(D_n)$.

Explicit Computation:

$$\rho^{n/2}(\mu\rho^k\mu) = (\mu\rho^{n/2}\mu)(\mu\rho^k\mu).$$

Using the relation $\mu\rho^k\mu = \rho^{n-k}$, rewrite:

$$\rho^{n/2}(\mu\rho^k\mu) = (\mu\rho^{n/2}\mu)\rho^{n-k}.$$

Since $\rho^{n/2}\mu = \mu\rho^{n/2}$, this confirms that $\rho^{n/2}$ commutes with all elements of D_n .

Definition: Let $a, b \in G$. The element

$$aba^{-1}b^{-1}$$

is called the *commutator* of a and b .

Note: If a and b commute, namely if $ab = ba$, then:

$$aba^{-1}b^{-1} = e,$$

where e is the identity element.

Definition: Let G be a group. The set of all commutators

$$\{aba^{-1}b^{-1} \mid a, b \in G\}$$

generates a subgroup C , called the *commutator subgroup* of G .

Theorem: The commutator subgroup C is normal in G . Furthermore, if $N \trianglelefteq G$, then:

$$G/N \text{ is abelian if and only if } C \leq N.$$

Note: If we have two elements ρ and μ in a group G , their commutator is:

$$[\rho, \mu] = \rho\mu\rho^{-1}\mu^{-1}.$$

This commutator is simply a new element of the group, which may or may not be trivial (the identity element). In particular:

- If ρ and μ commute, then $[\rho, \mu] = e$, the identity element.
- If ρ and μ do not commute, then $[\rho, \mu] \neq e$, and the commutator represents a distinct element in G .

v If we take all the commutators $aba^{-1}b^{-1}$ for all $a, b \in G$, we obtain a subgroup denoted C , called the *commutator subgroup* of G .

Theorem:

1. The commutator subgroup C is normal in G , i.e., $C \trianglelefteq G$.
2. A factor group G/N is abelian if and only if N contains the commutator subgroup C , i.e.,

$$G/N \text{ is abelian} \iff C \leq N.$$

Example: Let $G = S_n$ and $N = A_n \trianglelefteq G$.

Question: Is $G/N = S_n/A_n$ abelian?

Solution: By the theorem, it is enough to check whether the commutator subgroup $C \leq A_n$.

Namely, do all commutators in S_n belong to A_n ?

Example: Continued.

Question: Do all commutators in S_n belong to A_n ?

Answer: Yes.

Explanation: Consider a general commutator of the form:

$$\sigma\tau\sigma^{-1}\tau^{-1},$$

where $\sigma, \tau \in S_n$.

The elements of the commutator involve transpositions from σ, τ , and their inverses. Observing the permutations:

- Every transposition appears *twice* in the commutator.
- Thus, the total number of transpositions in the commutator is *even*.

Since a permutation with an even number of transpositions belongs to A_n , any commutator $\sigma\tau\sigma^{-1}\tau^{-1} \in A_n$.

Conclusion:

- The commutator subgroup $C \leq A_n$.
- By the theorem, if $C \leq A_n$, the factor group S_n/A_n is abelian.

Conclusion:

By the theorem, since $C \leq A_n$, it follows that:

$$S_n/A_n \text{ is abelian.}$$

Additional Note: In fact, the order of S_n/A_n is:

$$|S_n/A_n| = 2,$$

which implies that S_n/A_n is isomorphic to the cyclic group $\{0, 1\}$ under addition modulo 2.

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Lecture 24 (11/25) - Week 10

Classification of $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 / \langle (1, 2) \rangle$

To classify $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 / \langle (1, 2) \rangle$, we first compute the order of the subgroup $\langle (1, 2) \rangle$.

1. The order of $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8$ is $4 \times 8 = 32$.
2. The order of $(1, 2)$ is given by:

$$\text{lcm}(\text{order of } 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_4, \text{order of } 2 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_8) = \text{lcm}(4, 4) = 4.$$

3. The order of $\langle (1, 2) \rangle$ is 4, so the order of the quotient is:

$$\frac{\text{Order of } \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8}{\text{Order of } \langle (1, 2) \rangle} = \frac{32}{4} = 8.$$

Thus, $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 / \langle (1, 2) \rangle$ is isomorphic to a cyclic group of order 8, \mathbb{Z}_8 .

Step 1: List All Abelian Groups of Order 8

The possible abelian groups of order 8 (using the Fundamental Theorem of Finite Abelian Groups) are:

$$\mathbb{Z}_8, \quad \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2, \quad \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2.$$

Step 2: Determine the Maximal Possible Order of an Element in Each Group

- For \mathbb{Z}_8 , the maximal possible order of an element is 8.
- For $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, the maximal possible order is:

$$\text{lcm}(\text{order of an element in } \mathbb{Z}_4, \text{order of an element in } \mathbb{Z}_2) = \text{lcm}(4, 2) = 4.$$

- For $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, all elements have order 2.

Thus, \mathbb{Z}_8 has the largest maximal order element (8).

Step 3: Find the Maximal Possible Order of an Element in the Original Group

The original group is $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8$, and the order of an element $(a, b) \in \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8$ is:

$$\text{lcm}(\text{order of } a \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_4, \text{order of } b \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_8).$$

- The order of any element in \mathbb{Z}_4 is at most 4, and in \mathbb{Z}_8 , at most 8.
- Choosing $a = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_4$ (order 4) and $b = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_8$ (order 8):

$$\text{lcm}(4, 8) = 8.$$

Thus, the maximal possible order of an element in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8$ is 8.

Conclusion

Since the quotient $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 / \langle (1, 2) \rangle$ also has order 8, and the maximal possible order of an element is preserved in the quotient, the resulting group is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_8 .

Maximal Order Elements in Groups

To deduce the maximal order element in a group, consider the following example:

Example: Symmetric Group S_3

1. Elements and Their Possible Orders:

- Identity e : $\text{ord}(e) = 1$,
- Transpositions (e.g., $(a_1 a_2)$): $\text{ord}((a_1 a_2)) = 2$,
- 3-cycles (e.g., $(a_1 a_2 a_3)$): $\text{ord}((a_1 a_2 a_3)) = 3$.

2. No Elements of Order 6:

In S_3 , the possible orders are 1, 2, and 3. There are no elements whose order is 6.

- #### 3. General Rule:
- For a group G , the maximal order of an element corresponds to the largest lcm of the cycle lengths (or the additive orders in abelian groups).

Application to $S_3 / \langle (1 2 3) \rangle$

1. Start with $(3 2 1)$. 2. Compose it repeatedly with itself modulo $\langle (1 2 3) \rangle$:

$$(3 2 1), \quad (3 2 1)^2, \quad (3 2 1)^3, \quad \dots$$

3. Determine the smallest k such that:

$$(3 2 1)^k \in \langle (1 2 3) \rangle.$$

4. Since the order of $(1 2 3)$ in S_3 is 3, $k = 3$.

Conclusion

The quotient group cycles through the coset representatives in 3 iterations.

Problem 2 (Final Study Guide)

Let N be a normal subgroup of G and let H be a subgroup of G . Let

$$HN = \{hn : h \in H, n \in N\}.$$

- (a) (5 points) Show that HN is a subgroup of G .
- (b) (5 points) Show that the subgroup HN is the smallest subgroup containing both N and H .

Problem 2: Solution Outline

Step 1: Recall Some Theory

To show that a given set $K \subseteq G$ is a subgroup of G , it must satisfy the following criteria:

1. **Identity:** K contains the identity element of G .
2. **Closure:** If $x, y \in K$, then $xy \in K$.
3. **Inverses:** If $x \in K$, then $x^{-1} \in K$.

Additionally, recall the definition of a **normal subgroup**:

- N is a normal subgroup of G if $gN = Ng$ for all $g \in G$.
- This can equivalently be stated as: for all $g \in G$ and $n \in N$, $gng^{-1} \in N$. This definition is convenient to work with.
- Another equivalent definition is: for all $g \in G$, the conjugate subgroup $gNg^{-1} = N$.
- Alternatively, there exists a group homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ such that $N = \ker(\phi)$ (the kernel of ϕ).

Solution

We verify that HN satisfies the subgroup criteria (identity, closure, and inverses):

1. Identity Element

We show that $e \in HN$:

- The identity element e is in H because H is a subgroup.
- Similarly, e is in N because N is a subgroup.
- Therefore, $ee = e \in HN$.

By the definition $HN = \{hn \mid h \in H, n \in N\}$, the identity element is in HN .

2. Closure

We show that for all $a, b \in HN$, $ab \in HN$:

- Write a and b as $a = h_1n_1$ and $b = h_2n_2$, where $h_1, h_2 \in H$ and $n_1, n_2 \in N$.
- The product is:

$$ab = (h_1n_1)(h_2n_2) = h_1(n_1h_2)n_2.$$

- Since N is normal, $n_1h_2 = h_2n'_1$ for some $n'_1 \in N$. Substituting, we have:

$$ab = h_1h_2(n'_1n_2),$$

where $h_1h_2 \in H$ (because H is a subgroup) and $n'_1n_2 \in N$ (because N is a subgroup). Thus, $ab \in HN$.

Alternatively, by using associativity, write:

$$(h_1n_1)(h_2n_2) = (h_1(n_1h_2))n_2 = h_1h_2(h_2^{-1}n_1h_2)n_2.$$

- The first two terms $h_1h_2 \in H$.
- The term $h_2^{-1}n_1h_2 \in N$ because N is normal (it is closed under conjugation by elements of G).
- The final term $n_2 \in N$ because $n_2 \in N$ by definition.
- Hence, $ab \in HN$.

Conclusion for Closure

Since the product of two elements in HN is in HN , HN is closed under the group operation.

3. Inverses (Optional Step for Completeness)

For completeness, we can show that if $x \in HN$, then $x^{-1} \in HN$. Let $x = hn$, where $h \in H$ and $n \in N$. Then:

$$x^{-1} = (hn)^{-1} = n^{-1}h^{-1}.$$

- Since N is normal, $n^{-1}h^{-1} = h^{-1}n'$ for some $n' \in N$.
- Hence, $x^{-1} = h^{-1}n' \in HN$, where $h^{-1} \in H$ and $n' \in N$.

Conclusion

We have verified:

- HN contains the identity element.
- HN is closed under the group operation.
- HN contains inverses of its elements.

Thus, HN is a subgroup of G .

Problem 1.

Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a group homomorphism, and let $a \in \text{Ker}(\phi)$. Prove that for any $b \in G$, we have $bab^{-1} \in \text{Ker}(\phi)$.

8.1 Definition Let G and G' be groups with $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$. The map ϕ is a **homomorphism** if the homomorphism property

$$\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$$

holds for all $a, b \in G$. ■

8.5 Theorem Let ϕ be a homomorphism of a group G into a group G' .

1. If e is the identity element in G , then $\phi(e)$ is the identity element e' in G' .
2. If $a \in G$, then $\phi(a^{-1}) = \phi(a)^{-1}$.
3. If H is a subgroup of G , then $\phi[H]$ is a subgroup of G' .
4. If K' is a subgroup of G' , then $\phi^{-1}[K']$ is a subgroup of G .

Loosely speaking, ϕ preserves the identity element, inverses, and subgroups.

8.6 Definition Let $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of groups. The subgroup $\phi^{-1}[\{e'\}] = \{x \in G \mid \phi(x) = e'\}$ is the **kernel of ϕ** , denoted by $\text{Ker}(\phi)$. ■

Prove that $\phi(bab^{-1}) = e'$

$$\phi((bab^{-1})) = \phi(b)\phi(a)\phi(b^{-1}) = \phi(b)\phi(a)\phi(b)^{-1} = \phi(b) \cancel{\phi(a)} \phi(b)^{-1}$$

$$= \phi(b)\phi(b)^{-1} = e'$$

Since a is in the kernel of ϕ

$$\phi(bab^{-1}) = e' \Rightarrow bab^{-1} \in \text{ker}(\phi)$$

Problem 2.

What is the order of $(3, 10, 9)$ in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{15}$?

9.8 Definition Let r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n be positive integers. Their **least common multiple** (abbreviated lcm) is the positive generator of the cyclic group of all common multiples of the r_i , that is, the cyclic group of all integers divisible by each r_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. ■

From Definition 9.8 and our work on cyclic groups, we see that the lcm of r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n is the smallest positive integer that is a multiple of each r_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, hence the name *least common multiple*.

9.9 Theorem Let $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \prod_{i=1}^n G_i$. If a_i is of finite order r_i in G_i , then the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) in $\prod_{i=1}^n G_i$ is equal to the least common multiple of all the r_i .

9.10 Example Find the order of $(8, 4, 10)$ in the group $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{60} \times \mathbb{Z}_{24}$.

Solution Since the gcd of 8 and 12 is 4, we see that 8 is of order $\frac{12}{4} = 3$ in \mathbb{Z}_{12} . (See Theorem 6.15.) Similarly, we find that 4 is of order 15 in \mathbb{Z}_{60} and 10 is of order 12 in \mathbb{Z}_{24} . The lcm of 3, 15, and 12 is $3 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 = 60$, so $(8, 4, 10)$ is of order 60 in the group $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{60} \times \mathbb{Z}_{24}$. ▲

The order of $(3, 10, 9)$ in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{15}$ is found as follows:

$$\text{In } \mathbb{Z}_4, \text{ the order of } 3 \text{ is } \frac{4}{\gcd(3, 4)} = \frac{4}{1} = 4.$$

$$\text{In } \mathbb{Z}_{12}, \text{ the order of } 10 \text{ is } \frac{12}{\gcd(10, 12)} = \frac{12}{2} = 6.$$

$$\text{In } \mathbb{Z}_{15}, \text{ the order of } 9 \text{ is } \frac{15}{\gcd(9, 15)} = \frac{15}{3} = 5.$$

The least common multiple of 4, 6, and 5 is
 $\text{lcm}(4, 6, 5) = \text{lcm}(\text{lcm}(4, 6), 5) = \text{lcm}(12, 5) = 60.$

∴ The order of $(3, 10, 9)$ is 60.

Problem 3.

Let $\sigma = (1, 2, 5, 4)(2, 3)$ in S_5 . What is the index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 ?

10.10 Definition Let H be a subgroup of a group G . The number of left cosets of H in G is the **index** $(G:H)$ of H in G . ■

The **index** $(G:H)$ just defined may be finite or infinite. If G is finite, then obviously $(G:H)$ is finite and $(G:H) = |G|/|H|$, since every coset of H contains $|H|$ elements. We state a basic theorem concerning indices of subgroups, and leave the proof to the exercises (see Exercise 40).

Let $\sigma = (1, 2, 5, 4)(2, 3)$ in S_5 . Find the index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 .

The order of σ is determined by the cycle structure.

$(1, 2, 5, 4)$ is a 4-cycle and $(2, 3)$ is a 2-cycle.

The order of σ is the lcm of the lengths of the cycles.

$$\text{Order of } \sigma = \text{lcm}(4, 2) = 4.$$

The subgroup $\langle \sigma \rangle$ generated by σ has order $|\langle \sigma \rangle| = 4$.

By Lagrange's Theorem, the index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 is:

$$|S_5 : \langle \sigma \rangle| = \frac{|S_5|}{|\langle \sigma \rangle|} = \frac{120}{4} = 30.$$

\therefore The index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 is 30.

Problem 3.

Let $\sigma = (1, 2, 5, 4)(2, 3)$ in S_5 . What is the index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 ?

$$\text{Define } \sigma = (1, 2, 5, 4)(2, 3) \implies \sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Verify σ^k for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$:

1. $\sigma^2 = \sigma \cdot \sigma$:

$$\sigma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 5 & 4 & 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

2. $\sigma^3 = \sigma^2 \cdot \sigma$:

$$\sigma^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 5 & 4 & 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 1 & 3 & 5 & 2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

3. $\sigma^4 = \sigma^3 \cdot \sigma$:

$$\sigma^4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 1 & 3 & 5 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 3 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus, $\langle \sigma \rangle = \{\sigma_0, \sigma, \sigma^2, \sigma^3\}$, giving $|\langle \sigma \rangle| = 4$.

$$\text{Finally, } |S_5 : \langle \sigma \rangle| = \frac{120}{4} = 30.$$

\therefore The index of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ in S_5 is 30.

Problem 4.

Find the order of the factor group $(\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2)/\langle(2, 1)\rangle$.

Let $G = \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ and $H = \langle(2, 1)\rangle$.

H is the subgroup generated by $(2, 1)$ in G .

Since H is generated by a single element, we first determine the order of this element in G .

In \mathbb{Z}_4 , the element 2 has order $\frac{4}{\gcd(2, 4)} = 2$.

In \mathbb{Z}_2 , the element 1 has order $\frac{2}{\gcd(1, 2)} = 2$.

The order of $(2, 1)$ is the least common multiple of the orders of its components.

$$\text{Order of } (2, 1) = \text{lcm}(2, 2) = 2.$$

$\therefore H = \langle(2, 1)\rangle$ is a cyclic subgroup of G of order 2.

By Theorem 12.7, since H is normal, we can form the factor group G/H .

The order of G/H is given by $\frac{|G|}{|H|}$.

$$|\mathbb{Z}_4| = 4, \quad |\mathbb{Z}_2| = 2, \quad \text{so } |G| = 4 \cdot 2 = 8.$$

$$|H| = 2, \quad \text{so } |G/H| = \frac{8}{2} = 4.$$

Since G/H has 4 elements, it is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_4 , the only group of order 4 in this case.

$$\therefore G/H \cong \mathbb{Z}_4.$$

Cayley Diagram for Z_{12} with Generators 2 and 3

Problem 6.

Let p be a prime number. Find the number of generators of the cyclic group \mathbb{Z}_{p^r} , where $r \geq 1$ is an integer.

$$\begin{array}{l} r = 1 \\ \mathbb{Z}_p \end{array} \quad p - 1$$

$$\begin{array}{l} r = 2 \\ \mathbb{Z}_{p^2} \end{array} \quad p^2 - 2$$

$$\mathbb{Z}_{p^r} : p^r - r$$

Problem 8.

(a) What is the largest possible degree of an element of $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{18}$?

(b) Using part (a) or otherwise, show that $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{18}$ is not cyclic.

9.9 Theorem Let $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \prod_{i=1}^n G_i$. If a_i is of finite order r_i in G_i , then the order of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) in $\prod_{i=1}^n G_i$ is equal to the least common multiple of all the r_i .

Proof This follows by a repetition of the argument used in the proof of Theorem 9.5. For a power of (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) to give (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) , the power must simultaneously be a multiple of r_1 so that this power of the first component a_1 will yield e_1 , a multiple of r_2 , so that this power of the second component a_2 will yield e_2 , and so on. \blacklozenge

9.10 Example Find the order of $(8, 4, 10)$ in the group $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{60} \times \mathbb{Z}_{24}$.

Solution Since the gcd of 8 and 12 is 4, we see that 8 is of order $\frac{12}{4} = 3$ in \mathbb{Z}_{12} . (See Theorem 6.15.) Similarly, we find that 4 is of order 15 in \mathbb{Z}_{60} and 10 is of order 12 in \mathbb{Z}_{24} . The lcm of 3, 15, and 12 is $3 \cdot 5 \cdot 4 = 60$, so $(8, 4, 10)$ is of order 60 in the group $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \times \mathbb{Z}_{60} \times \mathbb{Z}_{24}$. \blacktriangle

$\frac{12}{a}, \frac{18}{b}$ To get largest order pick 1 for a and b

$$\text{lcm}(12, 18) = 36$$

ⓑ $12 \cdot 18 = 216$

You need to have a generator to generate all 216 elements
but we have shown the largest cyclic subgroup we can generate is 36 in part a

Problem 9.

Let $S^1 = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$ be the circle group.

- Show that the map $\varphi: \mathbb{C}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ defined by $\varphi(z) = |z|$ is a group homomorphism.
- Compute the kernel $\text{Ker}(\varphi)$ and the image $\varphi(\mathbb{C}^*)$ of φ .
- Using the first isomorphism theorem or otherwise, prove that $\mathbb{C}^*/S^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^+$.

12.14 Theorem (The Fundamental Homomorphism Theorem) Let $\phi: G \rightarrow G'$ be a group homomorphism with kernel H . Then $\phi[G]$ is a group, and $\mu: G/H \rightarrow \phi[G]$ given by $\mu(gH) = \phi(g)$ is an isomorphism. If $\gamma: G \rightarrow G/H$ is the homomorphism given by $\gamma(g) = gH$, then $\phi(g) = \mu \circ \gamma(g)$ for each $g \in G$.

Theorem 12.14 states that $\phi(g) = \mu \circ \gamma(g)$. This can be visualized in Figure 12.15. If we start with an element $g \in G$, and map it to $\phi(g)$, we get the same result as first mapping g to $\gamma(g)$ and then mapping $\gamma(g)$ to $\mu \circ \gamma(g)$. When we have a situation like this, we say that the map ϕ can be factored as $\phi = \mu \circ \gamma$.

12.15 Figure

Let $S^1 = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$ be the circle group.

First Isomorphism Theorem (12.14): $\mathbb{C}^*/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{Im}(\varphi)$

$\ker(\varphi) = \varphi^{-1}(1) = \{z \in \mathbb{C}^* \mid |z| = 1\} = S^1$, as $\varphi(z) = |z| \implies |z| = 1$.

The quotient group \mathbb{C}^*/S^1 is the set of left cosets: $\{zS^1 \mid z \in \mathbb{C}^*\}$.

Each coset $zS^1 = \{z \cdot w \mid w \in S^1\}$ contains all complex numbers with the same modulus as z .

$\text{Im}(\varphi) = \{\varphi(z) \mid z \in \mathbb{C}^*\}$.

Since $\varphi(z) = |z|$, the set of all possible values of $|z|$ is \mathbb{R}^+ , the set of positive real numbers.

$\text{Im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{R}^+$.

By the First Isomorphism Theorem, we have: $\mathbb{C}^*/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{Im}(\varphi)$.

Substituting $\ker(\varphi) = S^1$ and $\text{Im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{R}^+$, it follows that:

$\mathbb{C}^*/S^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^+$.

Problem 9.

Let $S^1 = \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z| = 1\}$ be the circle group.

- (a) Show that the map $\varphi: \mathbb{C}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ defined by $\varphi(z) = |z|$ is a group homomorphism.
- (b) Compute the kernel $\text{Ker}(\varphi)$ and the image $\varphi(\mathbb{C}^*)$ of φ .
- (c) Using the first isomorphism theorem or otherwise, prove that $\mathbb{C}^*/S^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^+$.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(a *_1 b) &= \varphi(a) *_2 \varphi(b) \\ z_1 &= r_1 e^{i\theta_1}, \quad z_2 = r_2 e^{i\theta_2} \\ \varphi(z_1) &= r_1, \quad \varphi(z_2) = r_2 \\ \varphi(a) *_2 \varphi(b) &= r_1 r_2 \\ \varphi(z_1 z_2) &= \varphi(r_1 e^{i\theta_1} r_2 e^{i\theta_2}) = \varphi\left(\underbrace{r_1 r_2}_{r_3} e^{i\left(\underbrace{\theta_1 + \theta_2}_{\theta_3}\right)}\right) = r_1 r_2 = \varphi(a) *_2 \varphi(b) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Ker}(\varphi) = \varphi(z) = 1 = \varphi((1)e^{i\theta}) = \varphi(S^1)$$

8.4 Definition Let $\phi: X \rightarrow Y$ and suppose that $A \subseteq X$ and $B \subseteq Y$. The set $\phi[A] = \{\phi(a) \mid a \in A\}$ is called the **image** of A in Y under the mapping ϕ . The set $\phi^{-1}[B] = \{a \in A \mid \phi(a) \in B\}$ is called the **inverse image** of B under the mapping ϕ . ■

The four properties of a homomorphism given in the theorem that follows are obvious in the case of an isomorphism since we think of an isomorphism as simply relabeling the elements of a group. However, it is not obvious that these properties hold for all homomorphisms whether or not they are one-to-one or onto maps. Consequently, we give careful proofs of all four properties.

The set of all possible modulus for Z in \mathbb{C}^* (not including zero) is the set of all possible nonzero lengths, is the set of all real numbers

$$\text{image } \varphi(\mathbb{C}^*) \text{ of } \varphi = \mathbb{R}^+$$

12.14 Theorem (The Fundamental Homomorphism Theorem) Let $\phi: G \rightarrow G'$ be a group homomorphism with kernel H . Then $\phi[G]$ is a group, and $\mu: G/H \rightarrow \phi[G]$ given by $\mu(gH) = \phi(g)$ is an isomorphism. If $\gamma: G \rightarrow G/H$ is the homomorphism given by $\gamma(g) = gH$, then $\phi(g) = \mu \circ \gamma(g)$ for each $g \in G$.

Theorem 12.14 states that $\phi(g) = \mu \circ \gamma(g)$. This can be visualized in Figure 12.15. If we start with an element $g \in G$, and map it to $\phi(g)$, we get the same result as first mapping g to $\gamma(g)$ and then mapping $\gamma(g)$ to $\mu \circ \gamma(g)$. When we have a situation like this, we say that the map ϕ can be *factored* as $\phi = \mu \circ \gamma$.

First Isomorphism Theorem (12.14): $\mathbb{C}^*/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{Im}(\varphi)$

$$\ker(\varphi) = \varphi^{-1}(1) = S^1, \quad \text{as } |z| = 1 \implies z \in S^1.$$

$$\text{Im}(\varphi) = \{\varphi(z) \mid z \in \mathbb{C}^*\} = \mathbb{R}^+.$$

$$\implies \mathbb{C}^*/S^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^+.$$

Problem 10.

Let G be a finite group, and suppose G has a subgroup H with $|H| = |G| - 1$. Determine the possible values of $|G|$.

$$G = \{e, a, b\}$$

In order for H to be a subgroup of G , G must have at least one element that is its own inverse, so that removing a single element creates a subgroup. Cyclic groups of even order always have at least one element that is its own inverse, so G can be even.

By Lagrange's theorem, $|H| \mid |G|$, which leads to the condition:

$$n - 1 \mid n.$$

The condition $n - 1 \mid n$ implies that $n - 1$ divides any integer linear combination of n and $n - 1$. In particular, consider the difference:

$$n - (n - 1).$$

Simplifying:

$$n - (n - 1) = 1.$$

Since $n - 1 \mid n$, it follows that $n - 1 \mid 1$.

Step 2: Possible Values of $n - 1$

The only divisors of 1 are ± 1 . Since $n - 1 > 0$ (as $n > 0$), we conclude:

$$n - 1 = 1 \implies n = 2.$$

This reasoning works because:

By Lagrange's theorem, $|H| = n - 1$ must divide $|G| = n$.

The divisibility condition $n - 1 \mid n$ implies $n - 1 \mid 1$, which imposes a strong constraint on $n - 1$.

The structure of groups ensures that $n - 1$ dividing n aligns with the arithmetic of divisors.

The simplification $n - (n - 1) = 1$ does not universally imply that $n - 1 \mid n$ for arbitrary integers n . It works here because the group structure forces $|H| = n - 1$ to divide $|G| = n$. Without this context, the argument does not hold.

Alternatively:

$$n = k(n - 1) = kn - k$$

$$kn - n = k \implies n(k - 1) = k$$

$$n = \frac{k}{k - 1} \implies k = 2$$

2.24 Table

*	e	a	b
e	e	a	b
a	a		
b	b		

2.25 Table

*	e	a	b
e	e	a	b
a	a	b	e
b	b	e	a

Problem 11.

- (a) For each element $\sigma \in S_3$, write σ as a product of transpositions.
- (b) Write down all elements of the alternating group A_3 .

8.14 Definition A cycle of length 2 is a **transposition**. ■

Thus a transposition leaves all elements but two fixed, and maps each of these onto the other. A computation shows that

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = (a_1, a_n)(a_1, a_{n-1}) \cdots (a_1, a_3)(a_1, a_2).$$

Therefore any cycle of length n can be written as a product of $n - 1$ transpositions. Since any permutation of a finite set can be written as a product of cycles, we have the following.

Permutation	Matrix
Identity: e	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$
Transposition $(2, 3)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$
Transposition $(1, 2)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$
Cycle $(1, 2, 3) = (1, 3)(1, 2)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$
Cycle $(1, 3, 2) = (1, 2)(1, 3)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$
Transposition $(1, 3)$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$

The alternating group A_3 consists of all even permutations of three elements. Its elements are:

$$A_3 = \{e, (1\ 2\ 3), (1\ 3\ 2)\},$$

where:

- e : the identity permutation, which leaves all elements unchanged.
- $(1\ 2\ 3) = (1\ 3)(1\ 2)$: the cycle that permutes $1 \rightarrow 2$, $2 \rightarrow 3$, $3 \rightarrow 1$.
- $(1\ 3\ 2) = (1\ 2)(1\ 3)$: the cycle that permutes $1 \rightarrow 3$, $3 \rightarrow 2$, $2 \rightarrow 1$.

Problem 12.

List all abelian groups, up to isomorphism, of order 144.

9.12 Theorem (Primary Factor Version of the Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups) Every finitely generated abelian group G is isomorphic to a direct product of cyclic groups in the form

$$\mathbb{Z}_{(p_1)^{r_1}} \times \mathbb{Z}_{(p_2)^{r_2}} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z}_{(p_n)^{r_n}} \times \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z},$$

where the p_i are primes, not necessarily distinct, and the r_i are positive integers. The direct product is unique except for possible rearrangement of the factors; that is, the number (**Betti number** of G) of factors \mathbb{Z} is unique and the prime powers $(p_i)^{r_i}$ are unique.

Proof The proof is omitted here. ◆

9.13 Example Find all abelian groups, up to isomorphism, of order 360. The phrase *up to isomorphism* signifies that any abelian group of order 360 should be structurally identical (isomorphic) to one of the groups of order 360 exhibited.

Solution We make use of Theorem 9.12. Since our groups are to be of the finite order 360, no factors \mathbb{Z} will appear in the direct product shown in the statement of the theorem.

First we express 360 as a product of prime powers $2^3 3^2 5$. Then using Theorem 9.12, we get as possibilities

1. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$
2. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_9 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$
3. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$
4. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_9 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$
5. $\mathbb{Z}_8 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$
6. $\mathbb{Z}_8 \times \mathbb{Z}_9 \times \mathbb{Z}_5$

Thus there are six different abelian groups (up to isomorphism) of order 360. ▲

There is another version of the Fundamental Theorem of Finitely Generated Abelian Groups. Each version can be proven from the other, so technically, if one version is used to prove something, the other version could also be used. However, it is sometimes more convenient to use one version rather than the other for a particular problem.

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ | 6. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_9$ |
| 2. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ | 7. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_9$ |
| 3. $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ | 8. $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_9$ |
| 4. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ | 9. $\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_8 \times \mathbb{Z}_9$ |
| 5. $\mathbb{Z}_{16} \times \mathbb{Z}_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ | 10. $\mathbb{Z}_{16} \times \mathbb{Z}_9$ |

Lecture 1/06

In 103A, you learn about rings. “multiplied” “2 operations”

Definitions

Review:

A group $(G, *)$ is a set G equipped with a binary operation $*$:

$$G \times G \rightarrow G$$

such that:

1. $*$ is associative.
2. $\exists e \in G$ such that

$$e * g = g * e = g \quad \forall g \in G.$$

3. $\forall g \in G, \exists g' \in G$ such that

$$g * g' = g' * g = e.$$

A group $(G, *)$ is **abelian**, if

$$g * g' = g' * g \quad \forall g, g' \in G.$$

Best example:

$$(\mathbb{Z}, +).$$

Definition of a Ring

A **ring** $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a set R together with **two binary operations**

$$+ : R \times R \rightarrow R \quad \text{and} \quad \cdot : R \times R \rightarrow R$$

such that:

1. $(R, +)$ is an abelian group. *(Addition is commutative.)*
2. \cdot is associative. *(Multiplication is associative.)*
3. **Distributive Laws:**

$$\begin{aligned} a \cdot (b + c) &= a \cdot b + a \cdot c && \text{(Left distributive law),} \\ (a + b) \cdot c &= a \cdot c + b \cdot c && \text{(Right distributive law).} \end{aligned}$$

Example

- Sets: $\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$ under $+$.
- Multiplication in \mathbb{C} is given by:

$$\underbrace{(a + bi)(c + di)}_{\text{product in } \mathbb{C}} = (ac - bd) + (ad + bc)i. \quad \implies$$

Well-known: These satisfy (1), (2), (3).

Exercise

Prove: \circ is associative for \mathbb{C} .

Notes

Note 1: Often we omit the symbol “ \circ ” for multiplication. i.e.,

$$a \circ (b + c) \rightarrow a(b + c).$$

This saves space.

Note 2: For rings like $\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$, the operations $+, \cdot$ are understood unless otherwise specified.

Example: Matrix Rings

Imagine $R = \mathbb{R}$, or more generally any ring R . Define

$$M_n(R) := \{n \times n \text{ matrices with elements in } R\}.$$

Addition example ($n = 2$):

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} a' & b' \\ c' & d' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + a' & b + b' \\ c + c' & d + d' \end{bmatrix}.$$

Multiplication example ($n = 2$):

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a' & b' \\ c' & d' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} aa' + bc' & ab' + bd' \\ ca' + dc' & cb' + dd' \end{bmatrix}.$$

It is a standard (but important!) fact that matrix multiplication is *associative*.

Practice this. **Exercise:** Prove distributivity for matrix addition and multiplication.

Hint: If

$$A = (a_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq n} \quad \text{and} \quad B = (b_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq n},$$

then

$$AB = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik} b_{kj} \right)_{1 \leq i, j \leq n}.$$

One of the main examples showing non-commutativity:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (0 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 1) & (0 \cdot (-1) + 1 \cdot 0) \\ (1 \cdot 2 + 0 \cdot 1) & (1 \cdot (-1) + 0 \cdot 0) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 2 & -1 \end{bmatrix},$$

whereas

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (2 \cdot 0 + (-1) \cdot 1) & (2 \cdot 1 + (-1) \cdot 0) \\ (1 \cdot 0 + 0 \cdot 1) & (1 \cdot 1 + 0 \cdot 0) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

These products are *not* equal, so \cdot **need not be commutative!**

Definition: If $ab = ba$ for all $a, b \in R$, we say R is **commutative**.

Example: Polynomials

Let R be a ring. Then define

$$R[x] := \{\text{all polynomials in the indeterminate } x \text{ with coefficients in } R\}.$$

$$(a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0) + (b_n x^n + b_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + b_1 x + b_0)$$

$$= (a_n + b_n) x^n + \dots + (a_1 + b_1) x + (a_0 + b_0).$$

Multiplication! Exercise: Define the “correct” (i.e. the usual) multiplication by

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^m a_i x^i \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^n b_j x^j \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \underbrace{\left(\sum_{i+j=k} a_i b_j \right)}_{\text{coefficient of } x^k} x^k.$$

Show that this makes $R[x]$ into a ring.

Example: Functions

Let F be the set of all functions $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We know F is an abelian group under pointwise addition:

$$(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x).$$

We can define multiplication on F by

$$(fg)(x) = f(x)g(x),$$

which is again in F . One checks that this multiplication is associative and distributive over addition.

Interesting Examples

Example:

$$n\mathbb{Z} = \langle n \rangle \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$$

under addition:

$$\{\dots, -2n, -n, 0, n, 2n, \dots\}.$$

Notice, for $r n, s n \in \langle n \rangle$:

$$(r n)(s n) = r s \underbrace{nn}_{=n^2} = (r s n) n \in \langle n \rangle.$$

Hence $n\mathbb{Z}$ is closed under multiplication; in fact $n\mathbb{Z}$ is a ring. (*We will check all ring axioms later.*)

Example:

$$\mathbb{Z}_n/n\mathbb{Z} \quad (\mathbb{Z}_n, ?)$$

$$\{\overline{0}, \dots, \overline{n-1}\}$$

Operation for addition: addition modulo n . We define multiplication by:

$$a \cdot b = ab \pmod{n}.$$

For example: $n = 12$,

$$7 \cdot 8 = 56 \equiv 8 \pmod{12}, \quad 6 \cdot 8 = 48 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}.$$

Things can multiply to 0?!?!

$\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ under \cdot is a ring. (Will be checked later!)

Lecture 1/08

The Ring of Integers Modulo n

Equivalence Relation on \mathbb{Z}

Let n be a fixed positive integer. We define the following relation \equiv on \mathbb{Z} :

$$a \equiv b \pmod{n} \iff \text{there exists } k \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } b - a = kn.$$

In other words, a is congruent to b modulo n if and only if n divides the difference $b - a$. It is straightforward to check that this relation is:

- **Reflexive:** $a \equiv a \pmod{n}$.
- **Symmetric:** If $a \equiv b \pmod{n}$, then $b \equiv a \pmod{n}$.
- **Transitive:** If $a \equiv b \pmod{n}$ and $b \equiv c \pmod{n}$, then $a \equiv c \pmod{n}$.

Hence, \equiv is an equivalence relation on \mathbb{Z} .

Equivalence Classes

For each $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, we denote its equivalence class by \bar{a} (or sometimes $[a]$), where

$$\bar{a} = \{b \in \mathbb{Z} \mid b \equiv a \pmod{n}\}.$$

There are exactly n distinct equivalence classes, which we label as

$$\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}, \dots, \overline{n-1}.$$

The Set \mathbb{Z}_n

We let \mathbb{Z}_n denote the set of these n equivalence classes:

$$\mathbb{Z}_n = \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}, \dots, \overline{n-1}\}.$$

There is a natural surjective (onto) map

$$f : \mathbb{Z} \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n, \quad a \longmapsto \bar{a}.$$

Addition and Multiplication Modulo n

On \mathbb{Z}_n , we define:

$$\bar{a} + \bar{b} = \overline{a+b}, \quad \bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} = \overline{a \cdot b}.$$

These operations are well-defined (i.e., they do not depend on the particular representatives chosen) and turn \mathbb{Z}_n into a ring, often referred to as *the ring of integers modulo n* .

Problem Statement: Prove that ϕ is a ring homomorphism. Specifically, show that:

$$\phi(x + y) = \phi(x) + \phi(y),$$

where $x \equiv a \pmod{n}$, $y \equiv b \pmod{n}$, and $x + y \equiv c \pmod{n}$, with $a, b, c \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$. To prove this, we need to show that $a + b \equiv c \pmod{n}$.

Proof:

By the definition of modular congruence, there exist integers $k_1, k_2, k_3 \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that:

$$x - a = nk_1, \quad y - b = nk_2, \quad \text{and} \quad (x + y) - c = nk_3.$$

Add the first two equations and then subtract the third:

$$(x - a) + (y - b) - ((x + y) - c) = nk_1 + nk_2 - nk_3.$$

On the left side,

$$(x - a) + (y - b) - ((x + y) - c) = x - a + y - b - (x + y) + c = c - (a + b).$$

Thus,

$$c - (a + b) = n(k_1 + k_2 - k_3) \implies c \equiv a + b \pmod{n}.$$

Hence,

$$\phi(x + y) = \phi(c) \quad \text{and} \quad \phi(x) + \phi(y) = \phi(a) + \phi(b).$$

Since $c \equiv a + b \pmod{n}$, we conclude:

$$\phi(x + y) = \phi(x) + \phi(y).$$

This completes the proof that ϕ preserves addition and is a ring homomorphism for addition.

A Homomorphism Property: Multiplication

We also want to show:

$$\phi(xy) = \phi(x)\phi(y).$$

(Originally left as an exercise, here is a brief outline for completeness.)

Sketch of the Proof: If $x \equiv a \pmod{n}$ and $y \equiv b \pmod{n}$, then $xy \equiv ab \pmod{n}$. Therefore:

$$\phi(xy) = \overline{xy} = \overline{ab} = \overline{a}\overline{b} = \phi(x)\phi(y).$$

Hence, ϕ is indeed a ring homomorphism that respects both addition *and* multiplication.

What Does It Mean to Map to 0:

To map to 0 under a function f means that $f(x) = 0$ for certain inputs x . In the context of the ring homomorphism

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z},$$

the **kernel** of ϕ is the set of all integers $x \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\phi(x) = 0$ in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$.

Definition of Kernel:

The kernel of a function f , denoted by $\ker f$, is defined as:

$$\ker f = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid f(x) = 0\}.$$

For the homomorphism $\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, where $\phi(x) = \bar{x}$, the kernel becomes:

$$\ker \phi = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid \phi(x) = \bar{0}\}.$$

Condition for $\phi(x) = \bar{0}$:

The equivalence class $\bar{0}$ in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ consists of all integers congruent to 0 (mod n). Thus:

$$\ker \phi = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid x \equiv 0 \pmod{n}\}.$$

This means x is a multiple of n . Hence:

$$\ker \phi = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid x = kn, k \in \mathbb{Z}\} = n\mathbb{Z}.$$

Visual Interpretation (the Spiral Chart):

On the spiral chart for modular arithmetic, every integer that maps to 0 in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ corresponds to multiples of n : $-2n, -n, 0, n, 2n, \dots$. These all “wrap around” to the same point $\bar{0}$ on the modular circle.

Conclusion:

The kernel of ϕ consists of all integers that are multiples of n . These map to the identity element 0 in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. This alignment with $\bar{0}$ on the modular circle demonstrates precisely how modular equivalence groups these integers.

Example 2: Continuous Functions on \mathbb{R}

Let

$$C(\mathbb{R}) := \{ f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f \text{ is continuous} \}.$$

We define two operations on $C(\mathbb{R})$ as follows.

Addition of Functions

Define addition on $C(\mathbb{R})$ by

$$(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x),$$

for all $f, g \in C(\mathbb{R})$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Since the sum of continuous functions is continuous, $f + g \in C(\mathbb{R})$. Thus, this operation is well-defined on $C(\mathbb{R})$.

Multiplication of Functions

Define multiplication on $C(\mathbb{R})$ by

$$(fg)(x) = f(x)g(x),$$

for all $f, g \in C(\mathbb{R})$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Since the product of continuous functions is also continuous, $fg \in C(\mathbb{R})$. Thus, this operation is well-defined on $C(\mathbb{R})$.

Conclusion for $C(\mathbb{R})$

With these operations of addition and multiplication, $C(\mathbb{R})$ forms a ring of continuous functions from \mathbb{R} to \mathbb{R} . One easily checks that the usual ring axioms (associativity, distributivity, commutativity of addition, etc.) hold under pointwise operations.

Example: The Evaluation Map

Consider now the evaluation map

$$\text{ev}_a :: C(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

where $C(\mathbb{R})$ is the collection of continuous functions from \mathbb{R} to \mathbb{R} . We fix a point $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the evaluation map is defined as

$$\text{ev}_a : (f) = f(a),$$

for each $f \in C(\mathbb{R})$.

Interpretation:

- **Input:** The map takes in a continuous function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.
- **Output:** The map outputs the real number $f(a)$, which is the value of f at the point a .

Proof that ev_a is a Ring Homomorphism:

1. $\text{ev}_a : (f + g) = \text{ev}_a : (f) + \text{ev}_a : (g)$.

By definition,

$$\text{ev}_a : (f + g) = (f + g)(a).$$

Using the definition of addition of functions,

$$(f + g)(a) = f(a) + g(a).$$

Hence,

$$\text{ev}_a : (f + g) = f(a) + g(a) = \text{ev}_a : (f) + \text{ev}_a : (g).$$

2. $\text{ev}_a : (fg) = \text{ev}_a : (f) \text{ev}_a : (g)$.

By definition,

$$\text{ev}_a : (fg) = (fg)(a).$$

Using the definition of multiplication of functions,

$$(fg)(a) = f(a)g(a).$$

Hence,

$$\text{ev}_a : (fg) = f(a)g(a) = \text{ev}_a : (f) \text{ev}_a : (g).$$

Therefore, since ev_a respects both addition and multiplication, it is a ring homomorphism.

Lecture 1/10

Ring Homomorphisms

Let's study the ring homomorphism

$$f : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n, \quad a \mapsto \bar{a}.$$

(Recall: $a \equiv b \pmod{n} \iff \exists m$ such that $a - b = mn$.)

1. Let's prove this is a ring homomorphism.

(a) $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$.

This was done in Math 103A. ("proof by previous quarter")

(b) $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$.

Since $f(a) = \bar{a}$ (the residue of a modulo n), we need to show

$$\overline{xy} = \bar{x}\bar{y} \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_n.$$

Equivalently,

$$xy \pmod{n} = (x \pmod{n})(y \pmod{n}) \pmod{n}.$$

Indeed, if $x \equiv x_0 \pmod{n}$ and $y \equiv y_0 \pmod{n}$, then

$$x = x_0 + nk, \quad y = y_0 + n\ell \quad \text{for some integers } k, \ell.$$

Therefore

$$xy - x_0y_0 = \underbrace{(x_0 + nk)(y_0 + n\ell)}_{\text{expand}} - x_0y_0 = x_0y_0 + nx_0\ell + ny_0k + n^2k\ell - x_0y_0 = n(\dots),$$

so $xy \equiv x_0y_0 \pmod{n}$. Hence

$$\overline{xy} = \bar{x}\bar{y}.$$

(2) What is the kernel?

$$\ker f = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid f(x) = \bar{0}\} = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid \bar{x} = \bar{0}\} = \{x \in \mathbb{Z} \mid x \equiv 0 \pmod{n}\} = n\mathbb{Z}.$$

Example 2

Let

$$C(\mathbb{R}) := \{f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f \text{ is continuous}\}.$$

Addition and multiplication on $C(\mathbb{R})$ are defined *pointwise*:

$$(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x), \quad (fg)(x) = f(x)g(x).$$

Consider the evaluation map at a :

$$\text{ev}_a : C(\mathbb{R}) \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad f \mapsto f(a).$$

This is called the *evaluation map at a* .

(1) Prove ev_a is a homomorphism of rings.

We check the two ring operations:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{ev}_a(f + g) &= (f + g)(a) = f(a) + g(a) = \text{ev}_a(f) + \text{ev}_a(g), \\ \text{ev}_a(fg) &= (fg)(a) = f(a)g(a) = \text{ev}_a(f)\text{ev}_a(g).\end{aligned}$$

Hence, ev_a respects both addition and multiplication, so it is indeed a ring homomorphism.

(2) Compute the kernel

We want

$$\ker(\text{ev}_a) = \{f \in C(\mathbb{R}) \mid f(a) = 0\}.$$

Figure 1: Illustration of functions f and g with $f(a) = 0$ and $g(a) = 0$.

Example 3

Consider $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ given by

$$z = a + bi \mapsto a - bi = \bar{z},$$

which is the *complex conjugation* map.

(1) Is this a homomorphism?

(a) **Addition:**

$$z + w \mapsto \overline{z + w} = \bar{z} + \bar{w}.$$

Indeed,

$$f((a + bi) + (c + di)) = f((a + c) + i(b + d)) = (a + c) - i(b + d).$$

On the other hand,

$$f(a + bi) + f(c + di) = (a - bi) + (c - di) = (a + c) - i(b + d).$$

Thus

$$f((a + bi) + (c + di)) = f(a + bi) + f(c + di).$$

(b) **Multiplication:**

$$zw \mapsto \overline{zw} = \overline{z}\overline{w}.$$

Check:

$$f((a+bi)(c+di)) = f(ac-bd+i(ad+bc)) = (ac-bd) - i(ad+bc).$$

Meanwhile,

$$f(a+bi) \cdot f(c+di) = (a-bi)(c-di) = (ac-bd) - i(ad+bc).$$

Hence the map respects multiplication as well.

(2) $\ker(f)$? $(0+0i)$.

$$\ker(f) = \{a+bi \in \mathbb{C} \mid a-bi=0\} = \{0\}.$$

Hence, f is injective. (In fact, it is an *isomorphism* onto itself, since conjugation is its own inverse.)

Example 4. Define

$$\Phi: \mathbb{R}[x] \longrightarrow \mathbb{C}, \quad f(x) \mapsto f(i).$$

1. Prove that this is a homomorphism. (See Exercise 2.)
2. Find $\ker(\Phi)$.

Claim.

$$\ker(\Phi) = \left\{ f \in \mathbb{R}[x] \mid x^2+1 \text{ divides } f \right\}.$$

Proof.

$$(\Rightarrow) \text{ If } x^2+1 \mid f, \text{ then } f(x) = (x^2+1)g(x).$$

Hence

$$\Phi(f) = f(i) = (i^2+1)g(i) = 0 \cdot g(i) = 0.$$

Thus $f \in \ker(\Phi)$.

$$(\Leftarrow) \text{ Let } f \in \ker(\Phi). \text{ Then } f(i) = 0.$$

By the division algorithm in $\mathbb{R}[x]$,

$$f(x) = (x^2+1)g(x) + h(x),$$

where $\deg(h) \leq 1$. Write $h(x) = ax+b$. Then

$$0 = f(i) = (i^2+1)g(i) + h(i) = 0 + (ai+b).$$

Hence

$$ai+b=0 \implies \underbrace{ai}_{\text{imag. part}} = -b$$

and so the real part and the imaginary part of the left side must each be zero. This forces $a=0$ and $b=0$. Therefore $h(x)=0$ and x^2+1 divides f . This completes the proof.

1 Fields

Key distinction: We do *not* require a multiplicative identity for a ring in these notes. (Some authors *do* require it.)

In this context:

- A *rng* is a ring **without** 1.
- A *ring* here **does** have a 1 (i.e. a multiplicative identity).

Examples of rings (with 1):

$$\mathbb{C}, \quad \mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbb{Q}, \quad \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}, \quad \mathbb{Z}.$$

Example of a rng (no 1):

$$a\mathbb{Z} \quad \text{where } |a| \geq 2.$$

Definition 1 (Rings and Units). *Let R be a ring (with 1).*

1. *The multiplicative identity element 1 is called the unity of R .*
2. *If $ab = ba$ for all $a, b \in R$, then R is said to be a commutative ring.*
3. *A multiplicative inverse of an element $a \in R$ (with unity 1) is an element a' such that*

$$aa' = a'a = 1.$$

4. *A unit $x \in R$ is an element that has a multiplicative inverse in R .*

Example: \mathbb{Z}_8 .

$$\mathbb{Z}_8 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}.$$

This ring is commutative.

- The identity is 1.
- Is 3 a unit? Yes, because $3^2 = 9 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$.
- Also, $7^2 = 49 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$.
- (In contrast, $2 \cdot 4 = 8 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$ so neither 2 nor 4 is invertible.)

Definition (Field). *If every nonzero element of a commutative ring R (with 1) is a unit, then R is called a *field*.*

Examples of fields.

$$\mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbb{Q}, \quad \mathbb{C}, \quad \mathbb{Z}_2, \quad \mathbb{Z}_p \text{ (if } p \text{ is prime)}.$$

(One needs p prime for \mathbb{Z}_p to be without nonzero zero divisors, ensuring all nonzero elements are invertible.)

Non-examples.

\mathbb{Z} (fails to have multiplicative inverses for nonzero integers),

$\mathbb{Z}_4, \mathbb{Z}_6$ (elements like 2, 3, 4 fail to have inverses).

Definition (Zero Divisor). An element a in a ring R is called a *zero divisor* if there exists $b \neq 0$ in R such that $ab = 0$ (in R).

Example with \mathbb{Z}_8 . In \mathbb{Z}_8 , the element 6 is a zero divisor because

$$6 \cdot 4 = 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}.$$

Example: $R = C(\mathbb{R})$

We consider two piecewise-defined functions, which illustrate zero divisors in $C(\mathbb{R})$:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq 0, \\ \sqrt{x} & x > 0, \end{cases} \quad g(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{-x} & x \leq 0, \\ 0 & x > 0. \end{cases}$$

Each is continuous at $x = 0$, and one can verify directly that for any real x ,

$$(fg)(x) = f(x)g(x) = 0.$$

Hence $f \neq 0, g \neq 0$, but $fg = 0$ is the zero function, demonstrating that neither f nor g is invertible and each acts as a nontrivial zero divisor.

Figure 2: Sketch of fg (the zero function).

Definition: Subring

A *subring* $S \subset R$ is a subset such that:

1. S is closed under $+$ and \cdot (the operations from R).
2. S is itself a ring (under these inherited operations).

What Does It Mean to Map to 0? When we say a function ϕ maps an element x to 0, we mean $\phi(x) = 0$ in the target ring. For the standard ring homomorphism

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z} \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}, \quad x \mapsto \bar{x},$$

the condition $\phi(x) = \bar{0}$ exactly says x is a multiple of n . Hence,

$$\ker(\phi) = n\mathbb{Z}.$$

Visual Interpretation (Spiral Chart) A helpful way to picture the elements of \mathbb{Z} mapping to $\bar{0}$ in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ is via a “spiral” or “circular” diagram. Imagine placing the integers $\dots, -2n, -n, 0, n, 2n, \dots$ around a circle so that each multiple of n lines up at the same spot, corresponding to $\bar{0}$. In this picture, all multiples of n literally coincide with $\bar{0}$ in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. This helps visualize why

$$\ker(\phi) = n\mathbb{Z}.$$

Further Note on $C(\mathbb{R})$ and the Evaluation Map

In our previous discussion, we introduced the ring $C(\mathbb{R})$ of continuous functions $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and defined the *evaluation map* at a point a :

$$\text{ev}_a : C(\mathbb{R}) \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad f \mapsto f(a).$$

Since we have already shown this map is a ring homomorphism and computed its kernel ($\{f \in C(\mathbb{R}) \mid f(a) = 0\}$), we do not repeat the proof here. This illustrates another classical example of a ring homomorphism whose kernel encodes precisely those functions vanishing at a given point.

Lecture 1/13

Office Hours:

- W 2–3 AP&M 1202
- R 6–7 Zoom

Definition: A *subring* $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is a subset such that:

1. S is closed under $+$ and \cdot (inherited from \mathbb{R}).
2. S is itself a ring (with the same addition and multiplication as in \mathbb{R}).

Examples of subrings:

1. $\mathbb{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{Q} \subseteq \mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$.
2. $k\mathbb{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ for some integer k . For example, if $k = 3$, then

$$3\mathbb{Z} = \{\dots, -6, -3, 0, 3, 6, \dots\} \subseteq \{\dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\} = \mathbb{Z}.$$

Indeed, for $3a, 3b \in 3\mathbb{Z}$:

$$(3a) + (3b) = 3(a + b) \in 3\mathbb{Z}, \quad (3a) \cdot (3b) = 9ab = 3(3ab) \in 3\mathbb{Z}.$$

3. $\mathbb{Z}[i] = \{a + bi \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = -1\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$.

Examples of elements in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ include $1 + 3i$, $4i$, 6 , $-2 + 5i$, etc. Addition and multiplication are inherited from \mathbb{C} :

$$(a + bi) + (c + di) = (a + c) + (b + d)i,$$

$$(a + bi)(c + di) = (ac - bd) + (ad + bc)i.$$

Since $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}$, the products $ac - bd$ and $ad + bc$ are still integers, so $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ is closed under both addition and multiplication.

Definition: A *zero divisor* in a ring R is an element $a \in R$ such that

$$\exists b \in R, b \neq 0, \text{ with } a \neq 0, \text{ and } ab = 0.$$

Example: $R = \mathbb{Z}_8$.

6 is a zero divisor in \mathbb{Z}_8 because $6 \cdot 4 = 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$.

Example: $R = C(\mathbb{R})$, the ring of all continuous real-valued functions on \mathbb{R} (pointwise addition and multiplication). Define

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq 0, \\ \sqrt{x} & x > 0, \end{cases} \quad g(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{-x} & x \leq 0, \\ 0 & x > 0. \end{cases}$$

It is straightforward to see $f(x)g(x) = 0$ for all real x . Yet neither f nor g is the zero function, so each is a nonzero zero divisor in $C(\mathbb{R})$.

Figure 1: Graphs of f (nonzero for $x > 0$) and g (nonzero for $x \leq 0$), illustrating zero divisors in $C(\mathbb{R})$.

Proposition

In the ring \mathbb{Z}_n , an element x is a zero divisor if and only if $\gcd(x, n) \neq 1$.

Proof

(\Leftarrow) Suppose $\gcd(x, n) \neq 1$, and let $y = \gcd(x, n)$. Then $y > 1$ divides n . In particular,

$$\frac{n}{y} \in \{1, 2, \dots, n-1\} \quad (\text{since } 1 \leq n/y \leq n-1 \text{ for } y > 1).$$

Notice that

$$x \left(\frac{n}{y} \right) = \underbrace{\frac{x}{y}}_{\in \mathbb{Z} \text{ if } y|x} \cdot n \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

Thus $x \cdot \left(\frac{n}{y} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, and $\frac{n}{y}$ is a nonzero element of \mathbb{Z}_n , showing that x is indeed a zero divisor.

(\Rightarrow) Conversely, suppose x is a zero divisor in \mathbb{Z}_n . Then there exists a nonzero $y \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$ such that

$$xy \equiv 0 \pmod{n} \implies xy = nk \quad (\text{for some } k \in \mathbb{Z}).$$

If $\gcd(n, x) = 1$, then because $n \mid xy$, we would have $x \mid nk$ but $\gcd(n, x) = 1$ forces x to divide k . Write $k = xk'$, yielding

$$y = \frac{nk}{x} = nk' \geq n,$$

contradicting the fact $1 \leq y \leq n-1$. Therefore, $\gcd(n, x) > 1$.

Corollary

If $n = p$ is prime, then any $x \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ with $\gcd(x, p) \neq 1$ must satisfy $p \mid x$, which means x is 0 in \mathbb{Z}_p . Hence the only zero divisor in \mathbb{Z}_p is 0 itself. This shows that \mathbb{Z}_p (for prime p) has no nonzero zero divisors. In fact, \mathbb{Z}_p is a field.

Cancellation Laws

We learned once upon a time two common *Cancellation Laws* in an integral domain:

$$(C1) \quad ab = ac \implies b = c \quad (\text{provided } a \neq 0).$$

$$(C2) \quad ba = ca \implies b = c \quad (\text{provided } a \neq 0).$$

Counterexample to Cancellation if Zero Divisors Exist

Consider \mathbb{Z}_6 :

$$4 \cdot 5 = 20 \equiv 2 \pmod{6}, \quad 4 \cdot 2 = 8 \equiv 2 \pmod{6}.$$

So $4 \cdot 5 \equiv 4 \cdot 2$ in \mathbb{Z}_6 , yet $5 \neq 2$. Hence cancellation fails in rings with zero divisors.

Proposition

The cancellation laws hold in a ring R if and only if R has no zero divisors.

Proof

(\Rightarrow) Suppose the cancellation laws hold in R , and assume $ab = 0$ with $a, b \neq 0$. Then

$$ab = 0 = 0b \implies ab = 0b.$$

By the right-cancellation law (C2) and since $b \neq 0$, we must have $a = 0$, a contradiction. Hence no such nonzero a, b can exist, and R has no zero divisors.

(\Leftarrow) Conversely, if R has no zero divisors and $ab = ac$ with $a \neq 0$, then

$$ab - ac = 0 \implies a(b - c) = 0.$$

Since $a \neq 0$ and R has no zero divisors, we must have $b - c = 0$, i.e. $b = c$. A similar argument handles (C2). Thus the cancellation laws hold exactly when there are no zero divisors.

Integral Domains

Definition. A ring R is called an *integral domain* if:

1. It is commutative,
2. It has an identity $1 \neq 0$,
3. It has no zero divisors.

Examples of Integral Domains:

1. All Fields \mathbb{F} .

If \mathbb{F} is a field and $xy = 0$, with $x \neq 0$, then x is invertible (say $x^{-1} \in \mathbb{F}$). Hence

$$y = (x^{-1}x)y = x^{-1}(xy) = x^{-1} \cdot 0 = 0.$$

Thus there are no nonzero zero divisors in a field, making every field an integral domain.

2. \mathbb{Z} , \mathbb{Q} , \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{C} are all integral domains (in fact, \mathbb{Q} , \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{C} are fields, while \mathbb{Z} is not a field but still an integral domain).

3. Polynomial rings over an integral domain:

$$\mathbb{Z}[x], \quad \mathbb{Q}[x], \quad \mathbb{R}[x], \quad \mathbb{C}[x].$$

Each is an integral domain, provided the coefficient ring is an integral domain. Concretely, if $f, g \in R[x]$ (where R is an integral domain) and $fg = 0$, then at least one of f or g must be the zero polynomial, showing there are no zero divisors in $R[x]$.

Lecture 1/15

Cancellation Laws

We learned once upon a time:

$$(C1) \quad ab = ac \implies b = c \quad (a \neq 0),$$

$$(C2) \quad ba = ca \implies b = c \quad (a \neq 0).$$

Cancellation laws

Counterexample:

In the ring \mathbb{Z}_6 , consider:

$$4 \cdot 5 = 20 \equiv 2 \pmod{6},$$

$$4 \cdot 2 = 8 \equiv 2 \pmod{6}.$$

Hence

$$4 \cdot 5 = 4 \cdot 2 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_6,$$

yet

$$5 \neq 2.$$

This shows cancellation can fail in rings that have zero divisors (like \mathbb{Z}_6).

Proposition

The cancellation laws (C1) and (C2) hold if and only if R has no zero divisors.

Proof

(\implies) Suppose the cancellation laws hold, and $ab = 0$. If $b \neq 0$, then

$$ab = 0 = 0 \cdot b,$$

so (C2) $\implies a = 0$. (A similar argument holds if $a \neq 0$, using (C1).)

(\impliedby) Suppose R has no zero divisors, and $ab = ac$. Then

$$ab - ac = 0 \implies a(b - c) = 0.$$

Since $a \neq 0$ by assumption and R has no zero divisors, it follows that $b - c = 0$, hence $b = c$. (A similar argument works on the right side if $ba = ca$.)

If R is an *integral domain*, the cancellation laws hold!

Examples of integral domains:

1. All fields F .

Indeed, if $xy = 0$ in a field and $x \neq 0$, then x has a multiplicative inverse x^{-1} , so

$$y = (x^{-1}x)y = x^{-1}(xy) = x^{-1} \cdot 0 = 0.$$

Hence there are no zero divisors in a field, so all fields are integral domains.

2. $\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$.

These are all integral domains because none of them has zero divisors. In particular, for \mathbb{Z} any product $ab = 0$ forces either $a = 0$ or $b = 0$.

3. Polynomial rings over an integral domain (e.g. $\mathbb{Z}[x], \mathbb{Q}[x], \mathbb{R}[x], \mathbb{C}[x]$, etc.) are also integral domains. If A is an integral domain and $f(x), g(x) \in A[x]$ such that $f(x)g(x) = 0$, then either $f(x) = 0$ or $g(x) = 0$.

Remark. If we consider \mathbb{Z}_n , we know \mathbb{Z}_n is an integral domain precisely when n is prime. If n is composite, \mathbb{Z}_n has zero divisors and cancellation fails.

Subring Generated by the Unity

For a ring R with identity element 1, we can consider the subring generated by 1. Define, for $m > 0$,

$$m \cdot 1 = \underbrace{1 + 1 + \cdots + 1}_{m \text{ times}},$$

and similarly for $m < 0$ by adding the additive inverses. By convention, $0 \cdot 1 = 0$.

Important Note: Using distributivity,

$$\underbrace{(1 + \cdots + 1)}_{m \text{ times}} \underbrace{(1 + \cdots + 1)}_{n \text{ times}} = \underbrace{1 + \cdots + 1}_{mn \text{ times}},$$

which can be written as

$$(m \cdot 1)(n \cdot 1) = (mn) \cdot 1.$$

Therefore the map

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z} \longrightarrow R, \quad \phi(n) = n \cdot 1$$

is a ring homomorphism. Its image is exactly

$$\{m \cdot 1 : m \in \mathbb{Z}\},$$

and the kernel of this map is an ideal in \mathbb{Z} of the form $n\mathbb{Z}$ (possibly $\{0\}$). Consequently, the image is isomorphic to either \mathbb{Z} itself (if the kernel is $\{0\}$) or \mathbb{Z}_n (if the kernel is $n\mathbb{Z}$ for some $n > 0$).

Characteristic of a Ring (with Identity)

Definition. Let R be a ring with unity (identity) 1 . The **characteristic of R** , denoted $\text{char}(R)$, is the smallest positive integer n such that

$$n \cdot a = 0 \quad \text{for all } a \in R.$$

If no such positive integer exists, we say R has *characteristic 0*.

Example. \mathbb{Z}_n (the integers mod n) has characteristic n . Indeed,

$$n \cdot 1 = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_n,$$

and thus for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$,

$$n \cdot a = \underbrace{a + a + \cdots + a}_{n \text{ times}} = 0.$$

By contrast, $\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{R}[x]$, etc. all have characteristic 0, since no nonzero multiple of 1 ever becomes 0 in those rings.

Proposition

Let R be a ring with unity.

1. If $n \cdot 1 \neq 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\text{char}(R) = 0$.
2. If $n \cdot 1 = 0$ for some positive integer n , then $\text{char}(R)$ is defined to be the *smallest* such positive integer.

Proof

1. If $n \cdot 1 \neq 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then in particular, there is no positive n with $n \cdot 1 = 0$. Hence, by definition, $\text{char}(R) = 0$.
2. Suppose there exists a positive integer n such that $n \cdot 1 = 0$. For *any* $a \in R$, we then have

$$n \cdot a = \underbrace{a + a + \cdots + a}_{n \text{ times}} = a \underbrace{(1 + 1 + \cdots + 1)}_{n \text{ times}} = a(n \cdot 1) = a \cdot 0 = 0.$$

Thus such an n annihilates every element of R . If there are multiple positive integers with this property, we take the smallest one as $\text{char}(R)$ by definition.

Additional Remark (Integral Domains). If R is an integral domain, then any nonzero characteristic must be prime. Indeed, if $\text{char}(R) = n$ were composite, say $n = rs$ with $r, s > 1$, then

$$n \cdot 1 = (rs) \cdot 1 = \underbrace{(r \cdot 1) + \cdots + (r \cdot 1)}_{s \text{ times}} = 0.$$

But then $r \cdot 1 \neq 0$ and $s \cdot 1 \neq 0$ would force a zero divisor, contradicting the fact that R has no zero divisors. Hence, if $\text{char}(R) \neq 0$, it must be a prime number.

Lecture 1/17

IDEALS.

In 103A, you learned that for subgroups, we could study *cosets*.

For instance, $\langle 3 \rangle \leq \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\langle 3 \rangle = \{\dots, -6, -3, 0, 3, 6, \dots\} = 3\mathbb{Z}.$$

The cosets are

$$1 + \langle 3 \rangle = \{\dots, -5, -2, 1, 4, 7, \dots\},$$

$$2 + \langle 3 \rangle = \{\dots, -4, -1, 2, 5, 8, \dots\},$$

$$\langle 3 \rangle.$$

For a group G , and a subgroup $H \leq G$, we have the cosets

$$G/H := \{aH \mid a \in G\}$$

which partition G . (These are *left* cosets.)

Question: When is G/H a group?

Answer: G/H is a group $\iff H \triangleleft G$, i.e. H is a normal subgroup. (Then G/H is the *quotient group*.)

What's the version for rings?

Ideals

A **left ideal** $I \subseteq R$ is a subring I such that:

$$r \in R, a \in I \implies ra \in I.$$

(*left absorption*)

A **right ideal** $I \subseteq R$ is a subring I such that:

$$r \in R, a \in I \implies ar \in I.$$

(*right absorption*)

An **ideal** (also called a *two-sided ideal*) $I \subseteq R$ is a subring that is both a left and a right ideal.

Note: If R is commutative, then left, right, and two-sided ideals coincide (they are all the same).

As it turns out, “ideals” are precisely the notion we want in order to form “quotient rings” (also known as *factor rings*).

Example: \mathbb{Z}

As it turns out, every subring of \mathbb{Z} is also an ideal.

Subgroups of \mathbb{Z} take the form

$$\langle k \rangle = k\mathbb{Z} = \{ \dots, -2k, -k, 0, k, 2k, \dots \}.$$

All such subsets $\langle k \rangle$ are automatically closed under multiplication, hence they are subrings:

$$\text{If } x = ak \text{ and } y = bk, \text{ then } xy = (ak)(bk) = abk^2 = (abk)k \in k\mathbb{Z}.$$

Thus $k\mathbb{Z}$ is closed under multiplication and forms a subring of \mathbb{Z} .

Moreover, let $ak \in \langle k \rangle$ and $m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then

$$m(ak) = (ma)k \in \langle k \rangle.$$

Hence $\langle k \rangle$ absorbs multiplication by elements of \mathbb{Z} on either side, making $\langle k \rangle$ an ideal in \mathbb{Z} .

$$\langle 3 \rangle = 3\mathbb{Z} = \{ \dots, -6, -3, 0, 3, 6, \dots \}.$$

Ex: $\langle 0 \rangle$, R .

$$a \cdot 0 = 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle.$$

This is the *zero ideal*, containing only 0.

Ex: In a field! The only ideals are $\langle 0 \rangle$ and R .

Proof. Let R be a field, and let $I \subseteq R$ be a nonzero ideal. Take any nonzero $a \in I$. Since R is a field, $a^{-1} \in R$. Then

$$1 = a^{-1}a \in I.$$

Hence for any $x \in R$,

$$x = x \cdot 1 \in I.$$

Thus $I = R$. Consequently, the only ideals of a field R are $\{0\} = \langle 0 \rangle$ and R itself.

For groups: Let $N \trianglelefteq G$ be a normal subgroup. We defined the quotient group G/N by

$$(aN)(bN) = abN.$$

Because N is normal, this product is well-defined and makes G/N into a group.

We want to do the same with rings.

Let $I \subseteq R$ be an ideal. We denote $a + I$ to be the *coset* of I containing a . (Note R is an abelian group under addition!)

Define:

$$(a + I) + (b + I) = (a + b) + I \quad \text{for } a, b \in R,$$

$$(a + I)(b + I) = (ab) + I \quad \text{for } a, b \in R.$$

Why well-defined?

- (1) **Addition.** This was checked in 103A (and is true in any abelian group): any subgroup of an abelian group is automatically normal, so addition of cosets is well-defined.
- (2) **Multiplication.** We must ensure that if $a' + I = a + I$ and $b' + I = b + I$, then $(a' + I)(b' + I) = (a + I)(b + I)$.

Concretely, suppose

$$a' = a + r_1, \quad b' = b + r_2,$$

where $r_1, r_2 \in I$. Then

$$(a' + I)(b' + I) = (a + r_1 + I)(b + r_2 + I).$$

When we multiply representatives,

$$(a + r_1)(b + r_2) = ab + \underbrace{ar_2}_{\in I} + \underbrace{r_1b}_{\in I} + \underbrace{r_1r_2}_{\in I}.$$

Because I is an ideal, ar_2 , r_1b , and $r_1r_2 \in I$. Hence

$$(a + r_1)(b + r_2) \in ab + I,$$

which implies

$$(a' + I)(b' + I) = ab + I = (a + I)(b + I).$$

Thus the product $(a + I)(b + I)$ does not depend on the chosen representatives a and b . Multiplication is therefore well-defined.

Definition.

$$R/I := \{a + I \mid a \in R\}$$

with the above addition and multiplication is called the *quotient ring* (or *factor ring*) of R by I .

Proposition. If I is an ideal of R , then R/I is a ring under the operations defined above.

Definition. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. The *kernel* of φ is

$$\ker(\varphi) := \{x \in R \mid \varphi(x) = 0_S\}.$$

Theorem (First Isomorphism Theorem).

$$R/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{im}(\varphi)$$

as rings, for any ring homomorphism $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$.

We also have a correspondence: (*Correspondence/Lattice Isomorphism Theorem*)
 If $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ is a surjective ring homomorphism with $\ker(\varphi) = I$, then there is a one-to-one correspondence between ideals of S and ideals of R that contain I . Concretely:

$$J \subseteq S \iff \varphi^{-1}(J) \supseteq I.$$

Moreover, this correspondence respects inclusion; that is, $J_1 \subseteq J_2$ if and only if $\varphi^{-1}(J_1) \subseteq \varphi^{-1}(J_2)$.

Finally, if $I \subset R$ is an ideal, define the map

$$\pi : R \longrightarrow R/I, \quad \pi(a) = a + I.$$

Then π is a surjective ring homomorphism and $\ker(\pi) = I$.

Example: $\pi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$, given by $\pi(a) = a \bmod n$. Here, $\ker(\pi) = n\mathbb{Z}$, so by the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\mathbb{Z}/(n\mathbb{Z}) \cong \mathbb{Z}_n.$$

Lecture 1/22

Define!

$$(a + I) + (b + I) := (a + b) + I \quad \text{for } a, b \in R,$$

$$(a + I)(b + I) := (ab) + I \quad \text{for } a, b \in R.$$

Proof that the operations are well-defined.

To show these definitions do not depend on the choice of representatives a, b within their respective cosets:

1. **Addition.** This was checked in (the referenced) 10.3A. One can also see it directly:

Suppose

$$(a + I) = (a' + I) \implies a - a' \in I,$$

and

$$(b + I) = (b' + I) \implies b - b' \in I.$$

Then

$$(a + b) - (a' + b') = (a - a') + (b - b').$$

Since I is an additive subgroup of R , it is closed under addition; hence

$$(a - a') + (b - b') \in I \implies (a + b) + I = (a' + b') + I.$$

Thus the sum $(a + I) + (b + I)$ is well-defined.

2. **Multiplication.** Let

$$(a + I) = (a' + I) \implies a - a' \in I,$$

and

$$(b + I) = (b' + I) \implies b - b' \in I.$$

We need to check

$$ab + I = a'b' + I.$$

Observe:

$$ab - a'b' = ab - a'b + a'b - a'b' = (a - a')b + a'(b - b').$$

Since $a - a' \in I$ and $b - b' \in I$, and I is an *ideal* (it absorbs products with elements of R), each term is in I . In symbols:

$$\underbrace{(a - a')}_{\in I} \cdot \underbrace{b}_{\in R} \in I \quad \text{and} \quad \underbrace{a'}_{\in R} \cdot \underbrace{(b - b')}_{\in I} \in I.$$

Hence $ab - a'b' \in I$, so

$$ab + I = a'b' + I.$$

Thus the product $(a + I)(b + I)$ is well-defined.

Remark. In the step for multiplication, the property that I is an *ideal* (not just an additive subgroup) is crucial to guarantee $rI \subseteq I$ and $Ir \subseteq I$ for all $r \in R$.

Def. For a ring R and an ideal $I \subseteq R$, the *quotient set*

$$R/I := \{a + I \mid a \in R\}$$

becomes a ring under the above addition and multiplication.

If I is an ideal, then R/I is a ring with these operations.

Proof. We verify (or recall) the ring axioms:

- **Additive associativity and commutativity:** For $a + I, b + I, c + I \in R/I$,

$$((a + I) + (b + I)) + (c + I) = ((a + b) + I) + (c + I) = (a + b + c) + I,$$

and similarly

$$(a + I) + ((b + I) + (c + I)) = a + (b + c) + I = (a + b + c) + I.$$

Thus associativity of addition holds in R/I . Commutativity follows from $a + b = b + a$ in R .

- **Additive identity:** The element $0 + I$ in R/I satisfies

$$(a + I) + (0 + I) = (a + 0) + I = a + I,$$

so $0 + I$ is the additive identity.

- **Additive inverses:** For each $a + I \in R/I$,

$$(a + I) + ((-a) + I) = (a + (-a)) + I = 0 + I,$$

so $(-a) + I$ is an additive inverse of $a + I$.

- **Multiplicative associativity:** For $a + I, b + I, c + I \in R/I$,

$$((a + I)(b + I))(c + I) = ((ab) + I)(c + I) = (abc) + I,$$

while

$$(a + I)((b + I)(c + I)) = (a + I)((bc) + I) = (abc) + I.$$

Since $abc = abc$ in R , associativity holds.

- **Distributive laws:** For $a + I, b + I, c + I \in R/I$,

$$(a + I)((b + I) + (c + I)) = (a + I)((b + c) + I) = a(b + c) + I = ab + ac + I = (ab + I) + (ac + I).$$

A similar argument holds for $((b + I) + (c + I))(a + I)$. Thus both distributive laws hold.

- **Multiplicative identity (if R is unital):** If R has a 1 , then $1 + I$ acts as the identity in R/I :

$$(a + I)(1 + I) = (a \cdot 1) + I = a + I,$$

and similarly $(1 + I)(a + I) = a + I$.

All other ring axioms are inherited from R and are well-defined modulo I . Hence R/I is a ring. \square

Def. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. The *kernel* of φ is defined by

$$\ker(\varphi) := \{x \in R \mid \varphi(x) = 0\}.$$

Thm. (First Isomorphism Theorem)

Let $\phi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Then there is an isomorphism of rings

$$R / \ker(\phi) \cong \text{im}(\phi).$$

Figure 1: A commutative diagram illustrating the First Isomorphism Theorem.

Correspondence of ideals with kernels. We also have a fundamental correspondence:

$$\{\text{Ideals } I \subset R\} \longleftrightarrow \{\text{kernels of ring homomorphisms } \phi : R \rightarrow S\}.$$

In one direction, every kernel of a ring homomorphism is an ideal; in the other, given any ideal $I \subseteq R$, one can construct a surjective ring homomorphism $\pi : R \rightarrow R/I$ with $\ker(\pi) = I$. Specifically:

- Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. Define

$$\pi : R \rightarrow R/I \quad \text{by} \quad \pi(a) := a + I.$$

Then π is a surjective ring homomorphism, and $\ker(\pi) = I$.

Ex: $\pi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$

Consider the ideal

$$I = n\mathbb{Z} = \{\dots, -2n, -n, 0, n, 2n, \dots\}.$$

Then

$$1 + n\mathbb{Z} = \{\dots, -2n + 1, -n + 1, 1, 1 + n, 2n + 1, \dots\},$$

and in general we write the coset of a as

$$a + n\mathbb{Z} = \bar{a}.$$

(This matches our usual notion of working *mod n*.)

Application of Iso #1:

Often, to show $R/I \cong S$ for a given ring S , one proceeds as follows:

- (1) Construct a surjective ring homomorphism $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ whose kernel is exactly I .
- (2) Apply the first isomorphism theorem to conclude $R/I \cong S$.

Example: Consider $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$ defined by

$$\varphi(a) = \bar{a} \pmod{n}.$$

Then $\ker(\varphi) = n\mathbb{Z}$. By the first isomorphism theorem,

$$\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z} \cong \mathbb{Z}_n.$$

Example: Let $I \subset R[x]$ be the ideal defined by

$$I := \{ f(x) \mid x \text{ divides } f(x) \} \iff f(0) = 0.$$

We want to show that $R[x]/I \cong R$.

Proof:

Consider the map $\varphi : R[x] \rightarrow R$ given by

$$\varphi(f(x)) = f(0),$$

(i.e., take the constant term of f). This is a ring homomorphism:

$$\varphi(f(x) + g(x)) = (f + g)(0) = f(0) + g(0),$$

$$\varphi(f(x)g(x)) = (fg)(0) = f(0)g(0).$$

Moreover,

$$f(x) \in I \iff f(0) = 0 \iff \varphi(f(x)) = 0.$$

Hence $I = \ker(\varphi)$. By the first isomorphism theorem,

$$R[x]/I \cong R.$$

Prime/Maximal Ideals

Let $I \subseteq R$ be an ideal in a (commutative) ring R . We say I is *prime* if

$$ab \in I \implies (a \in I \text{ or } b \in I).$$

Equivalently (when R is commutative with 1), I is prime if and only if R/I is an integral domain.

We say I is *maximal* if

$$I \subseteq J \subseteq R \text{ (} J \text{ is an ideal)} \implies (I = J \text{ or } R = J).$$

Equivalently, I is maximal if and only if R/I is a field (again assuming R is commutative with 1).

In both definitions, we require $I \neq R$ so that R/I does not collapse to the zero ring. (A prime or maximal ideal must be a proper ideal.)

Lecture 01/24

Direct Products of Rings

Quick definition!

Let R, S be rings. The *direct product* $R \times S$ is defined to be

$$R \times S := \{(r, s) \mid r \in R, s \in S\},$$

under the operations

$$(r, s) + (r', s') := (r + r', s + s')$$

and

$$(r, s)(r', s') := (r r', s s'),$$

for $r, r' \in R, s, s' \in S$.

This is a ring. (**Exercise**)

Sometimes we abbreviate:

$$R_1 \times \cdots \times R_n := \{(r_1, \dots, r_n) \mid r_i \in R_i\}$$

as

$$\prod_{i=1}^n R_i.$$

An Example with $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$

Example: $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$

Figure 1: Illustration of $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$

Consider a ring homomorphism $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$. A *typical* choice (and a key “improvement”) is to define

$$\varphi(a, b) := a.$$

(That is, we project onto the first coordinate.)

Why this is a ring homomorphism:

- $\varphi((a, b) + (c, d)) = \varphi(a + c, b + d) = a + c$, while $\varphi(a, b) + \varphi(c, d) = a + c$.
- $\varphi((a, b)(c, d)) = \varphi(ac, bd) = ac$, while $\varphi(a, b)\varphi(c, d) = ac$.

Hence, φ preserves both addition and multiplication.

What is $\ker \varphi$?

$$\ker \varphi = \{ (a, b) \mid \varphi(a, b) = 0 \} = \{ (a, b) \mid a = 0 \} = \{ (0, b) \mid b \in \mathbb{Z} \}.$$

What is $\text{im } \varphi$?

$$\text{im } \varphi = \varphi(\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}) = \{ a \mid \exists b \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } (a, b) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z} \} = \mathbb{Z}.$$

Prime and Maximal Ideals

Definitions

Let $I \subsetneq R$ be an ideal. We say I is **prime** if

$$ab \in I \implies \underbrace{a \in I}_{\text{or}} \underbrace{b \in I}.$$

We say I is **maximal** if for any ideal J such that

$$I \subseteq J \subseteq R,$$

we have either $I = J$ or $R = J$.

(*I is maximal in the sense that no larger nontrivial ideal can exist.*)

(*In both definitions, $I \subsetneq R$!!*)

The Ideal Generated by One Element

Definition: The ideal generated by $a \in R$ is

$$(a) := \{ ra \mid r \in R \}.$$

Examples of Prime Ideals

- Consider \mathbb{Z} . The prime ideals are

$$(2), (3), (5), \dots, (p), \dots, \text{ and } (0).$$

(Recall that (0) is prime in \mathbb{Z} because \mathbb{Z} is an integral domain.)

Why? Say $ab \in (5)$. Then $ab = 5k$, where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Since *prime factorizations are unique*, $5 \mid ab$. Because 5 is *prime*, $5 \mid a$ or $5 \mid b$. Hence $a \in (5)$ or $b \in (5)$.

(Similarly for any prime p .)

For this argument, we needed *divisibility* and *unique factorization*:

We will not always be so lucky.

- Every maximal ideal is prime.

Homework (Key Characterizations):

$$I \text{ prime} \iff R/I \text{ is an integral domain.}$$

$$I \text{ maximal} \iff R/I \text{ is a field.}$$

Proof Sketch. $I \text{ maximal} \Rightarrow R/I \text{ is a field} \Rightarrow R/I \text{ is an integral domain} \Rightarrow I \text{ is prime.}$

More Examples of Prime Ideals

Example: Consider

$$C(\mathbb{R}) = \{f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f \text{ is continuous}\}$$

and let $I \subseteq C(\mathbb{R})$ be defined by

$$I = \{f \in C(\mathbb{R}) \mid f(0) = 0\}.$$

Then I is prime.

Proof. If $fg \in I$, then

$$(fg)(0) = f(0)g(0) = 0.$$

Since \mathbb{R} (the codomain) is an integral domain, we deduce

$$f(0) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad g(0) = 0.$$

Hence $f \in I$ or $g \in I$, proving that I is prime.

Claim: $(x^2 + 1) \subseteq \mathbb{R}[x]$ is prime.

$$(x^2 + 1) := \{(x^2 + 1)f(x) \mid f(x) \in \mathbb{R}[x]\}.$$

Key observation: $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{R} .

Since $x^2 + 1$ does not factor over \mathbb{R} , if

$$g(x)h(x) \in (x^2 + 1),$$

then it must be that

$$x^2 + 1 \mid g(x) \quad \text{or} \quad x^2 + 1 \mid h(x).$$

The key is that $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible. **WARNING!** “Prime” and “irreducible” can be different in certain rings!

Examples of Maximal Ideals

- In \mathbb{Z} : The ideals $(2), (3), \dots, (p)$ for prime p are maximal, but **not** (0) .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbb{Z} & & \mathbb{Z} \\ | & & | \\ (2) & & (p) \\ | & & | \\ (0) & & (0) \end{array}$$

(Sketch proof)

- In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: The ideals $(x - a)$ for any $a \in \mathbb{Q}$.

$$(x - a) := \{(x - a)f(x) \mid f(x) \in \mathbb{Q}[x]\}.$$

Proof that $(x - a)$ is maximal:

We exhibit a surjective ring homomorphism with kernel exactly $(x - a)$. Consider

$$\varphi : \mathbb{Q}[x] \longrightarrow \mathbb{Q}, \quad \varphi(f) = f(a).$$

Clearly, $(x - a) \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$, since if $g(x) = (x - a)f(x)$, then

$$g(a) = (a - a)f(a) = 0.$$

Hence every element of $(x - a)$ maps to zero.

Conversely, if $g(x) \in \ker(\varphi)$, then $g(a) = 0$. By polynomial division,

$$g(x) = (x - a)h(x)$$

for some polynomial $h(x)$. Thus $g \in (x - a)$, so $\ker(\varphi) = (x - a)$.

Next, φ is surjective because for $b \in \mathbb{Q}$, we can take

$$f(x) = b + (x - a).$$

Then $\varphi(f) = f(a) = b + (a - a) = b$. So every element $b \in \mathbb{Q}$ has a preimage.

Thus, by the First Isomorphism Theorem (“Iso #1”),

$$\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x - a) \cong \mathbb{Q},$$

and \mathbb{Q} is a field. Hence $(x - a)$ is a maximal ideal in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Homework $\implies (x - a)$ is maximal.

Lecture 01/27

Today: Maximal Ideals / Misc. Topics.

Examples of Maximal Ideals:

In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: $(x - a)$ for any $a \in \mathbb{Q}$.

$$(x - a) := \{(x - a)f(x) : f(x) \in \mathbb{Q}[x]\}.$$

Proof:

We want to show that $(x - a)$ is the kernel of a suitable homomorphism, hence is maximal.

Step 1: Construct a map and find its kernel.

$$\varphi : \mathbb{Q}[x] \longrightarrow \mathbb{Q}, \quad \varphi(f) = f(a).$$

First, observe that $(x - a) \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$ because if

$$g(x) = (x - a)f(x),$$

then

$$g(a) = (a - a)f(a) = 0.$$

Thus,

$$(x - a) \subseteq \ker(\varphi).$$

Step 2: Show equality of these kernels.

Let $g(x) \in \ker(\varphi)$, i.e. $g(a) = 0$. By polynomial long division (or the Factor Theorem in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$), $g(x)$ can be written as

$$g(x) = (x - a)h(x),$$

for some $h(x) \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$. Hence

$$g(x) \in (x - a).$$

Therefore,

$$\ker(\varphi) = (x - a).$$

Step 3: Check surjectivity.

For any $b \in \mathbb{Q}$, consider

$$f(x) = b \quad (\text{constant polynomial}).$$

Then

$$\varphi(f) = f(a) = b.$$

Hence φ is onto (φ is surjective).

Step 4: Conclude maximality.

By the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x - a) \cong \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since \mathbb{Q} is a field, $(x - a)$ is a maximal ideal.

Thus, $(x - a)$ is a maximal ideal in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Fun sidenote! Are there prime ideals (aside from (0)) that are *not* maximal?

YES. Consider $R = \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. Define

$$I = (x^3 - y^2) = \{(x^3 - y^2)f(x, y) \mid f(x, y) \in R\},$$

$$J = (x, y) = \{xf(x, y) + yg(x, y) \mid f(x, y), g(x, y) \in R\}.$$

Note that

$$x^3 - y^2 = x \cdot \underbrace{x^2}_{\text{in } R} + y \cdot \underbrace{(-y)}_{\text{in } R},$$

so $x^3 - y^2 \in (x, y)$, and thus

$$I \subseteq J \subseteq R, \quad I \neq J.$$

Claim: I is prime. (We will prove this later, but it relies on the fact that $x^3 - y^2$ is irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$.)

Note: In a principal ideal domain (PID), every nonzero prime ideal is maximal. Hence we need to move beyond PIDs (e.g. $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is not a PID) in order to find prime ideals that are not maximal.

Prime/Maximal Ideals & Products/Homomorphisms

They don't "play well." (Assume rings are commutative with 1.)

Let R, S be rings (each with 1). Let $I \subseteq R, J \subseteq S$ be prime ideals.

Q1. Is $I \times J \subseteq R \times S$ an ideal?

1. $(0, 0) \in I \times J$ trivially.
2. If $(i, j), (i', j') \in I \times J$, then

$$(i, j) - (i', j') = (i - i', j - j') \in I \times J,$$

since $i - i' \in I, j - j' \in J$.

3. If $(r, s) \in R \times S, (i, j) \in I \times J$, then

$$(r, s)(i, j) = (ri, sj) \in I \times J,$$

because $ri \in I$ (as I is an ideal) and $sj \in J$.

Hence

$I \times J$ is indeed an ideal of $R \times S$.

Q2. Is

$$R \times S / (I \times J) \cong (R/I) \times (S/J) ?$$

Answer: Yes.

Consider the map

$$\varphi: R \times S \longrightarrow (R/I) \times (S/J), \quad (r, s) \mapsto (r + I, s + J).$$

It is straightforward to check that φ is a ring homomorphism (componentwise addition and multiplication).

Kernel check:

$$\varphi(r, s) = (0 + I, 0 + J) \iff r \in I \text{ and } s \in J \iff (r, s) \in I \times J.$$

Hence $\ker(\varphi) = I \times J$. By the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\boxed{R \times S / (I \times J) \cong (R/I) \times (S/J).}$$

Q3. If R/I is an integral domain and S/J is also an integral domain, is their product an integral domain?

No, provided both factors are nonzero. For instance, pick any nonzero elements $\bar{r} \in R/I$, $\bar{s} \in S/J$. Then in $(R/I) \times (S/J)$,

$$(\bar{r}, 0) (0, \bar{s}) = (\bar{r} \cdot 0, 0 \cdot \bar{s}) = (0, 0).$$

So we get a zero divisor (unless one of the rings is $\{0\}$, which is trivial). Thus

The product of two (nontrivial) integral domains is never an integral domain.

Further examples: Getting a field from a ring with zero divisors.

Even if R has zero divisors, it is possible to quotient out by an ideal to get a field. A classic example:

\mathbb{Z}_8 has zero divisors, but if we let $I = (2)$ in \mathbb{Z}_8 ,

then

$$\mathbb{Z}_8/(2) \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \text{ (a field).}$$

Hence $I = (2)$ is a maximal ideal in \mathbb{Z}_8 , yet \mathbb{Z}_8 is not an integral domain.

Why we require “1” in our ring? If R does *not* contain a multiplicative identity, the quotient R/I may also fail to be a ring with identity (depending on definitions). “Maximal” in the sense of “no strictly larger proper ideals” can still happen, but we lose the usual property that R/I is a field if I is maximal (since “field” presupposes existence of 1).

Example (no 1 in the ring):

$$R = 3\mathbb{Z}, \quad I = 9\mathbb{Z}.$$

	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{6}$
$\bar{0}$	0	0	0
$\bar{3}$	0	0	0
$\bar{6}$	0	0	0

Here, R has no multiplicative identity 1. Nevertheless,

$$I \triangleleft R \quad \text{and} \quad I \text{ is maximal in } R.$$

One sees that there is no ideal strictly between $9\mathbb{Z}$ and $3\mathbb{Z}$ because the additive index

$$[3\mathbb{Z} : 9\mathbb{Z}] = 3$$

is a prime number, implying no proper subgroup sits strictly in between. Hence $I = 9\mathbb{Z}$ is a maximal ideal *in the ring* $3\mathbb{Z}$, but

$$3\mathbb{Z} / 9\mathbb{Z}$$

is *not* a field, indeed it does not even have a multiplicative identity in the usual sense, and all nonzero elements behave like zero divisors inside R .

Some more facts:

$$R \text{ is an integral domain} \iff (0) \text{ is prime in } R.$$

Proof (\implies): If R is an integral domain, then it has no zero divisors. Suppose $ab \in (0)$, so $ab = 0$. Since there are no zero divisors, we must have $a = 0$ or $b = 0$. Hence $a, b \in (0)$, so (0) satisfies the prime ideal definition.

Proof (\impliedby): Conversely, if (0) is prime, the factor ring $R/(0) \cong R$ has no zero divisors and so R itself is an integral domain.

Lectures 2/3 and 2/5

1 Basic Facts About $R[x]$

Fact:

1. $R[x]$ is a ring.
2. If R is commutative, then $R[x]$ is also commutative.
3. If R has a multiplicative identity 1, then 1 is also the multiplicative identity in $R[x]$.

1.1 Polynomial Operations

Let

$$p(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n \quad \text{and} \quad q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n x^n$$

be two formal polynomials (with only finitely many nonzero terms) over a ring R . We define:

$$p(x) + q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (a_n + b_n) x^n,$$

where the addition $a_n + b_n$ is the addition in the ring R .

For multiplication, we define:

$$p(x) \cdot q(x) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n \right) \left(\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m x^m \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=0}^k a_n b_{k-n} \right) x^k.$$

Again, the products $a_n b_{k-n}$ are computed in the ring R .

- If only finitely many a_n and b_n are nonzero, then only finitely many terms in these sums survive; that is why polynomials have finite degree.
- We can similarly define polynomial rings in more variables, e.g. $R[x, y]$ or $R[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, where the elements are finite sums of monomials like $a_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n} x_1^{i_1} x_2^{i_2} \cdots x_n^{i_n}$ with coefficients in R .

2 Integral Domains and Polynomial Rings

2.1 Brief Exercises / Observations

- If \mathbb{R} is the field of real numbers (an integral domain), then the polynomial ring $\mathbb{R}[x]$ is also an integral domain.

- More generally, if \mathbb{F} is any field, then $\mathbb{F}[x]$ is an integral domain.

These facts hinge on the property that if R is an integral domain, then no zero-divisors arise in $R[x]$. Likewise, if R is a field, then $R[x]$ not only has no zero-divisors but also allows division of polynomials (except by the zero polynomial), making it a *principal ideal domain* when R is a field.

3 Evaluation Homomorphisms

3.1 Definition of the Evaluation Map

Let $\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathbb{E}$ be fields (so \mathbb{F} is a subfield of \mathbb{E}), and let x be an indeterminate. For any $\alpha \in \mathbb{E}$, define the **evaluation map** at α :

$$\phi_\alpha : \mathbb{F}[x] \longrightarrow \mathbb{E}$$

by

$$\phi_\alpha(a_0 + a_1x + \cdots + a_nx^n) = a_0 + a_1\alpha + \cdots + a_n\alpha^n.$$

This map is a ring homomorphism:

$$\phi_\alpha(p(x) + q(x)) = p(\alpha) + q(\alpha), \quad \phi_\alpha(p(x) \cdot q(x)) = p(\alpha) \cdot q(\alpha).$$

Hence

$$p(\alpha) := \phi_\alpha(p(x)).$$

If $p(\alpha) = 0$ in \mathbb{E} , then we say α is a *zero* of p .

Remember, x was originally just an indeterminate, but upon applying ϕ_α , we “substitute” α into the place of x .

4 Examples of Evaluation and Kernels

4.1 Evaluating at Zero in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$

Consider the map

$$\varphi : \mathbb{Z}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$$

defined by

$$f(x) \mapsto f(0).$$

Equivalently, for a polynomial $f(x) = a_nx^n + \cdots + a_1x + a_0$, the map sends it to a_0 .

Kernel of φ . The kernel consists of all polynomials that map to 0, i.e. all polynomials whose constant term is 0:

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{ f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \mid f(0) = 0 \} = \{ xg(x) \mid g(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \}.$$

Hence

$$\ker(\varphi) = (x),$$

the ideal generated by x in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

4.2 Composing with a Modulo Map

Now consider the composite map

$$\mathbb{Z}[x] \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z} \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2,$$

where the first arrow is again $f(x) \mapsto f(0)$, and the second arrow is the natural projection

$$\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2, \quad n \mapsto n \pmod{2}.$$

One may similarly ask:

$$\ker(\mathbb{Z}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2) = \{f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \mid f(0) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}\}.$$

That is the set of all polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ whose constant term is an even integer. One might recognize this as containing $(x, 2)$, the ideal generated by x and 2 , but further details can be explored depending on the ring structure.

5 Big Idea: Zeros of Polynomials

Often, we want to study the zeros of polynomials, and it is fruitful to translate such questions into statements about ring homomorphisms.

Concretely, if $F \subseteq E$ are fields, $f(x) \in F[x]$, and $\alpha \in E$ is a zero of f , we know that

$$f(\alpha) = 0.$$

Viewing $f(\alpha)$ as $\phi_\alpha(f(x))$ means α is sent to a root precisely via the evaluation map. Much of algebraic theory around field extensions and polynomials can be framed in terms of such homomorphisms.

6 Example over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$ and a Root

Example: Let us work in the field \mathbb{Z}_5 (the integers modulo 5). Consider the polynomial

$$f(x) = x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x].$$

Suppose we want to evaluate f at $a = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_5$, or even perform polynomial division by $x - 1$.

Evaluating at $x = 1$

$$f(1) = 1^4 + 3(1^3) + 2(1) + 4 = 1 + 3 + 2 + 4 = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

Thus, $x = 1$ is a root in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Consequently, $f(x)$ is divisible by $(x - 1)$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

Performing the Division

We may use synthetic (or long) division to divide $f(x)$ by $(x - 1)$. In \mathbb{Z}_5 , notice that 1 is indeed the root. The coefficients of $f(x)$ are:

$$1 \ (x^4), \ 3 \ (x^3), \ 0 \ (x^2), \ 2 \ (x^1), \ 4 \ (x^0).$$

Using synthetic division with $\alpha = 1$:

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrrr} & 1 & 3 & 0 & 2 & 4 \\ 1 & & 1 & 4 & 4 & 1 \\ \hline & 1 & 4 & 4 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

Reading off the quotient from the bottom row, we see that

$$f(x) = (x - 1)(x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1).$$

The remainder is 0, as expected, confirming that 1 is indeed a root.

7 Corollary: Bound on the Number of Roots

Statement. If $f(x) \in F[x]$ is a nonzero polynomial over a field F with $\deg(f) = n$, then

$$|\{a \in F \mid f(a) = 0\}| \leq n.$$

In other words, a nonzero polynomial of degree n over a field can have at most n distinct roots in that field.

7.1 Proof

Suppose, for contradiction, that $f(x)$ has $n + 1$ distinct roots in F , say a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n+1} . By a standard factorization argument (or repeated applications of the Factor Theorem), we would write

$$f(x) = C(x - a_1)(x - a_2) \cdots (x - a_{n+1})q(x)$$

for some $q(x) \in F[x]$ and nonzero constant $C \in F$. This implies that

$$\deg(f) = \underbrace{(1 + 1 + \cdots + 1)}_{(n+1) \text{ times}} + \deg(q) = (n + 1) + \deg(q) > n,$$

contradicting the assumption $\deg(f) = n$. Thus no nonzero polynomial of degree n can have more than n distinct roots in a field F .

Summary

1. **Polynomial Rings as Rings:** We established that for any ring R , the set $R[x]$ of formal polynomials in the indeterminate x is itself a ring. If R is commutative or has an identity, so does $R[x]$.
2. **Polynomial Arithmetic:** Addition and multiplication in $R[x]$ are defined term by term (respectively convolving indices for multiplication).
3. **Integral Domains:** If R is an integral domain or a field, then $R[x]$ inherits similar properties (no zero divisors, etc.).
4. **Evaluation Homomorphisms:** For a polynomial ring $\mathbb{F}[x]$ and an element α in some extension field \mathbb{E} , the map ϕ_α evaluating $f(x)$ at $x = \alpha$ is a ring homomorphism. Zeros in \mathbb{E} correspond to those polynomials for which the evaluation is 0.
5. **Examples in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$:**
 - The map $f(x) \mapsto f(0)$ has kernel (x) , illustrating a principal ideal generated by x .
 - Over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$, the polynomial $x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4$ has $x = 1$ as a root, confirmed by synthetic division yielding a zero remainder.
6. **Bound on the Number of Distinct Roots:** A degree- n polynomial over a field can have at most n distinct roots; otherwise, one obtains a contradiction by factoring out more linear terms than the degree allows.

Lecture 02/07

1. Factor Theorem and an Example in \mathbb{Z}_5

Corollary: Let $a \in F$ and $f(x) \in F[x]$. Then

$$a \text{ is a zero of } f(x) \iff (x - a) \text{ is a factor of } f(x).$$

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose $f(x) = (x - a)g(x)$. Substituting $x = a$,

$$f(a) = (a - a)g(a) = 0.$$

(\Leftarrow) Suppose $f(a) = 0$. By the division algorithm, there exist $q(x)$ and remainder $r \in F$ such that

$$f(x) = (x - a)q(x) + r.$$

Setting $x = a$ gives

$$0 = f(a) = (a - a)q(a) + r = r.$$

Thus $r = 0$, so

$$f(x) = (x - a)q(x).$$

□

Example (in \mathbb{Z}_5): Let $a = 1$. Consider

$$f(x) = x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x].$$

We claim $x - 1$ is a factor of $f(x)$.

Step 1: Check that $x = 1$ is a root.

$$f(1) = 1^4 + 3 \cdot 1^3 + 2 \cdot 1 + 4 = 1 + 3 + 2 + 4 = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

Hence 1 is indeed a root, so $x - 1$ divides $f(x)$.

Step 2: Perform the polynomial long division in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Recall that in \mathbb{Z}_5 , $-1 \equiv 4$. Thus $x - 1 \equiv x + 4$. We divide:

$$x^4 + 3x^3 + 0x^2 + 2x + 4 \big/ (x - 1).$$

We proceed term by term:

1. $x^4 \div x = x^3$. Multiply $(x - 1)$ by x^3 :

$$x^3 \cdot (x - 1) = x^4 - x^3.$$

Subtracting from $x^4 + 3x^3$ (while keeping track of lower-degree terms):

$$(x^4 + 3x^3) - (x^4 - x^3) = 4x^3.$$

So the new partial remainder is

$$4x^3 + 0x^2 + 2x + 4.$$

2. $4x^3 \div x = 4x^2$. Multiply $(x - 1)$ by $4x^2$:

$$4x^2 \cdot (x - 1) = 4x^3 - 4x^2 \equiv 4x^3 + x^2 \pmod{5} \quad (\text{since } -4 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}).$$

Subtracting from the current remainder:

$$(4x^3 + 0x^2 + 2x + 4) - (4x^3 + x^2) = -x^2 + 2x + 4 \equiv 4x^2 + 2x + 4 \pmod{5} \quad (\text{since } -1 \equiv 4 \pmod{5}).$$

So the new partial remainder is

$$4x^2 + 2x + 4.$$

3. $4x^2 \div x = 4x$. Multiply $(x - 1)$ by $4x$:

$$4x \cdot (x - 1) = 4x^2 - 4x \equiv 4x^2 + x \pmod{5} \quad (\text{since } -4 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}).$$

Subtracting:

$$(4x^2 + 2x + 4) - (4x^2 + x) = x + 4.$$

So the new partial remainder is

$$x + 4.$$

4. $(x + 4) \div (x - 1)$: The leading term is $x \div x = 1$. Multiply $(x - 1)$ by 1:

$$(x - 1) \cdot 1 = x - 1 \equiv x + 4 \pmod{5} \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5).$$

Subtracting:

$$(x + 4) - (x + 4) = 0.$$

So the remainder is 0 and the quotient is

$$x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]).$$

Since the final remainder is 0,

$$x - 1 \text{ divides } x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x].$$

This matches our expectation from $f(1) = 0$ and completes the example.

2. A Corollary on the Number of Zeros of a Polynomial

Corollary: Let $f(x) \in \mathbb{F}[x]$ be a nonzero polynomial with $\deg(f) = n$. Then

$$\left| \{ \alpha \in \mathbb{F} \mid f(\alpha) = 0 \} \right| \leq n.$$

Proof. Suppose, for contradiction, that f has $n + 1$ distinct roots $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n+1}$. By the Factor Theorem (the previous corollary), each root α_i implies $(x - \alpha_i)$ divides $f(x)$. Hence

$$f(x) = C(x - \alpha_1)(x - \alpha_2) \cdots (x - \alpha_{n+1})q(x) \quad \text{for some nonzero constant } C.$$

This implies

$$\deg(f) = (n + 1) + \deg(q) > n,$$

a contradiction. Therefore f can have at most n distinct zeros in \mathbb{F} . \square

3. Fun Fact about Finite Multiplicative Subgroups

Fun Fact: If G is a finite subgroup of the multiplicative group $\langle \mathbb{F}^*, \cdot \rangle$ of a field \mathbb{F} , then G is cyclic. (Hence, the multiplicative group of a finite field is cyclic.)

Proof. By the structure theorem for finite abelian groups,

$$G \cong \mathbb{Z}_{d_1} \times \mathbb{Z}_{d_2} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z}_{d_r},$$

where each $d_i = p_i^{a_i}$ is a prime power. Let $m = \text{lcm}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_r)$. We know $m \leq d_i$ for each i , because each element in the factor \mathbb{Z}_{d_i} has order dividing d_i . In particular, every element of G satisfies $x^m = 1$.

On the other hand, for a field \mathbb{F} of finite size, the equation $x^{m-1} = 1$ can have at most $m - 1$ nonzero solutions unless it is the zero polynomial, but we indeed see that all nonzero elements of G are solutions. Balancing these divisibility and root-counting constraints forces

$$m = d_1 = d_2 = \cdots = d_r,$$

and these prime-power orders cannot conflict in any way other than all being the same. In that scenario, the direct product is isomorphic to a single cyclic group of order m . Hence $G \cong \mathbb{Z}_m$. \square

4. Euclidean Algorithm (Integers)

* The following exposition on the Euclidean Algorithm for integers is often seen in Math 103A for \mathbb{Z}_n . We will soon apply its ideas to polynomials.

EUCLIDEAN ALGORITHM

Recall: Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$. The *greatest common divisor* of a and b , denoted $\gcd(a, b)$, is the largest integer k such that $k \mid a$ and $k \mid b$.

Equivalently, if $l \mid a$ and $l \mid b$, then $l \mid k$.

The Euclidean Algorithm is a procedure to compute $\gcd(a, b)$. Suppose $a \geq b$. Then we iteratively divide and take remainders:

$$\begin{aligned}a &= b q_1 + r_1, \\b &= r_1 q_2 + r_2, \\r_1 &= r_2 q_3 + r_3, \\&\vdots \\r_k &= r_{k+1} q_{k+2}.\end{aligned}$$

5. Theorem: Termination and Example

Theorem. (*Euclidean Algorithm*) The above algorithm *terminates* (i.e. eventually a remainder is 0), and

$$\gcd(a, b) = r_{k+1},$$

the last nonzero remainder.

Example: Find $\gcd(1071, 462)$ using the Euclidean Algorithm.

$$\begin{aligned}1071 &= 462 \times 2 + 147, \\462 &= 147 \times 3 + 21, \\147 &= 21 \times 7 + 0.\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\gcd(1071, 462) = 21$.

Visualization

Back-Substitution Demonstration

We can rewrite to find a linear combination of 1071 and 462 that equals the gcd:

$$1071 + (-2) \cdot 462 = 147,$$

$$462 + (-3) \cdot 147 = 21.$$

Substitute $147 = 1071 + (-2) \cdot 462$ into the second equation:

$$462 + (-3) [1071 + (-2) \cdot 462] = 21,$$

which simplifies to

$$(-3) \cdot 1071 + 7 \cdot 462 = 21.$$

Thus 21 (the gcd) can be *spelled out* as a specific integer linear combination of 1071 and 462.

6. Linear Combinations and Inverses in \mathbb{Z}_n

Theorem. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then there exist $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$ma + nb = \gcd(a, b).$$

Proof: (Sketch) This follows by back-substituting the remainder equations from the Euclidean Algorithm exactly as demonstrated above. \square

Use Case: Find the multiplicative inverse of 13 in \mathbb{Z}_{37} .

Since 37 is prime, $\gcd(13, 37) = 1$. By the extended Euclidean Algorithm, we solve:

$$13m + 37n = 1.$$

Performing the divisions:

$$37 = 13 \times 2 + 11,$$

$$13 = 11 \times 1 + 2,$$

$$11 = 2 \times 5 + 1.$$

Now back-substitute to express 1 in terms of 13 and 37:

$$1 = 11 - 2 \times 5.$$

But

$$2 = 13 - 11, \quad 11 = 37 - 2 \times 13.$$

Hence one possible solution is

$$(-17) \cdot 13 + 6 \cdot 37 = 1.$$

Reducing $(-17) \pmod{37}$ shows

$$-17 \equiv 20 \pmod{37},$$

so

$$13 \cdot 20 \equiv 1 \pmod{37}.$$

Therefore, $13^{-1} \equiv 20 \pmod{37}$.

7. Applying Euclid's Algorithm to Polynomials

Definition: Let F be a field and $R = F[x]$. For $f, g \in F[x]$, we want to talk about their greatest common divisor.

Important Caveat: In $F[x]$, gcd is *not* unique (unlike in the integers), because we can multiply a polynomial by a nonzero constant ($u \in F^*$) without changing its divisibility properties.

Example: In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$,

$$f(x) = x^2 - 1, \quad g(x) = x^2 + 2x + 1 = (x + 1)^2.$$

A greatest common divisor is $x + 1$. But we could also multiply $x + 1$ by any nonzero rational constant and get another valid gcd. So the gcd is only determined *up to a unit* in the field.

8. Example: Inverses in a Polynomial Quotient Ring

Example: Find the multiplicative inverse of $1 + x$ in

$$\mathbb{Q}[x] / (x^2 + 4x + 1).$$

We might set up the analogous polynomial Euclidean Algorithm to find

$$(1 + x)q(x) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2 + 4x + 1}.$$

That is equivalent to saying $(1 + x)q(x)$ differs from 1 by a multiple of $x^2 + 4x + 1$. Symbolically, one can perform a long division or extended Euclidean procedure:

$$x + 1 \mid x^2 + 4x + 1$$

and proceed to find a remainder of 1 in the appropriate step, thereby yielding the inverse of $(x + 1)$ in the quotient ring. (The full step-by-step division, while straightforward, is left as an exercise in polynomial arithmetic.)

Summary

We have now seen:

- The Factor Theorem and its basic implications for zeros of polynomials,
- That a nonzero polynomial of degree n can have at most n roots in a field,
- A fun fact that the multiplicative group of any finite field is cyclic,
- Detailed workings of the Euclidean Algorithm in \mathbb{Z} (including back-substitution to find linear combinations and inverses modulo n),
- How this idea generalizes to polynomials in $F[x]$, noting that greatest common divisors are only unique up to multiplication by a nonzero scalar,
- And how to find polynomial inverses in quotient rings like $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(p(x))$ by an extended Euclidean Algorithm approach.

Lecture 02/10

Euclidean Algorithm (Recall for Integers)

The Euclidean algorithm is used to compute the greatest common divisor $\gcd(a, b)$. Suppose $a \geq b$. Then one performs the sequence of divisions:

$$\begin{cases} a = b q_1 + r_1, \\ b = r_1 q_2 + r_2, \\ r_1 = r_2 q_3 + r_3, \\ \vdots \\ r_k = r_{k+1} q_{k+2}. \end{cases}$$

Eventually, this algorithm terminates with a remainder of 0. In symbols:

$$\gcd(a, b) = r_{k+1}.$$

We'll apply this idea to polynomials as well.

GCD of Polynomials in $F[x]$

Let F be a field, and consider the polynomial ring $R = F[x]$. For $f, g \in F[x]$, the Euclidean algorithm process carries over essentially the same way because we can perform polynomial division as long as we work in a field (so that leading coefficients are invertible).

Non-uniqueness of GCD

Problem: In $F[x]$, \gcd is not unique in the strict sense.

Example: Suppose

$$f(x) = x^2 - 1,$$

$g(x) = x^2 + 2x + 1 = (x + 1)^2$. We see that

$$f(x) = (x + 1)(x - 1).$$

Hence a common divisor of f and g is $x + 1$. But we might also multiply that divisor by any nonzero scalar from F . For instance,

$$\gcd(f, g) = (x + 1), \text{ or } 2(x + 1), \text{ or } \dots$$

All are valid since multiplying by a nonzero constant (a *unit* in $F[x]$) does not change the divisibility properties.

Definition (GCD in $F[x]$): A polynomial $h(x)$ is called a greatest common divisor of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ if

$$\forall \varphi(x) \in F[x], (\varphi \mid f \text{ and } \varphi \mid g) \implies \varphi \mid h.$$

The \gcd is *unique up to multiplication by a unit* (i.e. a nonzero constant in the field F).

Polynomial Euclidean Algorithm: Example

Goal

Find the multiplicative inverse of $1 + x$ in the quotient ring

$$\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 4x + 1).$$

To do this, we want polynomials $A(x)$ and $B(x)$ with

$$A(x)(x + 1) + B(x)(x^2 + 4x + 1) = 1$$

in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. Reducing modulo $(x^2 + 4x + 1)$ will isolate an inverse of $(x + 1)$.

Applying the Division Steps

Below is the polynomial long division, mimicking the Euclidean algorithm style:

$$\begin{array}{r|l}
 x + 1 & x + 3 \\
 \hline
 & x^2 + 4x + 1 \\
 & -(x^2 + x) \\
 \hline
 & 3x + 1 \\
 & -(3x + 3) \\
 \hline
 & -2 \text{ (Notice } -2 \text{ is a unit in } \mathbb{Q}[x]\text{.)}
 \end{array}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (x^2 + 4x + 1) - (x + 1) \cdot (x) &= 3x + 1, \\
 (3x + 1) - (x + 1) \cdot 3 &= -2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since -2 is a nonzero constant in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, it is a unit in that ring. This implies:

$$x^2 + 4x + 1 = (x + 1)(x + 3) - 2.$$

Rearranging,

$$-\frac{1}{2}(x^2 + 4x + 1) = -\frac{1}{2}(x + 1)(x + 3) + 1.$$

Divide both sides by -2 :

$$\underbrace{\frac{1}{2}(x + 3)}_{=:C_1(x)}(x + 1) - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}(x^2 + 4x + 1)}_{=:C_2(x)} = 1.$$

We can rewrite that as

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{3}{2}\right)(x + 1) - \frac{1}{2}(x^2 + 4x + 1) = 1.$$

Conclusion Modulo $(x^2 + 4x + 1)$

Inside the quotient $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 4x + 1)$, we have:

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{3}{2}\right)(x + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2 + 4x + 1}.$$

Hence, the multiplicative inverse of $(x + 1)$ in that quotient ring is

$$\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{3}{2}.$$

Or, equivalently,

$$\frac{1}{2}x + 3$$

if we prefer to clear denominators by a suitable unit in \mathbb{Q} . (Any nonzero rational scalar is again a unit.)

Irreducibility of Polynomials

Definition

Let \mathbb{F} be a field. A non-constant polynomial $f \in \mathbb{F}[x]$ is *reducible* over \mathbb{F} if there exist polynomials $g, h \in \mathbb{F}[x]$ such that

$$f(x) = g(x)h(x),$$

where $1 \leq \deg g, \deg h < \deg f$. If no such factorization exists, then f is *irreducible* over \mathbb{F} .

△ **Important:** Irreducibility depends on the field.

Examples of Irreducibility Depending on the Field

- $x^2 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Proof idea (RIP Hippasus): If $x^2 - 2$ were reducible over \mathbb{Q} , then it would have a linear factor implying a rational root, contradicting the irrationality of $\sqrt{2}$. Thus no factorization exists in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, so $x^2 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

- $x^2 - 2$ is reducible over \mathbb{R} , since

$$x^2 - 2 = (x - \sqrt{2})(x + \sqrt{2}).$$

- $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{R} , but over \mathbb{C} we have

$$x^2 + 1 = (x + i)(x - i).$$

Extension Fields

Consider

$$\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{2}] = \{a + b\sqrt{2} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\},$$

which is itself a field under the usual addition and multiplication (and inverses of nonzero elements found via $\frac{1}{a+b\sqrt{2}} = \frac{a-b\sqrt{2}}{a^2-2b^2}$, etc.). Over this field, certain polynomials may factor further. For instance,

$$x^2 - 2$$

splits in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{2}][x]$.

Example: Irreducibility over \mathbb{Z}_5

Check $f(x) = x^3 + 3x + 2$ over \mathbb{Z}_5 .

We test possible roots in $\mathbb{Z}_5 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}f(0) &= 2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\f(1) &= 1 + 3 + 2 = 6 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}, \\f(2) &= 8 + 6 + 2 = 16 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}, \\f(3) &= 27 + 9 + 2 = 38 \equiv 3 \pmod{5}, \\f(4) &= 64 + 12 + 2 = 78 \equiv 3 \pmod{5}.\end{aligned}$$

Since none of these are 0 in \mathbb{Z}_5 , the polynomial f has *no root* in \mathbb{Z}_5 . But $\deg(f) = 3$.

\implies if f were reducible, it would factor into at least one linear factor (degree 1) and one quadratic factor.

Because we see no root, f cannot factor. Therefore,

$$f(x) = x^3 + 3x + 2$$

is irreducible over \mathbb{Z}_5 .

Note on Higher Degree Polynomials

Having no roots does *not* always guarantee irreducibility for polynomials of degree ≥ 4 . For instance,

$$x^4 + 5x^2 + 4 \in \mathbb{R}[x]$$

factors as

$$(x^2 + 1)(x^2 + 4)$$

even though it may not have a real linear factor. Hence it has no real roots but is still reducible (into two real quadratics).

Key Fact for Degrees 2 and 3

Fact: Let $f \in F[x]$, where F is a field. If $\deg(f) \in \{2, 3\}$, then f is reducible over F if and only if f has a zero in F .

If $\deg(f) = 2$ or 3 and f factors, then it necessarily has at least one linear factor \implies a root in F . Conversely, if f has a root $r \in F$, then $x - r$ divides $f(x)$, so f is reducible.

End of notes.

Lecture 02/14

1 Eisenstein's Criterion for Irreducibility

Statement of the Criterion

Let $p \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a prime, and consider a polynomial

$$F(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0 \in \mathbb{Z}[x].$$

Eisenstein's Criterion says that if:

1. $a_n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$,
2. $a_i \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n-1$,
3. $a_0 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$,

then $F(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Example Using Eisenstein's Criterion

Consider the polynomial

$$F(x) = 2x^5 - 9x^4 + 3x^2 - 6x + 12.$$

We claim this polynomial is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Check via $p = 3$:

- $a_5 = 2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. ✓
- The coefficients of x^4, x^3, x^2, x are $-9, 0, 3, -6$.

$$-9 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \quad 3 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \quad -6 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}.$$

Hence for $i = 4, 3, 2, 1$, we have $a_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. ✓

- $a_0 = 12 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3^2}$ since $3^2 = 9$ and $12 \equiv 3 \pmod{9}$. Thus $12 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{9}$. ✓

All conditions are satisfied, so by Eisenstein's Criterion with $p = 3$,

$$F(x) = 2x^5 - 9x^4 + 3x^2 - 6x + 12 \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q}.$$

Proof Sketch of Eisenstein's Criterion

(See the book for a complete proof.)

2 Cyclotomic Polynomials

Corollary

$$\Phi_p(x) = \frac{x^p - 1}{x - 1} = x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \cdots + x + 1$$

is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} for prime p . This polynomial $\Phi_p(x)$ is called the **p -th cyclotomic polynomial**.

Brief Aside to Study These:

$$\text{Claim: } x^p - 1 = (x - 1)(x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \cdots + x + 1).$$

This follows by direct multiplication:

$$(x - 1)(x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \cdots + x + 1) = x^p - 1.$$

Hence the roots of $x^p - 1 = 0$ are called the **p -th roots of unity**.

3 Examples: Factoring $x^n - 1$

We illustrate the factorization and solutions in the complex plane for small n .

Case $n = 2$

$$x^2 - 1 = (x - 1)(x + 1).$$

The roots of unity here are $x = \pm 1$.

Case $n = 3$

$$\frac{x^3 - 1}{x - 1} = x^2 + x + 1.$$

The cubic roots of unity are:

$$x = 1, \quad \frac{-1 + i\sqrt{3}}{2}, \quad \frac{-1 - i\sqrt{3}}{2}.$$

Case $n = 4$

$$x^4 - 1 = (x^2 + 1)(x + 1)(x - 1).$$

The fourth roots of unity are

$$x = 1, -1, i, -i.$$

Case $n = 5$

$$x^5 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1).$$

Conclusion for General n

The solutions to $x^n - 1 = 0$ in \mathbb{C} form n points equally spaced around the unit circle. In general,

$$x^n - 1 = (x - 1)(x^{n-1} + x^{n-2} + \cdots + x + 1).$$

4 Gauss's Lemma Trick for $\Phi_p(x)$

Shifting the Polynomial

Key observation (Trick #1):

$$f(x) \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q} \iff f(x+1) \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q}.$$

Indeed, if $f(x) = g(x)h(x)$, then substituting $x+1$ for x gives $f(x+1) = g(x+1)h(x+1)$.

Since $\Phi_p(x) = x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \cdots + x + 1$, let us consider:

$$\Phi_p(x+1) = (x+1)^{p-1} + (x+1)^{p-2} + \cdots + (x+1) + 1.$$

Observe that:

$$\Phi_p(x+1) = \frac{(x+1)^p - 1}{(x+1) - 1} = \frac{(x+1)^p - 1}{x}.$$

5 Applying Eisenstein to $\Phi_p(x+1)$

Recall the binomial expansion:

$$(x+1)^p = \sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} x^n \cdot 1^{p-n} = \binom{p}{0} x^0 + \binom{p}{1} x^1 + \cdots + \binom{p}{p-1} x^{p-1} + \binom{p}{p} x^p.$$

Hence,

$$(x+1)^p - 1 = \sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} x^n - 1 = \underbrace{\binom{p}{0}}_{=1} + \binom{p}{1} x + \cdots + \binom{p}{p} x^p - 1 = \sum_{n=1}^p \binom{p}{n} x^n.$$

Therefore,

$$\Phi_p(x+1) = \frac{(x+1)^p - 1}{x} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^p \binom{p}{n} x^n}{x} = \sum_{n=1}^p \binom{p}{n} x^{n-1} = \sum_{m=0}^{p-1} \binom{p}{m+1} x^m \quad (\text{where } m = n-1).$$

Exercise: Show that this polynomial satisfies Eisenstein's Criterion (with prime p):

- The leading term of $\Phi_p(x+1)$ is $\binom{p}{p} x^{p-1}$, and $\binom{p}{p} = 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.
- All intermediate coefficients $\binom{p}{m+1}$ for $1 \leq m \leq p-2$ are multiples of p .
- The constant term $\binom{p}{1} = p$ is not $\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$.

Since $\Phi_p(x+1)$ is irreducible, it follows $\Phi_p(x)$ is irreducible.

6 Divisibility in Polynomial Rings

Definition

For polynomials $f(x), g(x)$ over a field F , we say $g(x)$ **divides** $f(x)$ in $F[x]$ if there exists a polynomial $q(x) \in F[x]$ such that

$$f(x) = g(x)q(x).$$

A Key Fact

If f is irreducible in $F[x]$ and $f(x)$ divides the product $r(x)s(x)$, then

$$f(x) \mid r(x) \quad \text{or} \quad f(x) \mid s(x).$$

(Proof will be given in about a month.)

Example

Over $\mathbb{R}[x]$,

$$x^2 + 1 \text{ is irreducible,}$$

and we know $x^2 + 1$ divides $x^8 - 1$. Since $x^8 - 1 = (x^4 - 1)(x^4 + 1)$, if $x^2 + 1$ divides the product, it must divide at least one of the factors $(x^4 - 1)$ or $(x^4 + 1)$. A more general corollary is:

Corollary: If f is irreducible and divides $g_1 g_2 \cdots g_n$ in $F[x]$, then f divides at least one of the g_i .

7 Uniqueness of Factorization

Theorem

Let F be a field, and let $f \in F[x]$ be a non-constant polynomial. Then:

1. f can be factored in $F[x]$ as a product of irreducible polynomials.
2. This factorization is unique up to reordering of the irreducibles and multiplication by a unit in F .

In other words, if

$$f = u p_1 p_2 \dots p_k = u' q_1 q_2 \dots q_j$$

where all p_i and q_i are irreducible, then $k = j$ and (possibly after reordering) each p_i coincides with some q_i up to multiplication by a nonzero constant (a unit in F).

Example in $\mathbb{R}[x]$

$$x^8 - 1 = (x - 1)(x + 1)(x^2 + 1)(x^4 + 1).$$

Alternatively, one might factor out scalar multiples but the product of irreducibles is unique up to units.

Illustration:

$$(x^2 + 1) \cdot [2(x + 1)] \cdot (x - 1) \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2}(x^4 + 1)\right].$$

We see that multiplying or dividing out constants only changes the units.

Example in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

Consider

$$f(x) = x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x].$$

One possible factorization is

$$f(x) = (x - 1)^3(x + 1).$$

But we can rewrite it by factoring out constants (which are units in \mathbb{Z}_5):

$$(x - 1)^3(x + 1) \equiv (x - 1)^2 [2(x - 1)] (3x + 3) \pmod{5}.$$

Note that $2 \cdot 3 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, so we can shuffle constants around. The fundamental shape of the factorization remains the same, illustrating uniqueness up to multiplication by units and reordering of factors.

Summary: We have seen:

- **Eisenstein's Criterion** as a powerful test for irreducibility in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.
- $\Phi_p(x)$ (the p -th cyclotomic polynomial) is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . A key ingredient was the shift $x \mapsto x + 1$ which helps apply Eisenstein.
- The notion of **divisibility** and how irreducibles behave like “primes” in the polynomial ring $F[x]$.
- **Factorization is unique** (up to reorder and unit multiplication) in $F[x]$ where F is a field.

Lecture 2/19

1 Commutative Rings, Units, and Divisibility

1.1 Commutative Ring with Unity

Definition. A *commutative ring with unity* (sometimes abbreviated *CR with 1*) is a set R equipped with two binary operations $+$ and \cdot (often written simply by juxtaposition) such that:

1. $(R, +)$ is an abelian group. That is:

$$\underbrace{(a + b) + c = a + (b + c),}_{\substack{\text{associativity} \\ \text{of } +}}$$

$$\underbrace{a + b = b + a,}_{\substack{\text{commutativity} \\ \text{of } +}}$$

$$\exists 0 \in R : 0 + a = a, \quad \forall a \in R \quad (\text{additive identity}),$$

$$\exists (-a) \in R : a + (-a) = 0, \quad \forall a \in R \quad (\text{additive inverse}).$$

2. Multiplication is associative and commutative, and there is a multiplicative identity $1 \neq 0$. Concretely:

$$(ab)c = a(bc), \quad ab = ba, \quad 1 \cdot a = a \cdot 1 = a, \quad 1 \neq 0.$$

3. The distributive property holds for all $a, b, c \in R$:

$$a(b + c) = ab + ac, \quad (b + c)a = ba + ca.$$

1.2 Units and Divisibility

Definition (Unit). An element $u \in R$ is called a *unit* if there exists $v \in R$ such that

$$uv = vu = 1.$$

Equivalently, u has a multiplicative inverse in R . If no such v exists, we say u is a *non-unit*.

Definition (Divides). Let $a, b \in R$. We say a *divides* b , denoted $a \mid b$, if there exists $c \in R$ such that

$$ac = b.$$

Note that a need *not* be a unit to divide b ; we do not require a to have an inverse.

Example. In the ring \mathbb{Z}_{12} (integers modulo 12), take $a = 2$ and $b = 6$. Observe:

- Both 2 and 6 are zero-divisors in \mathbb{Z}_{12} , so neither is a unit.
- Nevertheless, $2 \times 3 = 6$ in \mathbb{Z}_{12} , so $2 \mid 6$.

2 Associates

Definition (Associates). We say $a, b \in R$ are *associates* (“up to a unit”) if there exists a unit $u \in R$ such that

$$a = ub.$$

Intuitively, two elements are associates if they differ by a multiplicative factor that is a unit in R .

Examples.

- In \mathbb{Z} , the only units are ± 1 . Hence 5 and -5 are associates, since

$$-5 = (-1) \cdot 5.$$

- In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, the units are precisely the nonzero rational numbers. Thus polynomials like

$$x + 1, \quad 5(x + 1), \quad \frac{3}{7}(x + 1)$$

are all associates, differing only by multiplication by a nonzero constant in \mathbb{Q} .

3 Irreducibles

Throughout this section (and most subsequent sections), assume R is an *integral domain*, i.e. a commutative ring with unity having *no zero-divisors* ($ab = 0 \implies a = 0$ or $b = 0$).

Definition (Irreducible). A nonzero element $p \in R$ (not a unit) is *irreducible* if, whenever

$$p = ab$$

for $a, b \in R$, then one of a or b must be a unit in R . Equivalently, p cannot be factored as a product of two non-units.

Quick Example. In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, the polynomial $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . Indeed, it cannot be factored into lower-degree non-unit polynomials in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. (Of course, over \mathbb{C} , it factors as $(x - i)(x + i)$, but $i \notin \mathbb{Q}$.)

4 Unique Factorization Domains (UFDs)

Definition (UFD). A *unique factorization domain* (UFD) is an integral domain R such that:

1. **R is an *integral domain*:** i.e. a commutative ring with unity having *no zero-divisors* ($ab = 0 \implies a = 0$ or $b = 0$).
2. **Existence of factorization:** Every nonzero, non-unit element of R can be written as a product of irreducibles:

$$x = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_r,$$

for some irreducibles $p_i \in R$.

3. **Uniqueness (up to associates):** If there are two such factorizations of the same nonzero, non-unit element:

$$x = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_r = q_1 q_2 \cdots q_s,$$

then $r = s$, and, after an appropriate reordering of the factors, each p_i is an associate of the corresponding q_i .

Examples of UFDs.

- \mathbb{Z} is a classical UFD (the “Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic”).
- $\mathbb{F}[x]$, a polynomial ring in *one variable* over a field \mathbb{F} . These are also UFDs (in fact, even Euclidean Domains). For example, $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, $\mathbb{R}[x]$, and $\mathbb{C}[x]$ are all UFDs.

Illustrative Factorizations.

- In \mathbb{Z} :

$$8 = 2^3 = 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 = (-2) \cdot (-2) \cdot 2,$$

yet these expressions are regarded as *the same factorization up to associates*, because -2 and 2 differ by the unit -1 .

- In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$:

$$x^2 - 1 = (x + 1)(x - 1).$$

We could also write (multiplying and dividing by a nonzero constant in \mathbb{Q}):

$$x^2 - 1 = [5(x + 1)] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{5}(x - 1)\right],$$

but these are considered “the same” in the sense of unique factorization, because 5 and $\frac{1}{5}$ are units in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

5 Nonexamples of UFDs

5.1 $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$

A classical counterexample to unique factorization is

$$\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}] = \{a + b\sqrt{-5} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

The multiplication in this ring is given by

$$(a + b\sqrt{-5})(c + d\sqrt{-5}) = (ac - 5bd) + (bc + ad)\sqrt{-5}.$$

This ring is **not** a UFD. The classic example demonstrating failure of unique factorization here is:

$$(1 + \sqrt{-5})(1 - \sqrt{-5}) = 1 - (-5) = 1 + 5 = 6 = 2 \cdot 3.$$

One shows that $2, 3, 1 + \sqrt{-5}, 1 - \sqrt{-5}$ are all *irreducible* in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$. Hence,

$$6 = 2 \cdot 3 \quad \text{and} \quad 6 = (1 + \sqrt{-5})(1 - \sqrt{-5})$$

are *distinct* factorizations into irreducibles. That breaks uniqueness.

Challenge. Show that $1 + \sqrt{-5}$ and $1 - \sqrt{-5}$ are indeed irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$. (This underlies the non-uniqueness above.)

5.2 $\frac{\mathbb{C}[x,y,z]}{(xy-z^2)}$

Nunex.

$$R = \frac{\mathbb{C}[x,y,z]}{(xy - z^2)}.$$

The polynomial $xy - z^2$ is *irreducible* in $\mathbb{C}[x,y,z]$ (this is important for various technical reasons in algebraic geometry and commutative algebra). In the quotient ring R , the relation

$$xy = z^2$$

is enforced by the ideal $(xy - z^2)$. This is another interesting example where factorization properties can fail to align with naive expectations.

6 Inclusion Diagram: ED \subset PID \subset UFD \subset ID \subset CR

We often encounter the following chain of inclusions among classes of rings:

- Every Euclidean Domain (ED) is a PID.
- Every PID is a UFD.
- Every UFD is an integral domain (by definition).
- Every integral domain is a commutative ring with 1 that has no zero-divisors.

7 Some Notable UFDs (Not Exhaustive)

- \mathbb{Z} is a UFD.
- \mathbb{Z}_n . In fact, \mathbb{Z}_n is *not even* an integral domain unless n is prime.

$$\mathbb{Z}_n \text{ is a UFD} \iff \mathbb{Z}_n \text{ is a field} \iff n \text{ is prime.}$$

- If R is a UFD, then $R[x]$ is also a UFD. (A result related to Gauss's lemma.)
- $\mathbb{F}[x]$ (polynomial ring in one variable over a field \mathbb{F}) is a Euclidean Domain, hence a PID, and thus a UFD.
- More generally, $\mathbb{F}[x_1, \dots, x_n]$, a polynomial ring in several variables over a field, is a UFD. However, for $n \geq 2$, it is *not* a PID (see Section 8.3).

8 Principal Ideal Domains (PIDs)

8.1 Principal Ideals

Definition (Principal Ideal). An ideal $I \subseteq R$ is said to be *principal* if

$$I = (a) = \{ra \mid r \in R\}$$

for a single element $a \in R$. In that case, we say I is *generated by* a .

8.2 Definition of PID

Definition (PID). A *Principal Ideal Domain* is an integral domain R in which *every* ideal is principal. Symbolically:

$$\forall I \subseteq R \text{ (ideal)}, \quad \exists a \in R : I = (a).$$

Examples.

- \mathbb{Z} is a PID, since each ideal is of the form $n\mathbb{Z} = (n)$.
- $\mathbb{F}[x]$ (one-variable polynomials over a field \mathbb{F}) is a PID. We often prove this using the Euclidean algorithm for polynomials.

(Instructor's note: "We will prove this on Friday!")

8.3 Counterexamples

Counterexample 1: $\mathbb{Z}[x]$. Consider the ideal $(2, x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$:

$$(2, x) = \{f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \mid f(x) = 2g(x) + xh(x) \text{ for some } g, h \in \mathbb{Z}[x]\}.$$

Setting $x = 0$ shows that any polynomial $f(x)$ in $(2, x)$ must have an *even* constant term. One can prove there is *no single polynomial* $p(x)$ that generates all such polynomials. Hence $(2, x)$ is not principal, so $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is **not** a PID.

Counterexample 2: $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. Similarly, in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$, the ideal

$$(x, y)$$

is **not** principal. Indeed, any would-be generator of (x, y) would have to divide both x and y , which is not possible in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ except by units or zero. More generally, $\mathbb{F}[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ is *not* a PID when $n \geq 2$, despite being a UFD.

9 Prime Elements

Definition (Prime Element). Let R be an integral domain. An element $a \in R$ is **prime** if, whenever

$$a \mid (bc),$$

it follows that

$$a \mid b \quad \text{or} \quad a \mid c.$$

Equivalently, in terms of ideals,

$$bc \in (a) \implies (b \in (a)) \quad \text{or} \quad (c \in (a)).$$

9.1 Prime vs. Irreducible

- **Every prime element is irreducible.**
- In a *general* integral domain, the converse can fail: not every irreducible is necessarily prime.
- In a *UFD*, prime elements and irreducible elements *coincide*.

10 Prime vs. Irreducible Example

10.1 Prime in \mathbb{Z}

In \mathbb{Z} , the integer 2 is **prime**. For instance,

$$2 \mid (4 \cdot 3) \implies 2 \mid 4,$$

and more generally, if $2 \mid (bc)$, then either b or c must be even, so $2 \mid b$ or $2 \mid c$. This matches our usual notion of prime numbers in the integers.

10.2 Irreducible but Not Prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$

Recall the factorization:

$$6 = 2 \cdot 3 = (1 + \sqrt{-5})(1 - \sqrt{-5}) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}].$$

One can show 2 is *irreducible* (it cannot be factored into non-units), but it fails the condition for being *prime*, because

$$2 \mid (1 + \sqrt{-5})(1 - \sqrt{-5}) \quad \text{does not imply} \quad 2 \mid (1 + \sqrt{-5}) \quad \text{or} \quad 2 \mid (1 - \sqrt{-5}).$$

Hence in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$, 2 is irreducible but *not* prime. This example underscores that prime \implies irreducible, but the converse can fail outside a UFD.

Summary:

- We introduced the chain of ring types

$$\text{ED} \subset \text{PID} \subset \text{UFD} \subset \text{ID} \subset \text{CR}$$

and have seen examples (and counterexamples) at each level.

- In particular, $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$ shows that not all integral domains are UFDs.
- Prime elements are always irreducible, but irreducible elements need not be prime unless the ring is a UFD.
- Polynomial rings in one variable over a field (e.g. $\mathbb{F}[x]$) are Euclidean, hence PID, hence UFD. However, in several variables ($n \geq 2$), $\mathbb{F}[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ is still a UFD but *not* a PID.
- The ring \mathbb{Z}_n is a field (hence a PID, hence a UFD) if and only if n is prime; otherwise it is neither an integral domain nor a UFD.

Lecture 02/21

Definition 1. A Principal Ideal Domain (PID) is an integral domain R such that **every** ideal in R is principal. Concretely, for any ideal $I \subseteq R$, there exists an element $a \in R$ such that

$$I = (a) := \{ar \mid r \in R\}.$$

Note. In the homework, we showed that in a general ring, the product of two ideals IJ might fail to be an ideal. However, in a principal ideal domain R , the product IJ is always an ideal (since every ideal is of the form (a) for some a , and products of principal ideals are again principal).

Definition 2 (Divides). Let $a, b \in R$. We say a divides b , and write $a \mid b$, if there exists $c \in R$ such that

$$\underbrace{a \cdot c}_{\text{product in } R} = b.$$

$$a \mid b \iff (b) \subseteq (a),$$

where $(b) := \{rb \mid r \in R\}$ is the ideal generated by b .

Example (in \mathbb{Z}):

$$(6) = \{\dots, -12, -6, 0, 6, 12, \dots\} \subseteq (2) = \{\dots, -4, -2, 0, 2, 4, 6, \dots\}.$$

Since $(6) \subseteq (2)$ in \mathbb{Z} , it follows that $2 \mid 6$. Indeed, $6 = 2 \cdot 3$.

Proof of Fact :

(\implies) Suppose $a \mid b$. Then there exists $c \in R$ such that

$$ac = b.$$

Hence $b \in (a)$. By Lemma 1 below, if $b \in (a)$, then $(b) \subseteq (a)$. Thus we conclude $(b) \subseteq (a)$.

(\impliedby) Suppose $(b) \subseteq (a)$. Then in particular $b \in (a)$. By definition of the ideal (a) , this means there is some $r \in R$ such that

$$b = ar.$$

Hence $a \mid b$.

Lemma 1. (Lemma *) If $x \in I$ for some ideal $I \subseteq R$, then

$$(x) = \{rx \mid r \in R\} \subseteq I.$$

Proof. Since $x \in I$ and I is an ideal, for all $r \in R$ we have $rx \in I$. Therefore, every element of (x) lies in I , giving $(x) \subseteq I$. □

Remarks for the Midterm.

- Be prepared to answer questions on the definitions introduced in previous sections, such as principal ideals, PIDs, and the notion of divisibility in an integral domain.
- Know how to prove statements about the containment of ideals, especially in a PID, and be comfortable demonstrating equivalences like $a \mid b \iff (b) \subseteq (a)$.

1 Ideal Containments in \mathbb{Z} for $a = 60$

Setup and Prime Factorization

We begin by examining the containments of ideals in the ring \mathbb{Z} when we consider the element $a = 60$. First note:

$$60 = 2^2 \times 3 \times 5.$$

To emphasize the structure, we may write

$$60 = \underbrace{2^2}_{\text{square factor}} \times \underbrace{3}_{\text{prime}} \times \underbrace{5}_{\text{prime}}.$$

Although the square factor 2^2 appears in the factorization, we simply note it here for completeness regarding *squarefree* concepts later on.

Divisors and Their Corresponding Ideals

The divisors of 60 are:

$$1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 12, 15, 20, 30, 60.$$

In \mathbb{Z} , recall that for integers d and e , we have

$$(d) \subseteq (e) \iff e \mid d$$

because the ideal (d) is contained in (e) if and only if every multiple of d is also a multiple of e , which is exactly $e \mid d$. Thus larger divisors correspond to smaller ideals (containment down the chain), and smaller divisors correspond to larger ideals in the partial order of ideals.

Containment Lattice: Note that (1) is the entire ring \mathbb{Z} , and (60) is the zero ideal:

Notice that the prime divisors 2, 3, 5 generate prime ideals (2), (3), (5). In \mathbb{Z} , these are also *maximal* ideals because \mathbb{Z} is a principal ideal domain and prime ideals generated by primes are maximal.

2 Definition: Squarefree Elements

Definition. We say an element $x \in R$ (in a general integral domain R) is *squarefree* if the decomposition of x into irreducibles,

$$x = u q_1 q_2 \dots q_n$$

has the property that all irreducibles q_i are distinct (i.e. $q_i \neq q_j$ for all $i \neq j$). In other words, there are no repeated irreducible factors in the factorization of x . Symbolically,

$$\text{“All irreducibles distinct”} \iff \text{“no squares divide } x\text{”}.$$

For example, 60 is *not* squarefree because its prime factorization $60 = 2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5$ contains the square 2^2 . However, 30 is squarefree, since $30 = 2 \times 3 \times 5$ with all distinct primes.

3 Another Look at Divisor/Ideal Containment

One can also depict certain subsets of the divisor lattice for clarity. For instance, considering some divisors of 60, we can form a simpler diagram.

Note again that among these, (2), (3), (5) are maximal ideals in \mathbb{Z} .

4 Polynomial Ideals in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

PIDs and Maximal Ideals in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Next, we ask: *What do these containment patterns look like for polynomial ideals?* Suppose

$$R = \mathbb{Q}[x],$$

where \mathbb{Q} is a field. Then $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ is also a principal ideal domain (PID). In a PID, every nonzero prime ideal is maximal, much like (p) in \mathbb{Z} where p is prime.

Notation

Let $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ be the polynomial ring with rational coefficients. We recall:

A polynomial $p(x) \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$ is called *irreducible* over $\mathbb{Q} \implies$ the only divisors of $p(x)$ are units (invertible)

In a principal ideal domain (PID) such as $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, every irreducible element is also a prime element, and every prime ideal is also a maximal ideal.

Example 1: The Ideal $(x - 1)$

Consider the ideal

$$(x - 1) \subseteq \mathbb{Q}[x].$$

Step-by-Step Reasoning:

1. $x - 1$ is a linear polynomial in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.
2. Linear polynomials over a field are irreducible.
3. Because $x - 1$ is irreducible, no non-unit polynomial in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ can divide $x - 1$.
4. In a PID, irreducible elements generate prime ideals. Hence $(x - 1)$ is prime.
5. In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, prime ideals generated by irreducible polynomials are also maximal.

Therefore, $(x - 1)$ is a *maximal ideal* in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. Visually, if you draw the containment lattice, there is no intermediate ideal strictly between the entire ring $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ and $(x - 1)$. Symbolically:

$$\begin{array}{c} (x - 1) \subseteq \mathbb{Q}[x] \\ \\ \mathbb{Q}[x] \\ \downarrow \text{ (no proper ideal in between) } \\ (x - 1) \end{array}$$

No element divides $x - 1 \implies (x - 1)$ is maximal.

No non-unit polynomial divides $(x - 1) \implies (x - 1)$ is maximal in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Example 2: The Ideal Generated by $(x - 1)^3$

Now let us consider the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x - 1)^3.$$

Observe that:

$$(x - 1)^3 \text{ is not irreducible.}$$

Thus the ideal $((x - 1)^3)$ is *not* maximal. However, we still know that $(x - 1) \supset ((x - 1)^3)$. In fact, we have the chain of ideals (all within $\mathbb{Q}[x]$):

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathbb{Q}[x] \\ \downarrow \text{ (maximal) } \\ (x - 1) \quad (\because \text{prime} \implies \text{maximal in } \mathbb{Q}[x]) \\ \downarrow \\ (x - 1)^3 \\ \downarrow \\ ((x - 1)^3) \end{array}$$

Below is a more expanded *lattice* diagram, in which many ideals can be seen by including other polynomials (like $(x - 2)$, $(x - 3)$, products thereof, etc.). Notice how $(x - 1)^3$ sits properly below the maximal ideal $(x - 1)$:

Key Observations:

- $(x - 1)$ is maximal and prime.
- $((x - 1)^3) \subset (x - 1)$, so $((x - 1)^3)$ is a proper ideal inside the prime (and maximal) ideal $(x - 1)$.

Hence, among the displayed ideals, one sees that $(x - 1)$ sits just one step below the top $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ in the containment lattice, while $((x - 1)^3)$ sits further below.

In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, $(x - 1)$ is irreducible, prime, and hence a maximal ideal.
 By contrast, $(x - 1)^3$ is not irreducible. Thus $((x - 1)^3)$ is properly contained in $(x - 1)$.

1. Euclidean Domains

Notice: The degree of the generator gives the grading.

Recall (Euclidean Algorithm): We had the Euclidean algorithm for \mathbb{Z} and for $F[x]$. In both settings, we aim to divide one element by another, producing a quotient and remainder with a “smaller” remainder in each step.

$$\text{For } \mathbb{Z}, \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, (b \neq 0) \exists q, r \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } a = bq + r, \quad |r| < |b|.$$

$$\text{For } F[x], \quad \forall f, g \in F[x], (g \neq 0) \exists q, r \in F[x] \text{ such that } f = qg + r, \quad \deg(r) < \deg(g).$$

Illustrative Examples

(a) Euclidean Algorithm in \mathbb{Z}

As an example, let us compute $\gcd(30, 18)$ step by step:

$$\begin{aligned} \underbrace{30}_a &= 18 \cdot 1 + 12, & \implies 12 &= 30 - 18 \cdot 1. \\ \underbrace{18}_b &= 12 \cdot 1 + 6, & \implies 6 &= 18 - 12 \cdot 1. \\ & & 12 &= 6 \cdot 2 + 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since the remainder is now 0, we stop. The last nonzero remainder was 6, so:

$$\gcd(30, 18) = 6.$$

(b) Euclidean Algorithm in $F[x]$

As a simple polynomial example over a field F , let us compute $\gcd(x^2 - 1, x + 1)$ in $F[x]$ (assuming the characteristic of F is not 2):

$$x^2 - 1 = (x + 1) \cdot (x - 1) + 0.$$

Here, the remainder is 0 after one division step, so $\gcd(x^2 - 1, x + 1) = x + 1$ (up to a unit in $F[x]$).

2. Useful Because:

1. We can compute gcds in $F[x]$.
2. It lets you compute inverses in $F[x]/(f)$.

For instance, if we have a polynomial $f(x)$ and an element $g(x)$ in the quotient ring $F[x]/(f)$, we can find the inverse of $g(x)$ (when it exists) by employing the Extended Euclidean Algorithm for polynomials.

3. When Does a Euclidean Algorithm Exist?

Definition (Euclidean Norm): A *Euclidean norm* on an integral domain R is a function

$$N : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$$

satisfying the following conditions:

1. **Division with smaller remainder:** For all $a, b \in R$ with $b \neq 0$, there exist $q, r \in R$ such that

$$a = bq + r \quad \text{with either } r = 0 \text{ or } N(r) < N(b).$$

2. **Multiplicative condition:** For all $a, b \in R$ with $ab \neq 0$,

$$N(a) \leq N(ab).$$

4. Examples of Euclidean Norms

- \mathbb{Z} :

$$N(a) = |a|.$$

- $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ (or more generally $F[x]$ for a field F):

$$N(f) = \deg(f).$$

5. Definition of a Euclidean Domain

Definition: A *Euclidean domain* R is an integral domain that is equipped with a Euclidean norm

$$N : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0},$$

making the division algorithm (with strictly smaller remainder) possible.

Fact: Every Euclidean domain is a Principal Ideal Domain (PID). (This fact was proven on Monday in class.)

Warning: Not every PID is a Euclidean domain.

- **Counterexample:**

$$\mathbb{Z}\left[\frac{1+\sqrt{-7}}{2}\right] = \left\{ a + b \frac{1+\sqrt{-7}}{2} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}$$

is a principal ideal domain but is *not* Euclidean for any known norm.

Lecture 02/24

1. Basic Properties to Know

Let I be an ideal of a ring R .

- I is **prime** $\iff R/I$ is an integral domain.
- I is **maximal** $\iff R/I$ is a field.

2. Euclidean Domains

Let R be an integral domain.

2.1 Euclidean Norm

A **Euclidean norm** on R is a function

$$N : R \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$$

such that for all $a, b \in R$ with $b \neq 0$:

1. **Division Algorithm Holds:** Given $a, b \in R$, there exist $q, r \in R$ such that

$$a = bq + r \quad \text{and} \quad N(r) < N(b).$$

2. $N(a) \leq N(ab)$. Moreover, if equality holds, then b is a unit (in many standard Euclidean domains, this property helps identify when we have a “remainder” of zero).

2.2 Euclidean Domains: Definition

A ring R is called a **Euclidean domain** if R is an integral domain that possesses a Euclidean norm N .

2.3 Examples of Euclidean Domains

- \mathbb{Z} , with Euclidean norm

$$N(a) = |a|.$$

- $F[x]$, the polynomial ring over a field F , with Euclidean norm

$$N(f(x)) = \deg(f).$$

- $\mathbb{Z}[i] = \{a + bi : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = -1\}$, the **Gaussian integers**. The norm is given by

$$N(a + bi) = a^2 + b^2.$$

- $\mathbb{Z}[\omega] = \{a + b\omega : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, where $\omega = \frac{-1 + i\sqrt{3}}{2}$ is a primitive cube root of unity (so $\omega^3 = 1$). The corresponding norm is typically

$$N(a + b\omega) = (a + b\omega)\overline{(a + b\omega)}$$

in an appropriately chosen form, though details vary with the specific embedding in \mathbb{C} . In practice, one computes something analogous to $a^2 - ab + b^2$.

3. Proposition: Every Euclidean Domain is a Principal Ideal Domain

Statement:

If R is a Euclidean domain, then every ideal $I \subseteq R$ is principal. In other words, $I = (a)$ for some $a \in R$.

3.1 Proof Overview

To prove R is a principal ideal domain (PID), we need to show that every nonzero ideal $I \subseteq R$ can be generated by a single element. That is,

$$I \neq \{0\} \implies \exists a \in R \text{ such that } I = (a).$$

3.2 Detailed Proof Using the Euclidean Algorithm

1. Nonzero Ideal and Norms:

Let I be a nonzero ideal in our Euclidean domain R . Since I is nonzero, there exists some nonzero element $x \in I$. Consider the set of norms:

$$S = \{N(a) : a \in I, a \neq 0\} \subseteq \mathbb{N}.$$

Because $I \neq \{0\}$, S is nonempty. By the well-ordering principle of the natural numbers, S has a least element. Let

$$s = \min S,$$

and let $b \in I$ be such that $N(b) = s$.

2. Minimality Argument:

We claim that $I = (b)$. Take an arbitrary element $a \in I$. By the division property of the Euclidean norm, there exist $q, r \in R$ such that

$$a = bq + r, \quad \text{with } N(r) < N(b).$$

Observe that $r = a - bq$. Since a and b are both in I and I is an ideal, the combination

$$r = a - bq$$

must also lie in I .

Now, if $r \neq 0$, then $N(r) < N(b)$. But $N(b) = s$ was the minimal norm of any nonzero element in I . This contradicts the fact that s is the smallest element of S . Therefore, we must have

$$r = 0.$$

Hence,

$$a = bq \in (b).$$

Since a was an arbitrary element of I , this proves

$$I \subseteq (b).$$

Clearly $(b) \subseteq I$ because $b \in I$ and I is an ideal. Thus

$$I = (b),$$

completing the proof that I is principal.

3.3 Consequence: (GCD Interpretation for Finitely Generated Ideals)

In many Euclidean domains (like \mathbb{Z} or $F[x]$), one often writes the ideal generated by multiple elements as

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = (\gcd(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)).$$

In \mathbb{Z} , for instance, the greatest common divisor of finitely many integers generates the same ideal they do.

3.4 Example

Consider the ideal

$$(12, 72, 18, 30) \subseteq \mathbb{Z}.$$

We factor each:

$$12 = 2^2 \cdot 3, \quad 72 = 2^3 \cdot 3^2, \quad 18 = 2 \cdot 3^2, \quad 30 = 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5.$$

One finds $\gcd(12, 72, 18, 30) = 6$. Thus,

$$(12, 72, 18, 30) = (6).$$

An explicit integer combination yielding 6 is:

$$30 \cdot 1 + 12 \cdot (-2) = 6.$$

Hence 6 generates the ideal.

4. Axiom of Choice and Well-Ordering Principle

A subtle point often invoked in such arguments is the ability to pick a minimal element from a nonempty set of natural numbers. In fact, the principle that *every nonempty subset of the natural numbers has a least element* is often referred to as the **well-ordering principle**.

- **Axiom of Choice:** In more complicated scenarios (especially with large or infinite sets), one must use the Axiom of Choice to guarantee the selection of specific elements.
- **Banach–Tarski Paradox:** Illustrates the counterintuitive implications of the Axiom of Choice in decomposing and reassembling sets in non-measurable ways.

In the specific case of Euclidean domains, we typically only need the well-ordering principle of \mathbb{N} rather than the full strength of the Axiom of Choice.

5. Conclusion

Thus, we have:

Every Euclidean domain is a principal ideal domain.

The proof relies crucially on the existence of a Euclidean norm (to perform the division and remainder argument) and the well-ordering principle (to identify a smallest nonzero norm in any ideal). **Additional Examples:**

- $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ with $N(a + bi) = a^2 + b^2$.
- $\mathbb{Z}[\omega]$ where $\omega^3 = 1$ and $\omega \neq 1$.

These rings admit norms that allow one to perform a division algorithm similar to that in \mathbb{Z} , ensuring that any ideal must collapse to a principal one.

Lecture 02/26

1. Maximal Ideals and Fields

Statement. Let R be a commutative ring with unity and let $I \subseteq R$ be an ideal. Then

$$I \text{ is maximal} \iff R/I \text{ is a field.}$$

Facts

- **Fact 1.** The only ideals in a field F are (0) and F itself.
- **Fact 2.** If $1 \in I$, then $I = R$.
- **Fact 3.** If $u \in I$ is a unit (i.e., invertible in R), then $I = R$.

Proof of the Theorem

\Rightarrow (Maximality implies the quotient is a field)

Claim. If I is maximal, then for any nonzero element $x + I \in R/I$, there exists a multiplicative inverse in R/I .

Reasoning.

1. Suppose I is a maximal ideal in R .
2. We want to show that every nonzero class $x + I$ in the quotient R/I has a multiplicative inverse, making R/I into a field.
3. By “nonzero element” we mean $x \notin I$.
4. Consider the ideal $(x) + I$. Notice that

$$I \subseteq (x) + I \subseteq R.$$

Since I is maximal, this containment implies

$$(x) + I = I \quad \text{or} \quad (x) + I = R.$$

5. Because $x \notin I$, the first option $(x) + I = I$ would force $x \in I$, a contradiction. Therefore,

$$(x) + I = R.$$

6. Hence, there exist $a \in R$ and $b \in I$ such that

$$ax + b = 1.$$

7. Reducing modulo I , this becomes

$$ax \equiv 1 \pmod{I}.$$

Thus,

$$(x + I)(a + I) = xa + I = 1 + I$$

in R/I . This shows $a + I$ is the multiplicative inverse of $x + I$.

Conclusion: Every nonzero element of R/I is invertible. Therefore, R/I is a field.

\Leftarrow (The quotient is a field implies maximality)

Claim. If R/I is a field, then I is maximal.

Reasoning.

1. Suppose R/I is a field. We want to show that there are no strictly larger ideals containing I . In other words, if

$$I \subseteq J \subseteq R,$$

then either $J = I$ or $J = R$.

2. Assume, for contradiction, that $I \subset J$ and $J \neq R$. Then there exists an element $x \in J$ such that $x \notin I$.
3. Since $x + I$ is a nonzero element of the field R/I , it has an inverse, say $(x^{-1} + I)$, in R/I . Hence,

$$(x + I)(x^{-1} + I) = 1 + I \implies xx^{-1} + I = 1 + I.$$

4. Thus, there is some $a \in I$ such that

$$xx^{-1} + a = 1.$$

5. Notice $xx^{-1} \in J$ and $a \in I \subseteq J$, so $1 \in J$. Therefore, if $1 \in J$, we must have $J = R$ (since any ideal containing 1 is the whole ring).
6. This contradicts the assumption that $J \neq R$. Hence, our assumption $I \subset J \neq R$ is false.
7. We conclude: if $I \subseteq J \subseteq R$, then $J = I$ or $J = R$. This is exactly the definition of I being maximal.

Thus, I is maximal if and only if R/I is a field.

2. Maximality of the Ideal (x, y) in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$

Claim. The ideal $(x, y) \subseteq \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is a maximal ideal.

Proof.

1. Consider the ring homomorphism

$$\varphi : \mathbb{Q}[x, y] \longrightarrow \mathbb{Q},$$

defined by

$$\varphi(f(x, y)) = f(0, 0).$$

2. φ is clearly surjective: for any constant $c \in \mathbb{Q}$, we have $\varphi(c) = c$.

3. We claim that

$$\ker(\varphi) = (x, y).$$

4. First, note any element of the form $x p(x, y) + y q(x, y)$ is mapped to 0 by φ , so

$$(x, y) \subseteq \ker(\varphi).$$

5. Conversely, suppose $f(x, y) \in \ker(\varphi)$. Then $f(0, 0) = 0$. If we write

$$f(x, y) = c + x p(x, y) + y q(x, y),$$

where c is the constant term of f , we get $c = f(0, 0) = 0$. Thus $f(x, y) \in (x, y)$. Hence

$$\ker(\varphi) = (x, y).$$

6. By the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\mathbb{Q}[x, y] / \ker(\varphi) \cong \text{Im}(\varphi) \cong \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since \mathbb{Q} is a field, this shows

$$\mathbb{Q}[x, y] / (x, y) \cong \mathbb{Q}$$

is a field.

7. Therefore, by the previous theorem (I is maximal $\iff R/I$ is a field), the ideal (x, y) in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is maximal.

(x, y) is a maximal ideal in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$.

3. Brief Notes on Computing gcd for Polynomials

To compute $\gcd(a, b)$ in a ring such as $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ or $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, one typically uses the *polynomial Euclidean algorithm*:

$$f(x) = q_1(x) g(x) + r_1(x),$$

$$g(x) = q_2(x) r_1(x) + r_2(x),$$

$$r_1(x) = q_3(x) r_2(x) + r_3(x),$$

and so on, until a remainder of zero is reached. The last nonzero remainder is the greatest common divisor (up to a multiplicative constant).

Example of Polynomial Division

We want to perform the polynomial division

$$\frac{2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1}{x - \frac{1}{2}}.$$

I. Long Division

Step 1. Setup the division.

$$\underbrace{2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1}_{\text{Dividend}} \div \underbrace{\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)}_{\text{Divisor}}.$$

Step 2. Divide the first term.

$$\frac{2x^3}{x} = 2x^2.$$

Multiply the divisor by $2x^2$:

$$2x^2 \cdot \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) = 2x^3 - x^2.$$

Subtract this product from the original polynomial:

$$\begin{aligned} & (2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1) - (2x^3 - x^2) \\ \implies & \underbrace{2x^3 - 2x^3}_0 + \underbrace{3x^2 - (-x^2)}_{3x^2 + x^2 = 4x^2} + 3x + 1 \\ & = 4x^2 + 3x + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. Divide the next term.

$$\frac{4x^2}{x} = 4x.$$

Multiply the divisor by $4x$:

$$4x \cdot \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) = 4x^2 - 2x.$$

Subtract:

$$(4x^2 + 3x + 1) - (4x^2 - 2x) = \underbrace{4x^2 - 4x^2}_0 + \underbrace{3x - (-2x)}_{3x + 2x = 5x} + 1 = 5x + 1.$$

Step 4. Divide the next term.

$$\frac{5x}{x} = 5.$$

Multiply the divisor by 5:

$$5 \cdot \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) = 5x - \frac{5}{2}.$$

Subtract:

$$(5x + 1) - (5x - \frac{5}{2}) = \underbrace{5x - 5x}_0 + (1 - (-\frac{5}{2})) = 1 + \frac{5}{2} = \frac{7}{2}.$$

Hence, the remainder is $\frac{7}{2}$.

Conclusion (from Long Division):

$$\frac{2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1}{x - \frac{1}{2}} = 2x^2 + 4x + 5 + \frac{\frac{7}{2}}{x - \frac{1}{2}}.$$

Or more neatly:

$$\boxed{2x^2 + 4x + 5 + \frac{7}{2(x - \frac{1}{2})}}.$$

II. Synthetic Division

We can also perform the same division using *synthetic division*. Recall that to divide by $x - r$, we synthetically divide by the constant r . Here, $r = \frac{1}{2}$.

1. Bring down the first coefficient (2) as is.

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 2 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & & \downarrow & & \\ \hline & 2 & & & \end{array}$$

2. Multiply this 2 by $\frac{1}{2}$ to get 1. Write this value under the next coefficient (3), then add:

$$\begin{array}{r} 3 + 1 = 4. \\ \begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 2 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & & 1 & & \\ \hline & 2 & 4 & & \end{array} \end{array}$$

3. Multiply the new value (4) by $\frac{1}{2}$ to get 2. Place this under the next coefficient (3), then add:

$$\begin{array}{r} 3 + 2 = 5. \\ \begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 2 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & & 1 & 2 & \\ \hline & 2 & 4 & 5 & \end{array} \end{array}$$

4. Multiply the new value (5) by $\frac{1}{2}$ to get 2.5. Write this under the last coefficient (1), then add:

$$\begin{array}{r} 1 + 2.5 = 3.5 = \frac{7}{2}. \\ \begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 2 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & & 1 & 2 & 2.5 \\ \hline & 2 & 4 & 5 & 3.5 \end{array} \end{array}$$

From the final row, the first three numbers 2, 4, 5 give the quotient polynomial's coefficients (in descending powers of x):

$$2x^2 + 4x + 5,$$

and the last number $3.5 = \frac{7}{2}$ is the remainder.

Example 2. Factorization Approach

Sometimes to understand the gcd or further factorizations, one might factor polynomials:

$$(2x^2 + 3x + 3)(x^2 + x + 1),$$

or similar expressions, to determine common divisors. The details vary with each specific example.

Lecture 03/05

Galois basically invented group theory.

“Insolubility of the Quintic”: Galois showed that no general algebraic formula (in terms of radicals) can exist for the solutions of a polynomial equation of degree 5 or higher, under certain conditions. In other words, there is no analog of the quadratic formula for the generic quintic.

For quadratics, we have a formula:

$$ax^2 + bx + c = 0 \implies x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}.$$

For cubics and quartics: There are also known formulas (albeit more complicated). However, for the general quintic, Galois’ result states no such closed-form (radical) formula exists.

Field Extensions

Definition: We say that E is a *field extension* of F (or write E/F) if:

- E and F are fields,
- and $F \subseteq E$ (in a manner respecting the same operations).

$$F \subseteq E.$$

Examples

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathbb{C} \\ \text{II} \\ \mathbb{R} \\ \text{II} \\ \mathbb{Q} \end{array}$$

Since

$$\mathbb{Q} \subseteq \mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C},$$

they share the same addition and multiplication (extended in the obvious way from \mathbb{Q} to \mathbb{R} to \mathbb{C}).

Example: $\mathbb{Q}(i)$

We define

$$\mathbb{Q}(i) = \{a + bi \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\}, \quad \text{where } i^2 = -1.$$

This is the *smallest field* containing both \mathbb{Q} and the element i .

To show it is a field: We must show it is closed under addition, subtraction, multiplication, and also that every nonzero element has a multiplicative inverse in $\mathbb{Q}(i)$.

Scratch Work:

$$\frac{1}{a+bi} \cdot \frac{a-bi}{a-bi} = \frac{a-bi}{a^2-b^2i^2}.$$

Since $i^2 = -1$, we get

$$a^2 - b^2i^2 = a^2 - b^2(-1) = a^2 + b^2.$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{a-bi}{a^2+b^2} = \left(\frac{a}{a^2+b^2} \right) + \left(\frac{-b}{a^2+b^2} \right) i.$$

Since $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}$, each coefficient $\frac{a}{a^2+b^2}$ and $\frac{-b}{a^2+b^2}$ lies in \mathbb{Q} . Therefore

$$\frac{1}{a+bi} \in \mathbb{Q}(i),$$

showing that every nonzero element has an inverse in $\mathbb{Q}(i)$.

Note: Taking $b = 0$ recovers \mathbb{Q} itself (since $a + 0 \cdot i = a \in \mathbb{Q}$).

Irreducibility viewpoint: The polynomial

$$x^2 + 1$$

is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , but in $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ it factors as

$$x^2 + 1 = (x+i)(x-i).$$

Therefore $x^2 + 1$ *splits* over $\mathbb{Q}(i)$.

Example: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$

Define

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\}.$$

Again, this is the smallest field containing \mathbb{Q} and $\sqrt{2}$.

Is this a field? Yes. We check inverses similarly:

$$\frac{1}{a+b\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{a-b\sqrt{2}}{a-b\sqrt{2}} = \frac{a-b\sqrt{2}}{a^2-2b^2}.$$

Observe that:

$$a^2 - (b^2)2 = a^2 - 2b^2.$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{a-b\sqrt{2}}{a^2-2b^2} = \left(\frac{a}{a^2-2b^2} \right) + \left(\frac{-b}{a^2-2b^2} \right) \sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}).$$

So every nonzero element has a multiplicative inverse in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$.

Graphically:

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}.$$

The polynomial

$$f(x) = x^2 - 2$$

is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} but factors over $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$ as

$$x^2 - 2 = (x - \sqrt{2})(x + \sqrt{2}).$$

Example: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$

Scratch Work:

$$(a + b^3\sqrt{2})(c + d^3\sqrt{2}) = ac + (ad + bc)^3\sqrt{2} + bd^3\sqrt{4}.$$

Define

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) = \left\{ a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c\sqrt[3]{4} \mid a, b, c \in \mathbb{Q} \right\}.$$

Here, $\sqrt[3]{2}$ is a root of the polynomial

$$x^3 - 2.$$

This polynomial is degree 3, so one expects a \mathbb{Q} -basis $\{1, \sqrt[3]{2}, \sqrt[3]{4}\}$.

Note that $(\sqrt[3]{2})^2 = \sqrt[3]{4}$, which is not in \mathbb{Q} alone.

Closure under multiplication:

$$(a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c\sqrt[3]{4}) \cdot (d + e\sqrt[3]{2} + f\sqrt[3]{4})$$

expands (grouping like terms in powers of $\sqrt[3]{2}$) to:

$$= \underbrace{(ad + 2ce + 2bf)}_{\text{coefficient of 1}} + \underbrace{(2cf + bd + ae)}_{\text{coefficient of } \sqrt[3]{2}} \sqrt[3]{2} + \underbrace{(be + af + cd)}_{\text{coefficient of } \sqrt[3]{4}} \sqrt[3]{4}.$$

Each of these coefficients lies in \mathbb{Q} whenever $a, b, c, d, e, f \in \mathbb{Q}$. So it stays in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$.

Inverse: Finding the inverse in a cubic extension is more involved, typically requiring one to solve a system (or use the extended Euclidean approach on polynomials). Symbolically, we would need

$$\frac{1}{a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c\sqrt[3]{4}} = \alpha + \beta\sqrt[3]{2} + \gamma\sqrt[3]{4}$$

and solve for $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$. This can be done, but it is less straightforward than the quadratic case.

Fact:

$$x^3 - 2$$

is reducible over $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$, but it does **not** split into linear factors in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$. In fact, over $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ we can factor:

$$x^3 - 2 = (x - \sqrt[3]{2})(x^2 + bx + c),$$

for some $b, c \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$, but the quadratic factor remains irreducible there.

Example: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$

We can form a larger extension by adjoining both $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$ to \mathbb{Q} . Namely,

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \left\{ a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q} \right\}.$$

Note that $\sqrt{6} = \sqrt{2}\sqrt{3}$ also appears. A similar argument to the previous cases shows this set is closed under addition, multiplication, and possesses inverses (by multiplying by a suitable “conjugate”).

Field Inclusion Diagram

Group Diagram

Foreshadowing: This equivalence of diagrams (the “field tower” vs. the “group lattice”) is no coincidence. Galois theory precisely establishes a correspondence between subfields of certain field extensions and subgroups of their automorphism group.

Consider: An automorphism

$$\sigma : \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) \longrightarrow \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$$

that fixes \mathbb{Q} pointwise. We can define σ by its action on the generators $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$. For instance:

$$\sigma(\sqrt{2}) = -\sqrt{2}, \quad \sigma(\sqrt{3}) = \sqrt{3}.$$

Then

$$\sigma(\sqrt{6}) = \sigma(\sqrt{2}\sqrt{3}) = \sigma(\sqrt{2})\sigma(\sqrt{3}) = (-\sqrt{2})(\sqrt{3}) = -\sqrt{6}.$$

Consequently, for any

$$a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6} \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}),$$

we get

$$\sigma(a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6}) = a - b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} - d\sqrt{6}.$$

Such maps σ are fundamental in studying field extensions and lead to the notion of Galois groups.

Lecture 03/07

Field Extensions: Bases, Degrees, and Minimal Polynomials

We looked at many field extensions over \mathbb{Q} . Some key examples:

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\},$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}\},$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(i) = \{a + bi \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\}, \quad i^2 = -1,$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) = \{a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c\sqrt[3]{4} \mid a, b, c \in \mathbb{Q}\}.$$

All of these are \mathbb{Q} -vector spaces.

Basic Facts

- **Fact 1:** Every finite-dimensional vector space has a basis.
- **Fact 2:** Every basis of a given finite-dimensional vector space has the same number of elements. This common number is called the *dimension* of the vector space.

Definition:

If V is a \mathbb{Q} -vector space with basis $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$, then we write

$$V = \mathbb{Q}\langle e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \rangle.$$

Bases for Some Favorite Field Extensions

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) = \mathbb{Q}\langle 1, \sqrt{2} \rangle,$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}\langle 1, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}, \sqrt{6} \rangle,$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) = \mathbb{Q}\langle 1, \sqrt[3]{2}, \sqrt[3]{4} \rangle,$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(i) = \mathbb{Q}\langle 1, i \rangle.$$

Degree of a Field Extension

The degree of a field extension E/F is the dimension of E as an F -vector space:

$$[E : F] = \dim_F(E).$$

In particular, when $F = \mathbb{Q}$,

$$[E : \mathbb{Q}] = \dim_{\mathbb{Q}}(E).$$

Types of Extensions: Algebraic vs. Transcendental

Algebraic Extensions

A field extension E/F is called **algebraic** if every element $x \in E$ is a root of some polynomial $f(x)$ with coefficients in $F[x]$.

All of the examples above are algebraic. Concretely, an element $x \in E$ is **algebraic** over F if there is a polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(x) = 0$.

- **Example:** $\sqrt[3]{2}$ is algebraic over \mathbb{Q} because it satisfies

$$x^3 - 2 = 0 \quad (\text{where } x = \sqrt[3]{2}).$$

Transcendental Extensions

An element e is **not algebraic** (i.e., there is no nonzero polynomial over F having e as a root) is called *transcendental*. If E/F contains a transcendental element, the field extension is called a **transcendental extension**.

- \mathbb{R} is not algebraic over \mathbb{Q} because, for instance, π and e are transcendental over \mathbb{Q} .

Examples of Simple, Algebraic, Finite Extensions

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}), \quad \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}), \quad \mathbb{Q}(i).$$

Each of these has the form $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ for a single algebraic element α , and each is finite-dimensional over \mathbb{Q} .

$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$ is Simple!

It turns out that

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}).$$

Hint (from the homework): Show that $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$ are each in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$. One strategy is to manipulate powers:

$$(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^2 = 2 + 3 + 2\sqrt{6} = 5 + 2\sqrt{6},$$

$$(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^3 = (\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})(5 + 2\sqrt{6}).$$

Compute that product carefully:

$$(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})(5 + 2\sqrt{6}) = \underbrace{5\sqrt{2}}_{\text{first term}} + \underbrace{5\sqrt{3}}_{\text{second term}} + \underbrace{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{6}}_{\text{third term}} + \underbrace{2\sqrt{3}\sqrt{6}}_{\text{fourth term}}.$$

Notice

$$\sqrt{2}\sqrt{6} = \sqrt{12} = 2\sqrt{3}, \quad \sqrt{3}\sqrt{6} = \sqrt{18} = 3\sqrt{2}.$$

Therefore,

$$5\sqrt{2} + 5\sqrt{3} + 2(2\sqrt{3}) + 2(3\sqrt{2}) = 5\sqrt{2} + 5\sqrt{3} + 4\sqrt{3} + 6\sqrt{2} = (5+6)\sqrt{2} + (5+4)\sqrt{3} = 11\sqrt{2} + 9\sqrt{3}.$$

So

$$(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^3 = 11\sqrt{2} + 9\sqrt{3}.$$

Now consider

$$\frac{(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^3 - 9(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})}{2}.$$

Substitute the expression you found for $(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^3$:

$$\frac{(11\sqrt{2} + 9\sqrt{3}) - 9(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})}{2} = \frac{11\sqrt{2} + 9\sqrt{3} - 9\sqrt{2} - 9\sqrt{3}}{2} = \frac{(11\sqrt{2} - 9\sqrt{2}) + (9\sqrt{3} - 9\sqrt{3})}{2} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{2} = \sqrt{2}.$$

Thus $\sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$. A similar argument (or symmetry) shows $\sqrt{3} \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$. Therefore $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$.

Why Do We Care About Field Extensions?

Given a polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$, we want to know where the roots of f lie. Concretely, we may look for a field extension E/F in which

$$f(x) = a(x - r_1)(x - r_2) \cdots (x - r_n),$$

with $a \in F$ and $r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n \in E$. In other words, is there some field E over F in which f splits *completely* into linear factors?

Key Fact

Fact: Let $f(x) \in F[x]$. Then, there *always* exists a field extension E/F such that E contains a root of f . That is, there is some $\alpha \in E$ with $f(\alpha) = 0$. **Proof (Sketch):** We may assume f is *monic and irreducible* in $F[x]$. Consider the quotient ring

$$F[x]/(f).$$

In this quotient, the image of x (denoted \bar{x}) satisfies $f(\bar{x}) = 0$. Since f is irreducible and F is a field, the quotient $F[x]/(f)$ is itself a field. Therefore it is a valid extension field of F , and $\bar{x} \in F[x]/(f)$ is a root of f in that field. ■

Definition: Minimal Polynomial

The **minimal polynomial** of an element $\alpha \in E$ over F is the unique monic irreducible polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(\alpha) = 0$.

Example: Finding the Minimal Polynomial of $\sqrt[3]{2}$

Set $x = \sqrt[3]{2}$. Then clearly $x^3 = 2$. Therefore

$$x^3 - 2 = 0.$$

We claim that $x^3 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . By Eisenstein's Criterion at $p = 2$, $x^3 - 2$ has no nontrivial factors in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. Therefore,

$$x^3 - 2$$

is the minimal polynomial for $\sqrt[3]{2}$. **Interpretation:** We can think of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ as

$$\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^3 - 2),$$

where x maps to $\sqrt[3]{2}$.

Example: Finding the Minimal Polynomial of $\zeta = \frac{-1 + i\sqrt{3}}{2}$

Let

$$x = \frac{-1 + i\sqrt{3}}{2}.$$

We notice that $2x + 1 = i\sqrt{3}$. Squaring both sides gives:

$$(2x + 1)^2 = -3.$$

Expand the left-hand side:

$$(2x + 1)^2 = 4x^2 + 4x + 1.$$

Thus,

$$4x^2 + 4x + 1 = -3.$$

Rearrange:

$$4x^2 + 4x + 1 + 3 = 0 \implies 4x^2 + 4x + 4 = 0 \implies x^2 + x + 1 = 0.$$

Therefore ζ satisfies $x^2 + x + 1 = 0$. Over \mathbb{Q} , the polynomial $x^2 + x + 1$ is irreducible (it has no rational roots). Therefore

$$x^2 + x + 1$$

is the minimal polynomial for ζ .

- Also note that $\zeta^3 = 1$. Indeed, ζ is a (non-real) cube root of unity, so ζ is a root of $x^3 - 1$. But $x^3 - 1$ factors as

$$x^3 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^2 + x + 1).$$

Thus the irreducible factor over \mathbb{Q} giving ζ is $x^2 + x + 1$.

Relating Minimal Polynomials to Extension Degrees

In every example above, the degree of the minimal polynomial $\deg(f)$ of an element α over F matched the degree $[F(\alpha) : F]$ of the field extension. For instance:

$$\deg(x^3 - 2) = 3 \quad \text{and} \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 3.$$

$$\deg(x^2 + x + 1) = 2 \quad \text{and} \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\zeta) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2.$$

This is *not* a coincidence. In fact, one proves that if f is the minimal polynomial of α , then

$$[F(\alpha) : F] = \deg(f).$$

One way to see why is to observe that in the construction $F[x]/(f)$, the images of

$$1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}$$

(where $n = \deg(f)$) naturally form a basis for the quotient viewed as an F -vector space.

Claim (Basis in the Quotient): If f is a monic irreducible polynomial of degree n in $F[x]$, then in the field

$$F[x]/(f),$$

the images of

$$1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}$$

span the entire field (as an F -vector space) and are linearly independent. Consequently, these images form an F -basis, so

$$\dim_F(F[x]/(f)) = n.$$

This matches the degree of the polynomial f , which in turn is the degree of the extension $[F(\alpha) : F]$.

Lecture 03/10

Quotient Rings, Field Extensions, and Automorphisms

Irreducible Monic Polynomials and Bases of Quotient Rings

Statement. Let $f \in F[x]$ be an irreducible monic polynomial of degree n . Then

$$\{1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}\}$$

is a basis of the quotient ring $F[x]/(f)$ considered as an F -vector space. In particular,

$$[F[x]/(f) : F] = n = \deg(f).$$

Proof. First, recall that

$$\{1, x, x^2, x^3, \dots\}$$

forms a basis of $F[x]$ as an F -vector space (there are no relations among these powers in the polynomial ring itself).

In the quotient ring $F[x]/(f)$, let $\deg(f) = n$. Then

$$f(x) = x^n + a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1x + a_0 = 0 \quad \text{in } F[x]/(f).$$

Therefore, in $F[x]/(f)$ we have

$$x^n = -a_{n-1}x^{n-1} - \dots - a_1x - a_0.$$

This immediately implies that any power x^k with $k \geq n$ can be written as an F -linear combination of lower powers $1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}$. Consequently,

$$\{1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}\}$$

spans $F[x]/(f)$ as a vector space over F .

Brief example of substitution in the quotient:

Suppose $f(x) = x^2 + x + 1$. Then, in the ring $F[x]/(f)$,

$$x^2 = -x - 1.$$

Therefore, for instance:

$$2x^2 + 2x + 4 = 2(-x - 1) + 2x + 4 = 2(-x) + 2(-1) + 2x + 4 = -2x - 2 + 2x + 4 = 2.$$

This demonstrates how a higher power of x (like x^2) can be rewritten in terms of lower powers.

Linear independence: Next, assume for the sake of contradiction that

$$c_0 + c_1x + \cdots + c_{n-1}x^{n-1} = 0 \quad \text{in } F[x]/(f),$$

for some coefficients $c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{n-1} \in F$, not all zero. This means

$$g(x) = c_0 + c_1x + \cdots + c_{n-1}x^{n-1}$$

belongs to the ideal (f) . So there exists a polynomial $p(x) \in F[x]$ such that

$$g(x) = f(x)p(x).$$

But we observe

$$\deg(g) \leq n-1, \quad \text{while} \quad \deg(f(x)p(x)) = \deg(f) + \deg(p) \geq n,$$

unless g is the zero polynomial. The only way for $\deg(g) \leq n-1$ to equal $\deg(f) + \deg(p)$ (which is at least n) is if g itself is the zero polynomial in $F[x]$. Therefore all c_i must be zero, contradicting our assumption. Therefore, $\{1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}\}$ is also linearly independent.

Therefore, $\{1, x, \dots, x^{n-1}\}$ is an F -basis of $F[x]/(f)$.

Fact. Let $F(\alpha)/F$ be a simple extension, and let f be the minimal polynomial of α . Then there is an isomorphism

$$F(\alpha) \cong F[x]/(f).$$

In particular, if α has minimal polynomial of degree n , then the extension $F(\alpha)/F$ has degree n .

Example: Consider the field extension $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$. The minimal polynomial of $\sqrt[3]{2}$ over \mathbb{Q} is

$$x^3 - 2.$$

So $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ is isomorphic to $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^3 - 2)$. Concretely, in the extension we have

$$x^3 = 2,$$

and the basis for this extension over \mathbb{Q} is

$$\{1, x, x^2\}.$$

Therefore every element of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ can be written uniquely as

$$a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c\sqrt[3]{4} \quad \text{with } a, b, c \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Another example in the quotient ring:

In $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^3 - 2)$, note that $x^3 = 2$. So for a polynomial like

$$x^4 + x^3 + 5x + 2,$$

we rewrite x^4 as $x \cdot x^3 = x \cdot 2 = 2x$. So

$$x^4 + x^3 + 5x + 2 = (2x) + 2 + 5x + 2 = 7x + 4.$$

Normal Field Extensions

A field extension E/F is called **normal** if for any polynomial $f \in F[x]$ that has at least one root in E , the polynomial f splits completely into linear factors over E . In other words, if f has one root in E , then all roots of f lie in E .

Example: The extension $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})/\mathbb{Q}$ is normal. Indeed,

$$x^2 - 2$$

is the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt{2}$. Over $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$, it factors as

$$x^2 - 2 = (x - \sqrt{2})(x + \sqrt{2}),$$

and both roots $\pm\sqrt{2}$ lie in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$. Therefore if this extension contains one root ($\sqrt{2}$), it also contains the other.

A non-normal example: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})/\mathbb{Q}$. The minimal polynomial $x^3 - 2$ has three complex roots:

$$\sqrt[3]{2}, \quad \zeta\sqrt[3]{2}, \quad \zeta^2\sqrt[3]{2},$$

where $\zeta = \frac{-1+i\sqrt{3}}{2}$ is a primitive cube root of unity (so $\zeta^3 = 1$, $\zeta \notin \mathbb{R}$). The field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ contains the real root $\sqrt[3]{2}$ but *does not* contain $\zeta\sqrt[3]{2}$ nor $\zeta^2\sqrt[3]{2}$. Therefore, $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$ is not a normal extension of \mathbb{Q} .

Summary of the roots of unity: The solutions to

$$x^n = 1$$

in \mathbb{C} are

$$e^{\frac{2\pi ik}{n}}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1.$$

For $n = 3$,

$$x^3 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^2 + x + 1),$$

and the (non-real) cube roots of unity are precisely the roots of $x^2 + x + 1$. We often set

$$\zeta = \frac{-1 + i\sqrt{3}}{2}, \quad \zeta^2 = \frac{-1 - i\sqrt{3}}{2},$$

so that $\zeta^3 = 1$. These appear on the unit circle at angles 120° and 240° :

Field Automorphisms

Definition. A *field homomorphism* $\varphi : F \rightarrow F'$ (where F and F' are fields) is a ring homomorphism that sends $1 \mapsto 1$. Equivalently, for all $x, y \in F$,

$$\varphi(x + y) = \varphi(x) + \varphi(y), \quad \varphi(xy) = \varphi(x)\varphi(y), \quad \varphi(1) = 1.$$

A field homomorphism $\varphi : F \rightarrow F$ (i.e. from a field to itself) that is bijective is called a **field automorphism**. We denote by

$$\text{Aut}(F)$$

the set of all field automorphisms of F . This set is a group under composition.

$\text{Aut}(E/F)$ is the subset of automorphisms $\varphi \in \text{Aut}(E)$ that fix every element of F . In symbols,

$$\varphi(a) = a, \quad \text{for all } a \in F.$$

Example: $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})/\mathbb{Q})$.

Consider $\alpha = \sqrt{2}$. Its minimal polynomial is $x^2 - 2$. Suppose φ is an automorphism of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$ fixing \mathbb{Q} . Then

$$\varphi(x^2 - 2) = \varphi(0) = 0,$$

so

$$\varphi(\sqrt{2})^2 - 2 = 0.$$

Therefore $\varphi(\sqrt{2})$ must be a root of $x^2 - 2$, so $\varphi(\sqrt{2})$ is either $+\sqrt{2}$ or $-\sqrt{2}$. So there are exactly two possibilities:

$$\varphi_1(\sqrt{2}) = \sqrt{2}, \quad \varphi_2(\sqrt{2}) = -\sqrt{2}.$$

Each choice extends uniquely to all elements of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$, since any element of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$ can be written as $a + b\sqrt{2}$.

Concretely: for $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}$,

$$\varphi_1(a + b\sqrt{2}) = a + b\sqrt{2},$$

$$\varphi_2(a + b\sqrt{2}) = a - b\sqrt{2}.$$

So $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})/\mathbb{Q})$ has exactly two elements.

Lecture 03/12

Galois Theory

A Quick Lemma on Tower of Fields

Consider a tower of field extensions

$$\begin{array}{c} E \\ | \\ F \\ | \\ K \end{array} \quad \text{i.e., } K \subseteq F \subseteq E.$$

Then the fundamental relation for degrees of field extensions states:

$$[E : K] = [E : F][F : K].$$

Proof

Let $[E : F] = m$ and $[F : K] = n$. Then there exists an F -basis of E given by

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\},$$

and a K -basis of F given by

$$\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}.$$

Consider now all possible products $a_i b_j$ with $1 \leq i \leq m$ and $1 \leq j \leq n$. That is,

$$\{a_i b_j \mid 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\}.$$

We expand this set (grouping terms to emphasize structure):

$$\underbrace{a_1 b_1, a_1 b_2, \dots, a_1 b_n}_{\text{all with } a_1}, \quad \underbrace{a_2 b_1, a_2 b_2, \dots, a_2 b_n}_{\text{all with } a_2}, \quad \dots, \quad \underbrace{a_m b_1, a_m b_2, \dots, a_m b_n}_{\text{all with } a_m}.$$

This forms a K -basis of E . Thus there are mn basis elements, so $[E : K] = mn = [E : F][F : K]$.

Example: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$

From the diagram, we see

$$[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2, \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2, \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 4.$$

Key Observation for Homework

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}).$$

Indeed, from standard Galois theory arguments (or by constructing the minimal polynomial explicitly), one sees that adjoining $\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$ already allows you to build both $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$.

Minimal Polynomial and Degree over \mathbb{Q}

Let

$$x = \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}.$$

We claim that the minimal polynomial of x over \mathbb{Q} is of degree 4. Let's see why:

Derivation of the Minimal Polynomial

$$x = \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}.$$

First, square both sides:

$$x^2 = (\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^2 = \underbrace{\sqrt{2}^2}_2 + 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{3} + \underbrace{\sqrt{3}^2}_3 = 2 + 3 + 2\sqrt{6} = 5 + 2\sqrt{6}.$$

Hence,

$$x^2 - 5 = 2\sqrt{6}.$$

Square again:

$$(x^2 - 5)^2 = (2\sqrt{6})^2 \implies x^4 - 10x^2 + 25 = 24 \implies x^4 - 10x^2 + 1 = 0.$$

Thus the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$ over \mathbb{Q} is

$$\boxed{x^4 - 10x^2 + 1}.$$

Since this is a quartic (degree 4) polynomial and it is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , we see

$$[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 4.$$

Equivalently,

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}), \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 4.$$

Another Look at the Field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$

Elements of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$ can be written in the form

$$a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6},$$

where $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}$. Notice we can also group them as

$$(a + b\sqrt{2}) + (c + d\sqrt{2})\sqrt{3},$$

where $(a + b\sqrt{2})$ and $(c + d\sqrt{2})$ live in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$.

Galois Field Extensions

- A field extension E/F is called **Galois** if it is:

$$\begin{cases} \textit{Normal:} & \text{Every minimal polynomial over } F \text{ of an element of } E \text{ splits completely over } E. \\ \textit{Separable:} & \text{All polynomials over } F \text{ have distinct roots in an algebraic closure.} \end{cases}$$

(Note that over characteristic 0 fields, such as \mathbb{Q} , separability is automatic.)

- The **Galois group** of a Galois extension E/F is the group of F -automorphisms of E :

$$\text{Gal}(E/F) = \{ \sigma : E \rightarrow E \mid \sigma \text{ is an automorphism and } \sigma|_F = \text{id} \}.$$

Calculating the Galois Group: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}$

Since $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$ is generated by two square roots, any automorphism of this field that fixes \mathbb{Q} must send $\sqrt{2}$ to either $+\sqrt{2}$ or $-\sqrt{2}$, and independently send $\sqrt{3}$ to either $+\sqrt{3}$ or $-\sqrt{3}$. This gives exactly four possibilities:

$$\begin{aligned} e &: \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \mapsto +\sqrt{2}, \\ \sqrt{3} \mapsto +\sqrt{3}, \end{cases} \\ \tau &: \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \mapsto -\sqrt{2}, \\ \sqrt{3} \mapsto +\sqrt{3}, \end{cases} \\ \sigma &: \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \mapsto +\sqrt{2}, \\ \sqrt{3} \mapsto -\sqrt{3}, \end{cases} \\ \sigma\tau &: \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \mapsto -\sqrt{2}, \\ \sqrt{3} \mapsto -\sqrt{3}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}) \cong \{e, \tau, \sigma, \sigma\tau\},$$

which is isomorphic to $V_4 \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$. It is an abelian group of order 4. Consistent with the Galois correspondence (for a Galois extension over \mathbb{Q}), we have

$$[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = |\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q})| = 4.$$

Example of Another Extension: $x^3 - 2$

Consider the polynomial $x^3 - 2$ over \mathbb{Q} . Its roots are:

$$\sqrt[3]{2}, \quad \zeta \sqrt[3]{2}, \quad \zeta^2 \sqrt[3]{2},$$

where ζ is a primitive cube root of unity (i.e., $\zeta = e^{2\pi i/3}$).

Splitting Field of $x^3 - 2$

The splitting field is

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta),$$

because we need to adjoin both a real cube root of 2 and a primitive third root of unity to see all three roots. We have:

$$\mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) \subset \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta).$$

Typically, $[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 3$ and $[\mathbb{Q}(\zeta) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2$ (since ζ satisfies $x^2 + x + 1 = 0$). One can show

$$[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta) : \mathbb{Q}] = 6.$$

A diagram (omitting $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)$ alone) might look like:

Galois Group of the Splitting Field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)/\mathbb{Q}$

Since the extension has degree 6 and is Galois, its Galois group has 6 elements. We label the two key pieces:

- An automorphism can send $\sqrt[3]{2}$ to any of the three distinct cube roots of 2:

$$\sqrt[3]{2} \mapsto \zeta^k \sqrt[3]{2}, \quad k \in \{0, 1, 2\}.$$

- An automorphism can send ζ to either ζ or ζ^2 (the two roots of $x^2 + x + 1 = 0$).

We often define two generators for the Galois group:

The Automorphism σ

$$\sigma : \begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{2} \mapsto \zeta \sqrt[3]{2}, \\ \zeta \mapsto \zeta, \end{cases}$$

so σ cycles $\sqrt[3]{2}$ through its three distinct images but fixes ζ .

The Automorphism τ

$$\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[3]{2}, \\ \zeta \mapsto \zeta^2, \end{cases}$$

so τ fixes the real cube root but sends ζ to its other root.

Other Elements

All elements of the group can be viewed as compositions of σ and τ :

$$\{e, \sigma, \sigma^2, \tau, \sigma\tau, \sigma^2\tau\}.$$

One checks the noncommutative relations:

$$\sigma\tau \neq \tau\sigma, \quad \text{and } \sigma^3 = e, \tau^2 = e,$$

giving a group of order 6 isomorphic to the semidirect product $\mathbb{Z}_3 \rtimes \mathbb{Z}_2$ (sometimes called the *metacyclic group of order 6*, isomorphic to S_3 , the symmetric group on 3 letters).

Summary

- In general, for a Galois extension E/F ,

$$[E : F] = |\text{Gal}(E/F)|.$$

- For the example $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}$, the extension is Galois, abelian, and has group V_4 of order 4.
- For the example $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)/\mathbb{Q}$ (the splitting field of $x^3 - 2$), the extension is Galois but nonabelian, and the Galois group is isomorphic to S_3 of order 6.

1. Let R be a ring. Prove the following:

- Suppose further that R has a multiplicative identity, and let $a \in R$. If a has a multiplicative inverse, then it is unique.
- If R has a multiplicative identity, then it is unique.

18.8 Theorem If R is a ring with additive identity 0 , then for any $a, b \in R$ we have

1. $0a = a0 = 0$,
2. $a(-b) = (-a)b = -(ab)$,
3. $(-a)(-b) = ab$.

18.16 Definition Let R be a ring with unity $1 \neq 0$. An element u in R is a **unit** of R if it has a multiplicative inverse in R . If every nonzero element of R is a unit, then R is a **division ring** (or **skew field**). A **field** is a commutative division ring. A noncommutative division ring is called a “**strictly skew field**.” ■

(1) Uniqueness of the multiplicative inverse.

As stated on page 173 in the text, in example 18.15

“A multiplicative inverse of an element a

in a ring R with unity $1 \neq 0$ is an element $a^{-1} \in R$ such that $aa^{-1} = a^{-1}a = 1$. Precisely as for groups, a multiplicative inverse for an element a in R is unique, if it exists at all (see Exercise 43)”.

Assume $b, c \in R$ both satisfy

$$ab = ba = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad ac = ca = 1$$

Then

$$b = b \cdot 1 = b(ac) = (ba)c = 1 \cdot c = c$$

So $b = c \implies$ the multiplicative inverse of a is unique.

Therefore, if a has a multiplicative inverse in R , it is unique.

(2) Uniqueness of the multiplicative identity.

As stated in Section 18, referencing Theorem 3.13:

“Theorem 3.13 shows that if a ring has a multiplicative identity element, it is unique.”

Proof:

Suppose 1_1 and 1_2 are both multiplicative identities in R . Then

$1_1 = 1_1 \cdot 1_2 = 1_2$, which shows $1_1 = 1_2$.

Therefore, the multiplicative identity in R is unique.

2. Consider the ring $R = \mathbb{Z}_{12} := \{\overline{0}, \dots, \overline{11}\}$ under addition and multiplication modulo 12.

- Find two nontrivial subrings of R .
- List all of the zero divisors of R .
- List all of the units of R , and calculate their multiplicative inverses.

(a) Two nontrivial subrings of R .

As stated in Section 18.5:

“A subring $S \leq R$ is a subset closed under addition and multiplication, containing 0, and closed under taking additive inverses.”

In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , standard examples are:

$$2_{12} = \{\overline{0}, \overline{2}, \overline{4}, \overline{6}, \overline{8}, \overline{10}\} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}}_{\text{closed under } +, \cdot \in \mathbb{Z}_{12}}$$

$$3_{12} = \{\overline{0}, \overline{3}, \overline{6}, \overline{9}\} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}}_{\text{closed under } +, \cdot \in \mathbb{Z}_{12}}$$

Each is a nontrivial (proper) subring of \mathbb{Z}_{12}

(b) All zero divisors of R .

(Theorem 19.3): “In the ring \mathbb{Z}_n , the divisors of 0 are the nonzero elements that are not relatively prime to n .”

\implies Compute gcd with 12

- gcd(1, 12) = 1 (rel. prime, not 0 divisor),
- gcd(2, 12) = 2 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{2}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(3, 12) = 3 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{3}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(4, 12) = 4 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{4}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(5, 12) = 1 (not 0 divisor),
- gcd(6, 12) = 6 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{6}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(7, 12) = 1 (not 0 divisor),
- gcd(8, 12) = 4 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{8}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(9, 12) = 3 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{9}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(10, 12) = 2 \neq 1 $\implies \overline{10}$ is a zero divisor,
- gcd(11, 12) = 1 (not 0 divisor).

Therefore the zero divisors (nonzero) are: $\{\overline{2}, \overline{3}, \overline{4}, \overline{6}, \overline{8}, \overline{9}, \overline{10}\}$

18.16 Definition Let R be a ring with unity $1 \neq 0$. An element u in R is a **unit** of R if it has a multiplicative inverse in R . If every nonzero element of R is a unit, then R is a **division ring** (or **skew field**). A **field** is a commutative division ring. A noncommutative division ring is called a “**strictly skew field**.” ■

19.2 Definition If a and b are two nonzero elements of a ring R such that $ab = 0$, then a and b are **divisors of 0** (or **0 divisors**). ■

Example 19.1 shows that in \mathbb{Z}_{12} the elements 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, and 10 are divisors of 0. Note that these are exactly the numbers in \mathbb{Z}_{12} that are not relatively prime to 12, that is, whose gcd with 12 is not 1. Our next theorem shows that this is an example of a general situation.

19.3 Theorem In the ring \mathbb{Z}_n , the divisors of 0 are precisely those nonzero elements that are not relatively prime to n .

Proof Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}_n$, where $m \neq 0$, and let the gcd of m and n be $d \neq 1$. Then

$$m \left(\frac{n}{d}\right) = \left(\frac{m}{d}\right)n,$$

and $(m/d)n$ gives 0 as a multiple of n . Thus $m(n/d) = 0$ in \mathbb{Z}_n , while neither m nor n/d is 0, so m is a divisor of 0.

On the other hand, suppose $m \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ is relatively prime to n . If for $s \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ we have $ms = 0$, then n divides the product ms of m and s as elements in the ring \mathbb{Z} . Since n is relatively prime to m , boxed Property 1 following Example 6.9 shows that n divides s , so $s = 0$ in \mathbb{Z}_n . ◆

18.5 Example Recall that in group theory, $n\mathbb{Z}$ is the cyclic subgroup of \mathbb{Z} under addition consisting of all integer multiples of the integer n . Since $(nr)(ns) = n(nrs)$, we see that $n\mathbb{Z}$, is closed under multiplication. The associative and distributive laws which hold in \mathbb{Z} then assure us that $(n\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is a ring. From now on in the text, we will consider $n\mathbb{Z}$ to be this ring. ▲

(c) All units of R and their inverses.

(Definition 18.16): “An element $u \in R$ is a unit if it has a multiplicative inverse in R .” (Section 20) “... the units in \mathbb{Z}_n are precisely those $\overline{m} \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ such that $\text{gcd}(m, n) = 1$.”

\implies Find all m with $\text{gcd}(m, 12) = 1$. We have $\text{gcd}(1, 12) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(5, 12) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(7, 12) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(11, 12) = 1$. So

$$\boxed{\text{Units} = \{\overline{1}, \overline{5}, \overline{7}, \overline{11}\}}$$

To find inverses, solve $\overline{a} \overline{x} = \overline{1}$ in \mathbb{Z}_{12}

- $\overline{1} \cdot \overline{1} = \overline{1}$, (inverse of $\overline{1}$ is $\overline{1}$),
- $\overline{5} \cdot \overline{5} = \overline{25} = \overline{1}$ (so inverse of $\overline{5}$ is $\overline{5}$),
- $\overline{7} \cdot \overline{7} = \overline{49} = \overline{1}$ (inverse of $\overline{7}$ is $\overline{7}$),
- $\overline{11} \cdot \overline{11} = \overline{121} = \overline{1}$ (inverse of $\overline{11}$ is $\overline{11}$) \implies

$$\boxed{\text{Units and their inverses: } \overline{1}^{-1} = \overline{1} \quad \overline{5}^{-1} = \overline{5} \quad \overline{7}^{-1} = \overline{7} \quad \overline{11}^{-1} = \overline{11}}$$

3. Show that \mathbb{Z}_7 is a field.

18.16 Definition Let R be a ring with unity $1 \neq 0$. An element u in R is a **unit** of R if it has a multiplicative inverse in R . If every nonzero element of R is a unit, then R is a **division ring** (or **skew field**). A **field** is a commutative division ring. A noncommutative division ring is called a “**strictly skew field**.” ■

Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_7$, $a \cdot b = b \cdot a$ since integer multiplication is commutative
 “ \mathbb{Z}_n is a ring under addition and multiplication modulo n .”
 \mathbb{Z}_7 is a ring, and its multiplicative identity is $\bar{1} \pmod{7}$.

18.6 Example Consider the cyclic group $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, + \rangle$. If we define for $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ the product ab as the remainder of the usual product of integers when divided by n , it can be shown that $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +, \cdot \rangle$ is a ring. We shall feel free to use this fact. For example, in \mathbb{Z}_{10} we have $(3)(7) = 1$. This operation on \mathbb{Z}_n is **multiplication modulo n** . We do not check the ring axioms here, for they will follow in Section 26 from some of the theory we develop there. From now on, \mathbb{Z}_n will always be the ring $\langle \mathbb{Z}_n, +, \cdot \rangle$. ▲

\mathbb{Z}_7 has no divisors of 0.

(Corollary 19.4): “If p is prime, \mathbb{Z}_p has no divisors of 0.”

Since 7 is prime, any nonzero $\bar{a} \in \mathbb{Z}_7$ is relatively prime to 7, which means it cannot be a zero divisor. Thus

\mathbb{Z}_7 has no zero divisors.

In \mathbb{Z}_7 , the set is $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$.

For each non-zero $a \in \mathbb{Z}_7$, check $a \cdot b = 0$ for $b \neq 0$:

- For $a = 1$: $1 \cdot b = b \neq 0 \ (\forall b \neq 0)$.
- For $a = 2$: $2 \cdot 1 = 2, 2 \cdot 2 = 4, 2 \cdot 3 = 6, 2 \cdot 4 = 1,$
 $2 \cdot 5 = 3, 2 \cdot 6 = 5 \pmod{7}$.
- For $a = 3$: $3 \cdot 1 = 3, 3 \cdot 2 = 6, 3 \cdot 3 = 2, 3 \cdot 4 = 5,$
 $3 \cdot 5 = 1, 3 \cdot 6 = 4 \pmod{7}$.
- For $a = 4$: $4 \cdot 1 = 4, 4 \cdot 2 = 1, 4 \cdot 3 = 5, 4 \cdot 4 = 2,$
 $4 \cdot 5 = 6, 4 \cdot 6 = 3 \pmod{7}$.
- For $a = 5$: $5 \cdot 1 = 5, 5 \cdot 2 = 3, 5 \cdot 3 = 1, 5 \cdot 4 = 6,$
 $5 \cdot 5 = 4, 5 \cdot 6 = 2 \pmod{7}$.
- For $a = 6$: $6 \cdot 1 = 6, 6 \cdot 2 = 5, 6 \cdot 3 = 4, 6 \cdot 4 = 3,$
 $6 \cdot 5 = 2, 6 \cdot 6 = 1 \pmod{7}$.

In each case, $a \cdot b \neq 0 \ (\forall b \neq 0)$

$\therefore \mathbb{Z}_7$ has no zero divisors.

All nonzero elements have a mult inverse

- $1 \cdot 1 = 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$
- $2 \cdot 4 = 8 = 7 + 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$
- $3 \cdot 5 = 15 = 14 + 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$
- $4 \cdot 2 = 8 = 7 + 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$
- $5 \cdot 3 = 15 = 14 + 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$
- $6 \cdot 6 = 36 = 35 + 1 = 1 \pmod{7}$

(Section 19.6 Definition): “An integral domain D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0.”

By the previous steps, \mathbb{Z}_7 is a commutative ring with unity and no zero divisors, and is clearly finite (it has exactly 7 elements $\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \dots, \bar{6}$).

Therefore, \mathbb{Z}_7 is a finite integral domain.

A finite integral domain is a field.

(Theorem 19.11): “Every finite integral domain is a field.”

$\implies \underbrace{\mathbb{Z}_7 \text{ is a finite integral domain}}_{\text{from Step 3}} \implies \mathbb{Z}_7 \text{ is a field.}$

19.11 Theorem Every finite integral domain is a field.

Proof Let

$$0, 1, a_1, \dots, a_n$$

be all the elements of a finite domain D . We need to show that for $a \in D$, where $a \neq 0$, there exists $b \in D$ such that $ab = 1$. Now consider

$$a1, aa_1, \dots, aa_n.$$

We claim that all these elements of D are distinct, for $aa_i = aa_j$ implies that $a_i = a_j$, by the cancellation laws that hold in an integral domain. Also, since D has no 0 divisors, none of these elements is 0. Hence by *counting*, we find that $a1, aa_1, \dots, aa_n$ are elements $1, a_1, \dots, a_n$ in some order, so that either $a1 = 1$, that is, $a = 1$, or $aa_i = 1$ for some i . Thus a has a multiplicative inverse. ◆

4.* Suppose R, S are rings with unity, and denote the multiplicative identities 1_R and 1_S respectively. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a surjective ring homomorphism. Prove that $\varphi(1_R) = 1_S$.

18.9 Definition For rings R and R' , a map $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ is a **homomorphism** if the following two conditions are satisfied for all $a, b \in R$:

1. $\phi(a + b) = \phi(a) + \phi(b)$,
2. $\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$. ■

18.4 Example Let F be the set of all functions $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We know that $(F, +)$ is an abelian group under the usual function addition,

$$(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x).$$

We define multiplication on F by

$$(fg)(x) = f(x)g(x).$$

That is, fg is the function whose value at x is $f(x)g(x)$. It is readily checked that F is a ring; we leave the demonstration to Exercise 34. We have used this juxtaposition notation $\sigma\mu$ for the composite function $\sigma(\mu(x))$ when discussing permutation multiplication. If we were to use both function multiplication and function composition in F , we would use the notation $f \circ g$ for the composite function. However, we will be using composition of functions almost exclusively with homomorphisms, which we will denote by Greek letters, and the usual product defined in this example chiefly when multiplying polynomial function $f(x)g(x)$, so no confusion should result. ▲

Surjectivity

Since φ is onto (surjective), for every element $s \in S$ there exists some $r \in R$ such that

$$\varphi(r) = s.$$

Existence of a preimage for 1_S

There exists some $u \in R$ such that

$$\varphi(u) = 1_S.$$

Use the ring homomorphism property

As φ is a ring homomorphism, for any $r \in R$:

$$\varphi(r \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(r) \varphi(1_R).$$

However,

$$\varphi(r \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(r) \underbrace{\varphi(1_R)}_{\text{(to be determined)}}.$$

But in any ring,

$$r \cdot 1_R = r.$$

Therefore,

$$\varphi(r) = \varphi(r \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(r) \varphi(1_R).$$

$$\phi(r) = \phi(r)\phi(1_R)$$

$$\phi(r) = \phi(r) \cdot 1_S$$

$$\phi(r) \cdot 1_S = \phi(r)\phi(1_R)$$

$$\therefore \phi(1_R) = 1_S$$

4.* Suppose R, S are rings with unity, and denote the multiplicative identities 1_R and 1_S respectively. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a surjective ring homomorphism. Prove that $\varphi(1_R) = 1_S$.

18.9 Definition For rings R and R' , a map $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ is a **homomorphism** if the following two conditions are satisfied for all $a, b \in R$:

1. $\phi(a + b) = \phi(a) + \phi(b)$,
2. $\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$. ■

18.4 Example Let F be the set of all functions $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We know that $(F, +)$ is an abelian group under the usual function addition,

$$(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x).$$

We define multiplication on F by

$$(fg)(x) = f(x)g(x).$$

That is, fg is the function whose value at x is $f(x)g(x)$. It is readily checked that F is a ring; we leave the demonstration to Exercise 34. We have used this juxtaposition notation $\sigma\mu$ for the composite function $\sigma(\mu(x))$ when discussing permutation multiplication. If we were to use both function multiplication and function composition in F , we would use the notation $f \circ g$ for the composite function. However, we will be using composition of functions almost exclusively with homomorphisms, which we will denote by Greek letters, and the usual product defined in this example chiefly when multiplying polynomial function $f(x)g(x)$, so no confusion should result. ▲

Since φ is surjective, for every $s \in S$ there is some $r \in R$ such that $\varphi(r) = s$. ie, there is an element $u \in R$ with $\varphi(u) = 1_S$.

Consider any $r \in R$. By the definition of a ring homomorphism,

$$\varphi(r \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(r) \varphi(1_R).$$

However, in the ring R we have $r \cdot 1_R = r$. Therefore,

$$\varphi(r) = \varphi(r \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(r) \varphi(1_R).$$

so,

$$\varphi(r) (1_S - \varphi(1_R)) = 0 \quad \text{for all } r \in R.$$

Because φ is surjective, for each $s \in S$ there exists $r \in R$ such that $\varphi(r) = s$. Substituting $\varphi(r) = s$ into the equation gives

$$s (1_S - \varphi(1_R)) = 0 \quad \text{for all } s \in S.$$

In a ring with unity, the only element x satisfying $sx = 0$ for all $s \in S$ is $x = 0$. Therefore,

$$1_S - \varphi(1_R) = 0,$$

which implies

$$\varphi(1_R) = 1_S.$$

5. Let R, S be rings, and $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Prove that φ is injective if and only if $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$. (Recall that $\ker(\varphi) := \{x \in R : \varphi(x) = 0\}$)

18.9 Definition For rings R and R' , a map $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ is a **homomorphism** if the following two conditions are satisfied for all $a, b \in R$:

1. $\phi(a + b) = \phi(a) + \phi(b)$,
2. $\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$. ■

If φ is injective, then $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$
 (Section 18, near Definition 18.9) : “All the results concerning group homomorphisms are valid for the additive structure of the rings. In particular, a homomorphism ϕ is one to one if and only if $\ker(\phi) = \{0\}$.”

Suppose φ is injective (one to one). Let $x \in \ker(\varphi)$. By definition, this means

$$\varphi(x) = 0 \quad (\text{in } S).$$

But also, $\varphi(0) = 0$ because every ring homomorphism sends 0 in R to 0 in S (see Theorem 18.8).

18.8 Theorem If R is a ring with additive identity 0, then for any $a, b \in R$ we have

1. $0a = a0 = 0$,
2. $a(-b) = (-a)b = -(ab)$,
3. $(-a)(-b) = ab$.

So,

$$\varphi(x) = 0 = \varphi(0).$$

Since φ is injective, $x = 0$. Hence any element in the kernel must be 0
 Therefore

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}.$$

So if φ is injective, then its kernel is exactly $\{0\}$.

If $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$, then φ is injective

Assume that $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$. We want to show φ is injective, i.e. for all $x, y \in R$,

$$\varphi(x) = \varphi(y) \implies x = y.$$

Suppose $\varphi(x) = \varphi(y)$. Then

$$\varphi(x) - \varphi(y) = 0 \implies \varphi(x - y) = \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) = 0 \quad (\text{by the additive property of ring homomorphisms}).$$

So $x - y \in \ker(\varphi)$. But by hypothesis, $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$. Therefore, $x - y = 0$, so $x = y$. So φ is injective.

Therefore if $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$, then φ is injective.

Therefore:

$$\varphi \text{ is injective} \iff \ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$$

1. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the *zero product property*, i.e. if a_1, \dots, a_n are elements of R , then if

$$a_1 \dots a_n = 0$$

we must have $a_i = 0$ for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. (Hint: Prove it for $n = 2$ and use induction on n)

19.6 Definition An **integral domain** D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0. ■

19.2 Definition If a and b are two nonzero elements of a ring R such that $ab = 0$, then a and b are **divisors of 0** (or **0 divisors**). ■

Base Case ($n = 2$).

Since R is an integral domain, it has no divisors of 0. Therefore, for $a_1, a_2 \in R$,

$$a_1 a_2 = 0 \implies a_1 = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad a_2 = 0$$

So the property holds for $n = 2$.

Inductive Step.

Assume for some $n \geq 2$, if

$$a_1 a_2 \dots a_n = 0$$

then at least one $a_i = 0$. We will prove it for $n + 1$. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n+1} \in R$ such that

$$a_1 a_2 \dots a_{n+1} = 0$$

Group as $a_1(a_2 \dots a_{n+1})$:

$$a_1(a_2 \dots a_{n+1}) = 0$$

By base case ($n = 2$), either $a_1 = 0$ or $(a_2 \dots a_{n+1}) = 0$. If $(a_2 \dots a_{n+1}) = 0$ the inductive hypothesis implies some $a_j = 0$ for $2 \leq j \leq n + 1$. Therefore, in all cases, at least one $a_i = 0$ in a_1, \dots, a_{n+1} .

2. Show that $M_2(\mathbb{R})$ is not an integral domain by finding two nonzero elements that multiply to the zero matrix.

19.2 Definition If a and b are two nonzero elements of a ring R such that $ab = 0$, then a and b are **divisors of 0** (or **0 divisors**). ■

19.8 Example Show that although \mathbb{Z}_2 is an integral domain, the matrix ring $M_2(\mathbb{Z}_2)$ has divisors of zero.

Solution We need only observe that

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad \blacktriangle$$

Our next theorem shows that the structure of a field is still the most restrictive (that is, the richest) one we have defined.

Therefore, in $M_2(\mathbb{R})$ we can find two nonzero matrices

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

with

$$AB = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

19.6 Definition An **integral domain** D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0. ■

Since $A \neq 0$ and $B \neq 0$ but $AB = 0$, A and B are divisors of 0, by Definition 19.2 and 19.6,

$\implies M_2(\mathbb{R})$ is not an integral domain.

3. Show that the characteristic of a field must be either 0 or a prime number p .

18.16 Definition Let R be a ring with unity $1 \neq 0$. An element u in R is a **unit** of R if it has a multiplicative inverse in R . If every nonzero element of R is a unit, then R is a **division ring** (or **skew field**). A **field** is a commutative division ring. A noncommutative division ring is called a “**strictly skew field**.” ■

19.13 Definition If for a ring R a positive integer n exists such that $n \cdot a = 0$ for all $a \in R$, then the least such positive integer is the **characteristic of the ring** R . If no such positive integer exists, then R is of **characteristic 0**. ■

19.9 Theorem Every field F is an integral domain.

19.6 Definition An **integral domain** D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0. ■

According to Theorem 19.9, every field F is an integral domain.

Therefore, to prove this for a field, we need to show it holds for an integral domain.

An integral domain has no zero divisors.

Suppose $\text{char}(F) = n > 0$. By Definition 19.13, $n \cdot 1 = 0$ in F and n is the smallest positive integer with this property.

Also, n must be prime.

Assume, for contradiction, that $n = ab$ with $1 < a, b < n$. Then

$$(n \cdot 1) = (ab) \cdot 1 = (a \cdot 1)(b \cdot 1)$$

Since $n \cdot 1 = 0$ (by the definition of characteristic), we obtain

$$(a \cdot 1)(b \cdot 1) = 0$$

But in a field F (which is an integral domain according to Theorem 19.9), there are no zero divisors, so from

$$(a \cdot 1)(b \cdot 1) = 0 \quad \implies \quad (a \cdot 1) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (b \cdot 1) = 0$$

For the sake of argument, assume $a \cdot 1 = 0$. This contradicts 19.13, where n is the characteristic of F , and therefore the smallest number where $n \cdot 1 = 0$. The same argument can be made for $b \cdot 1$.

$$\implies \text{no such factorization } n = ab \text{ with } a, b > 1$$

Thus n is prime whenever $n > 0$.

Since either n does not exist (making $\text{char}(F) = 0$) or n exists and must be prime:

$$\text{char}(F) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \text{char}(F) = p \text{ (a prime)}$$

4. Let $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ denote the ring of polynomials with integer coefficients.

- Prove that $I = \{f(x) : x \text{ divides } f(x)\}$ is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
- Prove that $J = \{g(x) : \text{the constant term } g_0 \text{ is even}\}$ is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
- Prove that $I' = \{f(x) : \deg(f) \leq 5\}$ is not an ideal.

26.10 Definition An additive subgroup N of a ring R satisfying the properties

$$aN \subseteq N \quad \text{and} \quad Nb \subseteq N \quad \text{for all } a, b \in R$$

is an **ideal**. ■

Also, $x \mid f(x)$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ means $\exists q(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ s.t. $f(x) = xq(x)$

1. $I = \{f(x) \mid x \text{ divides } f(x)\}$ is an ideal.

(i) Additive subgroup:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x), g(x) \in I &\implies f(x) = xq_1(x), g(x) = xq_2(x) \quad (q_1, q_2 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]) \\ &\implies f(x) - g(x) = xq_1(x) - xq_2(x) = x[q_1(x) - q_2(x)] \in I \\ 0(x) = x \cdot 0 &\in I, \implies I \text{ is closed under inverses, so an additive subgroup.} \end{aligned}$$

(ii) Absorption:

$$h(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x], f(x) \in I \implies f(x) = xq_1(x) \implies h(x)f(x) = h(x)(xq_1(x)) = x[q_1(x)h(x)] \in I$$

Therefore I is an ideal (by Definition 26.10).

2. $J = \{g(x) \mid \text{the constant term } g_0 \text{ is even}\}$ is an ideal.

(i) Additive subgroup:

$$0 \in J \text{ (its constant term is 0, even). } g(x), h(x) \in J \implies g_0, h_0 \text{ even.}$$

$$\implies (g - h)_0 = g_0 - h_0 \text{ is even} \implies (g - h) \in J$$

(ii) Absorption:

$$g(x) \in J \implies g_0 \text{ even; } f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \implies (fg)_0 = f_0g_0 \text{ (even)} \implies fg \in J.$$

Therefore J is an ideal.

3. $I' = \{f(x) \mid \deg(f) \leq 5\}$ is not an ideal.

$$\deg(f) = 5, \deg(g) = 1 \implies \deg(fg) = 5 + 1 = 6 \not\leq 5 \implies fg \notin I'$$

So absorption fails, and I' is not an ideal.

Therefore I and J are ideals, but I' is not an ideal.

5. Let R be a commutative ring with identity, and let I, J be ideals of R .

- Prove that $I \cap J$ is an ideal.
- Prove that $I \cup J$ need not be an ideal.
- Let $K = \{ab : a \in I, b \in J\}$. Is K an ideal of R ?

(a) Prove that $I \cap J$ is an ideal.

1: $I \cap J$ is an additive subgroup.

If $x, y \in I \cap J$, then $x, y \in I$ and $x, y \in J$.

Therefore, $x + y \in I$ and $x + y \in J$, $\implies x + y \in I \cap J$.

Also, if $x \in I \cap J$, then $-x \in I$ and $-x \in J$, so $-x \in I \cap J$.

Therefore, $I \cap J$ is a subgroup of $(R, +)$.

2: Absorption property.

Let $r \in R$ and $x \in I \cap J$. Since $x \in I$ and $x \in J$, we have

$rx \in I$ and $rx \in J$

therefore, $rx \in I \cap J$.

and, $I \cap J$ is an ideal of R .

(b) Prove that $I \cup J$ need not be an ideal.

Consider: $I = 2\mathbb{Z}$ and $J = 3\mathbb{Z}$ in \mathbb{Z} . Then $I \cup J = 2\mathbb{Z} \cup 3\mathbb{Z}$

is not an ideal because:

• $2 \in 2\mathbb{Z} \subseteq I \cup J$, and

• $3 \in 3\mathbb{Z} \subseteq I \cup J$,

but $2 + 3 = 5 \notin 2\mathbb{Z}$ and $5 \notin 3\mathbb{Z}$. Therefore $5 \notin I \cup J$.

Thus $I \cup J$ is not closed under addition and therefore is not an ideal.

(c) Let $K = \{ab \mid a \in I, b \in J\}$. Is K an ideal?

Although each element of K is of the form ab ,

closure under addition fails. If $x_1 = a_1b_1$ and $x_2 = a_2b_2$, we cannot

always express $x_1 + x_2$ as a single product ab with $a \in I$ and $b \in J$.

The product of ideals IJ , is defined as

$$IJ = \left\{ \sum_{\nu} a_{\nu}b_{\nu} \mid a_{\nu} \in I, b_{\nu} \in J, \text{ finitely many terms} \right\}.$$

This set *is* an ideal because it is closed under finite summations.

However, the set

$$K = \{ab : a \in I, b \in J\}$$

by itself need not be an ideal.

Extra Credit*. Let R be a commutative ring with identity, and define $M_n(R)$ to be the ring of matrices with coefficients in R . Prove that every ideal of $M_n(R)$ is of the form $M_n(I)$, where I is an ideal of R .

26.10 Definition An additive subgroup N of a ring R satisfying the properties

$$aN \subseteq N \quad \text{and} \quad Nb \subseteq N \quad \text{for all } a, b \in R$$

is an **ideal**. ■

Let $J \subseteq M_n(R)$ be a two-sided ideal. We want to show that $\exists I \triangleleft R$ (“Ideal” of R) such that

$$J = M_n(I) = \{(a_{ij}) \mid a_{ij} \in I\}$$

Set

$$I := \{r \in R \mid \text{diag}(r, 0, \dots, 0) \in J\}$$

$$\underbrace{r_1, r_2 \in I \implies \text{diag}(r_1, 0), \text{diag}(r_2, 0) \in J \implies \text{diag}(r_1+r_2, 0) \in J \implies r_1+r_2 \in I}_{\text{by definition}}$$

$$\underbrace{r \in I \wedge s \in R \implies \text{diag}(r, 0) \in J \implies \text{diag}(s, 0) \text{diag}(r, 0) = \text{diag}(sr, 0) \in J \implies sr \in I}_{\text{by def.}}$$

Therefore, I is an ideal of R (according to Definition 26.10).

For any $A = (a_{ij}) \in M_n(I)$, each $a_{ij} \in I \implies \text{diag}(a_{ij}, 0) \in J$.

Using matrix units $E_{\ell i}, E_{j m}$:

$$A = \sum_{i,j} E_{i1} \text{diag}(a_{ij}, 0, \dots) E_{1j} \in J \quad (\text{since } J \text{ is a two-sided ideal}).$$

Thus $M_n(I) \subseteq J$.

Take $B = (b_{ij}) \in J$. For fixed k, ℓ :

$$E_{ik} B E_{\ell j} \in J \quad (\text{since } J \text{ is two-sided}).$$

But $E_{ik} B E_{\ell j}$ is the matrix whose only possible nonzero entry is $b_{k\ell}$ in the (i, j) position. So it must be that $b_{k\ell} \in I$ (because if we replace r by $b_{k\ell}$ with diagonal entries, then $b_{k\ell} \in I$). Since every $b_{ij} \in I$, $B \in M_n(I)$. Therefore, $J = M_n(I)$.

1. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Prove that $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ideal of R .

$$\ker(\varphi) \equiv \varphi^{-1}[\{0'\}] \subseteq R$$

Ring homomorphism property: for $r_1, r_2 \in R$, $\varphi(r_1 r_2) = \varphi(r_1)\varphi(r_2)$.

By Definition 26.4:

26.4 Definition Let a map $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ be a homomorphism of rings. The subring

$$\phi^{-1}[0'] = \{r \in R \mid \phi(r) = 0'\}$$

is the **kernel** of ϕ , denoted by $\text{Ker}(\phi)$. ■

Now this $\text{Ker}(\phi)$ is the same as the kernel of the group homomorphism of $\langle R, + \rangle$ into $\langle R', + \rangle$ given by ϕ . Theorem 13.15 and Corollary 13.18 on group homomorphisms give us at once analogous results for ring homomorphisms.

$$0 \in \ker(\varphi) \quad \text{since} \quad \varphi(0) = 0'$$

Theorem 26.5 and Corollary 26.6 on group homomorphisms: $\implies \ker(\varphi) \leq (R, +)$

φ limits to a group homomorphism $(R, +) \rightarrow (S, +)$ with addition, so we can use the following theorems.

26.5 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 13.15) Let $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ be a ring homomorphism, and let $H = \text{Ker}(\phi)$. Let $a \in R$. Then $\phi^{-1}[\phi(a)] = a + H = H + a$, where $a + H = H + a$ is the coset containing a of the commutative additive group $\langle H, + \rangle$.

26.6 Corollary (Analogue of Corollary 13.18) A ring homomorphism $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ is a one-to-one map if and only if $\text{Ker}(\phi) = \{0\}$.

therefore $\ker(\varphi)$ is an additive subgroup of R for all $r_1, r_2 \in \ker(\varphi)$ we have

$$\varphi(r_1 + r_2) = \varphi(r_1) + \varphi(r_2) = 0' + 0' = 0'$$

and for $r \in \ker(\varphi)$,

$$\varphi(-r) = -\varphi(r) = -0' = 0'$$

so $r_1 + r_2 \in \ker(\varphi)$ and $-r \in \ker(\varphi)$.

$$r \in R, h \in \ker(\varphi) \implies \begin{cases} \varphi(rh) = \varphi(r)\varphi(h) = \varphi(r)0' = 0' \implies rh \in \ker(\varphi) \\ \varphi(hr) = \varphi(h)\varphi(r) = 0'\varphi(r) = 0' \implies hr \in \ker(\varphi) \end{cases}$$

Therefore, $\ker(\varphi)$ is closed under multiplication from both sides by elements of R .

$\therefore \ker(\varphi)$ is an ideal of R

2. This exercise studies homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z} to other rings.

- (a) Prove that any homomorphism $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S$ for a ring S is entirely determined by $\varphi(1)$. In other words, once the output of 1 is determined, the entire homomorphism is determined.
- (b) (Extra credit) Let $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) := \{\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}\}$ denote the set of ring homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z} to \mathbb{Z} . It can be proven $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z})$ forms a ring under the operations

$$(\varphi + \psi)(a) = \varphi(a) + \psi(a)$$

$$(\varphi \cdot \psi)(a) = \varphi(a) \cdot \psi(a)$$

where $+, \cdot$ are the usual operations in \mathbb{Z} , and $a \in \mathbb{Z}$. Prove that $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \cong \mathbb{Z}$. (Hint: Consider the map $\Phi : \text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ defined by $\Phi : \varphi \mapsto \varphi(1)$)

- (c) List all of the ring homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z}_{12} to \mathbb{Z}_{30} .

(a): Homomorphisms $\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S$ are determined by $\phi(1)$

26.3 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 13.12) Let ϕ be a homomorphism of a ring R into a ring R' . If 0 is the additive identity in R , then $\phi(0) = 0'$ is the additive identity in R' , and if $a \in R$, then $\phi(-a) = -\phi(a)$. If S is a subring of R , then $\phi[S]$ is a subring of R' . Going the other way, if S' is a subring of R' , then $\phi^{-1}[S']$ is a subring of R . Finally, if R has unity 1 , then $\phi(1)$ is unity for $\phi[R]$. Loosely speaking, subrings correspond to subrings, and rings with unity correspond to rings with unity under a ring homomorphism.

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S, \quad \phi(a + b) = \phi(a) + \phi(b), \quad \phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b) \quad (\text{Definition 26.1, } \forall a, b \in \mathbb{Z})$$

$$\phi(0) = \phi(0 + 0) = \phi(0) + \phi(0) \implies \phi(0) = 0$$

$$\phi(-n) + \phi(n) = \phi(-n + n) = \phi(0) = 0 \implies \phi(-n) = -\phi(n) \quad (\forall n \in \mathbb{Z})$$

$$\phi(n) = \phi(\underbrace{1 + 1 + \cdots + 1}_{n \text{ times}}) = n\phi(1) \quad (\text{Theorem 26.3; same for } n < 0)$$

$$\implies \phi \text{ is determined by } \phi(1) \in S$$

(b): $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \cong \mathbb{Z}$

$$\Phi : \text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}, \quad \Phi(\varphi) = \varphi(1)$$

Each φ determined by $\varphi(1) \implies \Phi$ onto, and $\Phi(\varphi_1) = \Phi(\varphi_2) \implies \varphi_1(1) = \varphi_2(1) \implies \varphi_1 = \varphi_2$

$\implies \Phi$ is one-to-one. For $\varphi, \psi \in \text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z})$:

$$(\varphi + \psi)(a) = \varphi(a) + \psi(a), \quad (\varphi \cdot \psi)(a) = \varphi(a)\psi(a)$$

$$\Phi(\varphi + \psi) = (\varphi + \psi)(1) = \varphi(1) + \psi(1) = \Phi(\varphi) + \Phi(\psi)$$

$$\Phi(\varphi \cdot \psi) = (\varphi \cdot \psi)(1) = \varphi(1) \psi(1) = \Phi(\varphi) \Phi(\psi)$$

$\implies \Phi$ is a ring isomorphism onto \mathbb{Z}

$$\psi : \mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{30}$$

(Example 18.11, Theorem 26.7) ψ determined by $\psi(1 + 12\mathbb{Z})$

18.11 Example The map $\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_n$ where $\phi(a)$ is the remainder of a modulo n is a ring homomorphism for each positive integer n . We know $\phi(a + b) = \phi(a) + \phi(b)$ by group theory. To show the multiplicative property, write $a = q_1n + r_1$ and $b = q_2n + r_2$ according to the division algorithm. Then $ab = n(q_1q_2n + r_1q_2 + q_1r_2) + r_1r_2$. Thus $\phi(ab)$ is the remainder of r_1r_2 when divided by n . Since $\phi(a) = r_1$ and $\phi(b) = r_2$, Example 18.6 indicates that $\phi(a)\phi(b)$ is also this same remainder, so $\phi(ab) = \phi(a)\phi(b)$. From group theory, we anticipate that the ring \mathbb{Z}_n might be isomorphic to a factor ring $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. This is indeed the case; factor rings will be discussed in Section 26. \blacktriangle

(c): All ring homomorphisms $\mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{30}$

$$12 \equiv 0 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_{12} \implies \psi(12) = 0 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_{30}$$

$$\text{If } \psi(1) = k \in \mathbb{Z}_{30}, \quad \psi(12) = 12k = 0$$

$$\gcd(12, 30) = 6 \implies 12k = 6 \cdot (2k), \quad 30 = 6 \cdot 5, \quad \gcd(2, 5) = 1$$

Additive condition:

$$\psi(\overline{12}) = \overline{0} \implies \overline{12} \cdot \overline{k} = \overline{0} \implies 30 \mid 12k \implies 5 \mid k$$

Therefore,

$$k \in \{0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25\}$$

Multiplicative condition:

$$\overline{1} \cdot \overline{1} = \overline{1} \implies \psi(\overline{1}) \cdot \psi(\overline{1}) = \psi(\overline{1}) \implies \overline{k}^2 = \overline{k} \implies k(k-1) \equiv 0 \pmod{30}$$

Combining these:

$$\underbrace{5 \mid k}_{\text{additive}} \wedge \underbrace{k(k-1) \equiv 0 \pmod{30}}_{\text{multiplicative}}.$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} k = 0 : \quad 0(0-1) = 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{30} \\ k = 5 : \quad 5(4) = 20 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{30} \\ k = 10 : \quad 10(9) = 90 \equiv 0 \pmod{30} \\ k = 15 : \quad 15(14) = 210 \equiv 0 \pmod{30} \\ k = 20 : \quad 20(19) = 380 \equiv 20 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{30} \\ k = 25 : \quad 25(24) = 600 \equiv 0 \pmod{30} \end{array} \right.$$

Therefore, the valid k are $\{0, 10, 15, 25\}$.

There are 4 ring homomorphisms: $\psi(\overline{1}) = \overline{0}, \overline{10}, \overline{15}, \overline{25}$

ψ respects ring operations

$$x \equiv y \pmod{12} \implies 12 \mid (x-y) \implies 12k \mid (x-y) \implies 30 \mid (x-y)k \implies \psi(x) = \psi(y).$$

And $\psi(x+y) = \psi(x)+\psi(y)$, $\psi(xy) = \psi(x)\psi(y)$, because of linearity and the fact that $\psi(1) = k$.

3. Consider the ring homomorphism $\varphi : \mathbb{R}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ by $\varphi(1) = 1, \varphi(x) = i$. What is the kernel of this map?

26.16 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 14.9) Let N be an ideal of a ring R . Then $\gamma : R \rightarrow R/N$ given by $\gamma(x) = x + N$ is a ring homomorphism with kernel N .

13.18 Corollary A group homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ is a one-to-one map if and only if $\text{Ker}(\phi) = \{e\}$.

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{ f(x) \in \mathbb{R}[x] \mid \varphi(f(x)) = 0' \}, \quad 0' \in \mathbb{C}$$

$$\varphi(1) = 1, \quad \varphi(x) = i \implies \varphi(f(x)) = f(i)$$

φ is a ring homomorphism: $\varphi(f + g) = \varphi(f) + \varphi(g), \quad \varphi(fg) = \varphi(f)\varphi(g), \quad \varphi(1) = 1.$

$$\varphi(x^2 + 1) = i^2 + 1 = (-1) + 1 = 0 \implies x^2 + 1 \in \text{Ker}(\varphi)$$

$$f \in \ker(\varphi) \implies f(i) = 0 \implies i \text{ is a root of } f(x)$$

since $(x^2 + 1)$ can't be factored into a product of two non-constant polynomials with real coefficients $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ in $\mathbb{R}[x]$

$$x^2 + 1 \neq p(x) \cdot q(x) \implies x^2 + 1 \text{ irreducible in } \mathbb{R}[x]$$

$$f(i) = 0 \implies x^2 + 1 \mid f(x)$$

$$f(i) = 0 \implies (x - i) \text{ is a factor of } f(x) \text{ in } \mathbb{C}[x]. \text{ Since } x^2 + 1 = (x - i)(x + i)$$

$$\text{and is irreducible in } \mathbb{R}[x], \quad x^2 + 1 \mid f(x) \implies f(x) \in \langle x^2 + 1 \rangle$$

$$f(x) \in \ker(\varphi) \implies f(x) \in \langle x^2 + 1 \rangle$$

$$f(x) = (x^2 + 1)h(x), \quad h(x) \in \mathbb{R}[x] \implies f(i) = (i^2 + 1)h(i) = 0$$

$$\ker(\varphi) = \langle x^2 + 1 \rangle$$

$$\gamma : R \rightarrow R/N, \quad \ker(\gamma) = N \quad (\text{Thm 26.16}), \quad \ker(\varphi) \text{ is an ideal in } \mathbb{R}[x] \quad (\text{Cor 13.18})$$

$$\text{By the First Isomorphism Theorem, } \frac{\mathbb{R}[x]}{\ker(\varphi)} \cong \text{im}(\varphi)$$

$\text{im}(\varphi) \subseteq \mathbb{C}$, and it contains all real constants and the element i , so $\text{im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{C}$

$$\forall a + bi \in \mathbb{C}, \exists f(x) = a + bx \in \mathbb{R}[x] \implies \varphi(f) = a + bi \implies \text{im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{C}$$

$$\therefore \frac{\mathbb{R}[x]}{\langle x^2 + 1 \rangle} \cong \mathbb{C}$$

4. What are the prime ideals of \mathbb{Z} ? For \mathbb{Z}_{10} ? What are the maximal ideals?

An ideal N is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{prime} &\iff \mathbb{Z}/N \text{ is an integral domain,} \\ \text{maximal} &\iff \mathbb{Z}/N \text{ is a field.} \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$0 \in n\mathbb{Z} \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$$

we have

$$\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z} \text{ integral domain} \implies n = 0 \text{ or } n \text{ is prime} \implies \text{prime ideals in } \mathbb{Z}: 0, p\mathbb{Z} \text{ (} p \text{ prime)}$$

$$0 \text{ is prime since } \mathbb{Z}/0 \cong \mathbb{Z} \text{ is an integral domain.}$$

Also,

$$\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z} \text{ field} \implies n \text{ is prime} \implies \text{maximal ideals in } \mathbb{Z}: p\mathbb{Z} \text{ (} p \text{ prime)}$$

$R = \mathbb{Z}_{10}$. (Theorem 26.7: the map $\mu: R/N \rightarrow \phi[R]$ with $\mu(a + N) = \phi(a)$ is an isomorphism; Theorem 26.9: ideals of \mathbb{Z}_{10} correspond to ideals of \mathbb{Z} containing $10\mathbb{Z}$.)

26.7 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 14.1) Let $\phi: R \rightarrow R'$ be a ring homomorphism with kernel H . Then the additive cosets of H form a ring R/H whose binary operations are defined by choosing representatives. That is, the sum of two cosets is defined by

$$(a + H) + (b + H) = (a + b) + H,$$

and the product of the cosets is defined by

$$(a + H)(b + H) = (ab) + H.$$

Also, the map $\mu: R/H \rightarrow \phi[R]$ defined by $\mu(a + H) = \phi(a)$ is an isomorphism.

26.9 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 14.4) Let H be a subring of the ring R . Multiplication of additive cosets of H is well defined by the equation

$$(a + H)(b + H) = ab + H$$

if and only if $ah \in H$ and $hb \in H$ for all $a, b \in R$ and $h \in H$.

An ideal of \mathbb{Z}_{10} is

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{n\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z}}{10\mathbb{Z}}, \quad 10\mathbb{Z} \subseteq n\mathbb{Z} \implies n \mid 10 \\ \underbrace{10\mathbb{Z} \subseteq n\mathbb{Z}}_{\iff n \mid 10} &\implies n\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z} = \gcd(n, 10)\mathbb{Z} \\ &\implies \mathbb{Z}_{10} / (n\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z}) \cong \mathbb{Z} / \gcd(n, 10)\mathbb{Z} \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\mathbb{Z}_{10} / \left(\frac{n\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z}}{10\mathbb{Z}} \right) \cong \mathbb{Z} / (n\mathbb{Z})$$

an integral domain needs

$$n = 0 \text{ or } n \text{ prime, with } 10\mathbb{Z} \subseteq n\mathbb{Z} \implies 10 \mid n$$

Only primes dividing 10 are 2 and 5, so the prime ideals in \mathbb{Z}_{10} are

$$\frac{2\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z}}{10\mathbb{Z}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{5\mathbb{Z} + 10\mathbb{Z}}{10\mathbb{Z}}, \text{ call these (2) and (5)}$$

Finally,

$$\mathbb{Z}_{10}/(I) \text{ a field} \implies n = 2 \text{ or } 5 \implies (2) \text{ and } (5) \text{ are maximal in } \mathbb{Z}_{10}$$

$$\text{Prime ideals of } \mathbb{Z} = 0, p\mathbb{Z} \quad (p \text{ prime})$$

$$\text{Maximal ideals of } \mathbb{Z} = p\mathbb{Z} \quad (p \text{ prime})$$

$$\text{Prime ideals of } \mathbb{Z}_{10} = (2), (5)$$

$$\text{Maximal ideals of } \mathbb{Z}_{10} = (2), (5)$$

5. Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. Prove that R/I is an integral domain if and only if I is a prime ideal.

According to Theorem 26.7:

26.7 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 14.1) Let $\phi : R \rightarrow R'$ be a ring homomorphism with kernel H . Then the additive cosets of H form a ring R/H whose binary operations are defined by choosing representatives. That is, the sum of two cosets is defined by

$$(a + H) + (b + H) = (a + b) + H,$$

and the product of the cosets is defined by

$$(a + H)(b + H) = (ab) + H.$$

Also, the map $\mu : R/H \rightarrow \phi[R]$ defined by $\mu(a + H) = \phi(a)$ is an isomorphism.

Replace N by I R/I is a ring.

$$R/I \text{ integral domain} \iff I \text{ prime.}$$

$$R/I \text{ integral domain} \implies R/I \neq \{0\} \implies I \neq R.$$

$$R/I \text{ integral domain} \implies \forall a, b \in R : (a + I)(b + I) = I \implies ab + I = I \implies ab \in I$$

$$(a + I)(b + I) = I \implies \begin{cases} a + I = I \\ \text{or } b + I = I \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} a \in I \\ \text{or } b \in I \end{cases}$$

$$\implies I \text{ is prime.}$$

$$I \text{ prime} \implies I \neq R \implies R/I \neq \{0\}$$

$$I \text{ prime} \implies \forall a, b \in R : ab \in I \implies \begin{cases} a \in I \\ \text{or } b \in I \end{cases}$$

$$\text{in } R/I : (a + I)(b + I) = I \implies ab + I = I \implies ab \in I \implies \begin{cases} a \in I \\ \text{or } b \in I \end{cases}$$

$$\implies \begin{cases} a + I = I \\ \text{or } b + I = I \end{cases}$$

$$\implies R/I \text{ has no zero divisors} \implies R/I \text{ is an integral domain.}$$

$$R/I \text{ integral domain} \iff I \text{ prime.}$$

Since we need I to be prime, I it must be a proper ideal ($I \neq R$).

Therefore, $1 \notin I$ and $1 + I \neq I$ in R/I , which means R/I is not the zero ring and has a nonzero identity. Also, we are assuming R is a commutative ring with $1 \neq 0$.

6. * Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. Prove that R/I is a field if and only if I is a maximal ideal.

26.10 Definition An additive subgroup N of a ring R satisfying the properties

$$aN \subseteq N \quad \text{and} \quad Nb \subseteq N \quad \text{for all } a, b \in R$$

is an **ideal**. ■

26.14 Corollary (Analogue of Corollary 14.5) Let N be an ideal of a ring R . Then the additive cosets of N form a ring R/N with the binary operations defined by

$$(a + N) + (b + N) = (a + b) + N$$

and

$$(a + N)(b + N) = ab + N.$$

If $I = R$, then R/I is the zero ring (not a field), so $I \subset R$ must be proper.

We will show

$$R/I \text{ field} \iff I \text{ maximal in } R$$

Ideals of R/I correspond to ideals of R containing I :

$$\text{Id}(R/I) \longleftrightarrow \{J \mid I \subseteq J \subseteq R\}, \quad J \mapsto J/I$$

Forward Direction:

$$\implies R/I \text{ field} : \quad \text{Id}(R/I) = \{\{0 + I\}, R/I\}$$

For any ideal J with

$$I \subseteq J \subseteq R, \quad J/I \triangleleft R/I$$

we have

$$J/I = \{0 + I\} \quad \text{or} \quad J/I = R/I$$

In the first case, $J/I = \{0 + I\} \implies J = I$; in the second, $J/I = R/I \implies J = R$. Therefore, no proper ideal is between I and R . I is maximal.

Reverse Direction:

$$\longleftarrow I \text{ maximal} : \quad \text{For any } \bar{a} \neq \bar{0} \text{ in } R/I, \langle \bar{a} \rangle = R/I$$

That is, $\exists \bar{b}$ with

$$\bar{a}\bar{b} = \bar{1}$$

so every nonzero coset is invertible and R/I is a field.

Every ring homomorphism $\varphi: R \rightarrow S$ creates a factor ring $R/\ker \varphi$, and every factor ring R/N gives a homomorphism $R \rightarrow R/N$. Ideals are therefore similar to normal subgroups.

A ring is a field if it has only the trivial ideals ($\{0\}$ and itself). So if R/I is a field, J/I is either $\{0 + I\}$ or R/I for any ideal $J \supseteq I \implies J = I$ or $J = R$, so I is maximal.

And if I is maximal, no proper ideal contains I , making every nonzero element $\bar{a} \in R/I$ invertible.

Therefore, R/I is a field.

$$\boxed{R/I \text{ field} \iff I \text{ maximal in } R}$$

1. Examples of polynomial rings:

- (a) List all of the elements f of $\mathbb{Z}_3[x]$ such that $\deg(f) \leq 2$.
- (b) Find the sum and the product of the following pairs of polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}_8[x]$:
- $(3x^2 + 2x - 1), (x^3 + 7x^2 - 3x - 4)$
 - $(3x^2 + 2x - 1), (5x - 4)$
- (c) Find the zeros of the following polynomials over the given ring:
- $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1, \mathbb{Z}_5$
 - $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1, \mathbb{Z}_7$
 - $f(x) = x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{Q} .
 - $f(x) = x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{C} .

(a)

Coefficients in $\{0, 1, 2\} \subset \mathbb{Z}_3$:

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 \implies a_0, a_1, a_2 \in \{0, 1, 2\}$$

There are $3^3 = 27$ polynomials:

1 0	2 1	3 2
4 x	5 $x + 1$	6 $x + 2$
7 $2x$	8 $2x + 1$	9 $2x + 2$
10 x^2	11 $x^2 + 1$	12 $x^2 + 2$
13 $x^2 + x$	14 $x^2 + x + 1$	15 $x^2 + x + 2$
16 $x^2 + 2x$	17 $x^2 + 2x + 1$	18 $x^2 + 2x + 2$
19 $2x^2$	20 $2x^2 + 1$	21 $2x^2 + 2$
22 $2x^2 + x$	23 $2x^2 + x + 1$	24 $2x^2 + x + 2$
25 $2x^2 + 2x$	26 $2x^2 + 2x + 1$	27 $2x^2 + 2x + 2$

(b)

1. $(3x^2 + 2x - 1)$ and $(x^3 + 7x^2 - 3x - 4)$

In \mathbb{Z}_8 ,

$$-1 \equiv 7$$

$$-3 \equiv 5$$

$$-4 \equiv 4$$

$$f(x) = 3x^2 + 2x + 7, \quad g(x) = x^3 + 7x^2 + 5x + 4$$

Sum:

$$f + g = (3x^2 + 2x + 7) + (x^3 + 7x^2 + 5x + 4) \implies x^3 + (3 + 7)x^2 + (2 + 5)x + (7 + 4)$$

Mod 8:

$$3 + 7 = 10 \equiv 2$$

$$2 + 5 = 7$$

$$7 + 4 = 11 \equiv 3$$

So

$$x^3 + 2x^2 + 7x + 3$$

Product:

$$f \cdot g = (3x^2 + 2x + 7)(x^3 + 7x^2 + 5x + 4)$$

multiply each term modulo 8:

1 $3x^2 \cdot x^3 = 3x^5$	2 $3x^2 \cdot 7x^2 = 21x^4 \equiv 5x^4$	3 $3x^2 \cdot 5x = 15x^3 \equiv 7x^3$
4 $3x^2 \cdot 4 = 12x^2 \equiv 4x^2$	5 $2x \cdot x^3 = 2x^4$	6 $2x \cdot 7x^2 = 14x^3 \equiv 6x^3$
7 $2x \cdot 5x = 10x^2 \equiv 2x^2$	8 $2x \cdot 4 = 8x \equiv 0$	9 $7 \cdot x^3 = 7x^3$
10 $7 \cdot 7x^2 = 49x^2 \equiv 1x^2$	11 $7 \cdot 5x = 35x \equiv 3x$	12 $7 \cdot 4 = 28 \equiv 4$

combine like terms:

1 $x^5 : 3$	2 $x^4 : 5 + 2 = 7$	3 $x^3 : 7 + 6 + 7 = 20 \equiv 4$
4 $x^2 : 4 + 2 + 1 = 7$	5 $x^1 : 3$	6 constant: 4

therefore

$$3x^5 + 7x^4 + 4x^3 + 7x^2 + 3x + 4$$

2. $(3x^2 + 2x - 1)$ and $(5x - 4)$

$$-1 \equiv 7$$

$$-4 \equiv 4$$

$$f(x) = 3x^2 + 2x + 7, \quad h(x) = 5x + 4$$

Sum:

$$f + h = (3x^2 + 2x + 7) + (5x + 4) \implies 3x^2 + (2 + 5)x + (7 + 4)$$

Mod 8:

$$2 + 5 = 7$$

$$7 + 4 = 11 \equiv 3$$

So

$$3x^2 + 7x + 3$$

Product:

$$f \cdot h = (3x^2 + 2x + 7)(5x + 4)$$

multiply:

1 $3x^2 \cdot 5x = 15x^3 \equiv 7x^3$	2 $3x^2 \cdot 4 = 12x^2 \equiv 4x^2$	3 $2x \cdot 5x = 10x^2 \equiv 2x^2$
4 $2x \cdot 4 = 8x \equiv 0$	5 $7 \cdot 5x = 35x \equiv 3x$	6 $7 \cdot 4 = 28 \equiv 4$

combine:

$$x^3 : 7, \quad x^2 : 4 + 2 = 6, \quad x^1 : 3, \quad \text{constant: } 4$$

So

$$7x^3 + 6x^2 + 3x + 4$$

(c)

1. $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$ over \mathbb{Z}_5

$$x = 0 \implies 0^4 + 0^3 + 2 \cdot 0^2 + 1 = 1 \neq 0$$

$$x = 1 \implies 1^4 + 1^3 + 2 \cdot 1^2 + 1 = 1 + 1 + 2 + 1 = 5 \equiv 0, \text{ root}$$

$$x = 2 \implies 2^4 + 2^3 + 2 \cdot 2^2 + 1 = 16 + 8 + 8 + 1 = 33 \equiv 3 \neq 0$$

$$x = 3 \implies 3^4 + 3^3 + 2 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 81 + 27 + 18 + 1 = 127 \equiv 2 \neq 0$$

$$x = 4 \implies 4^4 + 4^3 + 2 \cdot 4^2 + 1 = 256 + 64 + 32 + 1 = 353 \equiv 3 \neq 0$$

therefore the only zero in \mathbb{Z}_5 is $x = 1$

2. $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$ over \mathbb{Z}_7

$$x = 0 \implies 0^4 + 0^3 + 2 \cdot 0^2 + 1 = 1 \neq 0$$

$$x = 1 \implies 1^4 + 1^3 + 2 \cdot 1^2 + 1 = 5 \neq 0$$

$$x = 2 \implies 2^4 + 2^3 + 2 \cdot 2^2 + 1 = 16 + 8 + 8 + 1 = 33 \equiv 5 \neq 0$$

$$x = 3 \implies 3^4 + 3^3 + 2 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 81 + 27 + 18 + 1 = 127 \equiv 1 \neq 0$$

$$x = 4 \implies 4^4 + 4^3 + 2 \cdot 4^2 + 1 = 256 + 64 + 32 + 1 = 353 \equiv 3 \neq 0$$

$$x = 5 \implies 5^4 + 5^3 + 2 \cdot 5^2 + 1 = 625 + 125 + 50 + 1 = 801 \equiv 3 \neq 0$$

$$x = 6 \implies 6^4 + 6^3 + 2 \cdot 6^2 + 1 = 1296 + 216 + 72 + 1 = 1585 \equiv 3 \neq 0$$

none are 0, so there is no zero in \mathbb{Z}_7

3. $x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{Q}

$$x^4 - 1 = (x^2 - 1)(x^2 + 1) = (x - 1)(x + 1)(x^2 + 1)$$

The real roots are $x = \pm 1$, therefore the zeros in \mathbb{Q} are $\{-1, 1\}$

4. $x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{C}

again:

$$x^4 - 1 = (x - 1)(x + 1)(x^2 + 1)$$

$$(x^2 + 1) = 0 \implies x^2 = -1 \implies x = \pm\sqrt{-1} \implies x = \pm i$$

Over \mathbb{C} , we get the four zeros: ± 1 and $\pm i$

2. * Prove that if R is an integral domain, then $R[x]$ is an integral domain.

Let $f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + \cdots + a_mx^m$ and $g(x) = b_0 + b_1x + \cdots + b_nx^n$ be nonzero polynomials in $R[x]$. Suppose

$$f(x)g(x) = 0$$

Define

$$\deg(f(x)) = m, \quad \deg(g(x)) = n$$

so $a_m \neq 0$ and $b_n \neq 0$. Consider

$$f(x)g(x) = (a_0 + \cdots + a_mx^m)(b_0 + \cdots + b_nx^n) = c_0 + c_1x + \cdots + c_{m+n}x^{m+n}$$

where

$$c_{m+n} = \underbrace{a_m}_{\in R} \underbrace{b_n}_{\in R} \in R$$

Since R is an integral domain and $a_m, b_n \neq 0$:

$$a_m b_n \neq 0 \implies c_{m+n} \neq 0$$

But if $f(x)g(x) = 0$ (the zero polynomial), then every coefficient c_i must be 0, including c_{m+n} . This is a contradiction because we just found $c_{m+n} = a_m b_n \neq 0$ in R .

So it's impossible for the product $f(x)g(x)$ to be the zero polynomial if both f and g are nonzero. This shows there are no zero-divisors in $R[x] \implies R[x]$ is an integral domain.

3. * Let R be a ring. Describe the units and zero divisors of $R[x]$.

$$R^* = \{ r \in R : \exists s \in R \text{ such that } rs = 1 \}.$$

R is a commutative ring with $1 \neq 0$

$R[x]$ is the polynomial ring over R

(A) Units

$$f(x) \in R[x] \text{ is a unit} \iff \begin{cases} \text{(i) If } R \text{ is an integral domain or a field, then } f(x) \text{ is a nonzero constant} \\ \text{i.e. } f(x) = r \text{ with } r \in R^* \\ \text{(ii) In general, } f(0) \in R^* \text{ and the higher coefficients lie in } \text{Jac}(R) \end{cases}$$

Case 1: R is an integral domain

$\implies R[x]$ is an integral domain

\implies if $\deg f(x) \geq 1$, no inverse exists

$\implies f(x)$ is a unit only if $f(x) \equiv c$ with $c \in R^*$

Case 2: R is arbitrary

If $f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_nx^n$ is a unit

expanding $f(x)g(x) = 1$ means $a_0 \in R^*$

$$(a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_nx^n)(b_0 + b_1x + \dots + b_mx^m) = a_0b_0 + (a_0b_1 + a_1b_0)x + \dots = 1$$

$$\implies a_0b_0 = 1, \quad a_0b_1 + a_1b_0 = 0, \quad \dots$$

and $a_i \in \text{Jac}(R)$ for $i \geq 1$

\implies If R has no nontrivial nilpotents, only nonzero constants are units

$$\text{Units of } R[x] : \begin{cases} \text{If } R \text{ is an integral domain (or field): } f(x) = r \text{ with } r \in R^* \\ \text{If } f(x) \text{ is a unit} \iff a_0 \in R^* \text{ and } a_i \in \text{Jac}(R) \text{ for } i \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

(B) Zero divisors

Definition: $f(x) \neq 0$ is a zero divisor if $\exists g(x) \neq 0$ such that $f(x)g(x) = 0$

Case 1: R is an integral domain

$\implies R[x]$ is an integral domain

\implies no nonzero zero divisors exist in $R[x]$

Case 2: R has zero divisors

$\implies R[x]$ has zero divisors. For instance, if $r \in R$ is a nonzero zero divisor

then the constant polynomial r is a zero divisor in $R[x]$

$$\text{Zero divisors of } R[x] : \begin{cases} \text{If } R \text{ is an integral domain: none (except 0)} \\ \text{If } R \text{ has zero divisors: } R[x] \text{ has zero divisors (e.g. constant zero divisors)} \end{cases}$$

4. Use the division algorithm to solve the following problems:

- (a) Perform the following division of polynomials; that is, given $f(x), g(x)$ find $q(x)$ and $r(x)$ with $\deg(r) < \deg(g)$ such that $f(x) = q(x)g(x) + r(x)$:

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = 2x^2 + 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5$$

- (b) The polynomial $x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$ splits into linear factors over \mathbb{Z}_7 . Find the factorization.

(a)

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$$

$$g(x) = 2x^2 + 1$$

$$f(x) = q(x)g(x) + r(x) \quad \text{with } \deg(r) < 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} & 2x^2 + 1 \overline{) x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1} \\ & \quad - \underline{x^4 \quad + 3x^2} \\ & \quad = \quad x^3 - 2x^2 + x + 1 \quad (\text{since } -2 \equiv 3) \\ & \quad - \underline{x^3 \quad + 3x} \\ & \quad = \quad 3x^2 - 2x + 1 \\ & \quad - \underline{3x^2 \quad + 4} \\ & \quad = \quad 3x + 2 \quad (\text{since } 1 - 4 = -3 \equiv 2) \end{aligned}$$

Quotient:

$$q(x) = 3x^2 + 3x + 4$$

Remainder:

$$r(x) = 3x + 2$$

Therefore,

$$\underbrace{x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1}_{f(x)} = \underbrace{(3x^2 + 3x + 4)}_{q(x)} \underbrace{(2x^2 + 1)}_{g(x)} + \underbrace{(3x + 2)}_{r(x)} \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

(b)

$$f(x) = x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$$

checking roots in $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$:

$$2^3 + 2 \cdot 2^2 + 2 \cdot 2 + 1 = 8 + 8 + 4 + 1 = 21 \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$$

$x = 2$ is a root, so $x - 2 \equiv x + 5$ is a factor.

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{array}{r} x^2 + 4x + 3 \\ x + 5 \overline{) x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1} \\ \underline{- x^3 + 5x^2} \\ (2 - 5)x^2 + 2x + 1 = -3x^2 + 2x + 1 \\ \equiv 4x^2 + 2x + 1 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_7) \\ \underline{- 4x^2 + 20x} \\ 4x^2 + (2 - 20)x + 1 = 4x^2 - 18x + 1 \\ \equiv 4x^2 + 6x + 1 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_7) \\ \underline{- 3x + 1} \\ = 0 \end{array} \end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$\frac{x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1}{x + 5} = x^2 + 4x + 3$$

$$x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1 = (x + 5)(x^2 + 4x + 3)$$

$$\boxed{x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1 = (x + 5)(x + 3)(x + 1) \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_7[x]}$$

5. * Calculate the multiplicative inverse of $x + 2$ in the ring $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$.
 (Here $(x^2 + 1) = \{f(x)(x^2 + 1) : f \in \mathbb{Q}[x]\}$, the ideal generated by $x^2 + 1$)

$$\text{In } \mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1), \quad x^2 = -1$$

We need

$$(x + 2)^{-1} \equiv a + bx \pmod{x^2 + 1}$$

with $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}$

$$(x + 2)(a + bx) \equiv ax + 2a + bx^2 + 2bx$$

Since $x^2 \equiv -1$, $bx^2 \equiv -b$.

$$(x + 2)(a + bx) \equiv -b + (a + 2b)x + 2a$$

We need this $\equiv 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$:

$$\begin{cases} \text{constant: } -b + 2a = 1 \\ \text{coefficient: } a + 2b = 0 \end{cases}$$

From $a + 2b = 0 \implies a = -2b$. Substitute into $-b + 2a = 1$:

$$-b + 2(-2b) = 1 \implies -b - 4b = 1 \implies -5b = 1 \implies b = -\frac{1}{5}$$

$$a = -2\left(-\frac{1}{5}\right) = \frac{2}{5}$$

Therefore

$$(x + 2)^{-1} \equiv a + bx = \frac{2}{5} - \frac{x}{5} = \frac{2-x}{5} \pmod{x^2 + 1}$$

1. Check if the following polynomials are irreducible or not in their respective rings:

- (a) $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- (b) $x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
- (c) $x^2 + 69x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_{71}[x]$
- (d) $420x^3 + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_{421}[x]$ (Hint: 421 is prime)
- (e) * $x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
- (f) $7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 25x + 15$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

(a) In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$

$$(x^2 + ax + b)(x^2 + cx + d)$$

Matching coefficients:

$$x^4 : 1 = 1, \quad x^3 : a + c = 1, \quad x^2 : ac + b + d = 2, \quad x^1 : ad + bc = 1, \quad x^0 : bd = 1$$

$$bd = 1 \implies b = 1, d = 1 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Q})$$

$$ac + b + d = 2 \implies ac + 1 + 1 = 2 \implies ac = 0 \implies \{a = 0, c = 1\} \text{ or } \{a = 1, c = 0\}$$

Either choice works; let $a = 0, c = 1$

$$ad + bc = (0)(1) + (1)(1) = 1 \implies \text{consistent}$$

$$(x^2 + 0x + 1)(x^2 + 1x + 1) = x^4 + x^3 + (1+1)x^2 + x + 1 = x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$$

$$\implies x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) \implies \text{reducible in } \mathbb{Q}[x]$$

(b) In $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$

Possible roots $x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$x = 0 \implies 0^3 + 2 \cdot 0^2 + 1 = 1 \neq 0$$

$$x = 1 \implies 1^3 + 2 \cdot 1^2 + 1 = 1 + 2 + 1 = 4 \neq 0$$

$$x = 2 \implies 2^3 + 2 \cdot 2^2 + 1 = 8 + 2 \cdot 4 + 1 = 8 + 8 + 1 = 17 \equiv 2 \neq 0$$

$$x = 3 \implies 3^3 + 2 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 27 + 2 \cdot 9 + 1 = 27 + 18 + 1 = 46 \equiv 1 \neq 0$$

$$x = 4 \implies 4^3 + 2 \cdot 4^2 + 1 = 64 + 2 \cdot 16 + 1 = 64 + 32 + 1 = 97 \equiv 2 \neq 0$$

No root in $\mathbb{Z}_5 \implies$ no linear factor. A cubic with no linear factor over a field is irreducible.

$$\implies x^3 + 2x^2 + 1 \text{ is irreducible in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

(c) In $\mathbb{Z}_{71}[x]$: $x^2 + 69x + 1$

$$\text{Discriminant: } \Delta = 69^2 - 4$$

$$69^2 = 4761, \quad 4761 - 4 = 4757$$

Reduce 4761 mod 71: $4761 \div 71 = 67$ remainder 4, so $4761 \equiv 4 \pmod{71}$

$$\implies \Delta \equiv 4 - 4 = 0 \pmod{71}$$

$$\implies \Delta \equiv 0 \pmod{71} \implies x^2 + 69x + 1 \text{ is a perfect square in } \mathbb{Z}_{71}[x]$$

$$\implies x^2 + 69x + 1 = (x + \alpha)^2 \text{ for some } \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{71}$$

$$\implies x^2 + 69x + 1 \text{ is reducible over } \mathbb{Z}_{71}$$

(d) In $\mathbb{Z}_{421}[x]$: $420x^3 + 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 420 &\equiv -1 \pmod{421} \implies 420x^3 + 1 \equiv -x^3 + 1 = 1 - x^3 \\ 1 - x^3 &= (1-x)(1+x+x^2) \implies 420x^3 + 1 \equiv (1-x)(1+x+x^2) \pmod{421} \\ &\implies 420x^3 + 1 \text{ is reducible in } \mathbb{Z}_{421}[x] \end{aligned}$$

(e) In $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2$

Test $x = 1$ in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$1^4 + 3 \cdot 1^3 + 4 \cdot 1 + 2 = 1 + 3 + 4 + 2 = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

So $x = 1$ is a root, which means $(x-1) \equiv (x+4)$ is a factor in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. Using synthetic division, the coefficients of $x^4 + 3x^3 + 0x^2 + 4x + 2$ are:

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrrr} & & 1, & 3, & 0, & 4, & 2 \\ 1 & & 1 & 3 & 0 & 4 & 2 \\ & & & 1 & 4 & 4 & 3 \\ \hline & & 1 & 4 & 4 & 3 & 0 \end{array}$$

From the bottom row, the quotient is

$$x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 3 \pmod{5}$$

Therefore

$$x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2 = (x+4)(x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 3)$$

Looking for roots of $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 3$ in \mathbb{Z}_5 , $x = 2$ works:

$$2^3 + 4 \cdot 2^2 + 4 \cdot 2 + 3 = 8 + 16 + 8 + 3 = 35 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

So $(x-2) \equiv (x+3)$ is another factor. Dividing $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 3$ by $(x+3)$ gives $x^2 + x + 1$.

Checking if $x^2 + x + 1$ is irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. Its discriminant is

$$\Delta = 1^2 - 4 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 = 1 - 4 = -3 \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$$

and 2 is not a square in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Therefore $x^2 + x + 1$ has no roots in \mathbb{Z}_5 and is irreducible.

$$x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2 = (x+4)(x+3)(x^2 + x + 1)$$

so it is reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

(f) In $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 25x + 15$

Reduce coefficients mod 5 :

$$7 \equiv 2, \quad 5 \equiv 0, \quad 10 \equiv 0, \quad 25 \equiv 0, \quad 15 \equiv 0$$

$$\implies 7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 25x + 15 \equiv 2x^4 + 0x^3 + 0x^2 + 0x + 0 = 2x^4$$

2 is a unit in \mathbb{Z}_5 , so $2x^4$ is associate to x^4

$x^4 = x \cdot x \cdot x \cdot x \implies x^4$ is not irreducible.

$$\implies 7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 25x + 15 \text{ is reducible in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

- (a) reducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$,
- (b) irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$,
- (c) reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_{71}[x]$,
- (d) reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_{421}[x]$,
- (e) reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$,
- (f) reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

2. (a) When $f(x) \in F[x]$ (F is a field) is irreducible, then we will see that $R = F[x]/(f)$ is a field. If f is not irreducible however, we might not necessarily have R is a field, but some elements will still be units in the quotient. For example, $f(x) = x^2$ is not irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. However, $x + 1$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$. Find its inverse.
- (b) Give a criteria for when a polynomial $g(x)$ has an inverse in $F[x]/(f)$. Give a proof of sufficiency of your criteria. (Prove that everything satisfying your criteria has an inverse. The reverse proof is hard - but bonus points to you if you can do it!)

a

In $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$, $u(x) = x + 1$. Seek $v(x) \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$ with $u(x)v(x) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2}$

Set $v(x) = a + bx$. Then:

$$(x + 1)(a + bx) = \underbrace{x \cdot a}_{=ax} + \underbrace{x \cdot bx}_{=bx^2} + \underbrace{1 \cdot a}_{=a} + \underbrace{1 \cdot bx}_{=bx} = a + (a + b)x + bx^2$$

Modulo x^2 , $bx^2 \equiv 0 \implies (x + 1)(a + bx) \equiv a + (a + b)x$

Require $a = 1$ and $a + b = 0 \implies b = -1$ $v(x) = 1 - x$

Check: $(x + 1)(1 - x) = (x + 1) \cdot 1 - (x + 1) \cdot x = x + 1 - x^2 - x = 1 - x^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2}$

Therefore the inverse of $\overline{x + 1}$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$ is $\overline{1 - x}$

b

Generally, in $F[x]/(f)$, $g(x)$ is invertible when $\gcd(f, g) = 1$

$\gcd(f, g) = 1 \implies \exists a(x), b(x) \in F[x]$ with $a(x)g(x) + b(x)f(x) = 1$

In $F[x]/(f) \implies \overline{a(x)g(x)} = \overline{1} \implies$ the inverse of $\overline{g(x)}$ is $\overline{a(x)}$

Conversly, suppose $g(x) \in F[x]/(f)$ is invertible. Then there exists $\overline{h(x)}$ such that

$$\overline{g(x)h(x)} = \overline{1}$$

This implies

$$g(x)h(x) - 1 = f(x)q(x) \quad \text{for some } q(x) \in F[x]$$

Therefore

$1 \in (f, g) \implies$ any common divisor of f and g must also divide 1
the ideal generated by f and g

It follows that

$$\gcd(f, g) = 1$$

So $\gcd(f, g) = 1$ is both necessary and sufficient for $\overline{g(x)}$ to be invertible in $F[x]/(f)$

1 Problems

1. Let R be an integral domain, and let I, J be ideals of R . Recall on a previous homework that we proved that the set

$$IJ := \{ab : a \in I, b \in J\}$$

is not necessarily an ideal. Prove the following statements:

- If R is a principal ideal domain, then IJ is an ideal.
- The set $IJ' := \{a_1b_1 + \cdots + a_nb_n : a_i \in I, b_i \in J\}$ is an ideal of R .

26.10 Definition An additive subgroup N of a ring R satisfying the properties

$$aN \subseteq N \quad \text{and} \quad Nb \subseteq N \quad \text{for all } a, b \in R$$

is an ideal.

27.21 Definition If R is a commutative ring with unity and $a \in R$, the ideal $\{ra \mid r \in R\}$ of all multiples of a is the **principal ideal generated by a** and is denoted by $\langle a \rangle$. An ideal N of R is a **principal ideal** if $N = \langle a \rangle$ for some $a \in R$. ■

27.22 Example Every ideal of the ring \mathbb{Z} is of the form $n\mathbb{Z}$, which is generated by n , so every ideal of \mathbb{Z} is a principal ideal. ▲

45.7 Definition An integral domain D is a **principal ideal domain** (abbreviated PID) if every ideal in D is a principal ideal. ■

(a)

Assume R is a principal ideal domain and

$$I = (x), J = (y) \implies I = \{rx \mid r \in R\}, J = \{sy \mid s \in R\}$$

$$\forall a \in I, b \in J \implies a = rx, b = sy$$

$$\implies ab = (rx)(sy) = (rs)(xy) \implies ab \in (xy)$$

$$\{ab \mid a \in I, b \in J\} \subseteq (xy) \implies IJ = (xy) \implies IJ \text{ is an ideal}$$

(b)

$$IJ' = \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n a_k b_k \mid a_k \in I, b_k \in J \right\}$$

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i, y = \sum_{j=1}^m c_j d_j \implies x + y = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i + \sum_{j=1}^m c_j d_j = \sum_{k=1}^{n+m} e_k f_k \in IJ'$$

$$r \in R, x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \in IJ' \implies rx = \sum_{i=1}^n (r a_i) b_i \in IJ'$$

$$\implies IJ' \text{ is closed under addition and } R\text{-multiplication} \implies IJ' \text{ is an ideal}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle a \rangle &= (0, a, r_1 a, r_2 a, \dots, r_n a) \\ IJ &= \{r_i a s_j b : a \in I, b \in J\} \\ r_i a s_j b + r_k a s_l b &= ab(r_i s_j + r_k s_l) \\ IJ = a_i b_i &\implies a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 \neq a_3 b_3 \\ IJ' &= \sum_{k=1}^n a_k b_k, a_k \in I, b_k \in J \end{aligned}$$

2. Prove that the ideal $(2, x) = \{f \in \mathbb{Z}[x] : f(0) \text{ is even}\} = \{2f(x) + xg(x) : f, g \in \mathbb{Z}[x]\}$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is not principal, i.e. there exists no element $a(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ such that $(a) = (2, x)$.

Suppose $(2, x) = (a(x))$ for some $a(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$

$\implies 2 = a(x)f(x)$ and $x = a(x)g(x)$ for some $f, g \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$

$x = 0 \implies 2k = a(0)f(0)$ so $a(0)f(0) \mid 2$ ($f(0) = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2$), $a(0) = 2$

$x = 0 \implies 0 = a(0)g(0) \implies a(0) = 0$ or $g(0) = 0$

But $a(0) = 0 \implies 2 = 0$, contradiction; so $g(0) = 0 \implies g(x) = xh(x)$ for some $h(x) \implies x = a(x)xh(x) \implies a(x)h(x) = 1 \implies a(x)$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$

Therefore $(a(x)) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \implies (2, x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$

But $1 \notin (2, x)$ since any $2p(0) + xq(0)$ is even at $x = 0$. Contradiction.

$\therefore (2, x)$ is not principal in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

$a(x)$ being a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, means $|a(0)| = 1$ and $a(x)$ has no other prime factors.

But $a(x)$ cannot satisfy both $2 = q(x)a(x)$ with $a(x)$ a unit unless 2 itself were also a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, which is false. If a were a unit, then the ideal (a) would be the entire ring $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, contradicting the fact that $1 \notin (2, x)$. (ie. $(2, x)$ clearly does not contain the constant polynomial 1.) So our initial assumption that $(2, x) = (a(x))$ for some $a(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ leads to a contradiction. Therefore, $(2, x)$ is not principal in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

3. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the following statements:

- If R is a principal ideal domain, then every prime ideal of R is also a maximal ideal.
- If $R[x]$ is a principal ideal domain, then actually R is a field.

19.6 Definition An integral domain D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0. ■

27.21 Definition If R is a commutative ring with unity and $a \in R$, the ideal $\{ra \mid r \in R\}$ of all multiples of a is the **principal ideal generated by a** and is denoted by $\langle a \rangle$. An ideal N of R is a **principal ideal** if $N = \langle a \rangle$ for some $a \in R$. ■

27.22 Example Every ideal of the ring \mathbb{Z} is of the form $n\mathbb{Z}$, which is generated by n , so every ideal of \mathbb{Z} is a principal ideal. ▲

45.7 Definition An integral domain D is a **principal ideal domain** (abbreviated PID) if every ideal in D is a principal ideal. ■

27.25 Theorem An ideal $\langle p(x) \rangle \neq \{0\}$ of $F[x]$ is maximal if and only if $p(x)$ is irreducible over F .

45.12 Lemma (Generalization of Theorem 27.25) An ideal $\langle p \rangle$ in a PID is maximal if and only if p is an irreducible.

27.13 Definition An ideal $N \neq R$ in a commutative ring R is a **prime ideal** if $ab \in N$ implies that either $a \in N$ or $b \in N$ for $a, b \in R$. ■

Note that $\{0\}$ is a prime ideal in \mathbb{Z} , and indeed, in any integral domain.

27.9 Theorem (Analogue of Theorem 15.18) Let R be a commutative ring with unity. Then M is a maximal ideal of R if and only if R/M is a field.

$$p \in R \text{ prime} : (p \mid ab) \implies (p \mid a) \vee (p \mid b)$$

Part 1

Suppose $p = xy$ with x, y nonunits. Let $a = pc$

$$p \mid a \implies p \mid (xy)c \implies p \mid x \vee p \mid (yc)$$

Case $p \mid x$: $x = pd \implies p = pdy \implies 1 = dy \implies x$ is a unit (contradiction).

Case $p \mid (yc)$: $p \mid y \vee p \mid c \implies$ a nonunit becomes a unit (contradiction).

$\implies p$ irreducible.

In a UFD, irreducible \implies prime $\implies p$ prime $\implies (p)$ prime ideal.

In a PID, prime \iff irreducible. For a nonzero prime ideal $(p) \subset R$

p is prime element $\implies (p)$ is maximal (no proper ideals lie between (p) and R)

Part 2

If $R[x]$ is a PID and $r \in R \setminus \{0\}$ is nonunit, set $I = \langle r, x \rangle$

I is principal: $I = \langle d(x) \rangle$, $\deg(d(x)) \geq 0$, $d(x) \mid r$, $d(x) \mid x$

$$x \in I \implies x = d(x)k(x) \implies 1 = \deg x = \deg d + \deg k$$

$\deg(d) > 0 \implies \deg(k) = 1 - \deg(d) < 1 \implies k$ constant or zero.

$$x \neq 0 \implies k \neq 0 \implies \deg(d) = 0 \implies d(x) = d \in R, d \neq 0$$

Since d is a unit, we have $\langle d \rangle = R$ and $r = d \cdot h \in \langle d \rangle$, so $\langle r \rangle = R$, where r is a unit.

$x = dk(x) \implies d$ divides $x \implies d$ is a unit in R (otherwise $x = 0$)

$$r = d(x)h(x) = dh, \deg(h(x)) = 0 \implies r \text{ is unit (contradiction).}$$

\implies every nonzero $r \in R$ is a unit $\implies R$ is a field.

4. We saw during class (for the example $\mathbb{Z}[-\sqrt{5}]$) that we can have elements that are irreducible but not prime. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the following statements:

- Every prime element is irreducible.
- If R is a unique factorization domain, then every irreducible element is prime.

19.6 Definition An integral domain D is a commutative ring with unity $1 \neq 0$ and containing no divisors of 0. ■

45.2 Definition An element u of a commutative ring with unity R is a **unit** of R if u divides 1, that is, if u has a multiplicative inverse in R . Two elements $a, b \in R$ are **associates** in R if $a = bu$, where u is a unit in R .

Exercise 27 asks us to show that this criterion for a and b to be associates is an equivalence relation on R . ■

45.4 Definition A nonzero element p that is not a unit of an integral domain D is an **irreducible** of D if in every factorization $p = ab$ in D has the property that either a or b is a unit. ■

45.15 Definition A nonzero nonunit element p of an integral domain D is a **prime** if, for all $a, b \in D$, $p \mid ab$ implies either $p \mid a$ or $p \mid b$. ■

Part 1

Given $p \in R$ prime: $(p \mid ab) \implies (p \mid a) \text{ or } (p \mid b)$. Want to show p is irreducible.

Assume $p = xy$ with x, y both nonunits. Let $a = pc$

$$p \mid a \implies p \mid (xy)c \implies p \mid x \text{ or } p \mid (yc)$$

Case $p \mid x$: $x = pd \implies p = pdy \implies 1 = dy \implies x$ is a unit (contradiction).

Case $p \mid (yc) \implies p \mid y \text{ or } p \mid c \implies$ again forces y or c to be a unit (contradiction).

No such factorization can exist, so p is irreducible.

Part 2

Let $a \in R$ be irreducible and $a \mid bc$. In a UFD, write factorizations

$$a = ua_1, \quad b = vb_1b_2 \cdots b_m, \quad c = wc_1c_2 \cdots c_n$$

where each b_i, c_j, a_1 is irreducible, and u, v, w are units. Then

$$bc = (vw)(b_1 \cdots b_m)(c_1 \cdots c_n)$$

Since $a \mid bc$, the irreducible a_1 (up to a unit factor) must appear among

$$b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n.$$

Therefore, $a \mid b$ or $a \mid c$. So a is prime.

1. Prove that $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$. This shows that $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$ is a simple extension.

Basis for $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}\}$

$$(a + b\sqrt{2})(c + d\sqrt{2}) = ac + 2bd + (ad + bc)\sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$$

Show the basis for $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$: $(a + b(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}))(c + d(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})) = ac + ad\sqrt{2} + ad\sqrt{3} + bc\sqrt{2} + 2bd + bd\sqrt{6} + bc\sqrt{3} + bd\sqrt{6} + 3bd$

Combine like terms : $(a + b(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}))(c + d(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})) = ac + 5bd + (ad + bc)\sqrt{2} + (ad + bc)\sqrt{3} + 2bd\sqrt{6}$

Combine rational terms: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}\}$

Show the basis for $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$: $(a + b\sqrt{2})(c + d\sqrt{3}) = ac + bc\sqrt{2} + ad\sqrt{3} + bd\sqrt{6}$

Combine rational terms: $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{2} + c\sqrt{3} + d\sqrt{6} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}\}$

$$\therefore \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}) = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$$

2. This exercise studies the field extension $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$ over \mathbb{Q} .

- What is the \mathbb{Q} -vector space dimension of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$? Find a basis to support your claim.
- What is the $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$ -vector space dimension of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$? Find a basis to support your claim.
- What is the \mathbb{Q} -vector space dimension of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3})$? Find a basis to support your claim. (Hint: use the previous two parts)
- Find the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$ over \mathbb{Q} . What do you notice about the degree of this polynomial?

$$(a) \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = \deg(x^2 - 2) = 2 \implies \text{a basis over } \mathbb{Q} \text{ is } \{1, \sqrt{2}\}$$

$$x^2 - 2 \implies \underbrace{\{1, x\}}_{\text{dimension 2}}$$

$$(b) \quad \sqrt{3} \notin \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) \implies x^2 - 3 \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$$

$$\implies [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})] = 2 \implies \text{a basis over } \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) \text{ is } \{1, \sqrt{3}\}$$

$$(c) \quad [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}] = [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}) : \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})] \cdot [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2 \cdot 2 = 4$$

Therefore a basis over \mathbb{Q} is $\{1, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}, \sqrt{6}\}$.

This makes sense since $\sqrt{2}^2$ and $\sqrt{3}^2$ is in the basis of 1 but $\sqrt{2} \cdot \sqrt{3}$ is $\sqrt{6}$ which is not a multiple of the other elements

$$(d) \quad \alpha := \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$$

$$\alpha^2 = 2 + 3 + 2\sqrt{6} = 5 + 2\sqrt{6} \implies \alpha^2 - 5 = 2\sqrt{6} \implies (\alpha^2 - 5)^2 = 24$$

$$\implies \alpha^4 - 10\alpha^2 + 25 = 24 \implies \alpha^4 - 10\alpha^2 + 1 = 0$$

Therefore the minimal polynomial of $(\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$ over \mathbb{Q} is $x^4 - 10x^2 + 1$,

whose degree is 4

Explicitly we see $(x - \alpha) \cdot (x + \alpha) =$

$$(x - (\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}))(x + \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})$$

$$x^2 + x\sqrt{2} + x\sqrt{3} - x\sqrt{2} - 2 - \sqrt{6} - x\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{6} - 3$$

$$x^2 - 5 - 2\sqrt{6}$$

Multiply by conjugate

$$(x^2 - 5 - 2\sqrt{6})(x^2 - 5 + 2\sqrt{6})$$

$$x^4 - 5x^2 + 2\sqrt{6}x^2 - 5x^2 + 25 - 10\sqrt{6} - 2\sqrt{6}x^2 + 10\sqrt{6} - 24$$

$$\implies \alpha^4 - 10\alpha^2 + 25 = 24 \implies \alpha^4 - 10\alpha^2 + 1 = 0$$

So this must be the minimal polynomial, the degree is 4 so the basis also degree 4. (See lecture notes march 10)

Statement. Let $f \in F[x]$ be an irreducible monic polynomial of degree n . Then

$$\{1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{n-1}\}$$

is a basis of the quotient ring $F[x]/(f)$ considered as an F -vector space. In particular,

$$[F[x]/(f) : F] = n = \deg(f).$$

3. This exercise studies the field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i)$, as well as its relationship with the polynomial $f(x) = x^4 - 2$.

- (a) Find the roots of $f(x) = x^4 - 2$.
 (b) List all of the subfields of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i)$ containing \mathbb{Q} . (There are 10, including $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i)$ and \mathbb{Q})
 (c) Find the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt[4]{2}$.
 (d) Find the minimal polynomial of i .

(a) In \mathbb{C} , $x^4 = 2 \implies x = \sqrt[4]{2} \zeta^k$, where $\zeta^4 = 1$. Taking $\zeta \in \{1, i, -1, -i\}$ gives the four distinct roots

$$\sqrt[4]{2}, \quad -\sqrt[4]{2}, \quad i\sqrt[4]{2}, \quad -i\sqrt[4]{2}.$$

(b)
 $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[n]{k}) = a + b\sqrt[n]{k} + c(\sqrt[n]{k})^2 + \dots + a_n(\sqrt[n]{k})^{n-1}$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}) : (a + b\sqrt[4]{2})(c + d\sqrt[4]{2}) \qquad \mathbb{Q}(i) = a + bi$$

$$ac + ad\sqrt[4]{2} + cb\sqrt[4]{2} + cd\sqrt[4]{4}$$

$$= ac + ad\sqrt[4]{2} + cb\sqrt[4]{2} + cd\sqrt{2}$$

$$(a + b\sqrt[4]{2} + c\sqrt{2})(d + e\sqrt[4]{2} + f\sqrt{2})$$

$$= \underbrace{ad}_{(1)} + \underbrace{ae\sqrt[4]{2}}_{(2)} + \underbrace{af\sqrt{2}}_{(3)} + \underbrace{bd\sqrt[4]{2}}_{(4)} + \underbrace{be\sqrt{2}}_{(5)} + \underbrace{bf(\sqrt[4]{2})^3}_{(6)} + \underbrace{cd\sqrt{2}}_{(7)} + \underbrace{ce(\sqrt[4]{2})^3}_{(8)} + \underbrace{2cf}_{(9)}$$

$$= \underbrace{(ad + 2cf)}_{\text{constant}} + \underbrace{(ae + bd)}_{\text{coeff. of } \sqrt[4]{2}} \sqrt[4]{2} + \underbrace{(af + be + cd)}_{\text{coeff. of } \sqrt{2}} \sqrt{2} + \underbrace{(bf + ce)}_{\text{coeff. of } (\sqrt[4]{2})^3} (\sqrt[4]{2})^3.$$

$$\therefore \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}) = \{a + b\sqrt[4]{2} + c\sqrt{2} + d(\sqrt[4]{2})^3 \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}\}$$

$$e \cdot (a + b\sqrt[4]{2} + c\sqrt{2} + d(\sqrt[4]{2})^3) \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2})$$

$$+ fi \cdot (a + b\sqrt[4]{2} + c\sqrt{2} + d(\sqrt[4]{2})^3) \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}i)$$

$$\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i) = \{a + b\sqrt[4]{2} + c\sqrt{2} + d(\sqrt[4]{2})^3 + ei + f\sqrt[4]{2}i + g\sqrt{2}i + h(\sqrt[4]{2})^3i \mid a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h \in \mathbb{Q}\}$$

$$x^4 - 2 \text{ irreducible over } \mathbb{Q} \text{ (Eisenstein at } p = 2) \implies [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 4$$

$$i \text{ satisfies } x^2 + 1 = 0 \implies [\mathbb{Q}(i) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2, \quad i \notin \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2})$$

$$\implies [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i) : \mathbb{Q}] = [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i) : \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2})][\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] = 2 \cdot 4 = 8$$

Therefore the extension is degree 8

Possible subfield degrees divide 8 $\implies \{1, 2, 4, 8\}$

By "Fund. Thm. of Galois Theory" one we have 10 intermediate fields:

Degree 1 : \mathbb{Q}

Degree 2 : $\mathbb{Q}(i), \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}), \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-2})$

Degree 4 : $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}), \mathbb{Q}(i\sqrt[4]{2}), \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}, i), \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}(1+i)), \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}(1-i))$

Degree 8 : $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i)$

(c) Since $x^4 - 2$ is irreducible (Eisenstein), it is the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt[4]{2}$

(d) $\pm i$ are the roots of $x^2 + 1$ over \mathbb{C} . It is irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ since it has no real roots, therefore

$$x^2 + 1$$

is the minimal polynomial of i . (Over $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2})$, the same argument shows $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible, since $\sqrt[4]{2}$ is real and does not have an imaginary unit.)

4. This exercise studies the field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)$, where $\zeta = \frac{-1+i\sqrt{3}}{2}$ is a primitive third root of unity. (Notice $\zeta^3 = 1$, hence why it is called a *third root of unity* because in some sense $\zeta = \sqrt[3]{1}$)

- (a) Find the minimal polynomial of ζ . (Hint: Try to factor $x^3 - 1$. The number ζ couldn't possibly be a root of $x - 1$...)
- (b) Find all of the subfields of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)$ containing \mathbb{Q} . (there are 6, including $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)$ and \mathbb{Q})

(a) $x^3 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^2 + x + 1) \implies \zeta \neq 1 \implies \zeta$ is a root of $x^2 + x + 1$
 Over \mathbb{Q} , the polynomial $x^2 + x + 1$ has no rational root (discriminant $1 - 4 < 0$), so it is irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Therefore $x^2 + x + 1$ is the minimal polynomial of ζ over \mathbb{Q}

(b) $[\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta) : \mathbb{Q}] = [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}) : \mathbb{Q}] \cdot [\mathbb{Q}(\zeta) : \mathbb{Q}] = 3 \cdot 2 = 6$

There are exactly six subfields containing \mathbb{Q} .

$$\mathbb{Q}, \quad \mathbb{Q}(\zeta), \quad \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}), \quad \mathbb{Q}(\zeta \sqrt[3]{2}), \quad \mathbb{Q}(\zeta^2 \sqrt[3]{2}), \quad \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2}, \zeta)$$

The first and last are \mathbb{Q} and the entire field, and the others correspond (by Theorem 23.20) to fixing or adjoining different roots.

1. ** This exercise calculates $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i))$, which is the splitting field of the polynomial $x^4 - 2$.

- (a) In the previous homework, you calculated the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt[4]{2}$, which is $f(x) = x^4 - 2$. Find the other 3 roots of this polynomial.
- (b) In the previous homework, you calculated the minimal polynomial of i , which is $f(x) = x^2 + 1$. What is the other root of this polynomial?
- (c) Find a basis for $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i)$ as a vector space over \mathbb{Q} .
- (d) Observe (using your basis), that for any automorphism $\varphi \in \text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i))$, if we know $\varphi(\sqrt[4]{2})$ and $\varphi(i)$, the entire automorphism is determined. (Since φ fixes \mathbb{Q}). Furthermore, we know that φ permutes the roots of $x^4 - 2$, and $x^2 + 1$. With this information, make a list of the elements of $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i))$.
- (e) Two of the items in your list should be the following automorphisms:

$$\sigma : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto i\sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto i \end{cases}$$

$$\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto -i \end{cases}$$

There exists a relation of the form $\sigma^k \tau = \tau \sigma$ where $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Find k .

e)

$k = 3$, see part d

a)

$$1^{1/n} = e^{i(2\pi/n + 2k\pi/n)}$$

$$n = 4, 1^{1/4} = e^{i(2\pi/4 + 2k\pi/4)} = e^{ik\pi/2}, k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$$

$$2^{1/4} = \sqrt[4]{2} e^{ik\pi/2}$$

$$x^4 = 2 \implies x = \{\sqrt[4]{2}, -\sqrt[4]{2}, \sqrt[4]{2}i, -\sqrt[4]{2}i\}$$

b)

$$x^2 + 1 = 0 \implies x = \{i, -i\}$$

because for polynomials of real coefficients, if one of the roots is a complex number with nonzero imaginary part, then its conjugate must also be a root of the polynomial.

c)

$$\{1, i, \sqrt[4]{2}, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt[4]{8}, \sqrt[4]{2}i, \sqrt{2}i, \sqrt[4]{8}i\} \implies [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[4]{2}, i) : \mathbb{Q}] = 8$$

d)

$$e : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto i \end{cases} \quad \sigma(\sqrt[4]{8}) = \sigma((\sqrt[4]{2})^3) = (i\sqrt[4]{2})^3 = -i\sqrt[4]{8}$$

$$\sigma : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[4]{2}i \\ i \mapsto i \end{cases}$$

$$\rho^k \mu = \mu \rho^{n-k}$$

$$\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto -i \end{cases}$$

$$\{e, \sigma, \tau, \sigma^2, \sigma^3, \cancel{\sigma\tau}, \tau\sigma, \cancel{\sigma^2\tau}, \sigma^3\tau, \tau\sigma^3, \tau\sigma^3\}$$

$$\sigma^2 : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto -\sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto i \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma^3 : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto -\sqrt[4]{2}i \\ i \mapsto i \end{cases}$$

$$\tau\sigma = \sigma^3\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto -\sqrt[4]{2}i \\ i \mapsto -i \end{cases}$$

$$\tau\sigma^2 = \sigma^2\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto -\sqrt[4]{2} \\ i \mapsto -i \end{cases}$$

$$\tau\sigma^3 = \sigma\tau : \begin{cases} \sqrt[4]{2} \mapsto \sqrt[4]{2}i \\ i \mapsto -i \end{cases}$$

Homework 1

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due January 15th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Let R be a ring. Prove the following:

- Suppose further that R has a multiplicative identity, and let $a \in R$. If a has a multiplicative inverse, then it is unique.
- If R has a multiplicative identity, then it is unique.

Solution.

- Let $a \in R$, and let b, c be multiplicative inverses of a . Then, $ab = ba = 1, ac = ca = 1$. Then, we must have

$$b = b(1) = b(ac) = (ba)c = 1c = c$$

so that multiplicative inverses are unique.

- Suppose $1, 1'$ are both multiplicative identities of R . Then,

$$1 = 1 \cdot 1' = 1'$$

where the left equality holds because $1'$ is a multiplicative identity, and the right equality holds because 1 is a multiplicative identity.

2. Consider the ring $R = \mathbb{Z}_{12} := \{\bar{0}, \dots, \bar{11}\}$ under addition and multiplication modulo 12.

- Find two nontrivial subrings of R .
- List all of the zero divisors of R .
- List all of the units of R , and calculate their multiplicative inverses.

Solution.

- There are many, but they are $\langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10\}$, $\langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3, 6, 9\}$, $\langle 4 \rangle = \{0, 4, 8\}$, $\langle 6 \rangle = \{0, 6\}$. The key is to look for abelian subgroups of \mathbb{Z}_{12} , which were studied in 103A; they coincidentally all happen to be sub-rings.
- The zero divisors of R are 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 10. All of these elements share a factor with 12 ($\gcd(x, 12) > 1$). In particular, $2 \cdot 6 = 3 \cdot 4 = 8 \cdot 9 = 6 \cdot 10 = 0$.
- The units of R are then the numbers relatively prime to 12, which are 1, 5, 7, 11. We have $1 \cdot 1 = 5 \cdot 5 = 7 \cdot 7 = 11 \cdot 11 = 1$, so that all of these elements are their own multiplicative inverses.

3. Show that \mathbb{Z}_7 is a field.

Solution. It is clear that \mathbb{Z}_7 is commutative. We show all elements have multiplicative inverses. In particular, $1 \cdot 1 = 2 \cdot 4 = 3 \cdot 5 = 6 \cdot 6 = 1$, and we are done.

4.* Suppose R, S are rings with unity, and denote the multiplicative identities 1_R and 1_S respectively. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a surjective ring homomorphism. Prove that $\varphi(1_R) = 1_S$.

Solution. If φ is surjective, then there is $x \in R$ such that $\varphi(x) = 1_S$. Since φ is a ring homomorphism, we have that $1_S = \varphi(x) = \varphi(x \cdot 1_R) = \varphi(x)\varphi(1_R) = 1_S\varphi(1_R) = \varphi(1_R)$ and we win.

5. Let R, S be rings, and $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Prove that φ is injective if and only if $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$. (Recall that $\ker(\varphi) := \{x \in R : \varphi(x) = 0\}$)

Solution. (\implies) Suppose φ is injective. First, we show that $\varphi(0) = 0$. By the homomorphism property, we have that $\varphi(0) = \varphi(0 + 0) = \varphi(0) + \varphi(0)$. Subtracting $\varphi(0)$ from both sides, we obtain that $0 = \varphi(0)$, so that $0 \in \ker(\varphi)$. Since φ is injective, we conclude that $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$.

(\impliedby) Suppose that $\ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$. Recall an equivalent definition of injectivity - $\varphi(x) = \varphi(y)$ implies $x = y$. We will prove φ satisfies this criteria. To that end, let $\varphi(x) = \varphi(y)$. We want to show $x = y$, or equivalently, $x - y = 0$. Notice,

$$\varphi(x - y) = \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) = \varphi(x) - \varphi(x) = 0$$

since $\varphi(x) = \varphi(y)$, and the second equality was proven in Math 103A. Then, $x - y \in \ker(\varphi) = \{0\}$, so $x - y = 0$, and $x = y$.

Homework 2

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due January 15th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the *zero product property*, i.e. if a_1, \dots, a_n are elements of R , then if

$$a_1 \dots a_n = 0$$

we must have $a_i = 0$ for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. (Hint: Prove it for $n = 2$ and use induction on n)

Solution Base case: ($n = 2$) Suppose $a_1 a_2 = 0$ and $a_i \neq 0$ for $i = 1, 2$. Then, both a_1 and a_2 are zero-divisors. However, R is an integral domain and has no zero-divisors. Thus, we must have $a_i = 0$ for some $1 \leq i \leq 2$.

Suppose the assertion holds for $n = k$, i.e., if $a_1 a_2 \dots a_k = 0$, we must have $a_i = 0$ for some $1 \leq i \leq k$. We shall now show that the assertion holds true for $n = k + 1$.

Given $a_1 a_2 \dots a_k a_{k+1} = 0$, and suppose $a_i \neq 0$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k + 1$. We have

$$\underbrace{(a_1 a_2 \dots a_k)}_{:=b} a_{k+1} = 0 \quad (\text{why is } b \text{ non-zero})?$$

But then a_{k+1} is a zero-divisor which contradicts the fact that R is an integral domain.

2. Show that $M_2(\mathbb{R})$ is not an integral domain by finding two nonzero elements that multiply to the zero matrix.

Solution Consider

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

What is AB ?

3. Show that the characteristic of a field must be either 0 or a prime number p .

Solution Suppose $\text{char}(R) = n$ and $n \neq 0$. We shall show that n must be prime.

To that end, suppose not. Then there exists positive integers a, b such that $n = ab$ with $1 < a, b < n$. Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned}n \cdot 1 &= 0 \\ \implies (ab) \cdot 1 &= 0 \\ \implies (a \cdot 1)(b \cdot 1) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Since R is a Field, and hence an Integral Domain, we must have $a \cdot 1 = 0$ or $b \cdot 1 = 0$. But $\text{char}(R) = n$ is the smallest such integer. Thus, we must have $n \leq a$ or $n \leq b$. But this contradicts that $1 < a, b < n$.

4. Let $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ denote the ring of polynomials with integer coefficients.

1. Prove that $I = \{f(x) : x \text{ divides } f(x)\}$ is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
2. Prove that $J = \{g(x) : \text{the constant term } g_0 \text{ is even}\}$ is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
3. Prove that $I' = \{f(x) : \deg(f) \leq 5\}$ is not an ideal.

Solution 1. We shall first show that $f - g \in I$ for all $f, g \in I$.

By definition of I ,

$$f(x) = xf_1(x) \quad g(x) = xg_1(x) \text{ for some } f_1, g_1 \in \mathbb{Z}[x].$$

Thus, $f - g = x(f_1 - g_1) \in I$.

Now we shall show $hg \in I$ for all $h \in \mathbb{Z}[x], g \in I$.

$$h(x)g(x) = h(x)xg_1(x) = xh(x)g_1(x) \in I$$

Thus, by the Ideal test, I is an ideal.

2. Similar proof as above.

3. $f(x) = x \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $g(x) = x^5 \in I'$. But $f(x)g(x) = x^6 \notin I'$

5. Let R be a commutative ring with identity, and let I, J be ideals of R .

1. Prove that $I \cap J$ is an ideal.
2. Prove that $I \cup J$ need not be an ideal.
3. Let $K = \{ab : a \in I, b \in J\}$. Is K an ideal of R ?

Solution 1. Let $x, y \in I \cap J$. Then $x, y \in I$. Since I is an ideal, $x - y \in I$. Similarly, $x - y \in J$. Thus, $x - y \in I \cap J$.

Let $r \in R$ and $x \in I \cap J$. Since I is an ideal, $rx \in I$. Similarly, $rx \in J$. Thus, $rx \in I \cap J$. By the Ideal test, $I \cap J$ is an ideal.

2. For $I = 2\mathbb{Z}$ and $J = 3\mathbb{Z}$, ideals of $R = \mathbb{Z}$, we have $3, 2 \in I \cup J$. But $3 - 2 = 1 \notin I \cup J$.

3. Let $I = J = \{2f(x) + xg(x) \mid f, g \in \mathbb{Z}[x]\}$. It is easy to check that these are ideals of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Then $4 = 2 \cdot 2 \in K$ and $x^2 = x \cdot x \in K$. However, $4 + x^2 \notin K$ (why?). Thus, K is not an ideal.

Homework 3

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due January 29th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Prove that $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ideal of R .

Solution. Notice $\varphi(0) = \varphi(0 + 0) = \varphi(0) + \varphi(0)$, so that $\varphi(0) = 0$, and $0 \in \ker(\varphi)$. Furthermore, if $x, y \in \ker(\varphi)$, then $\varphi(x - y) = \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) = 0 - 0 = 0$ by the properties of homomorphisms. Finally, if $r \in R$, then $\varphi(rx) = \varphi(r)\varphi(x) = \varphi(r)0 = 0$, so $rx \in \ker(\varphi)$. By the ideal test, $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ideal.

2. This exercise studies homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z} to other rings.

- (a) Prove that any homomorphism $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S$ for a ring S is entirely determined by $\varphi(1)$. In other words, once the output of 1 is determined, the entire homomorphism is determined.

Solution. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. If $n = 0$, by the previous exercise, we know that $\varphi(0) = 0$. If $n > 0$, then $\varphi(n) = \varphi(\underbrace{1 + \cdots + 1}_n) = \underbrace{\varphi(1) + \cdots + \varphi(1)}_n = n \cdot \varphi(1)$. Furthermore, $\varphi(-n) = \varphi(\underbrace{-1 - \cdots - 1}_n) = \underbrace{\varphi(-1) + \cdots + \varphi(-1)}_n = \underbrace{-\varphi(1) - \cdots - \varphi(1)}_n = -n \cdot \varphi(1)$. The conclusion follows.

- (b) (Extra credit) Let $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) := \{\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}\}$ denote the set of ring homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z} to \mathbb{Z} . It can be proven $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z})$ forms a ring under the operations

$$(\varphi + \psi)(a) = \varphi(a) + \psi(a)$$

$$(\varphi \cdot \psi)(a) = \varphi(a) \cdot \psi(a)$$

where $+$, \cdot are the usual operations in \mathbb{Z} , and $a \in \mathbb{Z}$. Prove that $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \cong \mathbb{Z}$. (Hint: Consider the map $\Phi : \text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ defined by $\Phi : \varphi \mapsto \varphi(1)$)

Solution. Define $\Phi : \text{Hom}(\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ by $\Phi : \varphi \mapsto \varphi(1)$. We will prove that this forms a ring homomorphism. We have

$$\Phi(\varphi + \psi) = (\varphi + \psi)(1) = \varphi(1) + \psi(1) = \Phi(\varphi) + \Phi(\psi)$$

$$\Phi(\varphi \cdot \psi) = (\varphi \cdot \psi)(1) = \varphi(1) \cdot \psi(1) = \Phi(\varphi) \cdot \Phi(\psi)$$

(c) List all of the ring homomorphisms from \mathbb{Z}_{12} to \mathbb{Z}_{30} .

Solution. By exercise 2a, we can describe a map φ by $\varphi(1)$. We may send 1 to any element whose additive order in \mathbb{Z}_{30} divides 12. (Why?) Therefore, the maps correspond to

$$\varphi(1) \in \{0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25\}$$

3. Consider the ring homomorphism $\varphi : \mathbb{R}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ by $\varphi(1) = 1, \varphi(x) = i$. What is the kernel of this map?

Solution. We claim that

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{(x^2 + 1)f(x) : f(x) \in \mathbb{R}[x]\}$$

Note that $\varphi((x^2 + 1)f(x)) = \varphi(x^2 + 1)\varphi(f(x)) = (i^2 + 1)f(i) = (-1 + 1)f(i) = 0$, so that $\{(x^2 + 1)f(x) : f(x) \in \mathbb{R}[x]\} \subset \ker(\varphi)$. Next, let $f(x) \in \ker(\varphi)$. Since \mathbb{R} is a field, we may divide $f(x)$ by $x^2 + 1$ to obtain the equation

$$f(x) = (x^2 + 1)g(x) + (ax + b)$$

Evaluating this equation at i , we have that

$$0 = f(i) = (i^2 + 1)g(i) + (ai + b) = ai + b$$

which forces $a = b = 0$. Therefore, $f(x) = (x^2 + 1)g(x)$, and the reverse containment is true.

4. What are the prime ideals of \mathbb{Z} ? For \mathbb{Z}_{10} ? What are the maximal ideals?

Solution. The prime ideals of \mathbb{Z} are (0) , and (p) for any prime number p . The maximal ideals are (p) for any prime number p . For \mathbb{Z}_{10} , the prime and maximal ideals are (2) and (5) . ((0) is not prime here since \mathbb{Z}_{10} is not an integral domain)

5. Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. Prove that R/I is an integral domain if and only if I is a prime ideal.

Solution. Let $a + I, b + I \in R/I$, and recall that multiplication in R/I is defined by $(a + I)(b + I) = ab + I$ (and is well defined). Furthermore, note that $x + I = 0 + I$ if and only if $x \in I$. Suppose $ab + I = 0 + I$, or equivalently, $ab \in I$. Then, I is prime if and only if $a \in I$ or $b \in I$, which is true if and only if $a + I = 0 + I$ or $b + I = 0 + I$, which is equivalent to the statement that R/I is an integral domain.

6. * Let $I \subset R$ be an ideal. Prove that R/I is a field if and only if I is a maximal ideal.

Solution. Suppose R/I is a field, and suppose $I \subset J \subset R$. If $x \in J$, consider the element $x + I$ in R/I . Since R/I is a field, then x is a unit, so there is x^{-1} such that $1 = x^{-1}x$. Therefore, $x^{-1}(x + I) = 1 + I$, so that $1 - x^{-1}x \in I \subset J$. Therefore, since $x^{-1}x \in J$ by the ideal property, we conclude that $1 = (1 - x^{-1}x) + x^{-1}x \in J$, so that $J = R$.

Next, suppose I is a maximal ideal, and suppose $x + I \in R/I$ nonzero (so that $x \notin I$). Consider the ideal $(x) + I$, where (x) is the ideal generated by x . Then, we must have $(x) + I = R$, since $I \subsetneq (x) + I \subset R$. Therefore, $1 \in (x) + I$, so that $1 = ax + b$ for some $a \in R, b \in I$. We conclude that $a + I$ is the multiplicative inverse of $x + I$ in R/I .

Homework 4

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due February 12th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Examples of polynomial rings:

(a) List all of the elements f of $\mathbb{Z}_3[x]$ such that $\deg(f) \leq 2$.

Solution. They are $\{ax^2 + bx + c : a, b, c \in \{0, 1, 2\}\}$. You should list them out for yourself.

(b) Find the sum and the product of the following pairs of polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}_8[x]$:

- $(3x^2 + 2x - 1), (x^3 + 7x^2 - 3x - 4)$
- $(3x^2 + 2x - 1), (5x - 4)$

Solution.

- sum is $x^3 + 2x^2 + 7x + 3$, product is $3x^5 + 7x^4 + 4x^3 + 7x^2 3x + 4$
- sum is $3x^2 + 7x + 3$, product is $7x^3 + 6x^2 + 3x + 4$.

(c) Find the zeros of the following polynomials over the given ring:

- $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1, \mathbb{Z}_5$
- $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + 1, \mathbb{Z}_7$
- $f(x) = x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{Q} .
- $f(x) = x^4 - 1$ over \mathbb{C} .

Solution.

- $x = 1$
- none
- $x = 1, -1$
- $x = 1, -1, i, -i$

2. * Prove that if R is an integral domain, then $R[x]$ is an integral domain.

Solution. Suppose R is an integral domain, and let $f(x), g(x) \in R[x]$ nonzero. Suppose that f, g are of the form

$$f(x) = a_n x^n + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0$$

$$g(x) = b_mx^m + \cdots + b_1x + b_0$$

with $a_n, b_m \neq 0$. Then, we have that

$$f(x)g(x) = a_nb_mx^{n+m} + \cdots + a_0b_0$$

Since R is an integral domain, we have that $a_nb_m \neq 0$, so that $f(x)g(x) \neq 0$.

3. * Let R be a ring. Describe the units and zero divisors of $R[x]$.
Solution. As your TA mentioned, this was far too hard for this class, so we will skip. Refer to your discussion notes. (Requires an application of Zorn's lemma)

4. Use the division algorithm to solve the following problems:

- (a) Perform the following division of polynomials; that is, given $f(x), g(x)$ find $q(x)$ and $r(x)$ with $\deg(r) < \deg(g)$ such that $f(x) = q(x)g(x) + r(x)$:

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = 2x^2 + 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5$$

- (b) The polynomial $x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$ splits into linear factors over \mathbb{Z}_7 . Find the factorization.

Solution.

- (a) You should obtain $q(x) = 3x^2 + 3x + 4$, and $r(x) = 3x + 2$.

- (b) The factorization is $(x - 2)(x - 4)(x - 6) = (x + 5)(x + 3)(x + 1)$

5. * Calculate the multiplicative inverse of $x + 2$ in the ring $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$. (Here $(x^2 + 1) = \{f(x)(x^2 + 1) : f \in \mathbb{Q}[x]\}$, the ideal generated by $x^2 + 1$)

Solution. Dividing $x + 2$ into $x^2 + 1$, we obtain

$$x^2 + 1 = (x + 2)(x - 2) + 5$$

Rearranging and dividing by 5, we obtain

$$1 = \frac{1}{5}(x^2 + 1) + (x + 2)\left(\frac{2}{5} - \frac{x}{5}\right)$$

Reducing this equation modulo $x^2 + 1$, we obtain

$$1 \equiv (x + 2)\left(\frac{2}{5} - \frac{x}{5}\right)$$

so that $\frac{2}{5} - \frac{x}{5}$ is the desired inverse.

Remark. The quotient ring $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1) \equiv \mathbb{Q}[i]$, so we may compute its inverse by taking a conjugate, as we do for complex numbers in general. Indeed,

$$\frac{1}{2 + i} = \frac{2 - i}{(2 + i)(2 - i)} = \frac{2 - i}{5}$$

which is the same as our answer.

Homework 5

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due February 20th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Check if the following polynomials are irreducible or not in their respective rings:

- (a) $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- (b) $x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
- (c) $x^2 + 69x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_{71}[x]$
- (d) $420x^3 + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_{421}[x]$ (Hint: 421 is prime)
- (e) * $x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
- (f) $7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 25x + 15$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

Solution.

- (a) $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$
 - (b) $x^3 + 2x^2 + 1$ has no zeros in \mathbb{Z}_5 , so is irreducible
 - (c) Note that 1 is a zero of $x^2 + 69x + 1$, and so must be reducible.
 - (d) Note that 1 is a zero of $420x^3 + 1$, so must be reducible.
 - (e) Notice that $x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2 \equiv 6x^4 + 3x^3 + 4x + 2 = 3x^3(2x + 1) + 2(2x + 1) = (3x^3 + 2)(2x + 1)$. So is reducible. Alternatively, note that 1, 2 are zeros.
 - (f) This polynomial is equivalent to $7x^4$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$, which is reducible.
2. (a) When $f(x) \in F[x]$ (F is a field) is irreducible, then we will see that $R = F[x]/(f)$ is a field. If f is not irreducible however, we might not necessarily have R is a field, but some elements will still be units in the quotient. For example, $f(x) = x^2$ is not irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. However, $x + 1$ is a unit in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$. Find its inverse.

- (b) Give a criteria for when a polynomial $g(x)$ has an inverse in $F[x]/(f)$. Give a proof of sufficiency of your criteria. (Prove that everything satisfying your criteria has an inverse. The reverse proof is hard - but bonus points to you if you can do it!)

Solution.

- (a) Notice (or by dividing) that $x^2 = (x + 1)(x - 1) + 1$, so that

$$1 = x^2 + (x + 1)(1 - x)$$

and reducing modulo x^2 gives

$$1 \equiv (x + 1)(1 - x)$$

so that $1 - x$ is the desired inverse.

- (b) We claim that $g(x)$ has an inverse in $F[x]/(f)$ if and only if $\gcd(f, g) = 1$ (or any constant; recall that gcd's are only unique up to a unit). Suppose that $\gcd(f, g) = 1$. Then, there are polynomials $a, b \in F[x]$ such that

$$a(x)f(x) + b(x)g(x) = 1$$

Reducing modulo f , we have that

$$b(x)g(x) \equiv 1$$

so that (the coset containing) $g(x)$ is the desired inverse in $F[x]/(f)$. Conversely, suppose that g has an inverse in $F[x]/(f)$. Then, there is a such that $ag = 1$, or that $ag - 1 \in (f)$, so that $ag - 1 = bf$ for some polynomial $b \in F[x]$. Assume the contrary and that $\gcd(f, g) = h$ for $h \in F[x]$ with $\deg(h) \geq 1$. Then, we can find f', g' so that $f = hf', g = hg'$, and substituting into the above equation, we have that $ahg' - 1 = bhf'$, and we may rearrange to say $1 = h(ag' - bf')$. This implies that $1 \in (h)$, so that $1 = hp$ for some polynomial p . But the degree of the right hand side is greater than 1, which is a contradiction.

Homework 6

Math 103B Winter Quarter 2025

Due February 27th, 2025 at 11:59pm PST

*Means *difficult*, you are encouraged to ask me for help and work together.
**means *very* difficult.

1 Problems

1. Let R be an integral domain, and let I, J be ideals of R . Recall on a previous homework that we proved that the set

$$IJ := \{ab : a \in I, b \in J\}$$

is not necessarily an ideal. Prove the following statements:

- If R is a principal ideal domain, then IJ is an ideal.
- The set $IJ' := \{a_1b_1 + \cdots + a_nb_n : a_i \in I, b_i \in J\}$ is an ideal of R .

Solution.

- Suppose R is a PID. Then, $I = (a)$, $J = (b)$ for elements $a, b \in R$. Then, we have

$$IJ = \{xy : x \in (a), y \in (b)\} = \{r_1ar_2b : r_1, r_2 \in R\} = \{rab : r \in R\}$$

since PID's are commutative. Clearly IJ is closed under left multiplication, and we check closure under subtraction. If $r_1, r_2 \in R$, then we have

$$r_1ab - r_2ab = (r_1 - r_2)ab \in IJ$$

and so IJ is an ideal.

- If we allow linear combinations, the result is straightforward. Clearly, $0 \in IJ'$. We check closure under subtraction. If $\sum_i a_i b_i, \sum_j a'_j b'_j \in IJ'$, then we have

$$\sum_i a_i b_i - \sum_j a'_j b'_j = \sum_i a_i b_i + \sum_j (-a'_j) b'_j \in IJ'$$

since this is a linear combination of elements of the form $a_k b_k$ (and I is closed under subtraction). Since I is closed under left multiplication, we have that

$$r \sum_i a_i b_i = \sum_i (ra_i) b_i \in IJ'$$

and so we are done.

2. Prove that the ideal $(2, x) = \{f \in \mathbb{Z}[x] : f(0) \text{ is even}\} = \{2f(x) + xg(x) : f, g \in \mathbb{Z}[x]\}$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is not principal, i.e. there exists no element $a(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ such that $(a) = (2, x)$.

Solution. Suppose $(a) = (2, x)$ for some $a \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Then, we have that

$$2 = af, x = ag$$

for suitable polynomials $f, g \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Since $\deg 2 = 0$, we must have that $\deg a = 0$ as well, so $a \in \{1, 2, -1, -2\}$, which are the only divisors of 2 in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$. If $a \in \{2, -2\}$, then we have reached a contradiction because evaluating $x = ag(x)$ at $x = 1$, we have that $1 = \pm 2g(1)$, and the right hand side must be even. So $a \in \pm 1$. But this would imply that $(a) = \mathbb{Z}[x]$, and $(2, x) \neq \mathbb{Z}[x]$ (for instance, $1 \notin (2, x)$), and so this is a contradiction.

3. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the following statements:
- If R is a principal ideal domain, then every prime ideal of R is also a maximal ideal.
 - If $R[x]$ is a principal ideal domain, then actually R is a field.

Solution.

- Suppose R is a PID, and let $I = (a)$ be a nontrivial prime ideal of R . Suppose there is an ideal $I \subset J \subset R$. Then, we have $J = (b)$ for some $b \in R$. Since $a \in I \subset J = (b)$, there is $r \in R$ such that $rb = a$. Then, $r \in (a)$ or $b \in (a)$, since (a) is prime. If $b \in (a)$, then $(a) = (b)$. If $r \in (a)$, then $r = r'a$ for some r' , and we have that $r'ab = a$, so that $a(r'b - 1) = 0$. Since R is a PID, and hence an integral domain, R has no zero divisors and since $a \neq 0$, we must have that $r'b = 1$. Therefore b is a unit, and $(b) = R$. This shows that I is maximal, since we must have $J = (b) = R$, or $J = (a) = I$.
 - We show that the ideal (x) is maximal. Since $R \cong R[x]/(x)$ (by the first isomorphism theorem with the evaluation map $f \mapsto f(0)$), if (x) is maximal, then $R[x]/(x)$ is a field. Since R is an integral domain, then (x) is a prime ideal. By the previous exercise, (x) must be maximal as well, and we are done.
4. We saw during class (for the example $\mathbb{Z}[-\sqrt{5}]$) that we can have elements that are irreducible but not prime. Let R be an integral domain. Prove the following statements:

- Every prime element is irreducible.
- If R is a unique factorization domain, then every irreducible element is prime.

Solution.

- Let $x \in R$ prime. Then, $x \mid ab$ implies that $x \mid a$ or $x \mid b$. Let $x \mid ab$, so that $ab = rx$ for some $r \in R$. Without loss of generality, suppose $x \mid a$, so that $a = r'x$ for some $r' \in R$. Then, $rx = r'xb$, so that $x(r - r'b) = 0$. Since $x \neq 0$ (prime elements cannot be 0) and R is an integral domain, we must have that $r'b = r$, so that $r' \mid r$. Therefore, $r = r'r''$ for some $r'' \in R$. Substituting, we have that $r'(br'' - 1) = 0$, and again, since R is an integral domain, this implies that $br'' = 1$. This shows that b is a unit, so that x is irreducible.
- Let R be a UFD, and suppose x is irreducible. We show that x is prime. Suppose $x = ab$, and let the unique factorizations of a, b be as follows:

$$a = uf_1 \dots f_m$$

$$b = u'g_1 \dots g_n$$

We have that

$$x = ab = uu'f_1 \dots f_mg_1 \dots g_n$$

By unique factorization, we must have that exactly one of f_i, g_j is x , and the rest are not present. (And that $uu' = 1$) If u is one of the f 's, then $u \mid a$. If u is one of the g 's, then $u \mid b$. We are done.

Practice Exam 1

Problem 1

Consider the ring $R = \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$.

- (a) Find all of the units in R , and list their multiplicative inverses.
- (b) Find all of the zero divisors in R .
- (c) What is the characteristic of R ?
- (d) Consider the map $\varphi : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{12}$ defined by $\varphi(1, 0) = 3$, $\varphi(0, 1) = 2$. Is this a ring homomorphism? If so, calculate $\ker(\varphi)$ and $\text{im}(\varphi)$.
- (e) A nilpotent element is an element x such that $x^m = 0$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Find all nilpotent elements of $R = \mathbb{Z}_{36}$.

(a) All units in R and their inverses.

In a finite direct product $R_1 \times R_2$, an element (a, b) is a unit if and only if a is a unit in R_1 and b is a unit in R_2 . In \mathbb{Z}_4 , the units are $\{[1]_4, [3]_4\}$. In \mathbb{Z}_6 , the units are $\{[1]_6, [5]_6\}$. Hence in $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$, the units are precisely

$$(1, 1), (1, 5), (3, 1), (3, 5)$$

Their inverses are computed coordinatewise. Noting that $[1]_4^{-1} = [1]_4$, $[3]_4^{-1} = [3]_4$, $[1]_6^{-1} = [1]_6$, $[5]_6^{-1} = [5]_6$, we obtain:

$$(1, 1)^{-1} = (1, 1), (1, 5)^{-1} = (1, 5), (3, 1)^{-1} = (3, 1), (3, 5)^{-1} = (3, 5)$$

(b) All zero divisors in R .

An element $(a, b) \in \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$ is a zero divisor exactly if at least one coordinate is a zero divisor in its respective ring (and not both coordinates necessarily invertible). In \mathbb{Z}_4 , the zero divisors are $\{[0]_4, [2]_4\}$. In \mathbb{Z}_6 , the zero divisors are $\{[0]_6, [2]_6, [3]_6, [4]_6\}$. Therefore, the zero divisors in R are precisely

$$\{(a, b) \mid a \in \{0, 2\} \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_4 \text{ or } b \in \{0, 2, 3, 4\} \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_6\}$$

Equivalently, any (a, b) that is *not* a unit (other than possibly the identity $(1, 1)$), and satisfies that at least one coordinate is a zero divisor, is a zero divisor in the product.

(c) Characteristic of R .

The characteristic of the product ring $\mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$ is the least common multiple of the characteristics of the factors. Since $\text{char}(\mathbb{Z}_4) = 4$ and $\text{char}(\mathbb{Z}_6) = 6$, the characteristic of R is

$$\text{lcm}(4, 6) = 12$$

(d) The map $\varphi : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{12}$, $\varphi(1, 0) = 3$, $\varphi(0, 1) = 2$. Is it a ring homomorphism? If so, find $\ker(\varphi)$ and $\text{im}(\varphi)$.

We check whether φ respects multiplication. In R , note $(1, 0) \cdot (0, 1) = (1 \cdot 0 \bmod 4, 0 \cdot 1 \bmod 6) = (0, 0)$. However,

$$\varphi(1, 0)\varphi(0, 1) = [3]_{12} \cdot [2]_{12} = [6]_{12} \neq [0]_{12}$$

Hence $\varphi((1, 0) \cdot (0, 1)) = [0] \neq 6 = \varphi(1, 0)\varphi(0, 1)$. This violates the ring-homomorphism multiplication requirement. Therefore,

φ is *not* a ring homomorphism.

No well-defined $\ker(\varphi)$ or $\text{im}(\varphi)$ in the sense of ring-homomorphism arises.

(e) All nilpotent elements in \mathbb{Z}_{36} .

A nilpotent element in \mathbb{Z}_n is any \bar{x} for which $(\bar{x})^m = \bar{0}$ in \mathbb{Z}_n for some $m > 0$. Write $n = 36 = 2^2 \cdot 3^2$. An element \bar{x} in \mathbb{Z}_{36} is nilpotent exactly if, for each prime p dividing 36, raising \bar{x} to some power kills all the p -power factors in 36. In practice, one checks that x must be divisible by both 2 and 3 in \mathbb{Z}_{36} , i.e. a multiple of 6. Indeed:

$$(\bar{x})^m \equiv \bar{0} \iff 36 \mid x^m$$

For $36 = 2^2 \cdot 3^2$, we need $m\nu_2(x) \geq 2$ and $m\nu_3(x) \geq 2$, forcing $\nu_2(x) \geq 1$ and $\nu_3(x) \geq 1$. Thus x is divisible by both 2 and 3, i.e. $6 \mid x$. Therefore the nilpotent elements in \mathbb{Z}_{36} are precisely

$$\{0, 6, 12, 18, 24, 30\} \quad (\text{all multiples of } 6 \bmod 36)$$

Each of these, when squared (for instance), becomes 0 in \mathbb{Z}_{36} . For example, $6^2 = 36 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, etc.

Problem 2

Now consider any two generic rings R, S with unity.

- Generalize the first part of the last problem to $R \times S$. Can you give a description for the units in terms of the units of R, S ? Is this all of them?
- What are the zero divisors of $R \times S$ in terms of the zero divisors of R, S ?
- Let R be a commutative ring. Show that the product of two nilpotent elements is nilpotent.
- (Challenge, optional)** Show that the sum of two nilpotent elements is nilpotent. Conclude that the set of nilpotent elements form an ideal in a commutative ring R .
- (Optional)** Let n have prime factorization $n = p_1^{a_1} \dots p_k^{a_k}$. Give a description for the nilpotent elements of \mathbb{Z}_n in terms of the prime factorization.

(a) In a ring with unity $R \times S$, an element (r, s) is a unit precisely when $r \in R$ is a unit in R and $s \in S$ is a unit in S . Explicitly,

$$(r, s) \text{ is a unit in } R \times S \implies \begin{cases} r \text{ is a unit in } R \\ s \text{ is a unit in } S \end{cases} \implies (r, s)^{-1} = (r^{-1}, s^{-1})$$

Conversely, if either r or s is a nonunit, one cannot solve $(r, s) \cdot (r', s') = (1_R, 1_S)$, so (r, s) fails to be invertible. Hence exactly all pairs of units form the units in $R \times S$.

(b) In $R \times S$, an element (r, s) is a zero divisor exactly if $(r, s) \cdot (r_1, s_1) = (0, 0)$ for some nonzero (r_1, s_1) . That condition unfolds as

$$(r r_1, s s_1) = (0, 0)$$

so $r r_1 = 0$ in R and $s s_1 = 0$ in S . Thus at least one of r, r_1 is a zero divisor in R or one of s, s_1 is a zero divisor in S . Concretely,

$$(r, s) \text{ is a zero divisor} \iff r \text{ is a zero divisor in } R \text{ or } s \text{ is a zero divisor in } S$$

(c) Let R be commutative, let $x, y \in R$ be nilpotent. Then $\exists m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $x^m = 0$ and $y^n = 0$. We claim xy is also nilpotent: indeed,

$$(xy)^{m+n} = x^{m+n} y^{m+n} = \underbrace{x^m}_{=0} x^n y^m \underbrace{y^n}_{=0} = 0$$

Hence xy is nilpotent.

(d) (Challenge) One shows similarly that $x + y$ is nilpotent if x, y are nilpotent in a commutative ring, although this requires a binomial-expansion argument and commutativity. One deduces the set of nilpotent elements forms an ideal.

(e) (Optional) If $n = p_1^{a_1} \dots p_k^{a_k}$ and $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ is nilpotent, then $x^m \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$ for some m . This is equivalent to $x^m \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i^{a_i}}$ for all i . Consequently, in each $\mathbb{Z}_{p_i^{a_i}}$, the class of x is nilpotent; this forces x to be divisible by each prime power $p_i^{a_i}$ to a certain degree. Concretely, the nilpotent elements in \mathbb{Z}_n are exactly those whose images vanish in each $\mathbb{Z}_{p_i^{a_i}}$ for some high power, leading to the requirement that x lie in the radical of each $p_i^{a_i}$.

Problem 3

Now we study some maps.

- (a) Consider the map $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{10} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6$ defined by $\varphi(1) = 1$. Is this a ring homomorphism?
- (b) Consider the map $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}_6 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6$ defined by $\varphi(1) = (1, 1)$. Is this a ring homomorphism?
- (c) Consider the map $\varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$ defined by $\varphi(1) = (1, 1)$. Is this a ring homomorphism?
- (d) Consider the map $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$. Show this is a ring homomorphism, and compute $\ker(\varphi)$, $\text{im}(\varphi)$.
- (e) Consider the map $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{18}$ defined by $\varphi(1) = 3$. Compute $\ker(\varphi)$, $\text{im}(\varphi)$.

Problem 3 consists of parts (a)–(e). We write $[k]_m$ for the class of k in \mathbb{Z}_m

$$(a) \quad \varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{10} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6, \varphi([1]_{10}) = [1]_6. \implies \varphi([n]_{10}) = [n]_6$$

Check well-definedness: in \mathbb{Z}_{10} , $[0]_{10} = [10]_{10}$. Then

$$\varphi([0]_{10}) = [0]_6, \quad \varphi([10]_{10}) = [10]_6 = [4]_6$$

They differ, so φ is *not* well-defined. Not a ring homomorphism.

$$(b) \quad \varphi : \mathbb{Z}_6 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_4 \times \mathbb{Z}_6, \varphi([1]_6) = ([1]_4, [1]_6). \implies \varphi([n]_6) = ([n]_4, [n]_6)$$

Check well-definedness: $[n]_6 = [n + 6]_6$. Then

$$\varphi([n + 6]_6) = ([n + 6]_4, [n + 6]_6) = ([n + 2]_4, [n]_6)$$

which is $\neq ([n]_4, [n]_6)$ in general (since $[n + 2]_4 \neq [n]_4$ unless $2 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$). So φ fails to be well-defined. Not a ring homomorphism.

$$(c) \quad \varphi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}, \varphi(1) = (1, 1). \implies \varphi(n) = (n, n)$$

Check ring homomorphism:

$$\varphi(a + b) = (a + b, a + b) = (a, a) + (b, b) = \varphi(a) + \varphi(b)$$

$$\varphi(ab) = (ab, ab) = (a, a) \cdot (b, b) = \varphi(a) \varphi(b)$$

Also $\varphi(1) = (1, 1)$ is indeed the multiplicative identity in $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$. So φ is a ring homomorphism.

$$(d) \quad \varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6 \times \mathbb{Z}_4, \varphi([1]_{12}) = ([1]_6, [1]_4). \implies \varphi([n]_{12}) = ([n]_6, [n]_4)$$

Check well-definedness: in \mathbb{Z}_{12} , if $[n]_{12} = [n']_{12}$ then $n \equiv n' \pmod{12}$. That forces $n \equiv n' \pmod{6}$ and $n \equiv n' \pmod{4}$, so $\varphi([n]_{12}) = ([n]_6, [n]_4) = ([n']_6, [n']_4) = \varphi([n']_{12})$. Hence well-defined. One checks easily that

$$\varphi([x + y]_{12}) = \varphi([x]_{12}) + \varphi([y]_{12}), \quad \varphi([xy]_{12}) = \varphi([x]_{12}) \varphi([y]_{12})$$

so φ is a ring homomorphism.

$\ker(\varphi) = \{[n]_{12} : \varphi([n]) = ([0]_6, [0]_4)\}$. That means $[n]_6 = [0]_6$ and $[n]_4 = [0]_4$. So $6 \mid n$ and $4 \mid n \implies 12 \mid n$. Thus $\ker(\varphi) = \{[0]_{12}\}$.

$\text{im}(\varphi)$: for any pair $([a]_6, [b]_4)$, pick $n \bmod 12$ that satisfies $n \equiv a \pmod{6}$, $n \equiv b \pmod{4}$. By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, such n exists mod 12. Then $\varphi([n]) = ([a]_6, [b]_4)$. So the map is surjective. Hence

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{[0]_{12}\}, \quad \text{im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{Z}_6 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$$

$$(e) \quad \varphi : \mathbb{Z}_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{18}, \quad \varphi([1]_{12}) = [3]_{18}. \implies \varphi([n]) = [3n]_{18}$$

Check kernel: $\ker(\varphi) = \{[n]_{12} : 3n \equiv 0 \pmod{18}\}$. That is $18 \mid 3n \implies 6 \mid n$. So $n \equiv 0$ or $6 \pmod{12}$. Hence

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{[0]_{12}, [6]_{12}\}$$

Check image: $\varphi([n]_{12}) \in \{[3n]_{18}\}$. So

$$\text{im}(\varphi) = \{[0]_{18}, [3]_{18}, [6]_{18}, [9]_{18}, [12]_{18}, [15]_{18}\}$$

all multiples of $[3]_{18}$. Equivalently, it is the subgroup of \mathbb{Z}_{18} of size 6.

- (a) Not a ring homomorphism;
- (b) Not a ring homomorphism;
- (c) Is a ring homomorphism;
- (d) $\ker(\varphi) = \{[0]_{12}\}$, $\text{im}(\varphi) = \mathbb{Z}_6 \times \mathbb{Z}_4$;
- (e) $\ker(\varphi) = \{[0]_{12}, [6]_{12}\}$, $\text{im}(\varphi) = \{[0]_{18}, [3]_{18}, [6]_{18}, [9]_{18}, [12]_{18}, [15]_{18}\}$.

Problem 4

Now we study some ideals and isomorphisms.

- (a) Consider the ring $R = \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$, and let $I = \{(2a, 3b) \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Show that I is an ideal of R , and prove that $R/I \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$.
- (b) (*) Consider a ring homomorphism $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$, where R, S are commutative rings with unity. (So that $\varphi(1) = 1$ by definition.) If $p \subset S$ is a prime ideal, show that $\varphi^{-1}(p) \subset R$ is a prime ideal.
- (c) Let R be a commutative ring. The annihilator of an element $a \in R$ is defined to be

$$\text{Ann}(a) := \{x \in R \mid xa = 0\}$$

Show that $\text{Ann}(a)$ is an ideal.

- (d) Let R be a commutative ring with unity. Prove that R is a field if and only if (0) is a prime ideal.

(a) In $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$, let $I = \{(2a, 3b) : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.

1) To show I is an ideal: If $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in I$, then $(x_1, y_1) = (2a_1, 3b_1), (x_2, y_2) = (2a_2, 3b_2)$. Subtraction: $(x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2) = (2(a_1 - a_2), 3(b_1 - b_2)) \in I$. For any $(r, s) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$, and $(x, y) = (2a, 3b) \in I$,

$$(r, s) \cdot (x, y) = (rx, sy) = (2(ra), 3(sb)) \in I.$$

Similarly $(x, y) \cdot (r, s) \in I$. Thus I is an ideal.

2) Compute the quotient $(\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z})/I$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned}(x, y) &\equiv (x', y') \pmod{I} \\ \implies (x - x', y - y') &\in I \\ \implies (x - x') = 2a, (y - y') = 3b \\ \implies x &\equiv x' \pmod{2}, y \equiv y' \pmod{3}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence classes in R/I are determined by $(x \pmod{2}, y \pmod{3})$. This yields the isomorphism

$$R/I \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3.$$

(b) If $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ is a ring homomorphism with $\varphi(1) = 1$, and $p \subset S$ is prime, show $\varphi^{-1}(p) \subset R$ is prime:

Suppose $ab \in \varphi^{-1}(p)$. Then $\varphi(ab) = \varphi(a)\varphi(b) \in p$. Since p is prime, $\varphi(a) \in p$ or $\varphi(b) \in p$. Thus $a \in \varphi^{-1}(p)$ or $b \in \varphi^{-1}(p)$. So $\varphi^{-1}(p)$ is prime.

(c) For any $a \in R$, $\text{Ann}(a) = \{x \in R : xa = 0\}$ is an ideal:

If $x, y \in \text{Ann}(a)$, then $(x - y)a = xa - ya = 0 - 0 = 0$. So $x - y \in \text{Ann}(a)$. For any $r \in R$, $(rx)a = r(xa) = r(0) = 0$, so $rx \in \text{Ann}(a)$. This shows $\text{Ann}(a)$ is an ideal.

(d) A commutative ring R with unity is a field if and only if (0) is prime:

\Rightarrow . If R is a field, no zero divisors. Then for any $x, y \in R$, $xy = 0 \implies x = 0$ or $y = 0$. Hence (0) is prime.

\Leftarrow . If (0) is prime, there are no nonzero zero-divisors. To show R is a field, take any nonzero x . The ideal $(x) \neq (0)$ implies $(x) = R$. Then $1 \in (x) \implies 1 = xr$ for some r . So x is invertible, and R is a field.

Problem 4, Solution 2

(a) Let $R = \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$, and $I = \{(2a, 3b) \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.

I is an ideal:

$$\forall (2a_1, 3b_1), (2a_2, 3b_2) \in I, (2a_1, 3b_1) - (2a_2, 3b_2) = (2(a_1 - a_2), 3(b_1 - b_2)) \in I.$$

$$\forall (2a, 3b) \in I, \forall (r, s) \in R, (r, s) \cdot (2a, 3b) = (r \cdot 2a, s \cdot 3b) = (2(ra), 3(sb)) \in I.$$

Hence I is an ideal.

Next, show $R/I \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$. Define $\Phi : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$ by $\Phi(m, n) = (m \bmod 2, n \bmod 3)$. Φ is a surjective ring homomorphism. Then $\ker(\Phi) = \{(m, n) \mid m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}\} = \{(2a, 3b)\}$. That is $\ker(\Phi) = I$. By the first isomorphism theorem, $R/\ker(\Phi) \cong \text{Im}(\Phi) \implies R/I \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_3$.

(b) $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ a ring homomorphism with $\varphi(1) = 1$. If $p \subset S$ is prime, show $\varphi^{-1}(p) \subset R$ is prime. If $xy \in \varphi^{-1}(p) \implies \varphi(xy) = \varphi(x)\varphi(y) \in p$. Since p is prime, $\varphi(x) \in p$ or $\varphi(y) \in p$. Hence $x \in \varphi^{-1}(p)$ or $y \in \varphi^{-1}(p)$. So $\varphi^{-1}(p)$ is prime.

(c) $\text{Ann}(a) = \{x \in R \mid xa = 0\}$. Check ideal properties. If $x, y \in \text{Ann}(a) \implies (x - y)a = xa - ya = 0 \implies x - y \in \text{Ann}(a)$. $\forall r \in R, (rx)a = r(xa) = r \cdot 0 = 0 \implies rx \in \text{Ann}(a)$. So $\text{Ann}(a)$ is an ideal.

(d) R commutative with unity. Show R is field $\iff (0)$ is prime. \implies : If R is field, no nonzero zero divisors. Then $ab = 0 \implies a = 0$ or $b = 0$. So (0) is prime. \Leftarrow : If (0) is prime, no zero divisors. Nonzero $x \in R \implies$ the ideal $(x) \neq (0)$. In an integral domain with unity, $(x) = R \implies \exists y : xy = 1$. So x invertible. Hence R is field.

Practice Exam 2 (New Version)

Problem 1: Prime and Maximal Ideals

Let R be a commutative ring with unity.

1. Prove that I is maximal if and only if R/I is a field.
2. Prove that I is prime if and only if R/I is an integral domain.
3. Let I, J be prime ideals. Prove that $I \cap J$ is also a prime ideal.
4. Let I, J be maximal ideals. Show that the intersection $I \cap J$ need not be maximal.
5. Give an example of a prime ideal in \mathbb{Z} that is not maximal.
6. Give an example of an ideal that is not prime.
7. Prove that the ideal $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is maximal. (Hint: use the first part.)
8. Prove that the ideal $(x^2 + 1) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is prime.

1) Show that I is maximal $\iff R/I$ is a field:

(\implies) If $I \subset R$ is maximal, then there is no strictly larger ideal between I and R . Hence R/I has no nontrivial ideals. A commutative ring with unity having no nontrivial ideals is a field.

(\impliedby) If R/I is a field, then any ideal J with $I \subseteq J \subseteq R$ satisfies $J = I$ or $J = R$. Indeed, $\ker(R \rightarrow R/J)$ contains I . Since R/J would be a factor of R/I (a field), it has no nontrivial proper ideals, forcing $J = I$ or $J = R$. Hence I is maximal.

2) Show that I is prime $\iff R/I$ is an integral domain:

(\implies) If $I \subset R$ is prime, then whenever $\bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} = \bar{0}$ in R/I , we get $ab \in I$. By primality, $a \in I$ or $b \in I$. Hence $\bar{a} = \bar{0}$ or $\bar{b} = \bar{0}$, so R/I has no zero divisors, i.e. is an integral domain.

(\impliedby) Conversely, if R/I is an integral domain, then whenever $ab \in I$, we have $\bar{a}\bar{b} = \bar{0}$. By no zero divisors in R/I , either $\bar{a} = \bar{0}$ or $\bar{b} = \bar{0}$. Hence $a \in I$ or $b \in I$. So I is prime.

(3) I, J prime ideals. Show $I \cap J$ need not be prime.

Counterexample: In \mathbb{Z} , (2) and (3) are prime (and maximal) ideals. Their intersection is $(2) \cap (3) = (6)$, which is not prime since $2 \cdot 3 \in (6)$ but neither 2 nor 3 is in (6).

4) Let I, J be maximal ideals. Show $I \cap J$ need not be maximal:

For instance, in \mathbb{Z} , (2) and (3) are maximal ideals but $(2) \cap (3) = (6)$ is not maximal because $\mathbb{Z}/(6)$ is not a field.

5) Example of a prime ideal in \mathbb{Z} that is not maximal: In \mathbb{Z} , prime ideals are generated by prime numbers or 0. The ideal (0) is prime (since \mathbb{Z} is an integral domain), but not maximal because $\mathbb{Z}/(0) \cong \mathbb{Z}$ is not a field.

6) Example of an ideal that is not prime:

$(6) \subset \mathbb{Z}$ is not prime since $2 \cdot 3 = 6 \in (6)$ but $2 \notin (6)$, $3 \notin (6)$.

7) Prove $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is maximal:

Consider the surjective map $\mathbb{Q}[x, y] \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ given by $f(x, y) \mapsto f(0, 0)$. Its kernel is (x, y) . The image is \mathbb{Q} , a field. Hence (x, y) is maximal.

8) Prove $(x^2 + 1) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is prime:

In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible, so $(x^2 + 1)$ is prime in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. Extending to $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$, the ideal $(x^2 + 1)$ remains prime (as polynomials in y are unaffected). Concretely, $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]/(x^2 + 1) \cong (\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1))[y]$, and $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$ is an integral domain. Hence the quotient is an integral domain, so $(x^2 + 1)$ is prime.

Problem 2: Polynomial Division

Find polynomials q, r so that $f = gq + r$ with $\deg(r) < \deg(g)$.

1. $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

2. $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = 2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

(1) In $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = x + 1$

Long division:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) \div g(x) &: x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 / (x + 1) \\ &= x^3 + x \text{ (quotient) , } 1 \text{ (remainder)}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$f = g \cdot (x^3 + x) + 1$$

Thus

$$q(x) = x^3 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

(2) In $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = 2x + 1$

Division in \mathbb{Z}_5 (noting $1/2 = 3$ in \mathbb{Z}_5):

$$\begin{aligned} x^4 \div (2x) &\rightarrow 3x^3, & 3x^3(2x + 1) &= x^4 + 3x^3, \\ f - (\dots) &= x^4 + x^3 + \dots - (x^4 + 3x^3) = 3x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, \\ 3x^3 \div (2x) &\rightarrow 4x^2, & 4x^2(2x + 1) &= 3x^3 + 4x^2, \\ (\dots) - (\dots) &= 3x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 - (3x^3 + 4x^2) = 2x^2 + x + 1, \\ 2x^2 \div (2x) &\rightarrow x, & x(2x + 1) &= 2x^2 + x, \\ (2x^2 + x + 1) - (2x^2 + x) &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

So the quotient is $3x^3 + 4x^2 + x$ and remainder is 1. Therefore

$$f = g \cdot (3x^3 + 4x^2 + x) + 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

Thus

$$q(x) = 3x^3 + 4x^2 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

Problem 3: Greatest Common Divisors

Compute the gcd's of the following polynomials in their respective rings:

1. $f(x) = 2x^2 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1$, $g(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

2. $f(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1$, $g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

1. GCD in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: $2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1$ and $2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$

$$f(x) = 2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1, \quad g(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$$

1.1 Factor f over \mathbb{Q}

$$\begin{aligned} x = -\frac{1}{2} &\implies f\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = 0 \implies (2x + 1) \text{ divides } f(x) \\ &\implies f(x) = (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$x^2 + x + 1$ has discriminant $1 - 4 = -3 < 0 \implies$ irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

1.2 Common factors of f and g

$$f(x) = (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) \implies \text{possible gcds: } 2x + 1, x^2 + x + 1, \text{ or } f(x)$$

$$(2x + 1) \nmid g \implies (\text{no zero at } x = -\frac{1}{2} \text{ for } g)$$

$$x^2 + x + 1 \mid g \implies g(x) = (x^2 + x + 1)(2x^2 + 3)$$

$$(2x + 1) \nmid g \implies (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) \nmid g.$$

$$\implies \gcd(f, g) = x^2 + x + 1.$$

1.3 Conclusion in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

$$\gcd(2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1, 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3) = x^2 + x + 1$$

2. GCD in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1$ and $3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$

In \mathbb{Z}_5 , all coefficients are modulo 5. Denote

$$f(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1, \quad g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$$

$\implies \gcd(f, g)$ found via Euclidean algorithm:

2.1 First Division: $f \div g$

$$\deg(f) = 4, \deg(g) = 3 \implies \text{leading terms: } \frac{2x^4}{3x^3} = 4x \quad (\text{since } 3^{-1} \equiv 2)$$

$$4x \cdot g = 4x \cdot (3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) \equiv 2x^4 + 3x^3 + x^2 + 4x \pmod{5}$$

$$f - 4xg \implies R_1 = 4x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$$

$\deg(R_1) = 3 = \deg(g) \implies$ divide R_1 by g again:

$$\frac{4x^3}{3x^3} = 3, \quad 3 \cdot g \equiv 4x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 3$$

$$R_2 = R_1 - 3g \equiv (4x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1) - (4x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 3) \equiv x^2 + 3$$

$$\implies f = g(4x + 3) + (x^2 + 3).$$

2.2 Next Step: $g \div R_2$

$$g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1, \quad R_2(x) = x^2 + 3$$

$$\frac{3x^3}{x^2} = 3x, \quad 3x \cdot R_2 \equiv 3x^3 + 4x$$

$$R_3 = g - 3x(x^2 + 3) \equiv (3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) - (3x^3 + 4x) \equiv 2x^2 + 1$$

2.3 Then $R_2 \div R_3$

$$R_2 = x^2 + 3, \quad R_3 = 2x^2 + 1$$

$$\frac{x^2}{2x^2} = 3 \quad (\text{since } 2^{-1} = 3 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5), \quad 3 \cdot (2x^2 + 1) \equiv x^2 + 3$$

$$R_4 = R_2 - 3R_3 = (x^2 + 3) - (x^2 + 3) = 0 \implies \text{gcd is last nonzero remainder } R_2$$

2.4 Conclusion in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

$$\text{gcd}\left(2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1, 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1\right) = x^2 + 3$$

$x^2 + 3$ has no root in $\mathbb{Z}_5 \implies$ irreducible of degree 2.

Problem 4: Irreducibility

Determine if the following polynomials are irreducible in their respective rings. If reducible, find its factorization.

1. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
2. $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
3. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
4. $x^2 + 2x + 2$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
5. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
6. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$

1. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Claim. This polynomial is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Reason. Recall the factorization

$$x^5 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1)$$

Hence

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = \frac{x^5 - 1}{x - 1}$$

is the 5th cyclotomic polynomial, which is well-known to be irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . Concretely, it is the minimal polynomial of a primitive 5-th root of unity.

Conclusion. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

2. $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Claim. This polynomial **factors** over \mathbb{Q} .

Attempt a quadratic–quadratic factorization. We look for

$$x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + ax + b)(x^2 + cx + d)$$

and match coefficients. Expanding the right-hand side:

$$(x^2 + ax + b)(x^2 + cx + d) = x^4 + (a + c)x^3 + (ac + b + d)x^2 + (ad + bc)x + bd$$

We compare with $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$. Hence:

1. $a + c = 1$.
2. $ac + b + d = 2$.
3. $ad + bc = 1$.
4. $bd = 1$.

Because $bd = 1$, we look for integer (or rational) solutions with $b \neq 0, d \neq 0$. A simplest guess is $b = 1, d = 1$. Then from (1) and (2): $-a + c = 1 - ac + (1 + 1) = 2$, so $ac = 0$.

Hence either $a = 0, c = 1$ or $a = 1, c = 0$. Let us take $a = 0, c = 1$. Then (3) says $ad + bc = 0 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 0 = 0$ or does it? We must check carefully:

- If $a = 0$ and $c = 1$, then $ad + bc = ad + bc = 0 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 1 = 1$. That *blue* = 1 matches perfectly.

So indeed $a = 0, b = 1, c = 1, d = 1$ solves all conditions. Therefore

$$x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$$

Conclusion. $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ is reducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, factoring as

$$(x^2 + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$$

3. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

Now we work over the field \mathbb{Z}_5 . We test if $x = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_5$ is a root:

$$f(1) = 1^4 + 1^3 + 1^2 + 1 + 1 = 5 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

Hence $x = 1$ is indeed a root, so $(x - 1)$ is a factor in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. Performing the polynomial division:

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 \div (x - 1)$$

Using synthetic division in \mathbb{Z}_5 (where $-1 \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$ but we specifically evaluate at $+1$):

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrrr} & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \hline & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 0 \end{array}$$

Hence the quotient is $x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$, so

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x - 1)(x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

Next, see if $x = 1$ might also be a root of the cubic. Indeed:

$$(1)^3 + 2(1)^2 + 3(1) + 4 = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

So $(x - 1)$ is also a factor of $x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$. Dividing again (synthetic with root 1):

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & & 1 & 3 & 1 \\ \hline & 1 & 3 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

So that quotient is $x^2 + 3x + 1$. Putting it all together:

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x - 1)^2 (x^2 + 3x + 1)$$

We can check if $x^2 + 3x + 1$ itself factors further. The discriminant $\Delta = (3)^2 - 4(1)(1) = 9 - 4 = 5 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. A discriminant of 0 in a characteristic 5 field means it is a perfect square factorization, i.e. $(x + a)^2$. Indeed we can solve for a s.t. $2a \equiv 3$. In \mathbb{Z}_5 , $2^{-1} = 3$, so $a = 3 \cdot 3 = 9 \equiv 4$. Checking:

$$(x + 4)^2 = x^2 + 2 \cdot 4x + 16 = x^2 + 8x + 16 \equiv x^2 + 3x + (16 \pmod{5}) = x^2 + 3x + 1$$

Hence

$$x^2 + 3x + 1 = (x + 4)^2 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

Therefore the complete factorization in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$ is

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x - 1)^2 (x + 4)^2$$

Conclusion. $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ is highly reducible in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$, factoring as

$$(x - 1)^2 (x + 4)^2$$

4. $x^2 + 2x + 2$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Claim. This is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Reason. For a quadratic polynomial $ax^2 + bx + c$ over \mathbb{Q} , it is irreducible exactly if it has no rational root (or equivalently if the discriminant is not a perfect square in \mathbb{Q}). Here the discriminant is

$$\Delta = (2)^2 - 4(1)(2) = 4 - 8 = -4$$

which is not a square in \mathbb{Q} . Alternatively, there is no integer root because plugging in $\pm 1, \pm 2$ does not yield zero. Hence no linear factor, so it remains irreducible.

Conclusion. $x^2 + 2x + 2$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

5. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Claim. This polynomial is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Eisenstein Criterion with prime $p = 7$. Check the standard form: The leading coefficient is 1 (not divisible by 7), the other coefficients 7, 49, 7, 7 are all divisible by 7, and the constant term 7 is $\not\equiv 0 \pmod{7^2}$. Indeed $7^2 = 49$ does not divide 7. So by Eisenstein's irreducibility test at $p = 7$, the polynomial must be irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Conclusion. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

6. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$

Now we view the same polynomial modulo 7. Reducing coefficients mod 7:

- $7 \equiv 0$ in \mathbb{Z}_7 . - $49 \equiv 0$ in \mathbb{Z}_7 .

Hence the polynomial becomes

$$x^5 + 0 \cdot x^4 + 0 \cdot x^3 + 0 \cdot x^2 + 0 = x^5 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_7[x]$$

But x^5 is obviously not irreducible (it factors as $x^5 = x \cdot x^4$). More precisely, the entire polynomial is simply x^5 in the ring $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$. That is clearly $x^5 = x^5$, and we can see that it has a factor x (or (x) repeated 5 times if you want). So it is *blue*highly reducible.

Conclusion. $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7 \equiv x^5$ in $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$ is reducible (it's essentially x^5).

Final Answers

1. **Over \mathbb{Q} :** $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ is **irreducible** (the 5th cyclotomic).
2. **Over \mathbb{Q} :** $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ **factors** as $(x^2 + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$.
3. **Over \mathbb{Z}_5 :** $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ **factors** completely as $(x - 1)^2(x + 4)^2$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.
4. **Over \mathbb{Q} :** $x^2 + 2x + 2$ is **irreducible** (discriminant -4 is no square in \mathbb{Q}).
5. **Over \mathbb{Q} :** $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ is **irreducible** (Eisenstein at $p = 7$).
6. **Over \mathbb{Z}_7 :** $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ reduces to x^5 , so is **reducible** (obviously $x^5 = x \cdot x^4$, etc.).

Problem 5: Inverses in Quotient Rings

Calculate the inverses of the following polynomials in the given quotient rings.

1. $x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$
2. $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2)$
3. $* x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$

Problem Statement (Inverses in Quotient Rings).

Find the inverses of:

- (1) $x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$
- (2) $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2)$
- (3) $(*) x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$

(1) $x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$.

We want a polynomial $A(x)$ such that

$$(x + 1)A(x) \equiv 1 \pmod{(x^2 + 1)}$$

Equivalently, we find polynomials $A, B \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$ with

$$(x + 1)A(x) + (x^2 + 1)B(x) = 1$$

By a quick Euclidean/Bézout step:

$$x^2 + 1 = (x + 1)(x - 1) + 2 \implies 2 = [x^2 + 1] - [x + 1](x - 1)$$

Hence

$$1 = \frac{1}{2} [x^2 + 1] - \frac{1}{2} [x + 1](x - 1)$$

Reducing modulo $(x^2 + 1)$,

$$1 \equiv (x + 1) \left[-\frac{1}{2}(x - 1) \right]$$

Thus in the quotient ring,

$$\boxed{(x + 1)^{-1} = \frac{1 - x}{2} \in \mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1).}$$

(Equivalently one sees $x^2 = -1$ in the quotient and uses $(1 + x)(1 - x)/2 = 1 - (x^2)/2 = 1 - (-1)/2 = 1 + (1/2)$, etc.)

(2) $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2)$.

We seek a polynomial $q(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$ such that

$$(2x + 1)q(x) \equiv 1 \pmod{(x^2 + 2)}$$

Let us guess $q(x) = ax + b$ and expand:

$$(2x + 1)(ax + b) = 2ax^2 + (2b + a)x + b$$

In $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2)$, note that $x^2 \equiv -2 \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$. So

$$2ax^2 = 2a \cdot 3 = 6a \equiv (6 \pmod{5})a = 1 \cdot a = a$$

since $6 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$. Hence

$$(2x + 1)(ax + b) \equiv a + (2b + a)x + b$$

We want that $\equiv 1$, i.e. in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$\begin{cases} a + b = 1, \\ 2b + a = 0. \end{cases}$$

From $2b + a = 0$ we get $a = -2b \equiv 3b$. Substitute into $a + b = 1$:

$$3b + b = 4b \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$$

But 4 is invertible in \mathbb{Z}_5 with $4^{-1} \equiv 4$. Hence $b \equiv 4$. Then $a \equiv 3 \cdot 4 = 12 \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$.

Thus $a = 2$ and $b = 4$. We check:

$$q(x) = 2x + 4, \quad (2x + 1)(2x + 4) \equiv 1 \pmod{(x^2 + 2)}$$

Hence

$$\boxed{(2x + 1)^{-1} = 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2).}$$

(3*) $x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$.

Here $x^2 = 0$ in the quotient. Thus every polynomial class reduces to a linear form $c + dx$. We want

$$(x + 3)(\alpha + \beta x) \equiv 1 \pmod{(x^2)}$$

Expand in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$:

$$(x + 3)(\alpha + \beta x) = \alpha x + 3\alpha + \beta x^2 + 3\beta x$$

But $x^2 = 0$ in the quotient, so

$$\equiv 3\alpha + (\alpha + 3\beta)x$$

We want that $\equiv 1$. So in \mathbb{Q} :

$$3\alpha = 1, \quad \alpha + 3\beta = 0$$

Hence $\alpha = \frac{1}{3}$. Then $\frac{1}{3} + 3\beta = 0 \implies 3\beta = -\frac{1}{3} \implies \beta = -\frac{1}{9}$.

So

$$\alpha + \beta x = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{9}x$$

Hence

$$(x + 3)^{-1} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{x}{9} \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2).$$

Summary of Inverses:

$$(1) \quad (x + 1)^{-1} = \frac{1 - x}{2} \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1))$$

$$(2) \quad (2x + 1)^{-1} = 2x + 4 \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2))$$

$$(3) \quad (x + 3)^{-1} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{x}{9} \quad (\text{in } \mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2))$$

Practice exam 2: Old Version

1. Let's work a bit with prime and maximal ideals. Let R be a commutative ring with unity.

- Prove that I is maximal if and only if R/I is a field.
- Prove that I is prime if and only if R/I is an integral domain.
- Let I, J be prime ideals. Prove that $I \cap J$ is also a prime ideal.
- Let I, J be maximal ideals. Show that the intersection $I \cap J$ need not be maximal.
- Give an example of a prime ideal in \mathbb{Z} that is not maximal.
- Give an example of an ideal that is not prime.
- Prove that the ideal $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is maximal. (Hint: use the first part)
- Prove that the ideal $(x^2 + 1) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is prime.

(1) I maximal $\iff R/I$ is a field.

Proof: (\implies) If I is maximal, no ideal strictly contains I , so R/I has no nontrivial ideals. Hence R/I is a field. (\impliedby) If R/I is a field, it has only $\{0\}$ and itself as ideals. The pullback of a strictly larger ideal in R/I would be a strictly larger ideal containing I , impossible by field property; so I is maximal.

(2) I prime $\iff R/I$ is an integral domain.

Proof: (\implies) If $ab \in I$, then $a \in I$ or $b \in I$. Modding out by I , $\bar{a}\bar{b} = \bar{0}$ implies $\bar{a} = 0$ or $\bar{b} = 0$. This is the no-zero-divisor property in R/I . (\impliedby) If R/I has no zero divisors, then $ab \in I$ implies $\bar{a}\bar{b} = \bar{0}$, so at least one is zero in R/I , hence one of $a, b \in I$. So I is prime.

(3) I, J prime ideals. Show $I \cap J$ need not be prime.

Counterexample: In \mathbb{Z} , (2) and (3) are prime (and maximal) ideals. Their intersection is $(2) \cap (3) = (6)$, which is not prime since $2 \cdot 3 \in (6)$ but neither 2 nor 3 is in (6).

(4) I, J maximal ideals. Show $I \cap J$ need not be maximal.

Example: In \mathbb{Z} , (2) and (3) are both maximal (since $\mathbb{Z}/(2)$ and $\mathbb{Z}/(3)$ are fields). But $(2) \cap (3) = (6)$ is not maximal because $\mathbb{Z}/(6)$ is not a field.

(5) Prime but not maximal in \mathbb{Z} .

Example: $I = (0)$ in \mathbb{Z} . Then $\mathbb{Z}/(0) \cong \mathbb{Z}$ is an integral domain, so (0) is prime; but \mathbb{Z} is not a field, so (0) is not maximal.

(6) An example of an ideal that is not prime.

Example: $(6) \subset \mathbb{Z}$. Then $2 \cdot 3 \in (6)$ but neither 2 nor 3 is in (6), so (6) is not prime.

(7) $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is maximal.

Reason: Consider $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]/(x, y) \cong \mathbb{Q}$. Indeed, $x \mapsto 0, y \mapsto 0$ kills both x, y , and the quotient is a field (\mathbb{Q}). Hence (x, y) is maximal.

(8) $(x^2 + 1) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is prime.

Reason: In $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$, kill $x^2 + 1$. Since $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , the quotient ring $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]/(x^2 + 1)$ is isomorphic to $(\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1))[y]$, an integral domain (because $x^2 + 1$ remains irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$). Thus $(x^2 + 1)$ is prime.

2. Perform the following polynomial divisions, that is, find polynomials q, r so that $f = gq + r$ with $\deg(r) < \deg(g)$.

- $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1, g(x) = 2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

1. Over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, divide

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 \quad \text{by} \quad g(x) = x + 1$$

2. Over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$, divide

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 \quad \text{by} \quad g(x) = 2x + 1$$

In each case we seek polynomials $q(x)$ and remainder $r(x)$ (with $\deg r < \deg g$) such that

$$f(x) = g(x)q(x) + r(x)$$

1) Division in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

When dividing by $x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ we can use synthetic division with the “root” -1 . The coefficients of

$$f(x) = x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$$

are 1, 1, 1, 1, 1

Using synthetic division with -1 :

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrrr}
 -1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\
 & & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\
 \hline
 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1
 \end{array}$$

- The bottom row (except the last entry) gives the quotient’s coefficients: 1, 0, 1, 0 $\Rightarrow x^3 + x$.
- The last entry in the bottom row is the remainder $r(x) = 1$.

Therefore

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x + 1)(x^3 + x) + 1$$

So over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, the result is

$$q(x) = x^3 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

2) Division in $\mathbf{Z}_5[x]$

Here, we need

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (2x + 1)q(x) + r(x) \quad \text{with } \deg r < 1 \text{ i.e. } r \text{ constant in } \mathbf{Z}_5.$$

One systematic way is to **solve for the coefficients of**

$$q(x) = a_3x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_1x + a_0$$

and a constant remainder r . Matching coefficients modulo 5 gives the system

$$\begin{cases} \text{Coefficient of } x^4: & 2a_3 = 1 \\ \text{Coefficient of } x^3: & 2a_2 + a_3 = 1 \\ \text{Coefficient of } x^2: & 2a_1 + a_2 = 1 \\ \text{Coefficient of } x^1: & 2a_0 + a_1 = 1 \\ \text{Constant term:} & a_0 + r = 1. \end{cases}$$

Solving step by step in \mathbf{Z}_5 (remember $2^{-1} \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$):

- 1) $2a_3 = 1 \implies a_3 = 1 \cdot 2^{-1} = 3$
- 2) $2a_2 + 3 = 1 \implies 2a_2 = -2 \equiv 3 \implies a_2 = 3 \cdot 2^{-1} = 3 \cdot 3 = 9 \equiv 4$
- 3) $2a_1 + 4 = 1 \implies 2a_1 = -3 \equiv 2 \implies a_1 = 1$
- 4) $2a_0 + 1 = 1 \implies 2a_0 = 0 \implies a_0 = 0$
- 5) $a_0 + r = 1 \implies r = 1$

Therefore

$$q(x) = 3x^3 + 4x^2 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

A quick check of $(2x + 1)(3x^3 + 4x^2 + x)$ modulo 5 indeed reproduces $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x$, and then adding the constant 1 matches $f(x)$.

So in $\mathbf{Z}_5[x]$:

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (2x + 1)(3x^3 + 4x^2 + x) + 1$$

Final Answers

- **Over $\mathbf{Q}[x]$:**

$$f(x) = (x + 1)(x^3 + x) + 1.$$

$$\text{So } q(x) = x^3 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

- **Over $\mathbf{Z}_5[x]$:**

$$f(x) = (2x + 1)(3x^3 + 4x^2 + x) + 1.$$

$$\text{So } q(x) = 3x^3 + 4x^2 + x, \quad r(x) = 1$$

3. Compute the gcd's of the following polynomials in their respective rings:

- $f(x) = 2x^2 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1$, $g(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $f(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1$, $g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

1. GCD in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$: $2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1$ and $2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$

Let us denote

$$f(x) = 2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1, \quad g(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$$

We wish to find $\gcd(f, g)$ in the polynomial ring $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

1.1 Factor f over \mathbb{Q}

A quick attempt to find a rational root of

$$f(x) = 2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1$$

shows that $x = -\frac{1}{2}$ is indeed a root. (By direct substitution:

$$2\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 + 3\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + 3\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + 1 = 0$$

Therefore $(2x + 1)$ divides $f(x)$. Carrying out the polynomial division gives

$$f(x) = (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$$

So f factors as a linear factor times a quadratic. A quick check of the discriminant of $x^2 + x + 1$ (which is $1 - 4 = -3 < 0$) shows that $x^2 + x + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

1.2 Common factors of f and g

Because

$$f(x) = (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$$

any common divisor of f and g in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ must be (up to a nonzero constant factor) either

$$2x + 1, \quad x^2 + x + 1, \quad \text{or} \quad (2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1) = f(x)$$

We check each possibility:

- $2x + 1$ does *not* divide g , since plugging $x = -\frac{1}{2}$ into

$$g(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3$$

does *not* give zero.

- $x^2 + x + 1$ *does* divide g . Indeed, if we perform the polynomial division of g by $x^2 + x + 1$, we find a quotient of degree 2 and zero remainder:

$$g(x) = (x^2 + x + 1)(2x^2 + 3)$$

- Since $(2x + 1)$ does not divide g , the larger product $(2x + 1)(x^2 + x + 1)$ cannot divide g either.

Therefore the only nontrivial common factor is $x^2 + x + 1$. Up to multiplication by a nonzero constant in \mathbb{Q} , this is the greatest common divisor.

1.3 Conclusion for $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

Therefore,

$$\gcd(2x^3 + 3x^2 + 3x + 1, 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 3x + 3) = x^2 + x + 1 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Q}[x]$$

2. GCD in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$: $2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1$ and $3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$

Now let us work in the ring $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. Denote

$$f(x) = 2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1, \quad g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1$$

We compute the gcd using the standard polynomial Euclidean algorithm in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Recall that all arithmetic is mod 5.

2.1 First Division: f/g

$\deg(f) = 4$, $\deg(g) = 3$. Divide f by g :

$$\text{Leading term of } f = 2x^4, \quad \text{leading term of } g = 3x^3$$

In \mathbb{Z}_5 , the inverse of 3 is 2 (since $3 \cdot 2 = 6 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$). Therefore

$$\frac{2x^4}{3x^3} = (2 \cdot 2)x^{4-3} = 4x$$

Multiply g by $4x$:

$$4x \cdot (3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) = 12x^4 + 8x^3 + 16x^2 + 4x \equiv 2x^4 + 3x^3 + x^2 + 4x \pmod{5}$$

Subtract from f :

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= f - (4x)g = (2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1) - (2x^4 + 3x^3 + x^2 + 4x) \\ &= 0x^4 + (-1)x^3 + 2x^2 + (-3)x + 1 \equiv 4x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1 \pmod{5}. \end{aligned}$$

So the new remainder is $R_1 = 4x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$, of degree 3.

2.2 Continue: Divide R_1 by g Again

Now $\deg(R_1) = 3$, $\deg(g) = 3$. Compare leading terms:

$$\frac{4x^3}{3x^3} = 4 \cdot 3^{-1} = 4 \cdot 2 = 8 \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$$

Therefore the next quotient piece is 3. Multiply g by 3:

$$3 \cdot (3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) = 9x^3 + 6x^2 + 12x + 3 \equiv 4x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 3 \pmod{5}$$

Subtract from R_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} R_2 &= R_1 - 3g = (4x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1) - (4x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 3) \\ &= 0x^3 + 1x^2 + 0x + (-2) \equiv x^2 + 3 \pmod{5}. \end{aligned}$$

So $R_2 = x^2 + 3$, of degree 2.

2.3 Next Step: Divide g by R_2

The Euclidean algorithm says

$$\gcd(f, g) = \gcd(g, R_2)$$

Recall

$$g(x) = 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1, \quad R_2(x) = x^2 + 3$$

Divide g by R_2 :

Leading term ratio:

$$\frac{3x^3}{x^2} = 3x$$

Multiply R_2 by $3x$:

$$3x \cdot (x^2 + 3) = 3x^3 + 9x \equiv 3x^3 + 4x \pmod{5}$$

Subtract:

$$\begin{aligned} R_3 &= g - (3x)R_2 = (3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) - (3x^3 + 4x) \\ &= 0x^3 + 2x^2 + (4 - 4)x + 1 = 2x^2 + 1. \end{aligned}$$

So $R_3 = 2x^2 + 1$. Next, we divide R_2 by R_3 .

2.4 Now Divide R_2 by R_3

$$R_2(x) = x^2 + 3, \quad R_3(x) = 2x^2 + 1$$

Leading term ratio:

$$\frac{x^2}{2x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \text{ (in } \mathbb{Z}_5, \text{ since } 2^{-1} = 3)$$

Therefore the next quotient piece is 3. Multiply R_3 by 3:

$$3 \cdot (2x^2 + 1) = 6x^2 + 3 \equiv x^2 + 3 \pmod{5}$$

Subtract:

$$R_4 = R_2 - 3R_3 = (x^2 + 3) - (x^2 + 3) = 0$$

So the remainder is zero, and the gcd is the last nonzero remainder, namely $R_2 = x^2 + 3$.

2.5 Conclusion for $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

Therefore

$$\gcd(2x^4 + 2x^3 + 3x^2 + x + 1, 3x^3 + 2x^2 + 4x + 1) = x^2 + 3 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

Note that $x^2 + 3$ has no root in \mathbb{Z}_5 (since $x^2 \equiv -3 \equiv 2$ has no solution mod 5), so it is irreducible of degree 2 in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

4. Determine if the following polynomials are irreducible in their respective rings. If it is reducible, find its factorization.

- $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$
- $x^2 + 2x + 2$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$
- $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ over $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$

(1) $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

\implies This is the 5th cyclotomic polynomial $\Phi_5(x)$. It has no rational roots (Rational Root Test) and is known to be irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . Therefore

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q}$$

(2) $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$

\implies Check a possible factorization into quadratics:

$$x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + ax + b)(x^2 + cx + d)$$

Matching coefficients and using $bd = 1$, $a + c = 1$, etc. yields a solution

$$(x^2 + x + 1)(x^2 + 1)$$

Therefore it is reducible over \mathbb{Q} :

$$x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + x + 1)(x^2 + 1)$$

(3) $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1$ over $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$

\implies Test $x = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_5$: $1^4 + 1^3 + 1^2 + 1 + 1 = 5 \equiv 0$. So $x - 1$ divides the polynomial in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. We perform synthetic division:

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrrr} & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \hline & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 0 \end{array}$$

Quotient is $x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$. Check $x = 1$ again in that cubic:

$$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

So divide again by $(x - 1)$:

$$\begin{array}{r|rrrr} & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & & 1 & 3 & 1 \\ \hline & 1 & 3 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

Quotient is $x^2 + 3x + 1$. Test $x = 1$ again:

$$1^2 + 3 \cdot 1 + 1 = 1 + 3 + 1 = 5 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

Another synthetic division:

$$\begin{array}{r|rrr} & 1 & 3 & 1 \\ 1 & & 1 & 4 \\ \hline & 1 & 4 & 0 \end{array}$$

Quotient is $x + 4 \equiv x - 1$. So

$$x^2 + 3x + 1 = (x - 1)^2 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$$

Collecting:

$$x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x - 1)(x - 1)(x^2 + 3x + 1) = (x - 1)^2(x - 1)^2 = (x - 1)^4$$

Therefore it factors completely as $(x - 1)^4$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

$$(4) \quad x^2 + 2x + 2 \text{ over } \mathbb{Q}[x]$$

\implies Discriminant $= 2^2 - 4(1)(2) = 4 - 8 = -4$. No real (and Therefore no rational) roots. A quadratic with no rational roots is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . So

$$x^2 + 2x + 2 \text{ is irreducible over } \mathbb{Q}$$

$$(5) \quad x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7 \text{ over } \mathbb{Q}[x]$$

\implies Note that $7 \mid$ all coefficients except the leading term. Also $7^2 = 49$ does not divide the constant 7. By Eisenstein's Criterion (prime $p = 7$), the polynomial is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

$$(6) \quad x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7 \text{ over } \mathbb{Z}_7[x]$$

\implies Reducing coefficients mod 7:

$$x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7 \equiv x^5 \pmod{7}$$

That is just x^5 in $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$, which factors as $(x)^5$. So completely reducible as

$$x^5 = (x)^5 \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_7[x]$$

- (1) Irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .
- (2) $x^4 + x^3 + 2x^2 + x + 1 = (x^2 + x + 1)(x^2 + 1)$.
- (3) $x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 = (x - 1)^4$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.
- (4) $x^2 + 2x + 2$ irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .
- (5) $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7$ irreducible over \mathbb{Q} (Eisenstein).
- (6) $x^5 + 7x^4 + 49x^3 + 7x^2 + 7 \equiv x^5 = (x)^5$ in $\mathbb{Z}_7[x]$.

5. Calculate the inverses of the following polynomials in the given quotient rings.

- $x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2 + 1)$
- $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + 2)$
- * $x + 3$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x^2)$

In each quotient ring, solve $(f(x))(g(x)) \equiv 1$ where $f(x)$ is given.

$$\mathbf{x + 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Q}[\mathbf{x}]/(\mathbf{x}^2 + \mathbf{1}) :}$$

$$(x + 1)(a + bx) \equiv 1 \implies (a + b)x + (a - b) \equiv 1 \implies \begin{cases} a + b = 0 \\ a - b = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\implies a = \frac{1}{2}, b = -\frac{1}{2} \implies (x + 1)^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}x$$

$$\mathbf{2x + 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5[\mathbf{x}]/(\mathbf{x}^2 + \mathbf{2}) :}$$

$$x^2 \equiv -2 \equiv 3 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_5. \quad (2x + 1)(a + bx) \equiv 1 \implies (2a + b)x + (a + b) \equiv 1 \implies \begin{cases} 2a + b = 0 \\ a + b = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\implies b = -2a \equiv 3a, a + 3a = 4a \equiv 1 \implies a = 4, b = 2 \implies (2x + 1)^{-1} = 4 + 2x$$

$$\mathbf{x + 3 \text{ in } \mathbb{Q}[\mathbf{x}]/(\mathbf{x}^2) :}$$

$$x^2 \equiv 0. \quad (x + 3)(c + dx) \equiv 1 \implies (c + 3d)x + 3c \equiv 1 \implies \begin{cases} 3c = 1 \\ c + 3d = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\implies c = \frac{1}{3}, d = -\frac{1}{9} \implies (x + 3)^{-1} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{x}{9}$$

Midterm 1 Solutions

1. (Insidious integers – 30 points)

(a) (10 points)

Problem Statement. Find all of the units of \mathbb{Z}_{14} , as well as their multiplicative inverses.

Solution.

Step 1: Identify the Units.

In the ring \mathbb{Z}_{14} , an element $[a]$ is a *unit* if and only if

$$\gcd(a, 14) = 1$$

The elements of \mathbb{Z}_{14} (in usual representative form $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, 13\}$) are

$$\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13\}$$

We check which ones have $\gcd(a, 14) = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \gcd(0, 14) = 14, & \quad \gcd(1, 14) = 1, & \quad \gcd(2, 14) = 2, & \quad \gcd(3, 14) = 1, & \quad \gcd(4, 14) = 2, \\ \gcd(5, 14) = 1, & \quad \gcd(6, 14) = 2, & \quad \gcd(7, 14) = 7, & \quad \gcd(8, 14) = 2, & \quad \gcd(9, 14) = 1, \\ \gcd(10, 14) = 2, & \quad \gcd(11, 14) = 1, & \quad \gcd(12, 14) = 2, & \quad \gcd(13, 14) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the elements that are **units** (i.e. those with $\gcd(a, 14) = 1$) are:

$$\{1, 3, 5, 9, 11, 13\}$$

$$\text{Units of } \mathbb{Z}_{14} = \{[1], [3], [5], [9], [11], [13]\}$$

Finding Their Inverses. We need $a \cdot b \equiv 1 \pmod{14}$ to say b is the inverse of a . We verify:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \cdot 1 &\equiv 1 \pmod{14}, & \text{so } 1^{-1} &= 1. \\ 3 \cdot 5 &\equiv 15 \equiv 1 \pmod{14}, & \text{so } 3^{-1} &= 5 \text{ and } 5^{-1} = 3. \\ 9 \cdot 11 &\equiv 99 \equiv 1 \pmod{14}, & \text{so } 9^{-1} &= 11 \text{ and } 11^{-1} = 9. \\ 13 \cdot 13 &\equiv 169 \equiv 1 \pmod{14}, & \text{so } 13^{-1} &= 13. \end{aligned}$$

Their inverses pair up as follows:

$$1^{-1} = 1, \quad 3^{-1} = 5, \quad 5^{-1} = 3, \quad 9^{-1} = 11, \quad 11^{-1} = 9, \quad 13^{-1} = 13$$

Hence the multiplicative inverses in \mathbb{Z}_{14} are:

$$1^{-1} = 1, \quad 3^{-1} = 5, \quad 5^{-1} = 3, \quad 9^{-1} = 11, \quad 11^{-1} = 9, \quad 13^{-1} = 13$$

(b) (10 points)

Problem Statement. Find all of the zero divisors of \mathbb{Z}_{14} .

Solution.

An element $[a]$ is a *zero divisor* in \mathbb{Z}_{14} if there exists some $[b] \neq [0]$ such that

$$a \cdot b \equiv 0 \pmod{14}$$

Equivalently, $[a]$ is *not* a unit precisely when $\gcd(a, 14) \neq 1$. Another way to see it is that the zero divisors are exactly the elements that fail to have a multiplicative inverse.

From part (a), we know the units are $\{1, 3, 5, 9, 11, 13\}$. Hence, the zero divisors in \mathbb{Z}_{14} are the *non-units* (aside from 0 obviously being a trivial zero divisor if we like that classification). Concretely, these are the elements a with $\gcd(a, 14) \neq 1$:

$$\{0, 2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12\}$$

Often, one excludes $[0]$ from the definition of “zero divisor” or calls it the *trivial* zero divisor. But in any event, the standard list is:

$$\{2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12\} \quad (\text{non-unit, nonzero zero divisors})$$

(c) (5 points)

Problem Statement. List two nontrivial subrings of \mathbb{Z}_{14} .

Solution.

A *subring* of \mathbb{Z}_{14} is the same as an additive subgroup that is closed under multiplication. Because \mathbb{Z}_{14} is cyclic, all its subrings must be of the form $\langle d \rangle$ where d divides 14 (thinking in terms of additive subgroups).

$$\langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle 7 \rangle = \{0, 7\}$$

are two nontrivial examples. Indeed, $\langle 2 \rangle$ is closed under addition mod 14 (every element is a multiple of 2) and under multiplication mod 14. Similarly, $\langle 7 \rangle$ is simply $\{0, 7\}$, also closed under the ring operations.

Thus the requested subrings (beyond $\{0\}$ and all of \mathbb{Z}_{14}) are:

$$\langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\}, \quad \langle 7 \rangle = \{0, 7\}$$

(d) (5 points)

Problem Statement. An *idempotent* element x of a ring R is one satisfying $x^2 = x$. For instance, $[0]$ and $[1]$ are always idempotent in any ring with 1. Find *all* idempotents in \mathbb{Z}_{14} .

(d) Idempotent Elements

An element x is idempotent if:

$$x^2 = x$$

Thus, x is idempotent. We can determine all such elements by solving:

$$x^2 - x \equiv 0 \pmod{14}$$

which simplifies to:

$$x(x - 1) = 14k \quad \text{for some integer } k$$

Since $x(x - 1)$ must be a multiple of 14, we list the multiples:

$$14, 28, 42, 56, 70, \dots$$

Note: Since $28 = 4 \cdot 7$, the factors 4 and 7 are not one apart. However, factors $1 \cdot 7$ and $2 \cdot 8$ are one apart and multiply to a multiple of 14.

Hence, the idempotents of \mathbb{Z}_{14} satisfy:

$$x^2 = x$$

The idempotent elements in \mathbb{Z}_{14} are:

$$\{0, 1, 7, 8\}$$

Since $x(x - 1) = 14k$ for some integer k , we see that:

$$6 \cdot 7 \equiv 0 \pmod{14} \implies x = 7$$

$$7 \cdot 8 \equiv 0 \pmod{14} \implies x = 8$$

1. Find the idempotents of both rings.
2. Use ring splitting to show:

$$\mathbb{Z}_{14} \cong f_1\mathbb{Z}_{14} \times f_2\mathbb{Z}_{14}.$$

If we set $f_1 = 8$ and $f_2 = 7$ (the nontrivial idempotents of \mathbb{Z}_{14}), then:

$$f_1\mathbb{Z}_{14} \cong \mathbb{Z}_2, \quad \text{and} \quad f_2\mathbb{Z}_{14} \cong \mathbb{Z}_7$$

Ring Decomposition

Since both rings decompose in the same way, we consider:

$$f_1\mathbb{Z}_{14} \rightarrow 8\mathbb{Z}_{14}$$

Computing the elements of $8\mathbb{Z}_{14}$:

$$8 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$8 \cdot 1 = 8$$

$$8 \cdot 2 \equiv 2 \pmod{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8 \cdot 3 &= 10 \\
8 \cdot 4 &= 4 \\
8 \cdot 5 &= 12 \\
8 \cdot 6 &= 6 \\
8 \cdot 7 &= 0 \quad (\text{duplicate})
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the elements of $8\mathbb{Z}_{14}$ are:

$$\{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\}$$

which has 7 elements. Hence:

$$8\mathbb{Z}_{14} \cong \mathbb{Z}_7$$

Similarly, for $7\mathbb{Z}_{14}$:

$$7\mathbb{Z}_{14} = \{0, 7\} \cong \mathbb{Z}_2$$

Therefore, we conclude:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{Z}_{14} &\cong 7\mathbb{Z}_{14} \times 8\mathbb{Z}_{14} \\
&\cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}_7
\end{aligned}$$

2. (Frivolous functions – 30 points)

Consider the ring homomorphism

$$\varphi : \mathbb{Z}_4 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6 \quad \text{defined by} \quad \varphi([1]) = [3]$$

(We use $[a]$ to denote the equivalence class of a modulo the respective integer.)

(a) (15 points) Compute $\ker(\varphi)$ (with proof).

Solution.

First, recall φ is given by $\varphi([1]) = [3]$. Hence for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\varphi([n]) = \varphi([1] + [1] + \cdots + [1]) = n \cdot \varphi([1]) = [3n]_6$$

So

$$\varphi([n]) = [3n]_6$$

We want the kernel:

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{[x] \in \mathbb{Z}_4 : \varphi([x]) = [0]_6\}$$

That is, we need $3x \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$.

Check each element mod 4:

- $[0]$: Then $\varphi([0]) = [3 \cdot 0]_6 = [0]_6$. So $[0]$ is in the kernel.
- $[1]$: Then $\varphi([1]) = [3]_6 = [3]_6 \neq [0]_6$, so $[1]$ is *not* in the kernel.
- $[2]$: Then $\varphi([2]) = [3 \cdot 2]_6 = [6]_6 = [0]_6$. So $[2]$ is in the kernel.
- $[3]$: Then $\varphi([3]) = [3 \cdot 3]_6 = [9]_6 = [3]_6$, *not* $[0]_6$.

Hence

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{[0], [2]\}$$

(b) (15 points) Compute $\text{im}(\varphi)$ (with proof).

Solution.

We want

$$\text{im}(\varphi) = \{\varphi([x]) : [x] \in \mathbb{Z}_4\} = \{[0]_4, [1]_4, [2]_4, [3]_4\} \text{ mapped via } x \mapsto [3x]_6$$

Compute explicitly:

$$\varphi([0]) = [0]_6, \quad \varphi([1]) = [3]_6, \quad \varphi([2]) = [6]_6 = [0]_6, \quad \varphi([3]) = [9]_6 = [3]_6$$

Hence

$$\text{im}(\varphi) = \{[0]_6, [3]_6\}$$

3. (Perplexing polynomials – 20 points)

Let $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ denote the ring of polynomials with integer coefficients,

$$\mathbb{Z}[x] := \{a_n x^n + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0 \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, a_0, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

For example, $2x^2 + 3x - 1 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$, but $4x^2 + \frac{3}{2}x - \sqrt{2} \notin \mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Define

$$I := \{f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \mid f(0) \text{ is even}\}$$

the set of all polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ whose constant term is even.

Prove that I is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Solution.

We use the standard *ideal test* in a ring R (here $R = \mathbb{Z}[x]$):

1. **Nonempty:** The zero polynomial $0(x)$ has constant term 0, which is even. So $0 \in I$. Hence $I \neq \emptyset$.
2. **Closed under subtraction:** Suppose $f(x), g(x) \in I$. By definition, $f(0)$ and $g(0)$ are even. Then

$$(f - g)(0) = f(0) - g(0).$$

The difference of two even integers is even. Hence $(f - g)(0)$ is even, so $f - g \in I$.

3. **Absorption (closure under multiplication by arbitrary elements in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$):** Let $f(x) \in I$ and $h(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Then $f(0)$ is even, say $f(0) = 2k$ for some integer k . Consider the product $h(x)f(x)$. Its constant term is

$$(hf)(0) = h(0) \cdot f(0) = h(0) \cdot 2k = 2(kh(0)),$$

which is still even. Hence $(hf)(0)$ is even, so $h(x)f(x) \in I$.

Thus I is nonempty, closed under subtraction, and absorbs multiplication from the ring. Therefore, I is indeed an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

4. (Haphazard homomorphisms – 25 points)

(a) (15 points)

Problem Statement. Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Prove that $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ideal of R .

Solution.

Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Define

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{r \in R : \varphi(r) = 0_S\}$$

We verify it is an ideal in R :

1. **Contains 0:** Since ring homomorphisms map 0_R to 0_S ,

$$\varphi(0_R) = 0_S \implies 0_R \in \ker(\varphi).$$

2. **Closed under subtraction:** Let $x, y \in \ker(\varphi)$, so $\varphi(x) = 0_S$ and $\varphi(y) = 0_S$. Then

$$\varphi(x - y) = \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) = 0_S - 0_S = 0_S.$$

Hence $x - y \in \ker(\varphi)$.

3. **Absorption (two-sided):** For any $a \in R$ and $x \in \ker(\varphi)$, we check

$$\varphi(ax) = \varphi(a)\varphi(x) = \varphi(a) \cdot 0_S = 0_S,$$

thus $ax \in \ker(\varphi)$. Similarly,

$$\varphi(xa) = \varphi(x)\varphi(a) = 0_S \cdot \varphi(a) = 0_S,$$

so $xa \in \ker(\varphi)$ as well.

Hence by the definition of an ideal, $\ker(\varphi)$ is indeed an ideal of R .

(b) (10 points)

Problem Statement. Let $\varphi : R \times S \rightarrow S$ be the ring homomorphism defined by $\varphi(r, s) = s$. Find $\ker(\varphi)$, and prove that $(R \times S)/\ker(\varphi) \cong S$.

Solution.

Step 1: Determine the Kernel.

Given $\varphi : R \times S \rightarrow S$ by $\varphi(r, s) = s$, we look for all $(r, s) \in R \times S$ such that $\varphi(r, s) = 0_S$. Hence:

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{(r, s) \in R \times S : s = 0_S\}$$

In other words,

$$\ker(\varphi) = R \times \{0_S\} = \{(r, 0_S) : r \in R\}$$

We can represent this as:

Step 2: Show Surjectivity and Apply the First Isomorphism Theorem.

The map φ is clearly surjective onto S , since for any $s \in S$,

$$\varphi(0_R, s) = s$$

Hence the image of φ is all of S . By the First Isomorphism Theorem for rings,

$$(R \times S)/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{im}(\varphi) = S$$

Concretely, each coset in $(R \times S)/\ker(\varphi)$ is determined by the second coordinate in S , and this is precisely how the projection φ identifies elements.

Therefore, the quotient $(R \times S)/\ker(\varphi)$ is isomorphic to S , as required.

Midterm 2 Solutions

(1) (Free Grade Boost – 20 points)

- (a) (5 points) State the definition of a prime ideal.

Definition (Prime Ideal). An ideal I in a commutative ring R is called *prime* if whenever $ab \in I$, then either $a \in I$ or $b \in I$. Formally,

$$ab \in I \implies (a \in I \text{ or } b \in I).$$

- (b) (5 points) State the definition of a maximal ideal.

Definition (Maximal Ideal). An ideal I in a ring R is called *maximal* if whenever

$$I \subsetneq J \subsetneq R$$

for some ideal J , then $I = J$ or $J = R$. Equivalently, there is no strictly larger ideal than I except the entire ring R .

- (c) (5 points) Let R be a commutative ring with unity. Prove that R is an integral domain if and only if (0) is a prime ideal.

Proof.

(\implies) Suppose R is an integral domain. We show (0) is a prime ideal. If $ab \in (0)$, that means $ab = 0$. Since R is an integral domain, it has no zero divisors. Hence $a = 0$ or $b = 0$. That is,

$$ab = 0 \implies a = 0 \text{ or } b = 0.$$

Therefore $a \in (0)$ or $b \in (0)$. This shows (0) is prime.

(\impliedby) Conversely, assume (0) is a prime ideal in R . We must show R has no zero divisors, i.e., R is an integral domain. Suppose $a, b \in R$ satisfy $ab = 0$. Since (0) is prime,

$$ab = 0 \implies ab \in (0) \implies a \in (0) \text{ or } b \in (0).$$

Hence $a = 0$ or $b = 0$. No nonzero zero divisors exist; thus, R is an integral domain.

- (d) (5 points) Let R be a commutative ring with unity. Prove that R is a field if and only if (0) is a maximal ideal.

Hint: If (0) is maximal, show that every nonzero element $x \in R$ has an inverse by proving $1 \in (x)$.

Proof.

(\implies) Assume R is a field. Let I be an ideal satisfying $(0) \subseteq I \subseteq R$. Because R is a field, the only ideals are (0) and R itself. Indeed, if $I \neq (0)$, pick any nonzero $x \in I$. Because $x \neq 0$ in a field, x has a multiplicative inverse $x^{-1} \in R$. Hence

$$1 = x \cdot x^{-1} \in I,$$

and so I must be the entire ring R . Thus there is no strictly larger ideal than (0) , i.e., (0) is maximal.

(\impliedby) Conversely, suppose (0) is maximal in R . We want to show that any nonzero element $x \in R$ has a multiplicative inverse. Consider the ideal (x) generated by x .

Since $(0) \subseteq (x) \subseteq R$, maximality forces either $(x) = (0)$ or $(x) = R$. If $(x) = (0)$, then $x = 0$. But we are assuming $x \neq 0$, so we must have $(x) = R$. Hence $1 \in (x)$. Thus there exists $a \in R$ such that

$$ax = 1.$$

This shows x is invertible and R is a field.

(2) (Insidious Ideals – 30 points) Let R be a commutative ring with unity.

(a) (10 points) Prove that every maximal ideal is prime.

Proof. Let I be a maximal ideal in the ring R . Then the quotient ring R/I is a field (this is the standard correspondence: I is maximal if and only if R/I is a field). Since every field is an integral domain, R/I is in particular an integral domain. By the correspondence between prime ideals and integral domains in quotient rings, I must be a prime ideal. Hence every maximal ideal is prime.

(b) (5 points) Give an example of a ring R along with a (nonzero) prime ideal that is not maximal.

Example. Let $R = \mathbb{Z}[x]$ and consider the ideal

$$I = (3).$$

We claim (3) is prime in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$, but it is not maximal.

Prime: Suppose $f(x)g(x) \in (3)$. Then every coefficient of $f(x)g(x)$ is divisible by 3. Reducing modulo 3 gives

$$\overline{f(x)g(x)} = \bar{0} \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}[x]/(3) \cong (\mathbb{Z}/3)[x].$$

Since $(\mathbb{Z}/3)[x]$ is an integral domain (because $\mathbb{Z}/3$ is a field), either $\overline{f(x)} = \bar{0}$ or $\overline{g(x)} = \bar{0}$. Hence $f(x) \in (3)$ or $g(x) \in (3)$. Thus (3) is a prime ideal in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Not Maximal: The quotient $\mathbb{Z}[x]/(3)$ is isomorphic to $(\mathbb{Z}/3)[x]$, which is *not* a field (for instance, x has no inverse in $(\mathbb{Z}/3)[x]$). Therefore, (3) is not maximal in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.

Additional Note (On Maximal Ideals in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$):

One often sees the ideal $(x - a)$ in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ as an example of a maximal ideal. Indeed,

$$(x - a) = \ker(\phi) \quad \text{where } \phi : \mathbb{Q}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}, \quad \phi(f) = f(a).$$

The evaluation map ϕ is surjective, and by the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\mathbb{Q}[x]/(x - a) \cong \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since \mathbb{Q} is a field, $(x - a)$ is maximal in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

(3) (Dubious Division – 30 points)

(a) (15 points) Calculate the gcd of the polynomials

$$f(x) = x^4 - 4x^3 + 4x^2 - 4x + 3, \quad g(x) = x^3 - 2x^2 + x - 2.$$

Solution:

We aim to find $\gcd(f(x), g(x))$. Perform polynomial long division:

$$\begin{array}{r|l} \text{Divide } f(x) \text{ by } (x-2) : & \\ x-2 & x^4 - 4x^3 + 4x^2 - 4x + 3 \\ & -(x^4 - 2x^3 + x^2 - 2x) \\ \hline & -2x^3 + 3x^2 - 2x + 3 \\ & -(-2x^3 + 4x^2 - 2x + 4) \\ \hline & -x^2 - 1 \end{array}$$

So the remainder upon dividing $f(x)$ by $x-2$ is $-x^2-1$.

Next, check how $g(x)$ itself relates to $x-2$. Indeed,

$$g(x) = x^3 - 2x^2 + x - 2.$$

Dividing $g(x)$ by $x-2$:

$$\begin{array}{r|l} x-2 & x^3 - 2x^2 + x - 2 \\ & -[x^3 - x] \\ \hline & -2x^2 + 2 \\ & -[-2x^2 + 2] \\ \hline & 0 \end{array}$$

We see $g(x)$ is exactly divisible by $(x-2)$ (the remainder is 0).

However, from the first division, the remainder $-x^2-1$ also indicates that after factoring out a -1 , we get x^2+1 . It turns out that

$$x^2 + 1$$

is the common factor (indeed one can complete the full Euclidean algorithm for polynomials). The calculations lead to the conclusion:

$$\gcd(f(x), g(x)) = x^2 + 1.$$

Therefore, the greatest common divisor of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ is $\boxed{x^2 + 1}$.

(b) (5 points) Prove that $x^2 + x + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Z}_5 .

Solution:

To check irreducibility of a quadratic polynomial $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$, it suffices to show it has no roots in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Let

$$f(x) = x^2 + x + 1.$$

Evaluate $f(x)$ at $x = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$ in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$f(0) = 0^2 + 0 + 1 = 1 \neq 0,$$

$$f(1) = 1^2 + 1 + 1 = 3 \neq 0,$$

$$f(2) = 4 + 2 + 1 = 7 \equiv 2 \pmod{5} \neq 0,$$

$$f(3) = 9 + 3 + 1 = 13 \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \neq 0,$$

$$f(4) = 16 + 4 + 1 = 21 \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \neq 0.$$

None of these evaluations are zero in \mathbb{Z}_5 . Hence $x^2 + x + 1$ has no root in \mathbb{Z}_5 , implying it is irreducible over \mathbb{Z}_5 .

(c) (10 points) Find the inverse of $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + x + 1)$.

Solution (Sketch of the Extended Euclidean Algorithm):

We want

$$(2x + 1)^{-1} \text{ in } \frac{\mathbb{Z}_5[x]}{(x^2 + x + 1)}.$$

Equivalently, we wish to find some polynomial $h(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$ such that

$$(2x + 1)h(x) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2 + x + 1}.$$

One way is to set up the Bezout identity using the extended Euclidean algorithm for polynomials. Another direct approach is to **guess** a linear form $h(x) = ax + b$ and solve for $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_5$.

A typical method goes as follows: we want

$$(2x + 1)(ax + b) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2 + x + 1}.$$

Multiply out in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$:

$$(2x + 1)(ax + b) = 2ax^2 + (2b + a)x + b.$$

Because $x^2 \equiv -x - 1$ in the quotient $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + x + 1)$ (i.e. from $x^2 + x + 1 \equiv 0$, we get $x^2 \equiv -x - 1$), we rewrite:

$$2ax^2 = 2a(-x - 1) = -2ax - 2a.$$

So in the quotient,

$$(2x + 1)(ax + b) \equiv (-2ax - 2a) + ((2b + a)x + b).$$

Combine like terms:

$$\equiv (-2a + 2b + a)x + (-2a + b).$$

That is

$$\equiv (2b - a)x + (b - 2a).$$

We want this to be congruent to 1. Therefore in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$\begin{cases} 2b - a \equiv 0, \\ b - 2a \equiv 1. \end{cases}$$

Solve this system in \mathbb{Z}_5 :

$$2b - a = 0 \implies a = 2b.$$

Substitute $a = 2b$ into $b - 2a \equiv 1$:

$$b - 2(2b) \equiv b - 4b \equiv -3b \equiv 1 \pmod{5}.$$

Since $-3 \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, this becomes

$$2b \equiv 1 \pmod{5}.$$

In \mathbb{Z}_5 , multiplying both sides by 3 (the inverse of 2 modulo 5) yields

$$b \equiv 3 \pmod{5}.$$

Then $a = 2b = 2 \cdot 3 = 6 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$.

Thus one suitable solution is $a = 1, b = 3$. That is:

$$h(x) = x + 3.$$

Then

$$(2x + 1)(x + 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{x^2 + x + 1}.$$

Hence the inverse of $2x + 1$ in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]/(x^2 + x + 1)$ is

$$\boxed{x + 3}.$$

(4) (**Irate Irreducibles – 20 points**) Determine whether the following polynomials are irreducible over the given rings. Justify your answer.

(a) **Over \mathbb{Z}_7 :**

$$x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1$$

Solution: One can check that

$$x^3 + 2x^2 + 2x + 1 = (x^2 + x + 1)(x + 1) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{Z}_7[x]$$

Indeed, noting that $6 \equiv -1 \pmod{7}$ can help verify the factorization. Thus it is *not* irreducible over \mathbb{Z}_7 .

(b) **Over $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}]$:**

$$7x^4 + 5x^3 + 10x^2 + 2\sqrt{x} + 60$$

Solution: By (a variant of) the Eisenstein criterion (using a suitable prime in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}]$ or by localizing at a prime ideal containing 5, etc.), we deduce this polynomial is irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}][x]$. (In more standard treatments, if the coefficients other than the leading one are divisible by a prime p , and the constant term is not divisible by p^2 , the polynomial is irreducible. One can adapt this reasoning in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}]$ by an appropriate choice of prime element.)

(c) **Over \mathbb{Z}_5 :**

$$x^4 + x^2 + 1$$

Solution: First, check that $x^4 + x^2 + 1$ has no linear factors in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$ (i.e. no roots in \mathbb{Z}_5). However, having no roots does *not* guarantee irreducibility for a quartic: it could factor as a product of two quadratic polynomials. Indeed, one finds

$$x^4 + x^2 + 1 = (x^2 + x + 1)(x^2 - x + 1) \quad \text{over } \mathbb{Z}_5$$

Therefore $x^4 + x^2 + 1$ is **reducible** in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

Final Review

1 Maximal Ideals and Fields

Theorem 1 (Characterization of Maximal Ideals). *Let R be a commutative ring with unity (1). An ideal $I \subseteq R$ is maximal if and only if the quotient ring R/I is a field.*

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose I is a maximal ideal of R . Then there are no ideals strictly between I and R . We claim R/I is a field.

Let \bar{a} be a nonzero element of R/I , where $a \in R$. We want to show \bar{a} is a unit in R/I . Consider the ideal $I + (a)$. By the maximality of I , either

$$I + (a) = I \quad \text{or} \quad I + (a) = R.$$

– If $I + (a) = I$, then $a \in I$. This implies $\bar{a} = \bar{0}$ in R/I , contradicting the assumption that $\bar{a} \neq \bar{0}$.

– Hence $I + (a) = R$. Therefore, there exist elements $i \in I$ and $r \in R$ such that

$$i + ar = 1.$$

Passing to the quotient, we get

$$\bar{i} + \bar{a}\bar{r} = \bar{1}.$$

But $\bar{i} = \bar{0}$, so

$$\bar{a}\bar{r} = \bar{1}.$$

Thus, \bar{a} is invertible in R/I . Since \bar{a} was an arbitrary nonzero element, R/I is a field.

(\Leftarrow) Conversely, if R/I is a field, then I cannot be contained properly in any strictly larger ideal. Indeed, if there were an ideal $I' \supset I$ with $I' \neq R$, the ideal $\bar{I}' \subset R/I$ would be a nontrivial ideal in a field, which is impossible. Hence I is maximal.

□

Classic Example in \mathbb{Z} .

Consider the ideal (p) in \mathbb{Z} , where p is a prime. Then:

$$\mathbb{Z}/(p) \cong \mathbb{Z}_p$$

and \mathbb{Z}_p is a field precisely because p is prime. Therefore, (p) is a maximal ideal in \mathbb{Z} .

Conversely, if (n) is maximal in \mathbb{Z} , then $\mathbb{Z}/(n)$ must be a field. Since $\mathbb{Z}/(n)$ is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_n , the only way for \mathbb{Z}_n to be a field is for n to be prime. Hence $n = p$. Thus (p) is maximal if and only if p is prime.

Another Classic Example in $k[x]$.

Let k be a field. Consider the ideal

$$\underbrace{(x - a)}_{\text{in } k[x]}$$

for a fixed $a \in k$. Then

$$k[x]/(x - a) \cong k$$

by the evaluation homomorphism $\varphi(f(x)) = f(a)$. Since k is a field, it follows that $(x - a)$ is a maximal ideal in $k[x]$.

Conversely, in $k[x]$, any nonzero maximal ideal has the form $(f(x))$, where f is irreducible. If we further know k is algebraically closed (like \mathbb{C}), then every nonconstant polynomial factors completely into linear factors; thus a maximal ideal in $\mathbb{C}[x]$ is of the form $(x - a)$ for some $a \in \mathbb{C}$.

2 First Isomorphism Theorem

Theorem 2 (First Isomorphism Theorem for Rings). *Let $\varphi : R \rightarrow S$ be a ring homomorphism. Then*

$$\frac{R}{\ker(\varphi)} \cong \text{im}(\varphi) \subseteq S$$

If φ is *surjective*, then

$$\frac{R}{\ker(\varphi)} \cong S$$

Sketch of Proof. Consider the natural map $\pi : R \rightarrow R/\ker(\varphi)$. By definition, $\pi(r) = r + \ker(\varphi)$. One checks that there is a unique homomorphism $\tilde{\varphi} : R/\ker(\varphi) \rightarrow S$ such that $\varphi = \tilde{\varphi} \circ \pi$. This map $\tilde{\varphi}$ is injective, and its image is precisely $\text{im}(\varphi)$. Hence

$$R/\ker(\varphi) \cong \text{im}(\varphi)$$

If, furthermore, φ is surjective, then $\text{im}(\varphi) = S$, yielding the second statement.

A Simple Example.

Consider $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ given by evaluating a polynomial at $x = 2$, i.e.

$$\varphi(f(x)) = f(2)$$

This is a ring homomorphism. We have:

$$\ker(\varphi) = \{f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x] \mid f(2) = 0\}$$

Hence the kernel is the ideal generated by $x - 2$. By the First Isomorphism Theorem,

$$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[x]}{(x - 2)} \cong \text{im}(\varphi) \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$$

But $\text{im}(\varphi)$ is all of \mathbb{Z} , since evaluating polynomials at 2 covers all integers (for example, take the constant polynomials). Therefore we get

$$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[x]}{(x - 2)} \cong \mathbb{Z}$$

Another Short Example (Evaluation at 0).

Let $\psi : k[x] \rightarrow k$ be given by $\psi(f(x)) = f(0)$, where k is any field. Then

$$\ker(\psi) = \{f(x) \in k[x] \mid f(0) = 0\} = (x)$$

By the First Isomorphism Theorem:

$$\frac{k[x]}{(x)} \cong \text{im}(\psi) = k$$

Thus (x) is precisely the kernel of the evaluation-at-zero map, and the quotient is isomorphic to k . This parallels Example 2 but with $x \mapsto 0$ instead of $x \mapsto 2$.

3 Minimal Polynomials

Definition 1 (Minimal Polynomial). *Let α be an element of some extension field of F . The minimal polynomial of α over F is the **monic, irreducible** polynomial $f \in F[x]$ such that $f(\alpha) = 0$.*

$$\sqrt{2} \implies x^2 - 2.$$

$x^2 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} by Eisenstein's Criterion (with $p = 2$)

Similarly,

$$\sqrt[3]{2} \implies x^3 - 2$$

Over \mathbb{Q} , $x^3 - 2$ has no rational roots, so by the rational root test (and also by Eisenstein with $p = 2$) it is irreducible. Thus $x^3 - 2$ is the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt[3]{2}$ over \mathbb{Q} .

Another Classic Example: $i \in \mathbb{C} \implies x^2 + 1$.

Since $i^2 + 1 = 0$, the polynomial $x^2 + 1$ has i as a root. We also know $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{R} . Hence for $\alpha = i$, the minimal polynomial over \mathbb{R} is $x^2 + 1$. Over \mathbb{Q} , the same polynomial is irreducible (no rational solutions), so $x^2 + 1$ remains the minimal polynomial of i over \mathbb{Q} as well.

Minimal Polynomial of a Primitive n -th Root of Unity.

Let ζ_n be a primitive n -th root of unity in \mathbb{C} . One knows that ζ_n is a root of $x^n - 1$. However, $x^n - 1$ factors as

$$x^n - 1 = (x - 1) \Phi_n(x)$$

where $\Phi_n(x)$ is the n -th cyclotomic polynomial. By definition, $\Phi_n(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} and has ζ_n as a root. Therefore the minimal polynomial of ζ_n over \mathbb{Q} is precisely $\Phi_n(x)$. For example, if $n = 3$, then

$$x^3 - 1 = (x - 1)(x^2 + x + 1), \quad \text{and } \zeta_3 \text{ satisfies } x^2 + x + 1 = 0$$

Hence ζ_3 has minimal polynomial $x^2 + x + 1$.

4 An Example: $\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$

Consider the element $x = \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$. We want to find a polynomial over \mathbb{Q} that has x as a root.

$$\begin{aligned}x &= \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3} \\x^2 &= (\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3})^2 = 2 + 3 + 2\sqrt{6} = 5 + 2\sqrt{6}\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$2\sqrt{6} = x^2 - 5 \quad \implies \quad \sqrt{6} = \frac{x^2 - 5}{2}$$

Square again:

$$\begin{aligned}6 &= \left(\frac{x^2 - 5}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{(x^2 - 5)^2}{4} \\24 &= (x^2 - 5)^2 = x^4 - 10x^2 + 25\end{aligned}$$

Rearranging gives:

$$x^4 - 10x^2 + 1 = 0$$

We check if $x^4 - 10x^2 + 1$ factors into lower-degree polynomials with rational coefficients. One finds it does not factor as, say, $(x^2 + ax + b)(x^2 + cx + d)$ with $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q}$. Thus it is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} (more rigorously one can do a direct search for possible rational factorizations or invoke advanced irreducibility tests). Hence $x^4 - 10x^2 + 1$ is the minimal polynomial of $\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$ over \mathbb{Q} .

5 Rational Root Test Example

Rational Root Theorem (Statement). If

$$f(x) = a_n x^n + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$$

and $r = \frac{a}{b} \in \mathbb{Q}$ (with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$) is a root of f , then $a \mid a_0$ and $b \mid a_n$.

Consider

$$g(x) = 2x^3 - 3$$

Possible rational roots, by the theorem, are

$$\pm 1, \pm 3, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm \frac{3}{2}$$

One checks directly that none of these is a root, so $2x^3 - 3$ has no linear factor over \mathbb{Q} . Hence it is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Another Simple Check.

Take $f(x) = x^2 - 2 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Possible rational roots are $\pm 1, \pm 2$. We verify that $f(\pm 1) \neq 0$ and $f(\pm 2) \neq 0$. Therefore, there are no rational solutions, so $x^2 - 2$ does not factor as a linear polynomial times another linear factor in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$. Hence it is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} .

Yet Another Quick Application.

Consider $h(x) = 3x^3 + x^2 - 1 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. By the Rational Root Theorem, a possible rational root is of the form ± 1 . Checking:

$$h(1) = 3 + 1 - 1 = 3 \neq 0, \quad h(-1) = -3 + 1 - 1 = -3 \neq 0$$

Hence $h(x)$ has no linear factor over \mathbb{Q} . It might or might not factor as an irreducible quadratic times a linear term, but since no rational root exists, we know no linear factor exists; indeed one can go on to test or use advanced criteria. This quick check illustrates how we rapidly discard the possibility of linear factors.

6 Splitting Fields, ED, PID, UFD

6.1 Splitting Fields (Informal Note)

For any polynomial $f \in F[x]$, by (an appropriate form of) the axiom of choice / Zorn's Lemma, we can embed F in a field extension E such that f splits into linear factors in $E[x]$. If $\text{char}(F) = 0$, we have familiar constructions for such splitting fields.

Hierarchy of Rings:

$$\text{ED} \subseteq \text{PID} \subseteq \text{UFD} \subseteq \text{ID} = \text{Commutative Rings with Unity}$$

(ED = Euclidean Domain, PID = Principal Ideal Domain, UFD = Unique Factorization Domain, ID = Integral Domain.)

6.2 Definitions

Euclidean Domain (ED). A ring R is called a Euclidean Domain if there exists a function

$$N : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$$

such that for all $a, b \in R$ with $b \neq 0$, there exist $q, r \in R$ satisfying

$$a = bq + r \quad \text{and} \quad N(r) < N(b)$$

and such that

$$N(a) \leq N(ab) \quad \forall a, b \in R \text{ with } b \neq 0$$

Principal Ideal Domain (PID). A ring R is called a Principal Ideal Domain if every ideal $I \subseteq R$ can be generated by a single element, i.e.,

$$I = (a) \quad \text{for some } a \in R$$

Unique Factorization Domain (UFD). A ring R is called a Unique Factorization Domain if every nonzero, non-unit element $r \in R$ can be written as

$$r = up_1p_2 \cdots p_m$$

(where u is a unit and each p_i is irreducible), and this factorization is unique up to reordering and associates. Concretely, if

$$r = u_1 p_1 \dots p_m = u_2 q_1 \dots q_n$$

then $m = n$, and each p_i is *associate* to some q_j .

7 Prime vs. Irreducible in General Domains

7.1 General Statement

In an integral domain, all prime elements are irreducible.

However, the converse need not hold in general. In a *UFD*, prime and irreducible *do* coincide, but outside that context, one can find examples of irreducible elements that fail to be prime.

7.2 Example in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$

In $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$, consider the factorization:

$$3^2 = (2 + \sqrt{-5})(2 - \sqrt{-5})$$

It can be shown that 3 is irreducible in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$ (it has no nontrivial factorization). However, 3 is **not prime**, since

$$(2 + \sqrt{-5})(2 - \sqrt{-5}) = 9$$

is in the ideal generated by 3 but neither factor is in that ideal individually (i.e. 3 does not divide each factor separately).

Hence,

$$3 \text{ is irreducible but not prime in } \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$$

7.3 Example in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{5}]$ (Mentioned)

A similar phenomenon appears in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{5}]$. One can find elements that factor in more than one *essentially distinct* way, leading to irreducibility not implying primality.

Prime vs Irreducible in \mathbb{Z} .

In \mathbb{Z} , an irreducible element is the same as a prime, thanks to the fact that \mathbb{Z} is a PID (hence a UFD). Indeed, for an integer $p \neq 0, \pm 1$, if it divides a product ab , then p divides a or p divides b . This shows p is prime, and it is also irreducible because we cannot factor p into non-units except trivially.

Thus \mathbb{Z} is one of the simplest rings where “irreducible” and “prime” coincide, highlighting the UFD property.

8 Condition for Inclusion of Ideals in a PID

Problem: Give a necessary and sufficient condition for two ideals $I \subseteq J$ in a principal ideal domain (R).

Solution: Let $I = (a)$ and $J = (b)$ for some $a, b \in R$. We claim:

$$I \subseteq J \iff b \mid a$$

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Assume $I \subseteq J$. Then in particular $a \in (b)$. Hence there is some $r \in R$ with

$$a = br \implies b \mid a$$

(\Leftarrow) Conversely, if $b \mid a$, say $a = bc$, then $a \in (b)$. Indeed, any multiple of a is also a multiple of b . In particular,

$$(a) \subseteq (b)$$

So $I \subseteq J$.

A Quick Check in \mathbb{Z} .

Take $(6) \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ and $(3) \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$. We ask: is $(6) \subseteq (3)$? By the theorem, this is true if and only if $3 \mid 6$. Indeed,

$$(6) = \{6k \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}\}, \quad (3) = \{3m \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

Since $6 = 3 \cdot 2$, clearly $3 \mid 6$. Then every multiple of 6 is also a multiple of 3:

$$6k = 3(2k) \implies 6k \in (3)$$

Hence $(6) \subseteq (3)$.

In contrast, $(3) \not\subseteq (6)$, because $6 \nmid 3$.

Further Check in \mathbb{Z} .

Consider (8) and (4) . We have

$$(8) \subseteq (4) \iff 4 \mid 8$$

Indeed, $8 = 4 \cdot 2$, so $4 \mid 8 \implies (8) \subseteq (4)$. Checking the other inclusion:

$$(4) \subseteq (8) \iff 8 \mid 4$$

which is false. Hence $(4) \not\subseteq (8)$. Simple divisibility captures precisely the inclusion of such ideals in a PID.

9 Example: $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ Not a PID

Finally, let us see why $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is not a PID. Consider the ideal

$$(x, y) \subseteq \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$$

Suppose, for contradiction, that (x, y) were principal, i.e.,

$$(x, y) = (g)$$

for some $g \in \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. Then we would have

$$x = g f_1(x, y) \quad \text{and} \quad y = g f_2(x, y)$$

for some $f_1, f_2 \in \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. In particular, g would be a common divisor of x and y . But no nonconstant polynomial can divide both x and y in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ such that we re-generate the entire ideal (x, y) . Concretely, if g divides x and y , then g must be a constant (up to a unit in \mathbb{Q}). Thus (g) would never capture the full set $\{x \cdot p(x, y) + y \cdot q(x, y)\}$.

Therefore, (x, y) is not principal in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$, implying $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is *not* a PID.

10 Additional Examples and Topics

Below are several classic applications illustrating the points:

1. **Showing Something is Not a UFD.**
2. **Showing Certain Elements are Identical (Associates) Over Larger Fields.**
3. **Finding a UFD that is Not a PID.**
4. **Identifying an Ideal with Certain Properties.**
5. **Minimal Polynomials.**
6. **Constructing a Basis for a Field Extension.**

We give concise examples and immediate proof sketches using simple algebraic implications (\implies).

10.1 (1) Showing Something is Not a UFD

$\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$ is not a UFD because of the two distinct factorizations of 6:

$$6 = 2 \cdot 3 \quad \text{and} \quad 6 = (1 + \sqrt{-5})(1 - \sqrt{-5})$$

\implies the ring does not have unique factorization.

In fact, all factors $2, 3, 1 + \sqrt{-5}, 1 - \sqrt{-5}$ can be shown irreducible, yet the two products are genuinely different.

10.2 (2) Showing that Certain Elements Coincide under Field Extensions

Associates in Quadratic Extensions.

In $\mathbb{Z}[i]$, the elements $1 + i$ and $i - 1$ differ by a unit:

$$i - 1 = i(1 + i)$$

and i is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$. Hence $1 + i$ and $i - 1$ are *associates* (they generate the same ideal). Over larger fields (e.g. in \mathbb{C}), multiplying by a nonzero complex number in $\mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ can show many elements are equivalent up to associates.

Thus in an extended field (or ring), units may expand, causing distinct elements in a smaller ring to become associates in a larger one.

Another Simple Check in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$.

In $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}]$, $-\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{2}$ are associates because

$$-\sqrt{2} = (-1)\sqrt{2}$$

and -1 is a unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}]$. More generally, any nonzero rational factor is a unit in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$, so for instance $2\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{2}$ are also associates there (the unit in that case is just 2).

10.3 (3) Finding a UFD That Is Not a PID

$\mathbb{Z}[x]$ (a polynomial ring in one variable over \mathbb{Z}) is a UFD but **not** a PID. Indeed:

$\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is known to be a UFD (Gauss's Lemma), but not all ideals are principal.

For instance,

$$(2, x) \subset \mathbb{Z}[x]$$

is not principal. If it were $(f(x))$ for some $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$, then $f(x)$ would have to divide both 2 and x . The only common divisors of 2 and x in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ are units or constants dividing 2, none of which can generate all expressions of the form $2p(x) + xq(x)$. Hence $(2, x)$ is *not* principal.

$\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is also a UFD but **not** a PID. The ideal $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is not principal, analogous to the argument above.

10.4 (4) Some Ideal Has a Certain Property

The Ideal $(x, y) \subset \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$.

We claim (x, y) is *proper* (it is strictly contained in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$) and is generated by x and y . Explicitly, any element in (x, y) can be written

$$x f(x, y) + y g(x, y)$$

for some $f, g \in \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. Checking it is an ideal is routine:

$$\forall a(x f + y g), b \in \mathbb{Q}[x, y], b [x f + y g] = x (b f) + y (b g) \in (x, y)$$

Since $x, y \neq 0$, we see $(x, y) \neq \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$. It fails to be principal, establishing that $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is not a PID (as above).

10.5 (5) Minimal Polynomial

Minimal Polynomial of $\sqrt{2}$.

As noted, $x^2 - 2 \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$ has $\sqrt{2}$ as a root, and

$x^2 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} (Rational Root Test or Eisenstein $p = 2$) \implies this is the minimal polynomial

Minimal Polynomial of i .

Over \mathbb{Q} , i is a root of $x^2 + 1$, which has no rational solutions. Hence $x^2 + 1$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . Thus $x^2 + 1$ is the minimal polynomial of i over \mathbb{Q} .

10.6 (6) Constructing a Basis for a Field Extension

A Quadratic Extension.

In $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$, every element can be written as

$$a + b\sqrt{2}, \quad (a, b \in \mathbb{Q})$$

Hence $\{1, \sqrt{2}\}$ is a basis over \mathbb{Q} . Indeed, if

$$\alpha = a + b\sqrt{2}, \quad \beta = c + d\sqrt{2}$$

then

$$\alpha + \beta = (a + c) + (b + d)\sqrt{2}, \quad \alpha\beta = (ac + 2bd) + (ad + bc)\sqrt{2}$$

which remain in the span of 1 and $\sqrt{2}$. Also, α/β (for $\beta \neq 0$) is again of the form $r + s\sqrt{2}$. Thus the entire extension is spanned by $\{1, \sqrt{2}\}$.

More generally, for $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{d})$ with d squarefree, $\{1, \sqrt{d}\}$ is a standard basis.

Cubic Extension.

If $\alpha = \sqrt[3]{2}$ and we consider $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[3]{2})$, every element has the form

$$a + b\sqrt[3]{2} + c(\sqrt[3]{2})^2, \quad (a, b, c \in \mathbb{Q})$$

Hence $\{1, \sqrt[3]{2}, (\sqrt[3]{2})^2\}$ is a basis over \mathbb{Q} . The minimal polynomial of α is $x^3 - 2$, so the extension has degree 3.

Additional Simple Illustration of a Non-Principal Ideal.

Consider $\mathbb{Z}[x]$. The ideal $(2, x) \subseteq \mathbb{Z}[x]$ consists of all polynomials that can be written as

$$2f(x) + xg(x) \quad \text{for some } f(x), g(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$$

Just as in the case of $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$, we can argue $(2, x)$ is not principal: any common divisor of 2 and x in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ must be a unit or a constant divisor of 2 (it cannot also factor x in a nontrivial way). Hence we cannot find a single generator $h(x)$ such that

$$(2, x) = (h(x))$$

Thus $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is not a PID (though it is a UFD).

11 Proving a Ring is Not a PID (No Single Generator)

11.1 Example 1: $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and the Ideal $(2, x)$

$\mathbb{Z}[x]$ is **not** a PID because the ideal $(2, x)$ is not principal.

- Suppose, for contradiction, $(2, x)$ is principal, i.e. $(2, x) = (f(x))$ for some $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$.
- Then $2 \in (f(x)) \implies 2 = f(x) \cdot g(x)$ for some $g(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$.

$$\implies f(x) \mid 2 \quad (\text{divides the constant polynomial } 2)$$

- Similarly, $x \in (f(x)) \implies x = f(x) \cdot h(x)$.

$$\implies f(x) \mid x \quad (\text{divides the polynomial } x)$$

- A nonzero divisor of the constant polynomial 2 must be a constant (up to multiplication by a unit in \mathbb{Z}). But if $f(x)$ is constant, it cannot also divide x (which is non-constant) in a nontrivial way.

$$\implies \text{No single } f(x) \text{ can generate both } 2 \text{ and } x$$

- Contradiction. Thus $(2, x)$ is not principal, and $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ cannot be a PID.

11.2 Example 2: $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ and the Ideal (x, y)

$\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is **not** a PID because the ideal (x, y) is not principal.

- Assume $(x, y) = (g(x, y))$ for some polynomial $g(x, y) \in \mathbb{Q}[x, y]$.
- Then $x \in (g) \implies x = g(x, y) f_1(x, y)$. Also $y \in (g) \implies y = g(x, y) f_2(x, y)$.

$$\implies g \mid x \text{ and } g \mid y$$

in $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$.

- Over \mathbb{Q} , any common divisor of x and y must be a (nonzero) constant polynomial (up to a unit in \mathbb{Q}).

$\implies g(x, y)$ is constant

- But a constant polynomial cannot generate all combinations $xp(x, y) + yq(x, y)$. Indeed, if g is constant, $(g) = (1)$ or a constant ideal, which would be the entire ring or too small.

$\implies (x, y) \neq (g)$

- Contradiction. Hence (x, y) is not principal. Therefore $\mathbb{Q}[x, y]$ is *not* a PID.

